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About the College

Bharathiar University Arts and Science College was established in Valparai, in the year 2006. It is one of the Constituent Colleges of Bharathiar University, with Recognition of UGC and Government of Tamilnadu (G.O.M.S 258 higher education G1 Department Dt.17/8/2006) to support offspring of plantation workers. The campus spreads over an area of 12.5 acres, offers 9 UG courses and 4 PG courses and has Research Programmes with developed Infrastructure, excellent Laboratories, Library, Transportation and cafeteria Facilities. Its constant drive in imparting higher education through excellent higher academic standard acquired 2F and 12B status in the year 2011.

About the Department

The department of commerce & commerce (CA) was established in 2006 and now it offers UG, PG , M.Phil and PhD Programmes (both full time and part time). The department has qualified and committed faculty credentials, persistently seeks and adopts innovative ideas of teaching high quality education in the field of commerce. Its stable constrain in conveying research programme for the benefit and to enhance the skill of the rural students. The research students are offered with admirable atmosphere to learn and acquire knowledge to become a young researcher.

Theme of the Seminar

The Goods and Service Tax (GST) is one of the most significant tax reforms in the fiscal history of India. The introduction of Goods and Service Tax (GST), a destination based consumption tax portents transformational change of the indirect tax landscape of the country.

GST is a proactive step towards a vivid opportunity for the country. It will redefine Indian economy on the international front as “one tax and one market”. The GST framework will subsume majority of the indirect taxes levied by Central and State Governments like Central Excise Duty, Service tax, State Value Added Tax, Central Sales Tax, Entry tax, Purchase tax, Entertainment tax, and Luxury tax.

GST is expected to provide a significant boost to investment and growth of the economy. It will have an impact on prices, business processes, investments and profitability in all segment of the economy and also entail a fundamental shift in the way tax policies are made in the country. GST will have a business-wide impact on the entire value chain of operations like procurement, manufacturing, sales and Pricing, finance, information technology, supply chain and warehousing. It is crucial for businesses to understand the impact of the proposed change, work collaboratively and be heard. This seminar aims to make a detailed impact assessment so as to understand the basics of GST Law and to ascertain the net impact on various sectors. This event will provide an opportunity to clear the doubts of the participants on key areas of the GST implementation.

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Principal's Message

I could much more delight with the proposal of two days national seminar on “Goods and service tax and its impacts”, jointly organized by Post graduate and Research Department of Commerce of Bharathiar University Arts and Science College and The Coimbatore Branch of SIRC, The Institute of Chartered Accountant of India.

This trendy approach is lucrative for students, faculty, business people and general public. The theme is a recent one and most wanted to keep abreast of the trend. Goods and Service tax has a wide scope and so having a clear knowledge is the first and foremost interest of everyone. Seminar is not only an act of securing knowledge but gathering practical applicability. This Seminar best suits this motto.

Research on this theme is appropriately selected as it provides a good platform for various education institutions, business sectors and academicians. I can assure that this effort brings out a prolific result for all the participants, students, faculty, research scholars and common man.

I am content about the organizing secretary of the seminar, faculty member of department of commerce, supporters and well wishers.

With an immense pleasure, I appreciate all the contributors and I wish the national seminar acquire a grand success.

Principal
Dr.L.Ramesh
Bharathiar University Arts and Science College,
Valparai.

CA. S. Rajesh
Vice Chairman
Coimbatore branch of ICAI

The Coimbatore branch of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI) is one of the vibrant branches of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (Setup under an Act of Parliament) and is a leader in playing a vital role in empowering the Students of Commerce, Accountancy and Management areas. It is indeed a proud privilege and an honor for our Institute to be associated with the PG & Research Department of Commerce & Commerce CA of the Bharathiar University Arts and Science College, Valparai and organizing this two Days National Seminar on Goods and Service Tax and its impacts on 27th & 28th September 2017 at the College Campus.

On behalf of the Coimbatore branch of ICAI I wholeheartedly thank the Principal, Head of Departments and all other distinguished faculty Members for giving us this wonderful opportunity. I sincerely express my gratitude for their kind cooperation and valuable support in organizing this National Seminar. ICAI is always committed to empower students with the latest developments and changes occurring in various fields and GST being one of the most important areas; our intention was to organize this Seminar so as to bring in more clarity and better understanding of the subject. With this perspective we fixed the best faculty Members to address on various aspects of GST. I am very sure that the eminent faculty Members will enlighten the participants and make this program a grand success.

From day one of implementation of GST, it was a great challenge to Professionals, business community, accounting fraternity and many more, but with the contribution and support of renowned scholars the challenge was faced successfully. Though there are changes and developments occurring frequently the law has taken a shape and ofcourse it is a great landmark in our Nation's growth. At this juncture, I congratulate and appreciate the entire team of Bharathiar University College of Arts and Science for taking sincere efforts and organizing this Seminar. The Coimbatore branch of ICAI would be glad to organize more such kind of programs in future for the collective benefit of the Students fraternity.

I wish the Seminar a great success.

CA. S. Rajesh
Vice Chairman
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GST (GOODS AND SERVICES TAX) AND INDIAN ECONOMY

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Goods and services Tax (GST) is a vast concept which reflects the giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of the country. GST is a comprehensively structured tax system which will be levied on manufacturing, sale and consumption of the goods and services at a national level. The constitution (one hundred and twenty second amendment Bill) 2014, seeks to amend the constitution of India to facilitate the introduction of Goods and services Tax (GST) in the country. The proposed amendments will confer power in both the parliament and the state legislatures to make laws for levying GST on the supply of Goods and Services on the same transaction. GST is an indirect tax in where all the stages of the production will bring to uniformity in the system.

In order to bring GST into practice, there will be an amalgamation of central taxes and state taxes into a single tax payment. It would also help to enhance the ease of doing business in India both for domestic and international investors.

Under GST regime, the consumer pays the final tax, but an effective input tax credit system which ensures the consumers that there will be no cascading of taxes i.e. tax on tax paid on inputs that go into manufacturing of goods. Moreover, in order to avoid the current payment of multiple taxes such as excise duty and service tax at central level and sale tax/VAT at the state level, GST would unify these taxes and create a uniform single tax market throughout the country. The present tax system generally taxes on production whereas the GST will aim to tax on final consumption.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are –

1. To sketch the structure of the proposed GST in India.
2. To observe the possible impact of GST in Indian economy.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study is based on secondary sources. The study of the proposed GST is the result of journals, magazines, books and internet sources.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Structure of the proposed GST

1. Dual GST:

Both Central Government and State Government will simultaneously levy GST across the value chain. Central Government will levy as well as collect Central Goods and Services Tax (CGST) and states would levy and collect state Goods and Services Tax (SGST) on all transactions within a state. The input tax credit of CGST will be available for paying the CGST liability on the output at each stage. Similarly the credit of SGST paid on inputs would be allowed for paying the SGST on output.

2. Inter State transaction and the IGST mechanism:

The Integrated Goods and Services Tax (IGST) have been designed to ensure seamless flow of input tax credit from one state to another. The centre will levy and collect the IGST on all inter-state supply of goods and services.

3. Central taxes to be Subsumed:

- A. Central excise duty
- B. Additional excise duty

C. The excise duty levied under the medicinal and Toiletries

D. Service tax

E. Additional custom duty commonly known as countervailing duty (CD)

F. Special additional duty of custom-4% (SAD)

G. Cesses and surcharges in so far as they relate to supply of goods and services.

State taxes to be subsumed:

A. VAT/sale tax

B. Central sale tax (levied by the centre and collected by the respective state)

C. Entertainment tax

D. Octroi and entry tax

E. Purchase tax

F. Luxury tax

G. Taxes on lottery, betting and gambling.

H. State cesses and surcharges in so far as they relate to supply of goods and services.

Destination-based consumption tax:

GST will be a destination based tax. This implies that all SGST collected will ordinarily accrue to the state where the consumer of the goods or services sold resides.

The reason behind moving towards GST:

1. Presently, the constitution empower both the Central Government and the State Government to levy excise duty on manufacturing and service tax on the supply of services by the Central Government and the State Government to levy sale tax or vat on the sale of goods. So, these types of indirect tax system creates multistage of taxes and complicated the tax administrative system.

2. In addition, the central sales tax (CST) is levied by the central government but collected and retained by the exporting state.

3. This multiplicity of taxes at the central and the state has resulted in a complex indirect tax structure that is ridden with hidden costs for the trade and industry. In the present system, there is no

uniformity of taxes and structure across states. So excise duty and services tax paid at the stages of manufacture, no credit is available to the traders while the same case also occurred in the state level of sale tax or VAT. Moreover due to cascading of taxes i.e. tax on tax, the prices of the goods and services get artificially inflated.

4. GST will simplify and harmonise the indirect tax regime in the country. It is expected to reduce the cost of production and inflation in the economy. Further, GST will broaden the tax base and result in better tax compliance due to a robust IT infrastructure.

Discussion

The possible impact of the proposed GST on the Indian Economy

1. Real Estate Sector:

In India, the real estate sector has strong multiplier effects through backward and forward leakages. After agriculture, the construction sector is the second largest employment generator medium for the country which accounts for a significant proportion of the GDP. Under the current law in force, there are different types of taxes involved in real estate sector, starting from the construction of property to sale of the same to the end consumers. These taxes are service tax, vat, stamp duty, building cesses on construction etc. Moreover there are various other taxes which are embedded in the cost of procurements such as excise duty, CST etc. Due to cascading of taxes, higher tax cost burdens on house purchasers. But the proposed GST is likely to result in transparency in the real estate sector, which will significantly reduce tax evasion through more efficient transaction tracking methods and improved enforcement and compliance.

2. Health Care Sector:

The proposed and recently passed GST Bill has generated a lot of curiosity in the economy. While the manufacturers are quite optimistic about the new tax

law regime, but common man are not sure of how it is going to impact on their lives. GST relies upon the positive effect on the pharmaceutical part. It will help the business by streamlining the tax structure since eight different taxes are exacted in the pharmaceutical industry right now. A solidification of all these into one tax would ease working together, as well as mitigates the falling effects of numerous taxes connected on one item.

3. **Telecommunication Sector:**

The proposed GST regime appears to be unfavourable for the telecommunication sector as well. The dual framework of GST regime could be the direct spike in the service tax rate from 14% to 18-20%. The proposed GST appears to be silent on whether the telecommunication can be considered under the category of goods and services. Being a regressive taxation system, the burn of increased tax rates will directly be faced by the end consumer unless the credit is passed on to the next in business chain.

4. **Banking and Financial Sector:**

The proposed GST will hamper the banking, financial services (i.e. securities, broking) and insurance industries which have both B2B and B2C operations due to the nature of their operations. The banking and financial services industry has historically paid service tax on its fee income; interest income was service tax free while fund based income were outside the ambit of service tax regulations. The proposed GST law however would require businesses to redefine this approach. Moreover buying and selling of securities is currently outside the indirect tax net but according to the proposed GST Law securities are regarded as a goods and securities in dematerialized form may be treated as a service. As a result, fund based activities such as derivatives trading may fall within GST purview. Furthermore, as GST is a destination based tax, it might be a challenge to GST on B2B and B2C transactions.

5. **Impact on Common Man:**

Although the GST reaches its final stage, there is confusion among the common people about its impact on them. In spite of the government claims that GST will increase GDP by 2 percent, services are bound to be more expensive. So, we can say that it is a mixed bag for consumers. Today consumer has no idea the extent of taxes they pay on goods. For instance, if we get a bill after buying merchandise which gives the extent of VAT we have paid on it but it is an understatement of the actual tax we have paid because before merchandise reached the retail outlet, the central government has collected excise duty, but the extent of excise duty is not mentioned in the bill. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume we pay well over 20% tax for most merchandise we purchase.

In GST, consumers will benefit in two ways. Firstly, all taxes will be collected at the point of consumption. Suppose if any merchandise is taxed at 18% it will include both Central Government and the State Government. So this will bring transparency in taxation system and will increase tax revenue.

Secondly, once barrier between states are removed, we as consumers will not face cascading of taxes i.e. tax on tax which appears goods moving across state borders.

V. **CONCLUSION**

The proposed GST regime is a half hearted attempt to rationalise multiple indirect tax structure. The real success of the GST lies on the impact on the common Indian consumer. The essence of GST is that all goods and services be taxed at moderate rate. "One Nation, one Tax", proves to be a game changer in a positive way. And no doubt, GST will simplify existing indirect tax system which will help to remove inefficiencies created by the existing current heterogeneous taxation system only if there is a clear consensus over issues of threshold limit, revenue rate and inclusion of petroleum products, electricity, liquor etc. We hope GST leaves a positive impact and

helps to boost up Indian economy and a rising Indian economy will help in the financial growth of the common man.

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ROLE OF GST IN E-COMMERCE

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Abstract

India's e-commerce market is estimated to have crossed Rs. 2,11,005 crore in December 2016 as per the study conducted by Internet and Mobile Association of India. The report further claim that India is expected to generate \$100 billion online retail revenue by the year 2020. The uprising of Electronic Commerce in India has also resulted in conception of online marketplaces. A Marketplace is an e-commerce platform owned by the E-commerce Operator such as Flipkart, Snapdeal and Amazon. Government has also allowed Foreign Direct Investments under such model to promote e-commerce marketplace business model in India. The Research Methodology used in the paper is descriptive. Internet, newspaper articles and government documents have been used. The main aim of this research paper is to bring about the loop holes which existed in the provisions governing the e-commerce sector and making the public aware of the benefits of GST.

Key words: E-Commerce , GST

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic commerce or EC is buying and selling of goods and services, or the transmitting of funds or data, over an electronic network, primarily the internet. GST has a noticeable impact on each and every sector including E-commerce sector. There can be two types of E-commerce sellers: 1. E-commerce operator/ marketplace (e.g. Flipkart, Amazon etc): It

is an entity which owns, operates or manages digital or electronic facility or platform for E-commerce.

2. Suppliers on E-commerce platform: It is an entity which supplies goods or services on/through an E-commerce platform.

1.2 Definition of E-Commerce Under GST in India

E-commerce or electronic commerce (an online shopping hub) manages the buying and selling of products and services exclusively through electronic channels. E-commerce captures around 33% of the global market with a positive growth in near future. According to the latest GST council 21st meeting the registration for all the taxpayers registered under TCS can start their registration from 18th September, 2017.

1.3 Review of Literature

1. Harshita Bachhawat & Vibhu Jai, (2017) in their article on "E-COMMERCE SECTOR- BEFORE AND AFTER GST" revealed that the fast changing information technology and convergence of various communication technologies has virtually taken the business practices by storm. E-commerce is becoming the key to success. This paper deals with the issues which are prevailing in the e-commerce sector with respect to the existing provisions and how after the implementation of GST such issues will be resolved.

2. Bhawna Manyal Aanchal Nagpal (2016) in their article on "GST on e-commerce in retail sector:

BOON or BANE”showed that The e-commerce industry in India is still in its infancy, but it has shown a remarkable growth over a period of time and has contributed significantly to the country’s GDP. In this paper, the researchers have tried to find out the implications of GST on e-commerce in the retail sector and whether it proves to be more of a boon than a bane to the e-commerce companies.

3.Jomsy Thomas , Radhika V Rand Anna Celine E J(2016) in their research study on INDIAN E-COMMERCE SECTOR - WILL IT BE EVOKED IN THE LIGHT OF GST? revealed that E- Commerce industries are growing day by day as the web expansion by the Information Technology. E-Com industries can turn even one’s bedroom as a shopping mall without any delay. This paper is a very humble effort to go through the loopholes used by E-Com companies of existing indirect taxation practices and how the problems are addressed in GST.

4.Girish Garg (2014) analyzed the impact of GST on Indian Tax Scenario in his paper titled “Basic Concepts and features of Goods and Service Tax in India”. He explained various objectives, challenges, opportunities, salient features and benefits of GST. He concluded by explaining the impact of GST on food industry, FMCG industry, housing and construction industry and financial services.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The paradigm shift in policies and focus in taxation, both at micro and macro level, on compliance and plugging possibilities of evasion has made it imperative for the people to know the impact of GST in E-Commerce Area. In this competitive environment have carved a niche for consumer and producer in the field of tax and to a good extent in GST, in the present decade. The phenomenal increase in e-commerce transaction has widened the ambit of Indirect Taxes specially the statutory provisions provided under upcoming regime of GST. In order to enhance the knowledge, it has become mandatory to

study, analyze, update and discuss the changes taking place in e-Commerce transactions, statutory provisions and regulatory guidelines from time to time. Hence, this study has focus the role of GST and its influence in development of E-Commerce.

1.5 Objectives of the Study

To present the role of GST in E-Commerce

1. To identify the present impact of GST in E-Commerce
2. To assess the key areas of GST that influence the e-commerce sector

1.6 Methodology

Research Design

- The study is descriptive in nature
- Sources and Collection of Data
- The secondary data has been used for the study. The data is collected from various journal, magazines, online newspapers and websites

1.7 Role of GST In E-Commerce

E-commerce companies such as Amazon Seller Services Pvt. Ltd and Flipkart Ltd are set to be among the winners in the transition to a single national market which will be created by the proposed goods and service tax (GST). GST should put an end to the numerous hurdles state administrations have been erecting amid complaints that online sales, and the hefty discounts they come with, are eroding the sales and profitability of physical retailers as well as state revenues.

It will mean a shift from the current model of taxing inter-state transactions, where the manufacturing state gets the proceeds of a 2% central sales tax on goods sold in other states. This will make way for a system in which the consuming state will get proceeds of taxes on interstate supply of goods. The integrated GST, which applies to inter-state supplies, has central and state components of roughly equal measure.

E-commerce firms achieve efficiency by building warehouses in a few states where merchandise is stored for selling to consumers across the country. These companies typically offer the service of an online marketplace, and in some cases a warehousing facility to vendors, and pay service tax to the central government on any fee or margin received for that.

Online retailers face one potential irritant in GST—a 1% tax collected at source from vendors and paid to the government. “Vendors will get full tax credit on this 1% tax, but it could cause administrative inconvenience to e-commerce firms when products are returned by the consumer,” said R. Muralidharan, senior director, Deloitte in India.

Marketplaces has provided retailers with additional channel of sales and reach which was unimaginable for an offline seller. Major marketplaces claim to have lacs of sellers affiliated with their platform with millions of SKUs. While the number of sellers and their business have increased significantly, GST has specifically taken up marketplaces and has come out with rules & regulations specific to this study.

Tax Collection at Source by Marketplace Operator: Under the new tax regime, marketplace operators are mandatorily required to deduct a percentage amount as the GST liability of seller and deposit it with government. This mechanism is being termed as “Tax Collection at Source (TCS)” under the GST law. Eventually the marketplace seller will have to file monthly return under GST to claim the credit of TCS collected by the marketplace operator. This will also impact the liquidity and cash flow of these sellers.

While all the marketplace operator have already completed the first level analysis of impact of GST on their operations, marketplace sellers are still unaware of these rules. Need of the hour is to keep themselves aware of the changes that are going to come. Also such sellers should now start planning

their transition strategy for GST regime. Every company in India, be it a multinational company or a small/medium enterprise, is gearing up for the implementation of GST. The e-commerce sector would follow suit in its preparation by focusing on provisions specific to this sector in the GST law.

1.8 Impact of GST In E-Commerce

- It will make the taxation system more transparent and simple and easy to understand.
- It will reduce the overall cost of goods and services to final consumer as cascading effect of taxation will be overcome.
- It will facilitate free flow of goods and services and thereby reducing overall transaction cost.
- Since GST is not levied on goods and services which are exported so it provides an incentive to EOU, SEZs and EPZs. And GST will be levied on goods or services imported into the country with destination principle where the imported goods or services are consumed that state will enjoy the tax revenue.
- Since intermediaries in the supply chain can claim the tax credit which will reduce the cost the cost of doing business.
- It will reduce the scope of corruption in the economy as a whole.
- It will increase the tax base as more firms will come under the tax regime which ultimately increases the tax revenue collection for the government.
- GST will guarantee the consistency of taxes over the states, irrespective of place of production or consumption.
- The normal taxation rate on organizations will fall which will decrease the expenses of Indian goods and services and make them competitive in the global market and ultimately GDP would increase
- The taxation burden will be divided equitably between manufacturing and services, through a lower tax rate by increasing the tax base and minimizing exemptions.

- For paying GST, 13/15 digit PAN-linked identification in line with Income tax will be allotted which will ease the tax payment system

GST could be key to unlock issues faced by e-commerce sector

The nascent e-commerce sector in India which took baby steps until about a couple of years ago is in a galloping mode today. The growth of the e-commerce sector in terms of revenue and shipments has been nothing but phenomenal..

Growth of any business is good news for the economy and especially the taxman. E-commerce sector, with its ever increasing number of transactions in goods & services, is a fertile land for sowing the seed of indirect taxes. While it is fair for the taxman to expect increase in tax revenues through growing businesses, the tax laws should also support the businesses with clarity on taxation matters and ease of doing business. Unfortunately, for the e-commerce sector, the indirect tax laws in India have been more of a snag than a driver for growth.

Firstly, e-commerce sector dealing in trading of goods have experimented with various business models. Starting with the traditional 'stock-and-sell' model, the e-commerce companies have transformed into a multi-model platform over time by introducing 'market place' and / or services model, thereby having to grapple with a more complex tax framework involving VAT / CST, excise, and / or service taxes.

Secondly, the e-commerce sector is having a hard time categorising their offerings into 'goods' or 'services' for charging either value added tax (VAT) / Central Sales Tax (CST) or service tax. This situation aggravates in the case of digital downloads involving software, music, e-books etc.

Thirdly, inter-state movement of goods from one state to another is a nightmare for an e-commerce operator.

Fourthly, the non-fungible VAT and service tax results in significant non-recoupable tax cost impact for the e-commerce sector.

In addition to the above, the tax laws in India have also failed the e-commerce sector by not providing enough clarity / guidelines on taxation and documentation management for typical e-commerce sector transactions like e-wallet (advance deposits by consumers), cash-on-delivery (payment collected at the door-step of the consumer), gift vouchers, drop-shipment (direct delivery of goods from the e-commerce company vendor to the e-commerce company customer) etc.

E-commerce sector is here to stay and would be one of the pillars of the Indian economy in the near future. Businesses can thrive and grow only in a tax conducive environment and it is obvious that the above issues cannot continue forever and would need resolution sooner than later. While the e-commerce sector is eagerly looking forward to the upcoming budget to address the concerns and act as a business catalyst for the sector, the Goods & Services Tax (GST) which would replace the current indirect tax regime and expected to be implemented in India from 1 April, 2016, could hold the key to unlock the issues faced by the e-commerce sector.

1.9 Key areas of GST that impact the e-commerce sector:

The success of the e-commerce sector is largely dependent on the increasing number of retail entrepreneurs, who fall in the unorganized retail sector category. The government has included such players in the ambit of GST with an intention of broadening the tax base and has introduced specific provisions for the e-commerce companies.

i.No trade barriers—one nation one tax

In the present regime, there is no uniformity in the tax rates among the different states and therefore every state determines its own tax rates specific to the products. However, such trade barriers will cease to

exist as GST is inclusive of entry tax. The destination state earns the revenue from GST on sales regardless of where the sale was made. Further, there is no rate arbitrage under GST because the classification of goods and rate of GST is common across states.

ii. Tax collection at source (TCS)

It is mandatory for all e-commerce operators to collect tax at the rate of two percent as TCS on the net value of sales made by suppliers through e-commerce operators. Such TCS has to be deducted in each state and deposited accordingly. This brings in significant compliance challenges to sellers and may discourage sales through marketplace model. However, this may not be applicable for inventory based models, where the e-commerce operator makes the sale from its own inventory. The key purpose of this provision is to encourage compliances under GST and provide a mechanism for the government to track suppliers who sell through e-commerce operators.

iii. Increase in compliances for e-commerce operators

The e-commerce operators should report all supplies made by the seller and the TCS collected thereof on a monthly basis. The sales reported by the e-commerce operator will have to match with the sales declared by the supplier himself at the end of every month, and any difference will be added to the turnover of the supplier and consequently be liable to discharge GST on such additional turnover.

The e-commerce operator has to report the product/service code and the applicable rates for each item level individually. This requires them to map every sale done by the dealer and ensure TCS is deducted at the right value. The implementation of compliance is cumbersome for both e-commerce operator and the supplier. Additionally, the e-commerce operators will have to register in each state and file the reports separately on a monthly basis.

This process increases the challenges in compliance and costs of running the business.

iv. Mandatory registration of sellers and unavailability of composition scheme

GST mandates that all sellers supplying through an e-commerce operator need to be registered under GST irrespective of the threshold limit of Rs 20 lakh. These sellers cannot opt for composition scheme, where they pay a flat tax at the rate of two percent and do not maintain details of each product sold. In this scenario, it is not feasible for small businesses to maintain a detailed record of purchases and sales and pay higher rate of tax. Because of this, many small retailers may not prefer to work with an e-commerce company, which impacts the business for e-commerce operators.

V. Increase in credits

Statutory framework introduced by the government should be towards the advancement of business rather than creating obstacles. The GST law should provide an enabling environment that encourages e-commerce operators and suppliers. In the run-up to one of the biggest tax reforms in the country, the market is abuzz with new rules and guidelines about the Goods and Services Tax (GST).

II. CONCLUSION

E-commerce companies are totally working like other dealers. They earn profit margin with every sale. They even offer secondary packing services, pick the product and supply goods to the end customers. It is same as other dealers do. Aggregators can say that they are not sellers but e-commerce operators are surely working like dealers and should be covered under GST.

GST will have a positive impact on E Commerce sector. Both the suppliers and the consumers will be benefited. It will be easier for the supplier to supply goods in other states. Burden of tax collection and payment to the government is removed from the consumers and suppliers through E Commerce and

put squarely on the shoulders of the E Commerce Operators.

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IMPACT OF GST ON MSME

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Abstract

With the Goods and Services Tax (GST) making rapid progress over the last few months, the technology leveraged, unified indirect tax regime is all set to be introduced by 1 July. While the MSME sector is likely to benefit from the far-reaching tax reform, there are some concerns regarding its various clauses and processes. A complicated compliances system and a rigid taxation regime place added limits on the growth potential of small enterprises. Uncertainty about claiming the Input Tax Credit (ITC), multiple registrations and returns, transference of tax liability, complex procedures, etc are some of the problem areas for MSMEs. To build technical literacy in MSMEs to make optimal use of the technology-enabled platform for GST, CII, under the Technology Facilitation Center (CII-TFC) initiative, is working to enhance awareness on GST and its provisions amongst MSMEs through webinars, road shows and policy roundtables across the country. In this paper discuss about the impact of Goods and Services Tax on Micro Small Medium Enterprises.

Key words: *Improved MSME, Impact and causes of Goods and Services Tax, revised tax, GST Rates on Services*

I. INTRODUCTION

The first meeting of the GST Council has set the threshold exemption limit at `20 lakhs, as against the

earlier proposed limit of 10 lakhs. This bodes well for MSMEs, as many of these enterprises will be saved from undertaking GST compliance. In another attempt to ease the compliance burden for small traders, the Government has announced the Composition/Compounding Scheme. A consensus on the scheme was arrived at during the GST Council meeting, which decided that traders with gross turnover cut-off of `50 lakhs will pay 1-2%, which is much lower than the GST rate. The Government has also set up the GST Network (GSTN) for online administration of the dealer registration process, tax payment and tax return filing and refund to tax payers with respect to GST. This is a paradigm shift in the taxation system and will result in a simplified and transparent tax regime which is easier to administer and monitor. Taxpayers registered under VAT, service tax, central excise duty, etc are being automatically migrated to the GSTN. Till March end, about 74% of the VAT assesses had shifted to the GSTN, while only 28% of the excise and service tax assesses had registered. Out of 8 million assesses, it is believed that 5.4 million will not need to register as they are below the turnover threshold. Those with turnover of `20 lakhs and above must register by April end, as unregistered entities would not be able to do business and obtain input credit under GST. The CBEC has started a 24x7 helpline and is undertaking

programs to complete the registration process at the earliest.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have been considered as the primary growth driver of the Indian economy for decades. It is further evident from the fact that today we have around 3 million SMEs in India contributing almost 50% of the industrial output and 42% of India's total export. For a developing country like India and its demographic diversity, SMEs have emerged as the leading employment-generating sector and has provided balanced development across sectors. Let's examine what would be the impact of GST on Small & Medium Enterprises.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to CII MSME Policy Dialogue Series 2016-17 describe that the Indian MSME sector is critical for the growth and development of the nation. The contribution of Indian MSMEs to the national output, employment generation, exports and industrial output is enormous. But a complicated compliances system and a rigid taxation regime place added limits on the growth potential of these enterprises. The Indian MSME sector will gain tremendously from the GST and the implementation of this taxation regime has been a recurring policy recommendation by various stakeholders engaged in initiatives for the amelioration of the SME sector in India.

Kumar (May 2014) studied "Goods and Service Tax in India-A way forward" and found that GST will be levied on all the goods and services except those exempted, dual model of GST will be there, which will include Central GST (CGST) collected by Center and State GST (SGST) collected by State. Central tax such as Central excise tax, additional excise duty, service tax, surcharges, countervailing duty, special additional duty of customs and state tax such as VAT/Sales tax, entertainment tax, luxury tax,

taxes on lottery, betting and gambling, state cesses and entry tax not in lieu of Octroi to be subsumed.

Lavanya Kumari (2017) No matter its effect on different sectors, the implementation of GST may want to propel the growth of Indian SMEs by using selling the authorities-led "Make in India" initiative and helping small-scale enterprises in terms of ease of doing enterprise. Not like country precise taxes, the GST regime will introduce a centralized registration device, which can help new businesses through allowing them to check in themselves on file. Moreover, decreased tax on new businesses can also spare such firms from the usual tax burden.

Statement of the Problem

Every initiative taken by the Government will have both pros and cons. It is important to study which of these two is greater. In the GST bill, it is proposed that if any goods or services are supplied by a person who is unregistered and supplied to a registered person, then GST needs to be paid by the registered person under reverse charge as a recipient. Therefore, even if any small businesses who does not take registration and claim the basic exemption threshold then the person receiving goods or services from them need to pay GST under reverse charge.

Significance of the problem

Since India hasn't implemented GST, a study of this kind besides creating awareness would also help in analyzing the pros and cons of GST and the important points that has to be kept in mind before its implementation as it would affect different stakeholders differently.

Objectives of the study

1. To measure the benefit of Goods and Services Tax in MSMEs.
2. To identify the impact and causes of Goods and Services Tax in MSMEs.

III. METHODOLOGY

Nature of study	Descriptive nature
Sources of Data	Secondary data
Collection of Data	Online and Web Resources
Secondary Data	Journals, Magazines, Newspaper, Websites & Reports

MSMEs will benefit as follows:

The uniform goods and service tax is going to benefit MSME sector the most by way of cutting down bureaucracy and the existing layered tax structure, West Bengal finance minister Amit Mitra said Wednesday. Mitra is also the chairman of the empowered committee of the state finance ministers. Mitra said that SME feeds large industries and the most labour-intensive sector and therefore they should be given simpler passage for doing business. The single tax structure of GST would be ideal platform for them. The single tax structure of GST would be ideal platform for them. "SMEs will benefit the most from single tax system, said Mitra, who is also the Empowered Committee of State Finance Ministers. Mitra said that to make life easier for SMEs, dual control of the centre and the states have been done away with. He was addressing an interactive session with SBI chairman Arundhuti Bhattacharya and him, at FICCI Banking Conclave here.

1. Starting business becomes easier:

Currently, the Sales Tax department has various turnover slabs which require VAT registration. A business with multi-state operation in this case has to follow varied tax rules applicable to different states. This not only creates excess complication but also adds to procedural fees, due to which the price sensitive MSMEs will be burdened. Uniform GST will standardize the process.

2. Improved MSME market expansion:

In the current system, big corporations procured goods based on MSME's locality in order to reduce overheads. Thus MSMEs limit their customers within state as they will bear the ultimate burden of tax on interstate sales, reducing their customer base. With implementation of GST, this will be nullified as tax credit will transfer irrespective of location of buyer and seller. This allows MSME segment to expand their reach across borders.

3. Lower logistical overheads:

As GST is tax neutral it will eliminate time consuming border tax procedures and toll check posts and encourages supply of goods across borders. Accordingly the logistical cost for companies manufacturing bulk good will be reduced. Such costs can be crucial for the survival of MSMEs.

4. Aids MSMEs dealing in sales and services:

GST will not distinguish between sales and services. This is good news for the MSMEs that deal with sales and services model of business, for them the taxation is simplified and will be calculated on total.

5. Unified market:

GST will allow flexibility in transfer of goods across states and reduce the cost of doing business, as the reform will cut down multiple taxes imposed by state and central government.

6. Purchase of Capital Goods:

In the current system, only 50% of the input tax credit against purchase of Capital Goods is available in the year of purchase and the balance amount in subsequent years. Under GST regime, entire amount of input tax credit can be availed in the year of purchase itself. This will support "Make in India" campaign.

7. Negative Impact of GST on MSMEs:

While the MSMEs will enjoy the tax neutrality, reduction in duty threshold is one of

their main concerns in warming up to the GST bill.

8. The burden of lower threshold:

The GST bill proposes a reduction in threshold to be Rs.

9 lakh to increase the tax net, Rs. 41akh for North Eastern states. (However, GST council has increased the threshold limit from 10 lakh to 20 lakh and from 41akh to 10 lakh for North eastern states) Under the reform, any service provider or retailer will be subject to tax levy. In the current central excise law threshold is Rs.1.5 crore. This reduction will significantly impact the MSMEs' working capital.

9. Selective tax levying:

IV. Impact and causes of Goods and Services Tax

Compliance Procedure	Positives	Negatives
Registration	Online registration will ensure timely receipt of certificate of registration and minimal bureaucracy interface	Not all the SMEs have technical expertise to deal with online systems, thus most of them will need intermediaries to obtain registration for them. This will add to their registration cost.
Payment	Electronic compliance will bring transparency and will also reduce the compliance cost.	Since funds are required to be maintained in the form of electronic credit ledger with the tax department, it may result in liquidity crunch.
Refund	Electronic refund procedures will fast track the process and enhance liquidity for SMEs	Refunds can be claimed only after filing of relevant returns. Also it depends on the compliances done by the supplier and his rating.
Returns	All returns are required to be filed electronically and input tax credit and tax liability adjustment will happen automatically on the basis of these returns	Minimum of thirty-seven returns are required to be filed by every registered taxpayer during a financial year. Thus SMEs will have to deploy additional resources and eventual cost of compliance will increase.

No doubt that GST is aimed to increase the taxpayer base, majorly SMEs into its scope and will put a burden of compliance and associated costs to them. But in the long run, GST will turn these SMEs more competitive with a level playing field between large enterprises and them. Furthermore, these Indian SMEs would be able to compete with foreign competition coming from cheap cost centers such as China, Philippines and Bangladesh.

GST will not be applicable to Alcoholic liquor for human consumption and Petroleum based businesses, which creates further gap and does not support the 'unified market' ideology of GST.

10. The burden of higher tax rate for Service Provider:

Presently Service Tax rate is 15%. GST rate will be around 18%. The scenario in the service sector will further be impacted as the concept of Centralised Registration has been done away with and each unit in different states will have to take separate registration. Thus even if services are supplied by company's one Unit in State A to another Unit in State B, then also taxes will be payable.

The Burden of Lower Threshold:

The GST bill proposes a reduction in threshold to be around Rs. 10 lakhs to increase the tax net, Rs. 5 lakh for North Eastern states. Under the reform, any service provider or retailer will be subject to tax levy. In the current central excise law threshold is Rs.1.5 crore. This reduction will significantly impact the SMEs' working capital. For example, a manufacturer who trades today at Rs. 25 lakhs

without any tax levy will be expected to pay GST post implementation. As the threshold is low, most MSMEs are now exempted and will have to pay a chunk of their capital towards tax in future.

No Tax Differentiation for Luxury Items and Services:

The tax neutrality won't differentiate luxury goods and normal goods. Currently the state and central government levy higher taxes on luxury goods and services. Under GST implementation, all goods and services will have to pay the same tax. Which will lead to rich becoming richer and poor becoming poorer? It is not an ideal situation for SMEs competing against large businesses.

Some of the revised tax items were:

- There would be two categories of GST rates on cinema, 28% in case tickets above Rs.100 and 18% in case of tickets up to Rs.100
- Cashew revised from 12% to 5%
- Packaged food, including some fruits and vegetables, pickles, toppings, instant food, sauces revised from 18% to 12%
- Agarbatti revised from 12% to 5%
- Dental wax revised from 28% to 18%
- Insulin revised from 12% to 5%
- Plastic beads revised from 28% to 18%
- Plastic turpolin revised from 28% to 18%
- School bags revised from 28% to 18%
- Exercise books revised from 18% to 12%
- Coloring books revised from 12% to nil
- Pre-cast concrete pipes revised from 28% to 18%
- Cutlery revised from 18% to 12%
- Tractor components revised from 28% to 18%
- Computer printers revised from 28% to 18%

GST Rates on Services

- All services have been fitted into four different rates, which are 5%, 12%, the standard 18% and the luxury rate of 28%
- Travelling on metro, local train, religious travel, Haj yatra will all be exempt from GST: revenue secretary, Hasmukh Adhia.
- AC train travel to get cheaper under GST
- Transport services (Railways, air transport) will be under the 5% category because their main input is petroleum, which is outside GST ambit.
- 18% tax slab for telecom, financial services
- Healthcare and education have been exempted from the service list. Most service structures will remain as is, said sources. This implies services will become cheaper in some segments

V. CONCLUSION

It shall be very important that the sector through its associations or various representation bodies highlight these issues to the law makers so that the same can be resolved at the earliest. In fact, recently government has also formed a special committee to look after the issues faced by MSME sector in GST. It is urged to the industry that they proactively highlight the above issues and obtain the relief prior to advent of GST as once GST is implemented; the chances of respite would be very minimal for the sector. Every major reform is faced with certain hurdles, and arguments from various stakeholders. However, from an SME perspective, GST will bring in many positives compared to the current systems such as easy process of availing input credit, single point tax, elimination of cascading tax system, and simpler taxation

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ROLE ON GOODS AND SERVICES TAX (GST)

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Abstract

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax which was introduced in India on 1 July 2017 and was applicable throughout India. The reform process of India's indirect tax regime was started in 1986 by VishwanathPratap Singh, Finance Minister in Rajiv Gandhi's government, with the introduction of the Modified Value Added Tax (MODVAT). IGST complicates tax collection for State Governments by disabling them from collecting the tax owed to them directly from the Central Government. The GST is imposed at different rates on different items. In the GST system, taxes for both Centre and State will be collected at the point of sale. The introduction of the GST increased the costs of most consumer goods and services in India. Introduction of a GST is very much essential in the emerging environment of the Indian economy. By implementing the GST, India will gain \$15 billion a year. Adoption and migration to the new GST system would involve teething troubles and learning for the entire ecosystem. GST is the most logical steps towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country since independence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax which was introduced in India on 1 July 2017 and was applicable throughout India which replaced multiple cascading taxes levied by the central and state governments. It was introduced as The Constitution (One Hundred and First Amendment) Act 2017, following the passage of Constitution 122nd Amendment Bill. The GST is governed by a GST Council and its Chairman is the Finance Minister of India. Under GST, goods and services are

taxed at the following rates, 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. There is a special rate of 0.25% on rough precious and semi-precious stones and 3% on gold. In addition a cess of 15% or other rates on top of 28% GST applies on few items like aerated drinks, luxury cars and tobacco products. GST was initially proposed to replace a slew of indirect taxes with a unified tax and was therefore set to dramatically reshape the country's 2 trillion dollar economy. The rate of GST in India is between double to four times that levied in other countries like Singapore.

History

The reform process of India's indirect tax regime was started in 1986 by VishwanathPratap Singh, Finance Minister in Rajiv Gandhi's government, with the introduction of the Modified Value Added Tax (MODVAT). Subsequently, Manmohan Singh, then Finance Minister under of P V Narasimha Rao, initiated early discussions on a Value Added Tax at the state level.[7] A single common "Goods and Services Tax (GST)" was proposed and given a go-ahead in 1999 during a meeting between then Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee and his economic advisory panel, which included three former RBI governors IG Patel, Bimal Jalan and C Rangarajan. Vajpayee set up a committee headed by the then finance minister of West Bengal, Asim Dasgupta to design a GST model. The Ravi Dasgupta committee was also tasked with putting in place the backend technology and logistics (later came to be known as the GST Network, or GSTN, in 2017) for rolling out a uniform taxation regime in the country. In 2002, the Vajpayee government formed a task force under Vijay Kelkar to recommend tax reforms. In 2005, the

Kelkar committee recommended rolling out GST as suggested by the 12th Finance Commission.

After the fall of the BJP-led NDA government in 2004, and the election of a Congress-led UPA government, the new Finance Minister P Chidambaram in February 2006 continued work on the same and proposed a GST rollout by 1 April 2010. However in 2010, with the Trinamool Congress routing CPI(M) out of power in West Bengal, Asim Dasgupta resigned as the head of the GST committee. Dasgupta admitted in an interview that 80% of the task had been done. In 2014, the NDA government was re-elected into power, this time under the leadership of Narendra Modi. With the consequential dissolution of the 15th Lok Sabha, the GST Bill – approved by the standing committee for reintroduction – lapsed. Seven months after the formation of the Modi government, the new Finance Minister Arun Jaitley introduced the GST Bill in the Lok Sabha, where the BJP had a majority. In February 2015, Jaitley set another deadline of 1 April 2016 to implement GST. In May 2016, the Lok Sabha passed the Constitution Amendment Bill, paving way for GST. However, the Opposition, led by the Congress demanded that the GST Bill be again sent back to the Select Committee of the Rajya Sabha due to disagreements on several statements in the Bill relating to taxation. Finally in August 2016, the Amendment Bill was passed. Over the next 15 to 20 days, 18 states ratified the GST Bill and the President Pranab Mukherjee gave his assent to it. A 21-members select committee was formed to look into the proposed GST laws. State and Union Territory GST laws were passed by all the states and Union Territories of India except Jammu & Kashmir, paving the way for smooth rollout of the tax from 1 July 2017. There was to be no GST on the sale and purchase of securities. That continues to be governed by Securities Transaction Tax (STT).

Launch

The Goods and Services Tax was launched at midnight on 1 July 2017 by the then President of India, Pranab Mukherjee, and Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi. The launch was marked by a historic midnight (1 July – 2 July) session of both the houses of parliament convened at the Central Hall of the Parliament. Though the session was attended by high-profile guests from the business and the entertainment industry including Ratan Tata, it was boycotted by the opposition due to the predicted problems that it was bound to lead to for the middle and lower class Indians. It is one of the few midnight sessions that have been held by the parliament - the others being the declaration of India's independence on 15 August 1947, and the silver and golden jubilees of that occasion. Members of the Congress boycotted the GST launch altogether. They were joined by members of the Trinamool Congress, Communist Parties of India and the DMK. These parties reported that they found virtually no difference between the GST and the existing taxation system, claiming that the government was trying to merely rebrand the current taxation system. They also argued that the GST would increase existing rates on common daily goods while reducing rates on luxury items, and affect many Indians adversely, especially the middle, lower middle and poorer classes.

Taxation Scheme

Taxes Subsumed

The single GST replaced several former taxes and levies which included: central excise duty, services tax, additional customs duty, surcharges, state-level value added tax and Octroi. Other levies which were applicable on inter-state transportation of goods have also been done away with in GST regime. GST is levied on all transactions such as sale, transfer, purchase, barter, lease, or import of goods and/or services. India adopted a dual GST model, meaning that taxation is administered by both the Union and State Governments. Transactions made

within a single state are levied with Central GST (CGST) by the Central Government and State GST (SGST) by the State governments. For inter-state transactions and imported goods or services, an Integrated GST (IGST) is levied by the Central Government. GST is a consumption-based tax, therefore, taxes are paid to the state where the goods or services are consumed not the state in which they were produced. IGST complicates tax collection for State Governments by disabling them from collecting the tax owed to them directly from the Central Government. Under the previous system, a state would only have to deal with a single government in order to collect tax revenue.

HSN code in GST:

HSN (Harmonized System of Nomenclature) is a 6-digit code for identifying the applicable rate of GST on different products as per CGST rules. If a company has turnover up to RS. 1.5 Crore in preceding financial year then they need not to mention HSN code while supplying goods on invoices, if a company has turnover more than 1.5 Cr but up to 5 Cr then they need to mention 2 digit HSN code while supplying goods on invoices and if turnover cross 5 Cr then they shall mention 4 digit HSN code on invoices.

Rates

The GST is imposed at different rates on different items. The rate of GST is 18% for soaps and 28% on washing detergents. GST on movie tickets is based on slabs, with 18% GST for tickets that cost less than Rs. 100 and 28% GST on tickets costing more than Rs.100. The rate on under-construction property booking is 12%. Some industries and products were exempted by the government and remain untaxed under GST, such as dairy products, products of milling industries, fresh vegetables & fruits, meat products, and other groceries and necessities.

The introduction of the GST increased the costs of most consumer goods and services in India including food, hotel charges, insurance and cinema tickets. Upon its introduction in the country, GST led to a number of protests by the business community, primarily due to an increase in overall taxes and hence the prices of goods. Checkposts across the country were abolished ensuring free and fast movement of goods. The Central Government had proposed to insulate the revenues of the States from the impact of GST, with the expectation that in due course, GST will be levied on petroleum and petroleum products. The central government had assured states of compensation for any revenue loss incurred by them from the date of GST for a period of five years. However, no concrete laws have yet been made to support such action.

Goods and Services Tax Network (GSTN):

As per the government website on GST, "Goods and Services Tax" Network (GSTN) is a nonprofit organisation proposed to be formed for creating a website / platform for all the concerned parties related to the GST, namely stakeholders, government and taxpayers to collaborate on a single portal. When up and running, the portal is supposed to be accessible to the central government which allows it to track down every transaction on its end while taxpayers are advertised to have the ability of connecting this to their tax returns. However its efficacy and efficiency is yet to be tested. The IT network was touted to be developed by unnamed private firms. The known authorised capital of GSTN is ₹10 crore (US\$1.6 million) in which Central Government holds 24.5 percent of shares while the state government holds 24.5 percent and rest with private banking firms for smooth running of the transactions.

The proposed model of GST and the rate:

A dual GST system is planned to be implemented in India as proposed by the Empowered

Committee under which the GST will be divided into two parts:

- State Goods and Services Tax (SGST)
- Central Goods and Services Tax (CGST)

Both SGST and CGST will be levied on the taxable value of a transaction. All goods and services, leaving aside a few, will be brought into the GST and there will be no difference between goods and services. The GST system will combine Central excise duty, additional excise duty, services tax, State VAT entertainment tax etc. under one banner. The GST rate is expected to be around 14-16 per cent. After the combined GST rate is fixed, the States and the Centre will decide on the SGST and CGST rates. At present, 10 per cent is levied on services and the indirect taxes on most goods is around 20 per cent.

Advantages of GST Bill:

Introduction of a GST is very much essential in the emerging environment of the Indian economy.

- There is no doubt that in production and distribution of goods, services are increasingly used or consumed and vice versa. Separate taxes for goods and services, which is the present taxation system, requires division of transaction values into value of goods and services for taxation, leading to greater complications, administration, including compliances costs. In the GST system, when all the taxes are integrated, it would make possible the taxation burden to be split equitably between manufacturing and services.

- GST will be levied only at the final destination of consumption based on VAT principle and not at various points (from manufacturing to retail outlets). This will help in removing economic distortions and bring about development of a common national market.

- It will also help to build a transparent and corruption-free tax administration. Presently, a tax is levied on when a finished product moves out from a

factory, which is paid by the manufacturer, and it is again levied at the retail outlet when sold.

Benefits of GST Bill:

For the Centre and the States

According to experts, by implementing the GST, India will gain \$15 billion a year. This is because, it will promote more exports, create more employment opportunities and boost growth. It will divide the burden of tax between manufacturing and services.

For individuals and companies

In the GST system, taxes for both Centre and State will be collected at the point of sale. Both will be charged on the manufacturing cost. Individuals will be benefited by this as prices are likely to come down and lower prices mean more consumption, and more consumption means more production, thereby helping in the growth of the companies.

Items not under GST

Alcohol, tobacco, petroleum products

GST Disadvantages:

- Some Economist say that GST in India would impact negatively on the real estate market. It would add up to 8 percent to the cost of new homes and reduce demand by about 12 percent.

- Some Experts says that CGST(Central GST), SGST(State GST) are nothing but new names for Central Excise/Service Tax, VAT and CST. Hence, there is no major reduction in the number of tax layers.

- Some retail products currently have only four percent tax on them. After GST, garments and clothes could become more expensive.

- The aviation industry would be affected. Service taxes on airfares currently range from six to nine percent. With GST, this rate will surpass fifteen percent and effectively double the tax rate.

- Adoption and migration to the new GST system would involve teething troubles and learning for the entire ecosystem.

II. CONCLUSION

GST is the most logical steps towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country since independence. GST is leviable on all supply of goods and provision of services as well combination thereof. All sectors of economy whether the industry, business including Govt. departments and service sector shall have to bear impact of GST. All sections of economy viz. big, medium, small scale units, intermediaries, importers, exporters, traders, professionals and consumers shall be directly affected by GST... One of the biggest taxation reforms in India – the Goods and Service Tax (GST) -- is all set to integrate State economies and boost overall growth. GST will create a single, unified Indian market to make the economy stronger. Experts say that GST is likely to improve tax collections and Boost India's economic development by breaking tax barriers between States and integrating India through a uniform tax rate. Under GST, the taxation burden will be divided equitably between manufacturing and services, through a lower tax rate by increasing the tax base and minimizing exemptions.

IMPACT OF GST ON E-COMMERCE AND TCS PROVISIONS UNDER GST

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Abstract

Electronic commerce or EC is buying and selling of goods and services, or the transmitting of funds or data, over an electronic network, primarily the internet. GST has a noticeable impact on each and every sector including E commerce sector. This paper focus on the impact of GST on Ec-commerce and TCS provisions under GST.

Keyword: E commerce, Tax, TCS provisions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Introduction of the goods and services tax (GST) may be a big positive for the e-commerce industry. With no tax laws in place for the industry currently, tax is imposed based on the understanding of various state governments. GST will help resolve many supply chain issues which impact the e-commerce sector.

GST is a single comprehensive tax regime that will be applicable across all states in India on the sale, manufacture and consumption of goods and services. Since the same tax regulation will apply across different states, e-commerce companies (as well as those from other industries) will not have to struggle with the complex regulatory structure that currently prevails in the country. They will also be

able to devise strategies in keeping with the GST norms.

The roll-out of GST is likely to simplify the logistics issue for e-commerce companies. Also, the practice of companies to minimise their tax liabilities by finding loopholes in existing sourcing, distribution and warehousing strategies will have to undergo a change.

Types of E Commerce

There can be two types of E commerce sellers:

1. E commerce operator/ marketplace (e.g. Flipkart, Amazon etc): It is an entity which owns, operates or manages digital or electronic facility or platform for E commerce.

2. Suppliers on E commerce platform: It is an entity which supplies goods or services on/through an E commerce platform.

II. BENEFITS OF GST FOR ONLINE SELLERS

- Higher transparency when comes to state wise tax regimes.

- Pan-Indian rate structure
- Removing Cascading tax effect
- Simplification of tax procedures
- Smoother interstate logistics management with common a tax
- Lesser trade barriers

- Uniform tax structure helps to price and margin properly regardless of where it's being shipped.

- Addresses challenges and concerns, Similar to tax evasion by Amazon and few of its sellers

- A coherent flow of Input tax credit.

III. IMPACT OF GST ON E COMMERCE

Advantages of GST for E commerce:

- GST will replace 17 indirect taxes which will reduce the cost and provide a common market.

- Standard tax rates for each product, bringing offline sellers to the same level in terms of costing and pricing.

- TCS will be handed over as collection towards GST to the government.

- E commerce will be effectively used in all the states.

- Logistics, inventory costs will fall and reduction in number of warehouses..

Disadvantages of GST for E commerce:

- Dual control on every business by central and state government.

- States may loose autonomy to change their tax rates.

- Retail businesses may oppose because their taxes will go up.

- Small businesses may find it difficult to use the online connectivity with GST network.

- Service sector may oppose because they have to register in every state they want to cater.

TCS Provisions for E Commerce Operator

Rate of TCS under GST

Every e-commerce operator has to collect 1% under CGST Act and 1% under SGST Act and if an interstate transaction is being done, he will collect 2% of tax under IGST Act on the net values of taxable supplies. It means that any dealers/traders who are selling goods online through e commerce platforms like Flipkart, Amazon etc. would get their payment after deduction of 2% tax by e commerce operators.

It may be noted that as per the notification issued by the government on 26th June 2017, the provisions of TCS has been put on hold and it will come into force from a date which will be communicated later.

IV. CONCLUSION

GST will have a positive impact on E Commerce sector. Both the suppliers and the consumers will be benefited. It will be easier for the supplier to supply goods in other states. Burden of tax collection and payment to the government is removed from the consumers and suppliers through E Commerce and put squarely on the shoulders of the E Commerce Operators.

GST AND ITS IMPACT IN INDIA

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Abstract

In India, taxes are collected by the State and Union governments separately, leading to cascading effect of taxes. There are taxes at different rates and at multiple points. These taxes lead to increased tax burden on the Indian products affecting the prices and sales in the domestic as well as international markets. Remedy to the above scenario of multiple taxes and its cascading effect which is a burden on common man is GST. The framework has dual GST which means it will have a federal structure. GST will basically have three kinds of taxes namely Central, State and one called integrated GST that will help to tackle inter-state transactions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is defined as the tax levied when a consumer buys a good or service. It is proposed to be a comprehensive indirect tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods as well as services. GST aims to replace all indirect taxes levied on goods and services by the Indian Central and State governments. GST would subsume with a single comprehensive tax, bringing it all under a single umbrella, eliminating the cascading effect of taxes on the production and distribution prices of goods and services. Under the current GST tax reform, all forms of supply of goods and services like transfer, sale, barter, exchange and rental will have a CGST and SGST.

II. FEATURES OF GST

- GST will have two components namely Central GST levied by the Centre and State GST levied by the states.
- Petroleum products, alcohol for human consumption and tobacco have been kept out of the purview of the GST.
- The final consumer will have to bear only the GST charged by the last dealer in the supply chain.
- The tax collected would be divided between the Centre and the States in a manner that would be defined by the parliament, as per the recommendations of the GST Council.
- It proposes an additional tax not exceeding 1% on inter-state trade in goods, to be levied and collected by the Centre to compensate the states for two years, or as recommended by the GST Council, for losses resulting from implementing the GST.

III. EMERGENCE OF GST IN INDIA

Implementing GST is considered as a significant step in the reform of indirect taxation in India. Amalgamating several Central and State taxes into a single tax would help mitigate the double taxation,

leading to a common national market. From the consumers point of view, the advantage would be in terms of a reduction in the overall tax burden on goods, which is currently estimated at 25%-30%.

Advantages

- Reduction in prices: Manufacturers or traders would not have to include taxes as a part of their cost of production, which would lead to reduction in prices.

- Lower compliance and procedural cost: There would be reduction in the load to maintain compliance. Also keeping record of CGST, SGST and IGST separately would not be required.

- Move towards a Unified GST: Although India is adopting dual GST, it is still a good move towards a Unified GST which is regarded as the best method of Indirect Taxes.

- Growth in GDP: GST rollout can help boost India's GDP growth by 100-200 bps or (1% to 2%) as this will help faster and cheaper movement of goods across the country with a uniform taxation structure.

- Invites foreign investors: GST's successful implementation would give a strong signal to the foreign investors about India's ability to support business.

- Beneficial to common man: GST will be beneficial with more transparency, efficient compliance, ramp up in GDP growth to the Centre, states, industrialists, manufacturers, the common man and the country at large.

- Will help in reducing tax evasion: All the distributors will prefer purchase with invoices, because that would give them better profit margins as the distributor will get credit of all the taxes paid at the previous stage. Currently, it is the distributor who has to bear the burden of the excise duty. So if the customer insists on taking the bill, we can presume that the tax evasion should fall. This will indeed be the biggest advantage of GST.

- Removal of location bias approach: GST would help to even out the tax structures across various states, omitting location bias. As taxes should not be a hindrance to the investment decision of an individual, introduction of GST would help an investor to put up business units in any state without the worry of tax difference. This would boost the business in undeveloped locations as well.

- Lesser incentive for tax evasion: Currently, taxes are being paid on the entire underlying value of a product or service, but with GST, companies will have to pay tax only on the value-addition. This would lead to reduction in the actual tax paid and also decrease the incentive for evasion.

- Unified market: With the implementation of GST, there will be cut down of individual taxes imposed by the central government as well by the states. This would lead to a unified market and would boost the movement of goods across states with drop in the business costs.

- Increase in State revenues: GST will expand the tax base and thereby lead to increase in the revenues available at the States' and Centre's disposal. This would thereby help in increasing the resources of the poorer / consumer states like, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh will increase substantially.

- Improvement in tax governance: GST would improve tax governance in two ways. One it is related to self-policing incentive inherent to a valued-added tax that can work very powerfully in the GST. The second relates to the dual monitoring structure of GST, one by the States and the other by the Centre.

IV. CHALLENGES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF GST

India is adopting a dual GST, namely the Central GST (CGST) and state GST (SGST). The main hurdle in the implementation will be the coordination among different states. The Centre and States will have to come to consensus on the uniform GST rates,

inter-state transaction of goods and services, infrastructural requirements to implement the new tax reform, all of which needs to be worked upon for the smooth transition into GST pattern.

Other factors to be considered:

- **Impact and Incidence of tax:** Since GST is a destination based tax, there should be clarity on where the goods are going. Proper methodology should be chalked out as it would require proper management in terms of services provided.

- **Rate of Tax:** There has to be uniformity in the implementation of GST in all states at the same time and the same rates or else it would be difficult to comply with the law provisions.

- **Change in Business Software:** Most businesses use accounting software or ERPs for filing tax returns which have excise, VAT, and service tax already incorporated in them. The transition to GST will require businesses to change their ERPs, too; either by upgrading the software or by purchasing new GST-compliant software. This will lead to increased costs of buying new software and training employees on how to use it.

ClearTax is the first company in India to launch a ready-to-use GST software. It is currently available at reduced prices for SMEs, to help them to transit to GST smoothly. To ease the pain of the people, it doesn't require to update the existing software and provide free services for first 3 months.

- **GST Compliance:** SMEs are still not completely aware of the nuances of the new tax regime. Changing over to a completely new system of taxation requires understanding of the minutiae, which businesses lack right now. Most of them are worried about filing timely returns, but it is important to note that even before businesses can reach the filing stage they have to issue GST-compliant invoices. For a traditionally pen-and-paper economy like India, this change to digital record-keeping is going to be massive. Invoices after 1st July will need

to be GST-compliant with all details such as GSTIN, place of supply, HSN code etc. as mandated by the law.

- **Increase in Operating Costs:** Most small businesses in India do not employ tax professionals, and have traditionally preferred to pay taxes and file returns on their own to save costs. However, they will require professional assistance to become GST compliant as it is a completely new system. While this will benefit the professionals, the small businesses will have to bear the additional cost of hiring experts. Also, businesses will need to train their employees in GST compliance, further increasing their overhead expenses.

- **Policy Change during the middle of the year:** GST goes live three months into the financial year 2017-18. So, for FY 2017-18, business will follow the old tax structure for the first 3 months, and GST for the rest of the time. It is impossible to cross over from one tax structure to the other in just a day, and hence businesses will end up running both tax systems in parallel, which might result in confusion and compliance issues.

- **Online Procedure:** GST compliance, return filing and payments all have to be done online. Many small businesses are not tech-savvy and do not have the resources for fully computerized compliance. Even as the rest of the nation gets ready to go digital, businesses in small cities across India face a huge technology problem in the days ahead.

Cloud-based software like the ClearTax GST software could be an answer to this problem. This does not require any downloads, and the process for return filing on ClearTax GST is very simple. Business owners need only upload their invoices, and the software will populate the return forms automatically with the information from the invoices. Any errors in invoices will be clearly identified by the software in real-time thus increasing efficiency and timeliness.

- **Higher Tax Burden for Manufacturing SMEs:** Small businesses in the manufacturing sector will not have it easy in the GST regime. Under the excise laws, only manufacturing business with a turnover exceeding Rs.1.50 crores had to pay excise duty. Whereas, under GST the turnover limit has been reduced to Rs.20 lakhs, thus increasing the tax burden for many manufacturing SMEs. However, SMEs with a turnover of upto Rs.75 lakhs can opt for the composition scheme and pay only 1% tax on turnover in lieu of GST and enjoy lesser compliances. The catch though is these businesses will then not be able to claim any input tax credit. The decision to choose between higher taxes or the composition scheme (and thereby no ITC) will be a tough one for many SMEs.

- **No Clarity on Tax Holidays:** Many manufacturers (textile, pharmaceutical, FMCG industries) enjoy tax holidays and state benefit schemes. There is still no notification regarding these benefits. This will mean increased costs for these industries, which will probably be passed on to the end consumers.

- **Disruption to Business:** Cloth merchants (unorganized) are going on strike to protest against GST. Eateries and drug shops in Chennai are also protesting the regime change – and this is only the tip of the iceberg. After the days, we had seen more of these protests happening across the country and these had undoubtedly disrupted business. If there's any solace, it's in knowing that other countries who implemented GST never had it easy either.

V. CONCLUSION

The government has reduced the burden of compliance for businesses by relaxing the return filing requirements for the first two months post implementation. Also, the provisions of TCS on e-commerce and registration for online sellers have also been relaxed for the time being. Change is definitely never easy. The government had smoothed the road to GST. It is important to take a leaf from global

economies that have implemented GST before us, and who overcame the teething troubles to experience the advantages of having a unified tax system and easy input credits.

At present, GST is implemented, most of the current challenges of this move are only a story of the past. India will become a single market where goods can move freely and there will lesser compliances to deal with for businesses. The benefits of GST will definitely outweigh the disadvantages of GST.

GOODS AND SERVICE TAXES (GST)

AND ITS IMPACTS

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Abstract

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax which was come into force in India on 1 July 2017 and was applicable throughout India which replaced multiple cascading taxes levied by the central and state government. Only a registered person can charge and collect GST on the taxable supplies of goods and services made by him. GST is charged on the value or selling price of the products. The amount of GST incurred on input (input tax) can be deducted from the amount of GST charged (output tax) by the registered person. Through GST, the government aims to create a single comprehensive tax structure that will subsume all the other smaller indirect taxes on consumption like service tax, vat, and etc. GST will break the complicated structure of separate central and state taxes. Under GST, the government has fixed GST rates on 1,211 goods and 500 services in the range of five to 28 per cent. Certain items such as alcohol, petrol, diesel and natural gas will be out of GST. In addition to these, the GST Council has also classified certain items under the 0 per cent tax rate, implying that GST will not be levied on them. This list includes items of daily use such as wheat, rice, milk, eggs etc. GST is applicable mainly for businesses and hence won't directly affect the salaried class and self-employed professionals such as doctors, lawyers etc. However, it will impact their expenses due to the change in rates of goods and services they avail. Other than that, they will continue to pay their income tax like before. The medical sector has been exempted from GST. GST will bring in transparent

and corruption-free tax administration, removing the current shortcomings in indirect tax structure. GST is business friendly as well as consumer friendly. GST in India is poised to drastically improve the positions of each of these stakeholders.

I. INTRODUCTION

What is GST

Full form of GST is 'Goods and Services Tax'. It is a single indirect tax for the whole nation, one which will make India a unified common market. It is a single tax on the supply of goods and services, right from the manufacturer to the consumer. The GST Bill was introduced in Lok Saba in 2009 by erstwhile UPA government but they failed to get it passed. The NDA government introduced a 'slightly modified' version of the GST Bill in the Parliament and both the Houses passed it. Through GST, the government aims to create a single comprehensive tax structure that will subsume all the other smaller indirect taxes on consumption like service tax, etc. Currently, tax rates differ from state to state. GST will ensure a comprehensive tax base with minimum exemptions, will help industry, which will be able to reap benefits of common procedures and claim credit for taxes paid. GST, as per government estimates, will boost India's GDP by around 2 per cent.

Necessities of GST

GST will break the complicated structure of separate central and state taxes which often overlap with each other to create a uniform taxation system which will be applicable across the country. Taxes will be implemented more effectively since a network

of indirect taxes like excise duty, service tax, central sales tax, value added tax (VAT) and octopi will be replaced by one single tax. The state will still have a say in taxation, as the number of taxes will be reduced to three with Central GST, State GST and Integrated GST for inter-state dealings.

Rates of GST

The GST Council, headed by Jaitley and of which all states Finance Ministers are members, has approved four main tax slabs – 0 per cent, 5 per cent, 12 per cent, 18 per cent and 28 per cent that aims to lower tax incidence on essential items and to keep the highest rate for luxury and demerits goods. The lowest rate of zero and 5 per cent will be on items of mass consumption which are used particularly by common people. The second and third category of standard rates of 12 and 18 per cent will accommodate most of the goods and services. The fourth slab of 28 per cent is levied mainly on white goods such as refrigerators, washing machines etc.

Exemptions Under GST

Under GST, the government has fixed GST rates on 1,211 goods and 500 services in the range of five to 28 per cent. Certain items such as alcohol, petrol,

diesel and natural gas will be exempt under the GST. In addition to these, the GST Council has also classified certain items under the 0 per cent tax rate, implying that GST will not be levied on them. This list includes items of daily use such as wheat, rice, milk, eggs, fresh vegetables, meat, fish, stamps, judicial papers, printed books, newspapers, bangles, handloom, bones and horn cores, bone grist, bone meal, children's' picture, drawing or coloring books, human hair.

II. IMPACT ON GST OF SALARIED EMPLOYEES AND SELF EMPLOYED PROFESSIONALS

GST is applicable mainly for businesses and hence won't directly affect the salaried class and self-employed professionals such as doctors, lawyers etc. However, it will impact their expenses due to the change in rates of goods and services they avail. Other than that, they will continue to pay their income tax like before. The medical sector has been exempted from GST.

Benefits of GST:

To trade	To Consumers	
Reduction in multiplicity of taxes	Simpler Tax system	Create unified common national market for India, giving a boost to Foreign investment and "Make in India" campaign
Mitigation of cascading / double taxation	Reduction in prices of goods & services due to elimination of cascading	Boost export and manufacturing activity and leading to substantive economic growth
More efficient neutralization of taxes especially for exports	Uniform prices throughout the country	Help in poverty eradication by generating more employment
Development of common national market	Transparency in taxation system	Uniform SGST and IGST rates to reduce the incentive for tax evasion
Simpler tax regime	Increase in employment opportunities	
Fewer rates and exemptions		
Distinction between Goods & Services no longer required		

Other Benefits of Goods and Services Tax:

- Will prevent cascading of taxes as Input Tax Credit will be available across goods and services at every stage of supply.
- Harmonization of laws, procedures and rates of tax.
- More efficient neutralization of taxes especially for exports thereby making our products more competitive in the international market and give boost to Indian Exports.
- Improve the overall investment climate in the country which will naturally benefit the development in the states.
- Average tax burden on companies is likely to come down which is expected to reduce prices and lower prices mean more consumption, which in turn means more production thereby helping in the growth of the industries . This will create India as a "Manufacturing hub".
- Will improve environment of compliance as all returns to be filed online, input credits to be verified online, encouraging more paper trail of transactions.
- Common procedures for registration of taxpayers, refund of taxes, uniform formats of tax return, common tax base, common system of classification of goods and services will lend greater certainty to taxation system.
- Timelines to be provided for important activities like obtaining registration, refunds, etc.
- GST will be beneficial with more transparency, efficient compliance, ramp up in GDP growth to the Centre, states, industrialists, manufacturers, the common man and the country at large.

Impact of GST

The impact of the GST on the prices of goods and services will largely depend on the item in question. It will also depend upon the respective State governments and their intervention with respect to controlling prices of essential commodities. Milk, for example, which is likely to see a spike in prices after GST is implemented, can still be sold at cheaper rates, if the State government offers a subsidy on it. A comprehensive IT system, GSTN, will allot universal GST numbers (similar to PAN) to all manufacturers, traders, stockiest, wholesalers and retailers. This will simplify the administration of indirect taxes and plug leakages. The government also plans to incentivise tax compliance by traders. Whether the GST will be beneficial to the poor or not only time can tell. Prices of vegetables and fruits are likely to rise under the GST regime and services such as eating at restaurants will get more expensive. What will likely get cheaper are items such as clothes, as cascading taxes at various stages of manufacturing would no longer apply to them. With respect to those living below the poverty line, there might not be a direct impact of the GST on them as such since basic necessities like food are unlikely to attract the GST but increased collections of the GST with a larger tax base should provide an impetus to the government to allocate more money for social and poverty alleviation programmes. Thus, the GST should benefit all sections of the society. Additionally, the GST, being a nationwide tax, could lead to possibly higher inflation in the first few years of its introduction but would gradually increase the overall GDP.

III. CONCLUSION

GST is one of the biggest indirect tax reforms in the country. GST is expected to bring together state economies and improve overall economic growth of the nation. GST is a comprehensive indirect tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods as well as services at the national level. It will replace

all indirect taxes levied on goods and services by states and Central. GST will bring in transparent and corruption-free tax administration, removing the current shortcomings in indirect tax structure. GST is business friendly as well as consumer friendly. GST in India is poised to drastically improve the positions of each of these stakeholders. We need a change in the taxation system which is better than earlier taxation. This need for change leads us to 'need for GST'. GST will allow India to better negotiate its terms in the international trade forums. GST aimed at increasing the taxpayer base by bringing SMEs and the unorganized sector under its compliance. This will make the Indian market more stable than b Thus, the final consumer will bear only the GST charged by the last dealer in the supply chain with set-off benefits at all the previous stages. The impact of the GST depends upon the respective State governments and their intervention with respect to controlling prices of essential commodities. Milk, for example, which is likely to see a spike in prices after GST is implemented, can still be sold at cheaper rates, if the State government offers a subsidy on it. A comprehensive IT system, GSTN, will allot universal GST numbers (similar to PAN) to all manufacturers, traders, stockiest, wholesalers and retailers. This will simplify the administration of indirect taxes and plug leakages. The government also plans to incentivize tax compliance by traders. Whether the GST will be beneficial to the poor or not only time can tell. Prices of vegetables and fruits are likely to rise under the GST regime and services such as eating at restaurants will get more expensive. What will likely get cheaper are items such as clothes, as cascading taxes at various stages of manufacturing would no longer apply to them

IMPACT OF GST ON THE IMPORTED COMMODITIES

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Abstract

Under the GST regime, both the import of goods and or services into the territory of India would be treated as supply of goods or services in the course of inter-state trade attracting the levy of IGST. So import of goods or services will be treated as deemed inter-state supplies and would be subject to GST. This article focus on the applicability of GST on goods imported into India..

Keywords: Imports, Provisions, Taxes.

I. INTRODUCTION

GST on Import of Goods

The GST Act has defined import of goods as bringing goods into India from abroad. Accordingly, all imports into India will be deemed as inter-state attracting IGST. In addition to the IGST, the import would also be subject to Customs Duties. Thus, when goods are imported into India, IGST would be applied on the value of the goods and collected along with Customs Duty. The Customs Tariff Act, 1975 has already been amended to provide for levy of integrated tax and the compensation cess on imported goods, in anticipation of the GST rollout.

While, GST would be applied to imports in addition to the Basic Customs Duty, GST Compensation Cess can also be levied on certain luxury and demerit goods under the Goods and Services Tax (Compensation to States) Cess Act, 2017.

Amount of GST on Imported Goods

HSN (Harmonised System of Nomenclature) code has been used for the purpose of classification of goods under the GST regime. Hence, the classification of the item for Customs Duty purpose and IGST calculation purpose would be harmonized.

The amount of GST payable on imported goods would be dependent on the assessable value plus customs duty levied under the Customs Act, and any other duty chargeable on the goods. The value of the imported article for the purpose of levying GST Compensation cess would be, assessable value plus Basic Customs Duty levied under the Act, and any sum chargeable on the goods in the same manner as a duty of customs. Thus, the IGST paid would not be added to the value for the purpose of calculating GST Compensation cess.

Import of Services Under GST

Under GST, the import of service is taxable if –

- The supplier of service is located outside India;
 - The recipient of service is located in India;
 - The place of supply of service is in India;
- and
- The supplier of service and the recipient of service are not merely establishments of a distinct person

Transitional provision

Businesses must note that if the import of services is made on or after July 1, 2017, it shall be chargeable to tax under GST law even if the

transaction was initiated before July 1, 2017. Furthermore, if the tax on import of services has been paid in part under the previous law, the balance tax shall be paid under the new GST law.

Tax Returns

An importer is required to file monthly tax returns under GST. Under the previous law, the importer was required to file returns under state tax law for purchase of goods (import of goods) and under central tax laws for claiming countervailing duties. While filing monthly returns, importers must declare the goods imported in table-5 of the GSTR-2 form, and services imported in table-6 of the GSTR-2 form.

Paying GST for Imports

Under The Customs Act, 1962, removal of goods from a customs station can be done only after payment of Customs Duty and the Integrated GST tax payable. Thus, the importer would be required to pay the Integrated tax at the time of removal of goods from a customs station to a warehouse.

Input Tax Credit for Imports

Input tax credit is available under the GST regime to set off the cascading effect of indirect tax and ensure that the consumer bears GST. Input tax credit is also available for integrated tax charged on import of goods. Input tax credit of the IGST paid at the time of import would be credited to the importer and the same can be utilized by the taxpayer as Input Tax credit for payment of IGST liability on outward supplies.

Though input tax credit is available for the IGST paid, input tax credit cannot be claimed for The Basic Customs Duty (BCD) paid by the importer.

Here is a sector-wise details excerpted from a recent Nomura report on GST on how the bill is likely to impact various sectors and stocks.

Automobiles

Largely positive for demand, as it will lead to a 10-17 per cent fall in prices, assuming an 18 per cent

GST rate. Margin benefits to accrue for tractors, as these can claim set-off against taxes paid on input. Organised battery and other spares would become more cost competitive and gain market share.

Stock impact: Positive for Maruti Suzuki, Hero MotoCorp, Exide, Amara Raja, Eicher Motor, Mahindra & Mahindra, Bajaj Auto. Negative for Ashok Leyland

FMCG

GST will be positive for household and personal care space, as the effective tax rate reduces by 200-500 basis points (bps), apart from reducing warehousing and logistical requirements. However, working capital for retailers, and additional tax rates for jewelry and cigarette manufacturers are negatives.

Stock impact: Positive for Hindustan Unilever, Emami, Godrej Consumer. Negative for Titan, Bata, ITC

Logistics

Passage of GST will lead to elimination of central sales tax and inter-state value-added tax arbitrage possibilities. This will lead to consolidation of warehouses and increased efficiencies in the logistics chain.

Stock impact: Positive for Container Corporation of India, Adani SEZ, Gujarat Pipav Port (longer term)

Infrastructure

Clarity on works contract taxation is the key benefit for the sector. This could reduce litigation, as it eliminates the difference between sales and services.

Stock impact: Positive for Larsen & Toubro (L&T)

Consumer Durables

Consumer durables will benefit from improved logistics. Direct benefits up to 200-300 bps in cost savings may accrue. A significant portion of direct benefits will be passed on to end consumers because of a highly competitive market.

Stock impact: Positive for Voltas, Havells, Crompton Greaves

Oil & Gas

Key petroleum products like crude, natural gas, high speed diesel and ATF have been kept out of GST. Clarity is awaited for others. Compliance costs are likely to rise because of dual indirect tax mechanism.

Stock impact: Neutral. Do not foresee any meaningful change on oil & gas companies

Cement

Overall tax incidence on the sector could decline. The sector will also benefit from expected decline in logistic costs. Firms can be expected to pass on the benefits, given that demand and plant utilisation levels are picking up.

Stock impact: Positive for most companies

Wind Power

GST will be negative for wind, turbine generator manufactures like Suzlon and InoxWind, as pressure on developer margins and internal rates of return could eventually force reduction in prices and realizations, up to 10-13 per cent. However, if components are included in the exemption list, the impact of GST will be nullified.

Stock impact: Negative for Suzlon, Inox Wind

Utilities

Exclusion of "sale of electricity" from GST could potentially raise the cost of coal-fired and renewable energy for Discoms. Profitability of independent power producers selling via medium/long-term PPAs is unlikely to be dented as cost escalation would likely be passed on.

Stock impact: Positive for CESC, negative for JSW Energy

Pharmaceuticals

GST rollout could be negative for the sector, as it is likely to increase indirect tax. Analysts say indirect taxes paid by pharma companies could increase by 60 per cent and MRP by four per cent.

II. CONCLUSION OF GST

Implementation of GST is one of the best decision taken by the Indian government. For the same reason, July 1 was celebrated as Financial Independence day in India when all the Members of Parliament attended the function in Parliament House. The transition to the GST regime which is accepted by 159 countries would not be easy. Confusions and complexities were expected and will happen. India, at some point, had to comply with such regime. Though the structure might not be a perfect one but once in place, such a tax structure will make India a better economy favorable for foreign investments. Until now India was a union of 29 small tax economies and 7 union territories with different levies unique to each state. It is a much accepted and appreciated regime because it does away with multiple tax rates by Centre and States. On imports, there would be no impact on levy of Basic Customs Duty, Education Cess, Anti-Dumping Duty and Safeguard Duty. However, Additional Duties of Customs, which are commonly referred to Special Additional Duty of Customs (SAD) and Countervailing Duty (CVD), would be replaced with the levy of Integrated Goods and Services (IGST).

WOONG SMALL BUSINESS AND NEW TAXPAYERS

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Abstract

Today in India, GST is a game changer as because of its execution, a remarkable outflow of benefits is expected. Since there are numerous taxes such as Service Tax, VAT, Excise every tax system prescribes several actions, so small taxpayers get rid of tedious GST formalities like periodic payment of taxes, filing timely returns and maintaining prescribed records and pay GST at a fixed rate of turnover. Where, small and new taxpayers will find difficult to maintain such numerous records. Hence, the government has introduced the concept of Composition Scheme make compliance easier for small businesses. Composition scheme under the law is for small businesses. This is to bring relief to small businesses so that they need not be burdened with the compliance provisions under the law.

Now there is an option for small and new taxpayer to opt for Composition scheme and have lesser compliance. Also, a taxpayer opting for composition scheme has to pay tax at a nominal rate. It is simple and easy scheme under GST for taxpayers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The One Nation One Tax Scheme (GST) which promises to club all the indirect taxes into one also bring a composition scheme for small businesses. This scheme can be opted by any taxpayer whose turnover is less than Rs. 1 crore.

The following are the people who cannot opt for the scheme

- Supplier of services other than restaurant related services
- Manufacturer of ice cream, pan masala, or tobacco
- Casual taxable person or a non-resident taxable person
- Businesses which supply goods through an e-commerce operator

II. ADVANTAGES OF GST COMPOSITION SCHEME

The following are the advantages of registering under composition scheme

- Lesser compliance (returns, maintaining books of record, issuance of invoices)
- Limited tax liability.
- High liquidity as taxes are at a lower rate.

III. LIMITATIONS OF GST COMPOSITION SCHEME

There are some of the limitations that every business owner must be aware of

- No Credit of Input Tax
- No Inter-state business
- Pay tax from own pocket

IV. FEATURES OF THE SCHEME

Everyone is not eligible to enrol under this scheme.

- It is for the taxpayers whose total turnover does not exceed Rs. 75 lakh in a fiscal year.
- Tax rate as set will be less than regular GST but not less than 1% of the turnover during the financial year.

- Rate of tax under the scheme are expected to be between 1% and 3%.

- Goods and Services on which Composition Tax has been paid do not qualify for Input Tax Credit, As per Section (16).

- Those who supply within a state can only take benefit of this scheme , i.e., Local suppliers

- Suppliers of Inter-state will come under regular GST laws.

- Voluntary registration has to be done by the taxpayers every year for getting the benefits of GST Composition Scheme. However, if the taxpayer crosses the minimum turnover limit of Rs. 75 lakh then he will be transferred to regular scheme.

- Taxpayers who are already a part of VAT Composition Scheme also need to voluntarily register for this scheme.

- Taxpayers registered under this scheme will be required to file returns once every quarter, instead of filing 3-4 returns monthly.

- Taxpayers registered under this scheme need to present bill of supply and invoice to the tax authorities

- Utmost care needs to be taken when opting for this scheme because if a taxable person is found not eligible for this scheme, then the tax authorities can impose a penalty equal to the amount of tax on such person along with his tax liability.

Procedures Followed

Composition Scheme is a preference, the qualified Tax payer needs to inform the Government of his option for the Scheme. Such decision need to be preferred for all the businesses of the Taxable Person (both supply of Goods and Services), without such information, regular tax would be valid by default. The Input Credit relevant to the opening balance in stock would be lapsed, if the taxpayer switches from regular scheme to composition Scheme and it is liable to be cleared off in the books. Similarly, in case of a changeover from composition

scheme to the regular scheme, the Input Credit relevant to the opening balance in stock would become available and the person can avail them on selling such goods It is highly suggested for small service providers in which the occurrence of GST on Inputs is insignificant.

V. CONCLUSION

Due to lack of resource and adequate mechanism small , medium and start-up firms face difficulty in complying numerous provisions hence to lower the burden of compliance composition scheme will be very beneficial and it safeguard the interest small businesses. To conclude the tax rates have also been reduced to a great deal under this scheme for all the registered taxpayers.

NEW CHANGES ENVISAGED UNDER GST

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Abstract

The GST is one of the biggest fiscal reforms in India, which is set to be introduced from July 1 2017. GST stands for Goods and Services Tax. France was first to introduce GST in 1954. Almost 160 countries implemented destination based tax on consumption of goods and services (either by name GST or VAT). At present, only Canada and Brazil has dual GST model (almost like our Indian □ Dual GST model) GST is destination-based Consumption Taxation Applies to all supplies of goods/services. While every business is busy in complying with GST regime HR professionals are also engaged to assess the effect of GST on amenities to employees. As per GST Bill, which is slated in the Lok Sabha, that various amenities provided to employees, such as free food, car pick-up and drops, essentially anything which is not part of their CTC and thus not subject to income tax -- can attract the new levy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gifts to Employees

In India every employer distributes gifts to their employees under various program during festivals like Diwali incur huge show of gifts for most companies' workforce. Celebrating special days like birthdays, work anniversary, farewell and Even in off sites, gifting T-Shirts, Bags and other items are common which is blended in the culture of every organization. Now

All of these gifts will now come under the range of GST.

Gifts upto Rs 50,000 in a year by employer to employee would however not be liable to GST.

GST will be applicable if the value of gifts increases INR 50,000 in a financial year. If the value of all gifts in the year is more than INR 50,000 then the GST is applicable on the amount above INR 50,000.

However, if the amount of a single gift is more than INR 50,000, then GST will be applicable on the total amount of the single gift. And cash gifts will not be liable to GST since tax is applicable on goods and services and cash being money, is neither goods nor service. However, there could be Income Tax implications for cash gifts beyond Rs 5,000. Now, HR and the related department will have to start planning and tracking of various gifts of an individual employee in the financial year to ascertain the applicability of GST.

Free Cab Facility

Cabs are an important part of our lives. Especially for cities where other forms of transport are not very accessible, taxis form the lifeline of daily commuters. In fact, for the emerging white collar or pink collar segment of the society, taxis are godsent. Many companies provide cab services to its employees at a subsidized rate to commute from home to workplace. If it is a part of the employment contract then it is not subjected to GST because it becomes a contractual liability of the company to provide the services.

However, if it is not a part of the employment agreement then it is considered as a supply by the employer to the employee which attracts GST and it will be taxed at 5% rate. It's time for HR folks to explore new possible solutions to amend their contracts with transporters to reflect that cab services are being directly offered to employees. They may have to show and prove that the company is merely acting as a medium to recover invoices from employees on their behalf. This will safeguard the liability of GST on the company.

Free Food Subsidize

Food is offered either free or in subsidized prices to employees in their regular work day. In fact, some companies offer free lunches to their employees. Also, the majority of organizations have been providing delicious rewarding food on special days for celebrations like Diwali, Christmas, Women's Day, New Year, etc. In all these cases, GST will be applicable on the amount paid to outdoor caterers.

However, the credit can be claimed by the company only if it can be treated as outward supply to employees at the open market price. Companies need to alter their existing contract by structuring it in a way that the caterer is supplying food directly to the employees and company is acting as a recovery entity of the invoice from the employees. This will help the company in safeguarding itself from such GST liabilities.

The value of any goods provided free to employee but not covered by the contract of employment or the gift rule, will be based on the open market value.

Whatever the case be, it has become necessary for HR to restructure some of the processes and transactions for GST compatibility. Not only this, HR and top executives must re-think the other often overlooked areas to further refine and simplify their existing process.

The good news is that, apart from the above employer to employee transactions where we can see a visible impact, there are other areas which are not covered under the purview of GST as of now.

Given below are some of the transactions which remain unaffected by the new change

- Medical insurance
- Health check facility
- Company issued devices
- Mobile reimbursements
- Relocation benefits
- Personal accident insurance
- Temporary accommodation
- Mobile handset
- Company car
- Employee referral program
- Long service award
- House lease

II. CONCLUSION

The above merely sets out the basic GST principles applicable to benefits provided to employee and connected persons. It must be reiterated here that it is very important to understand the impact of GST on each and every benefit an employer provides to the employee and mechanics of accounting for the input and output tax. All the above should ideally be integrated with accounting system. HR to rethink and bring in new guidelines to create a win-win situation for both employee and employer by accommodating the new changes envisaged under GST.

GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST) - IMPACT, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the process of introducing the Goods and Services Tax (GST), bringing out the perspectives of different stakeholders and the contentious issues. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a value added tax implemented in India and it has been made clear that there would be a dual GST, taxation power – both by the centre and the state to levy the taxes on the goods and services. Almost 150 countries have introduced get in some form. GST is the only indirect tax that directly affects all sectors and sections of our economy. Goods and service tax is a new story of VAT which gives a widespread setoff for input tax credit and subsuming many indirect taxes from state and national level. The Empowered Committee (EC) was mandated in 2007, to bring about consensus among the States to move towards GST. The important stakeholders in the process were the Government of India (GoI), individual States, industry and the committees commissioned by the GoI or EC. However, the EC faced challenges since there were issues of control between the Centre and States, perceived loss of revenue by some States, extent of uniformity across various commodities and their tax rates, input credit mechanism and dispute settlement. The deadline for the introduction of GST kept getting postponed due to the slow resolution of the challenging issues. Finally,

it was tabled in the Parliament as the 122nd Constitutional Amendment Bill (CAB) in December 2014.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tax policies play an important role on the economy through their impact on both efficiency and equity. A good tax system should keep in view issues of income distribution and, at the same time, also endeavour to generate tax revenues to support government expenditure on public services and infrastructure development. Cascading tax revenues have differential impacts on firms in the economy with relatively high burden on those not getting full offsets. Analysis of the tax levy can be extended to international competitiveness of the adversely affected sectors of production in the economy. Such domestic and international factors lead to inefficient allocation of productive resources in the economy. This results in loss of income and welfare of the affected economy. Even though the country has moved on the path of tax reforms since mid 1980s yet there are various issues which need to be restructured so as to boost productivity and international competitiveness of the Indian exporters.

- Sales of services to consumers are not appropriately taxed with many types of services escaping the tax net.

- Intermediate purchases of inputs by the business firms do not get full offset and part of non-offset taxes may get added up in prices quoted for exports thus making exporters less competitive in world markets (Poddar and Ahmad, 2009)

- The proposed reform on moving to a 'goods and services tax' would impact the national economy, international trade, firms and consumers.

- GST is a tax on both goods and services across the supply chain/Value Chain.

- It is levied at every stage of supply/Value Addition.

- The GST on Inputs (known as ITC - Input Tax Credit) is generally available as credit for set-off against the GST on the output supply.

New Article 366(12A) of the Indian Constitution, defines Goods and Services Tax (GST) to mean any tax on supply of goods or services or both except taxes on the supply of the alcoholic liquor for human consumption. New Article 366(26A) defines service to mean anything other than goods. Existing Article 366(12) defines goods to include all materials, commodities and articles. Goods and Services Tax (GST) in India is proposed to be the maiden REFORM (and not an amendment) in the existing indirect taxation structure.

The proposed GST is a long pending and much awaited tax reform which India which is hoped to iron out the wrinkles in the existing indirect taxation system. This comprehensive tax policy is expected to be one of the most important contributors to the India growth story.

- Harmonized system of nomenclature (HSN) to be applied for goods.

- Uniform return & collection procedure for central and state GST.

- PAN based Common TIN registration.

- Turnover criteria to be prescribed for registration under both central goods and services tax (CGST) and state goods and services tax (SGST).

- TINXSYS to track transactions.
- Tax Payment will be by exporting dealer to the account of receiving state.

- Credit will be allowed to the buying dealer by receiving state on verification.

- Submission of declaration form is likely to be discontinued.

- Area based exemptions will continue up to legitimate expiry time both for the Centre and the States.

- Product based exemptions to be converted into cash refund.

- Limited flexibility to be given to Centre and States for exceptions like natural disasters etc.

- Simplified structure to reduce transaction cost.

- Separate rules and procedures for the administration of CGST and SGST.

- Specific provisions for issues of dispute resolution and advance ruling.

- To eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution cost of goods and services.

- To streamline indirect tax regime in India which can remove cascading effects in supply chain till the level of final consumers

- To restrict on free trade of certain goods and products.

- To widen the dealer base to increase central revenue through indirect taxes.

Relevance of GST

Goods & Service Tax (GST) or VAT serves the purpose to impose a broad-based tax on final consumption by households. Hence, GST is a comprehensive tax levy on supply of goods and services.

- Both Government and Industry are keen to implement GST
- Governments are looking at increasing the tax base and tax collections (i.e. Increase revenue buoyancy) through GST
- State is looking at GST as a window for taxing services
- Centre is looking at GST to go beyond the point of manufacture
- Industry wants GST to eliminate the cascading effect of taxes
- Harmonization of taxes

GST would also address issues of development through greater interaction between VAT/GST systems, along with growing risks of double taxation and unintended nontaxation in the absence of international VAT/GST coordination. Basic principles of VAT/GST are generally same across the tax jurisdictions in so far as they are designed to tax final consumption in the jurisdiction where it occurs according to the destination principle. The fundamental proposition is that GST/VAT is a tax on final consumption and hence the burden should not rest on the business. GST/VAT prescribes that the tax should be collected at every stage of value addition. Each business entity/tax payer in the supply chain should take integral part in the process of controlling and collecting the tax, remitting the proportion of tax corresponding to its margin, i.e. on the difference between GST imposed on its taxed inputs/supplies and the GST imposed on its taxed outputs/supplies. This design of tax structure, ensures the neutrality of the tax. As a result, the GST thereby "flow through the business" to tax supplies

made to final consumers, hence gives its essential character in domestic trade/supplies as an economically neutral tax. The proposed reform through introduction of GST would bring about a sea change in the legal provisions for imposing duty/tax liability in stages of manufacture, sale (inter-state/intra-state) of goods, rendering of services and shall stand replaced with the place of supply, where the final revolutionary reform is necessary to be introduced to perceive the following benefits for the intended stakeholders:

(A) To Trade

- Reduction in multiplicity of taxes
- Mitigation of cascading/ double taxation
- More efficient neutralization of taxes especially for exports
 - Development of Common National Market or Common Economic Market
 - Simpler tax regime with fewer rates and exemptions
 - Increase in cost competitiveness' for domestic industries with reduction in tax cost and also reduced cost of compliance

(B) To Government

- Simpler tax system
- Broadening tax base
- Improved compliance and revenue collections
- Efficient use of resources.
- Investments out of savings by consumers - due to mitigation of cascading effect, contributes to increase in availability of funds out of savings of consumer - which may be used for financing developmental activities.

(C) To Consumer

- Reduction in cost of goods and services due to elimination of cascading effect of taxes.
- Increase in purchasing power and real income.

- Increase in savings due to decrease in cost.
- Increase in investments due to increase in savings.

Justification of GST

Despite the success of VAT, there are still certain shortcomings in the structure of VAT, both at the Centre and at the State level.

A. Justification at the Central Level

- At present excise duty paid on the raw material consumed is being allowed as input credit only. For other taxes and duties paid for post-manufacturing expenses, there is no mechanism for input credit under the Central Excise Duty Act.
- Credit for service tax paid is being allowed manufacturer/ service provider to a limited extent. In order to give the credit of service tax paid in respect of services consumed, it is necessary that there should be a comprehensive system under which both the goods and services are covered.
- At present, the service tax is levied on restricted items only. Many other large number of services could not be taxed. It is to reduce the effect of cascading of taxes, which means levying tax on taxes.

A. Justification at the State Level

- A major defect under the State VAT is that the State is charging VAT on the excise duty paid to the Central Government, which goes against the principle of not levying tax on taxes.
- In the present State level VAT scheme, Cenvat allowed on the goods remains included in the value of goods to be taxed which is a cascading effect on account of Cenvat element.
- Many of the States are still continuing with various types of indirect taxes, such as luxury tax, entertainment tax, etc.

- As tax is being levied on inter-state transfer of goods, there is no provision for taking input credit on CST leading to additional burden on the dealers.

II. GST MODELS – INTERNATIONALLY

Goods & Services Tax (GST) is implemented by about 160 countries in the world. France being the first country to implement GST in 1960. There are various models of GST followed across the World. They are stated with salient features associated therein:

GST Model	Main Features	Applicable in Countries
National GST	Tax levied by Centre with provisions for revenue sharing with Provinces/States	Australia, China
State GST	Tax levied by Provinces/States	USA
Non-concurrent Dual GST	GST on Goods levied by State & on Services levied by Centre	Brazil & Canada —India's Proposed Model
Concurrent Dual GST	Tax levied by Centre & State on both Goods & Services	
Quebec Model	Separate legislation for Federal/ Provinces – Tax collection, Administration, Enforcements, etc. by Provinces	

Proposed GST Model for India

India is opting for —Concurrent Dual GST model. The need for a Dual-GST model is based on the following premise:

- At existing framework, both levels of Government i.e. Centre and State, as per Constitution holds concurrent powers to levy tax domestic goods and services;

The proposed Concurrent Dual-GST model would be a dual levy imposed concurrently by the Centre and the States, but independently;

Both the Centre and State will operate over a common base, i.e. the base for levy and imposition of duty/tax liability would be identical.

To understand the operating procedure of —Concurrent Dual GST Model we have to consider the tax/taxes which shall be levied as per place of supply of goods and services.

- CGST – Central Goods and Service Tax
- SGST – State Goods and Service Tax
- IGST – Integrated Goods and Service Tax

Additional Tax (upto 1%) to be levied in case of inter-state supply of goods, which is an non-vatable item. Hence, no input credit available on such.

Now we will try to understand when each of these will be levied by the below chart:

A summary of levy and the imposing and collecting authority:

Nature of Levy	To be levied by	To be paid to the account of
CGST	Central Government on Intra-State Supply of Goods and/or Services	CG
SGST	State Government Intra State Supply of Goods and/ or Services	SG
IGST = CGST + SGST	Central Government on Inter-State Supply of Goods and/or Services	CG
Additional Tax	Central Government on Inter-state supply of goods, but the net proceeds to be assigned to the States from where supply originates	CG

Goods & Services Tax (GST) In India – Type Of Gst

To arrive at the method / type of GST, one must remember/recall the three methods applied for computation of National Income of a country. They are Income Method, Production Method and Expenditure (or Consumption) Method.

GST can also be classified in similar types - Gross Income, Production and Consumption.

The diagram demonstrates the type of GST and its corresponding features

Goods & Services Tax (GST) In India

There is a common saying that GST in India is a 'destination-based consumption tax'. To justify the features and related advantages of destination based

consumption tax, we shall have to understand the 'origin-based GST' and its relevance in comparison.

Note: In closed economy, both are same, the question of taxation of either imports or exports does not arise at all.

OECD VAT guidelines support the adoption of the "Destination Principle" for supplies of services and intangibles. This guideline support the universal adoption of the 'destination principle' as a means of reducing both potential double taxation (i.e. supplies being taxed in both the source and destination) and potential under taxation (i.e. supplies not being taxed in either the source or the destination).

Destination based Consumption type GST should be adopted as it contributes towards increased

international competitiveness and sustainability of domestic industries.

GST Coverage:

Coverage in general

The proposed GST in India would include All Goods & Services except:

- Industrial incentives to be converted into investment link cash subsidy

- Special Industrial Area Schemes to be also converted into investment based through their validity period

- Around 99 items presently exempted under VAT may continue in GST regime without any scope to change any list.

- Common list of exemption for CGST & SGST

- Transactions which are below threshold limits

It is also advised that there should not be exemption except in following cases:

- All public services of Government (Central, State and Municipal / Panchayati Raj) including Civil Administration, Health Services & Formal Education Services provided by Government Schools & Colleges, Defence, Para-Military, Police, Intelligence & Government Departments.

- However, Public Services will not include Railways, Post & Telegraph, other Commercial Departments, Public Sector Enterprises, Banks & Insurance, Health & Education Services.

- Any service transactions between an employer and employee either as a service provider, recipient or vice versa;

- Any unprocessed food article which is covered under the public distribution system should be exempt regardless of the outlet through which it is sold

- Education services provided by an educational institution to its students, faculty and Staff

Currently exempt under Mega Notification

- Health care services provided by a clinical establishment, authorised medical practitioner.

GST to include - Real Estate sector

- Land development
- Construction on own land and sale of flats
- Construction on land under Development Agreement and sale of Apartments there on Maintenance

- Rent
- Brokerage
- Tours and tourism
- Rent a cab
- Air / Rail / Sea Travel
- Road Transport (Inter / Intra State)
- Transport Services + Agents

GST to include – Financial services

- Banks / Financial Institutions and various services offered by them including interest

- Credit Society / Co-operative Bank and service offered by them

- Foreign Exchange Services including transactions

- Inter Corporate Deposits / Term loans / Group Companies Transactions / Personal Borrowing appear in Personal Balance Sheet

- Agricultural Loan
- NBFCs / Leasing Transactions / Mutual Fund / Shares / Investment Based Link Schemes / Stock Markets /

- Brokers and Sub Broker / Portfolio Management

- Risk Management Services
- Chit Funds / Bhis and auctions thereof
- Money Lenders (licensed and unlicensed)
- Scheme like gold loans or market linked schemes

- Petroleum products would be subject to GST only from a date specified by the GST Council. Appropriate amendments made in the Seventh

Schedule to the Constitution in List I (Union List) and in List II (State list) Centre & State will continue to levy excise duty on

- petroleum crude,
- high speed diesel,
- natural gas,
- aviation turbine fuel,
- tobacco and tobacco products

Note: States shall not have the power to tax sale of these goods in the course of inter-State trade or commerce or sale in the course of international trade or commerce.

Note: New Entry 84, List-I & 54, List-II are very limited in scope and confined to petroleum and alcoholic liquor for human consumption.

Note: Entry 51 of the State List which enables excise duty on alcoholic liquor for human consumption continues.

Tax Mechanism - Levy and Chargeability

The following are the proposals on GST mechanism

Note: Assumptions underlying the above :

CGST = 10%; SGST = 10%; Additional Tax = 1%; IGST = CGST + SGST + 20%; ITC = Input Tax Credit

Impact of Goods and Service Tax

Food Industry :The application of GST to food items will have a significant impact on those who are living under subsistence level. But at the same time, a complete exemption for food items would drastically shrink the tax base. Food includes grains and cereals, meat, fish and poultry, milk and dairy products, fruits and vegetables, candy and confectionary, snacks, prepared meals for home consumption, restaurant meals and beverages. Even if the food is within the scope of GST, such sales would largely remain exempt due to small business registration threshold. Given the exemption of food from CENVAT and 4% VAT on food item, the GST under a single rate would lead to a doubling of tax burden on food.

Housing and Construction Industry: In India, construction and Housing sector need to be included in the GST tax base because construction sector is a significant contributor to the national economy.

FMCG Sector: Despite of the economic slowdown, India's Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) has grown consistently during the past three – four years reaching to \$25 billion at retail sales in 2008. Implementation of proposed GST and opening of Foreign Direct Investment (F.D.I.) are expected to fuel the growth and raise industry's size to \$95 Billion by 2018.

Rail Sector: There have been suggestions for including the rail sector under the GST umbrella to bring about significant tax gains and widen the tax net so as to keep overall GST rate low. This will have the added benefit of ensuring that all inter – state transportation of goods can be tracked through the proposed Information technology (IT) network.

Financial Services: In most of the countries GST is not charged on the financial services. Example, In New Zealand most of the services covered except financial services as GST. Under the service tax, India has followed the approach of bringing virtually all financial services within the ambit of tax where consideration for them is in the form of an explicit fee. GST also include financial services on the above grounds only.

Information Technology enabled services: To be in sync with the best International practices, domestic supply of software should also attract G.S.T. on the basis of mode of transaction. Hence if the software is transferred through electronic form, it should be considered as Intellectual Property and regarded as a service. And if the software is transmitted on media or any other tangible property, then it should be treated as goods and subject to G.S.T. 35 According to a FICCI – Technopak Report. Implementation of GST will also help in uniform, simplified and single point Taxation and thereby reduced prices.

Impact on Small Enterprises: There will be three categories of Small Enterprises in the GST regime. Those below threshold need not register for the GST. Those between the threshold and composition turnovers will have the option to pay a turnover based tax or opt to join the GST regime. Those above threshold limit will need to be within framework of GST. Possible downward changes in the threshold in some States consequent to the introduction of GST may result in obligation being created for some dealers. In this case considerable assistance is desired. In respect of Central GST, the position is slightly more complex. Small scale units manufacturing specified goods are allowed exemptions of excise up to Rs. 1.5 Crores. These units may be required to register for payment of GST, may see this as an additional cost.

Challenges

- The threshold limit for turnover above which GST would be levied will be one area which would have to be strictly looked at. First of all, the threshold limit should not be so low to bother small scale traders and service providers. It also increases the allocation of government resources for such a petty amount of revenue which may be much more costly than the amount of revenue collected. The first impact of setting higher tax threshold would naturally lead to less revenue to the government as the margin of tax base shrinks; second it may have on such small and not so developed states which have set low threshold limit under current VAT regime.

- The taxes that are generally included in GST would be excise duty, countervailing duty, cess, service tax, and state level VATs among others. Interestingly, there are numerous other states and union taxes that would be still out of GST.

- There will two types of GST laws, one at a centre level called 'Central GST (CGST)' and the other one at the state level - 'State GST (SGST)'. As there seems to have different tax rates for goods and services at the Central Level and at the State Level, and further division based on necessary and other property based on the need, location geography and resources of each state.

- It is true that a tax rate should be devised in accordance with the state's necessity of funds. Whenever states feel that they need to raise greater revenues to fund the increased expenditure, then, ideally, they should have power to decide how to increase the revenue

III. CONCLUSION

GST is the most logical steps towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country since independence. GST is leviable on all supply of goods and provision of services as well combination thereof. All sectors of economy whether the industry, business including Govt. departments and service sector shall have to bear impact of GST. All sections of economy viz., big, medium, small scale units, intermediaries, importers, exporters, traders, professionals and consumers shall be directly affected by GST... One of the biggest taxation reforms in India – the Goods and Service Tax (GST) -- is all set to integrate State economies and boost overall growth.

IMPACT OF GST ON ONLINE SHOPPING

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Abstract

E-commerce is fast gaining traction in today's world. In simple terms, e-commerce can be described as the conduct of any commercial activity using the Internet as a medium. The scope of e-commerce is dynamic and consistently expanding. The online marketplace business model has been the most successful model in India, given the foreign direct investment (FDI) and regulatory norms currently in existence. Therefore, this study focuses more on online marketplaces while studying the e-commerce sector in India.

Keywords: *Online shopping, Tax etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

E-commerce giants like Amazon, Flipkart, Snapdeal and many more online platforms have come up with lucrative offers this entire month across all top brands at never seen before prices. With the roll out of the indirect tax regime, online shopping is going to be a lot easier. Customers will enjoy faster delivery of products after July 1 as all retailers will not have to file a separate paperwork for each state. This will help reducing time and effort and will benefit the consumer with faster delivery of services.

II. CHANGE IN SHOPPING ONLINE

Under the new regime, goods will be delivered to a customer much faster than the previous regime due to removal of paperwork to be filed with state authorities. Though goods will reach on time, a pain point for consumers would be returns and cancellations as e-commerce companies may make this a tad difficult since they would now have to bear the tax amount on their own and only later be able to get a refund from the government in case of returns and cancellations. The companies will face a major

cash-flow disadvantage due to returns and cancellations.

III. RELIEF TO CONSUMERS

A huge relief to consumers has been the reduction in nominal tax rates for a majority of goods. Half of the items in the Consumer Price Index (CPI) basket will be exempt from GST and another tenth will be taxed at the lowest rate of 5%. The balance CPI goods would come under either of the two standard rates of 12% or 18%, rather than the highest rate of 28%.

IV. ANTI-PROFITEERING CLAUSE

The government has set up an anti-profiteering body to keep a watch on how businesses recalibrate the tax-inclusive price charged from consumers. Hence, companies and traders are expected to pass on the benefit to the consumers. This would result in further reduction of prices on various goods and services.

V. GETTING TECH SAVVY

In lines with Digital India, all filings in GST will have to be done online. Hence, all businesses would not only have to update their systems but also train their workforce to become tech savvy. It will specifically effect smaller traders who earlier managed their tax filings manually.

Ease of process

GST will not only ease the process of business but also bring in transparency in the whole process. All the invoices uploaded by sellers will also be visible to buyers. For the first time, consumers will get to know the actual amount of taxes they are paying for goods and services in the form of single GST. The efficiency of GST is expected to bring down the tax burden and improve transparency.

GST. The efficiency of GST is expected to bring down the tax burden and improve transparency.

Tax breaks to end

There is no more excise duty exemption for setting up production units in the north east or hill states. Businesses will have to make investment decisions based on sound economics rather than tax arbitrage. Units that have already come up on the promise of excise exemption for a specified period will have to pay tax first and claim refunds in the remaining period.

Competitive business environment

It will shift the burden of taxes from the manufacturers in India where the tax system is unfairly skewed towards the consumers. Manufacturers will pay lower taxes and there will be an environment of greater competitiveness and more freedom in business.

Most of your online shopping will get expensive after the GST. They are :

Tax collected at source

Currently, e-commerce websites do not collect tax in any form. Under the GST, they will collect tax at a fixed rate of 1 per cent while paying to the sellers listed on their websites. This is likely to impact prices and make your online shopping more expensive. Though, the move has been deferred, it is likely to come in force at a later date.

Faster delivery

Under the GST, goods will reach faster as the retailers will not have to file a separate paperwork for each state. Currently, for example, if your seller is in Bangalore and you are based in Delhi, your seller will file a separate bill for logistics, another one for the state tax, etc. Under the GST, the extra paperwork imposed by states will end and make deliveries faster.

The end of freebies and discounts?

Used to mega discounts and freebies? There may not be many in future because they will attract an additional tax. Also, since an e-commerce company

will have to pay the tax on the price it has purchased the goods from the supplier, it will not be worth its while to offer discount in many cases.

Shopping from global players

Shopping from portals like Amazon.com and Ebay.com, they transact in foreign currency. The government has yet to come up with clarification of rules for such operators.

Returns and cancellations will get difficult

Returns and cancellations are going to face challenges. E-commerce companies have a return or cancellation rate of nearly 18%.

Rates of GST and revenue-neutral rate (RNR)

RNR has been the subject of deliberation between the central and state governments, and a final verdict has still not been reached. Provided below are the various changes that the proposed RNR has gone through since the idea of GST was first floated in the Indian economy:

- The first official recommendation by the Thirteenth Finance Commission Report of the Task Force on GST4 proposed taxation of all goods and services at a single GST rate of 12%—comprising 5% for CGST and 7% for SGST.
- Subsequently, the then finance minister had proposed a rate of 16% for services, 24% for goods and 12% for concessional goods.
- The National Institute of Public Finance and Policy (NIPFP), in its report submitted to EC, suggested an RNR of up to 26.68%, which is being recalculated by NIPFP on the basis of current revenue data.
- It is anticipated that a single rate would be applicable for both goods and services.
- The incumbent finance minister has stated in a public forum that the RNR would be lower than 27%.
- A new committee has been set up to examine the RNR, depending on various factors, including growth of the economy

VI. CONCLUSION

E-commerce sector in India is one of the most rapidly advancing sectors and the government is vigorously promoting digitized economy, the introduction of such cumbersome compliances cringes the growth of this sector. Statutory framework

introduced by the government should be towards the advancement of business rather than creating obstacles. The GST law should provide an enabling environment that encourages e-commerce operators and suppliers.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ORGANIC AND INORGANIC FOOD

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Abstract

Increased use of chemicals, under intensive cultivation has disturbed the harmony existing among soil, plants and animals and human health. The extensive use of chemicals and antibiotics in inorganic food production technology has compelled the health conscious people to explore and support organic farming. The study reveals the fact that the food produced using organic methods taste better and contains a better balance of vitamins and minerals than inorganically grown food. The eating of organic food considerably reduces the heart attacks, strokes, cancer, bowel cancer, and many other diseases. Hence, importance of organic farming has increased due to its environmental friendly methods and growing consumer awareness of food safety. The role of the Government is critical in motivating the farmers switching over from inorganic farming system to organic farming system where organic farming is economically viable in the country. Besides, the government has to take appropriate measures like the separate market for organic products; announcement of support price, creation of demand by more awareness programmes, subsidy for organic inputs producers, subsidies for encouraging organic farmers; certification of farms and increase in investment on research and development activities in organic farming practices.

Keywords: *Organic Farming System, Inorganic Farming System, eco system, sustainability, food security, certification.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture sector in India has undergone significant structural changes. Inorganic farming has made the farmers of today searching for something better, in addition, farmers are pursuing chemical supplements to push crop yield, which is only harming the earth. Farmers and communities faced many socio-economic problems, particularly small farmers who found themselves increasingly marginalized due to lack of access to external inputs (Yasin 2007). Their soil is depleted from the constant application of harsh and harmful chemicals. This is particularly true in its heavy reliance on chemical fertilizers and pesticides, it depends upon subsidies and price support and external costs such as threat to other species, environmental pollution, habitat destruction and risks to human health and welfare. Besides, increase incidence of miscarriage, birth malfunctions, still births and delayed pregnancy have been documented among women agricultural workers and wives of men employed in pesticide mixing and spraying (Ranson,2002). In this background, the solution for this problem and ills of IFS now lies in Organic Farming System (OFS) a strong feeling world-over.

Organic agriculture in general is a system of crop and livestock production that promotes and enhances the health of agricultural ecosystem while providing healthy food and reflects the profound inter relationship that exists between farm biota, its production and the overall environment. Therefore, the extensive use of chemicals and anti-biotic in inorganic food production technology has compelled

the health conscious people to explore and support organic farming methods in agriculture. It is generally believed that organic farming with its central focus on maintaining and improving soil health, its avoidance of pollutants, and its reliance on local inputs and labour could materially advance the economic and ecological health. Organic farming can contribute to sustainable food security by improving nutrition intake, supporting livelihoods in rural areas and enhancing biodiversity while simultaneously reducing vulnerability to climate change. In this context, the study has been undertaken to compare the quality of food produced under organic farming and Inorganic Farming Practices.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study is based on the following specific objectives

To know the concepts of organic and inorganic farming.

To study the quality of organic and inorganic food.

III. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The study is based on secondary data which have been collected from the Government reports, national and international journals etc. In this study, the use of inorganic inputs in production of crops and rearing animals in agriculture is called conventional or modern or chemical, or inorganic agriculture, but from here onwards, it is termed as inorganic farming. On the other hand, the application of organic or natural inputs in the farm operations is known as organic or biodynamic or natural or biodynamic organic agriculture but it is termed as organic farming. Some of the important studies related to this area of the study have, therefore, been summarized under the following headings.

IV. ORGANIC VERSUS INORGANIC FARMING

Organic farming though is not a „new“ concept; it was marginalized against the large-scale inorganic based farming practices that have steadily dominated

food production over the years (50 years). The difference between organic and inorganic farming accounts for the most of the controversy with claims and counter claims surrounding organic agriculture methods and organic food. They are as follows; Terry Cacek and Lind, L Langer (1986) have distinguished the organic farming from inorganic farming in the following ways. The term inorganic farming refers to a production system which employs a full range of pre and post-plant tillage practices (eg. plow, disk, plant, cultivate), synthetic fertilizers and pesticides. Therefore, inorganic farming is characterized by a high degree of crops specialization. By contrast, organic farming is characterized by a diversity of crops. Organic farmers need to borrow less money than inorganic farmers do because organic farmers buy fewer inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides. Moreover, costs and income are more evenly distributed throughout the year on diversified organic farms. The technology used in organic farming is nature based, environment friendly and sustainable. However, inorganic farming is based on synthetic fertilizer which is harmful to environment.

Subhash Chand and Sunil Pabbi (2005) made difference between organic and inorganic farming in the following ways. Products produced by organic farming are good in taste, flavor, nutritional and free from chemicals whereas products produced under inorganic farming are tasteless, less nutritious, may contain toxic residues of chemicals. Organic farming may not lead to higher production and income in the short-run as its returns are of a long-term nature. However, inorganic farming leads to higher production and income in the short-run and returns are declining in the long run. Therefore, returns from organic farming are of a long-term nature whereas returns are of short-run nature under inorganic farming. It is increasingly felt that inorganic farming is becoming unsustainable as evidenced by declining crop productivities, damage to environment, chemical

contaminations. The necessity of having an alternate agriculture method which can function in a friendly eco-system and could sustain the crop productivity is widely spread. Hence, organic farming is recognized as the best know alternative to the inorganic agriculture.

V. QUALITY OF ORGANIC AND INORGANIC FOOD

The quality and superiority of organic food production over inorganic food production has been reviewed as under. Organic farming is becoming increasingly popular not only in India, all over the world. Many consumers are feeling disillusioned from chemically produced foods and are started to make the effort to buy organic food. The reasons are; their concern for the family members as well as the health of the environment. The good taste and nutritional value of organic food also attract the consumers. Inorganic agriculture uses a wide range of synthetic chemicals that inevitably leave residue in the produce: There are more than 130 different classes of pesticides containing some 800 entries (Plimmer, 2001). Pesticides residues enter the food chain via four main routes; on-farm pesticide use, post-harvest pesticides use, pesticide use on imported food and cancelled pesticides that persist in the environment (Kuchler et al., 1996). According to WHO estimate approximately one million people are taken ill every year with pesticides poisoning and up to 20,000 of them die in agony and a variety of reproductive health impacts on women. Increased incidence of miscarriage, birth malfunctions, still births and delayed pregnancy have been documented among women agricultural workers and wives of men employed in pesticide mixing and spraying (Ranson,2002). This is mainly due to overuse or misuse of chemicals, particularly synthetic insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, fertilizers, plant growth regulators etc that resulted in undesirable side effects not only in the agro-ecosystems, but also on

human health and life systems of beneficial fauna and microorganisms. Further, the Inorganic farming's benefits have come at the cost of extensive environmental degradation and considerable health problems due to exposure to agro-chemicals. The toxic residues poison the body slowly causing intensive damage to human body; the food products containing toxic pesticides residues cause heart disease, brain, kidney and liver damage and even cancer, limb deformities and poor eyesight. Thus, the extensive use of chemicals and antibiotics in inorganic food production technology has compelled the health conscious people to explore and support organic farming.

Now a day's all over the world, food safety is receiving more attention than ever before by governments and policy makers, health professionals, the food industry, the biomedical community and last but not least, the public (Crutch field and Roberts, 2000). The multiple factors have been associated with the preference for organic food that, in general, reflect an increased interest towards personal health, animal welfare and environmental protection (Makatouni, 2002). Health-related issues seem to assume greater importance than other concerns and notions about food safety are fundamental for purchasing organics (Magnusson et al., 2003;

The United Kingdom Parliament, 1999; Lohr, 2001; Harper and Makatouni, 2002; Beharrell and Mac Fie, 1991). A study based on data collected by the US government found pesticide residues on 23 percent of organic fruits and vegetables and nearly 75 percent of conventionally grown produce, though the residues in all the samples well below statutory limits (Baker et al., 2002). A study of three apple production system (organic integrated and conventional) in Washington state assessed their impact on some factors in all three dimensions of sustainability. They concluded that organic production systems were more profitable, had a lower

environmental impact and produced sweeter and less tart apples (Reganold et al., 2001).

There is a widespread belief that organic food is significantly healthier and safer than inorganic food and consumers are willing to pay significant price premium to obtain it (Beharrell and Mac Fie, 1991). Organic farming uses almost exclusively biological and natural materials and processes to produce food. The practice aims to protect human health and conserve or enhance natural resources, with the goal to presume the quality of the environment for future generations while being economically sustainable. Hence, farmers are converting to organic methods for a variety of reasons but the most important have to do with a general unease with the health and environmental impacts of conventional practice, increasing disease and pest problems and the expectation that organic methods might be more profitable (Blobsaum, 1983; Kramer, 1984; United states GAO, 1990; MacRae et al. 1990).

Singh and Dinesh Kumar (2007) have explained organic farming vis-à-vis human health and environment. The study revealed that organic farming was superior to conventional farming or chemical farming in terms of pollution free environment, good quality of food and health: conventional farming was produced food and fodder by using chemical fertilizers and pesticides, which contaminated the food, health hazardous and environment pollution. Besides, organic farming produces good quality of food, by using different plant nutrition, weed management, pest and disease management so that eating of organic food considerably reduces the heart attacks, strokes, cancer, bowel cancer and many other diseases.

Faido Magkos et. al., (2006) reported the critical and transparent overview of organic food safety to identify potential drawbacks in organic food production. The results revealed that food safety of organic verses conventional produce is difficult

because of divergent conditions prevailing in terms of soil, water, climatic conditions. Organic food is not free from pesticides. However, fruits and vegetables are grown under organic farming can be found much less agrochemical residues than their conventional alternatives. Further, the health risk associated with dietary exposure to agrochemicals remains to be evaluated. Organically cultivated nitrophillic vegetables viz. leafy root and tuber were found lower content than the respective conventional ones.

Pragya Agarawal et. al., (2007) compared the quality characteristics and sensory quality in fresh green peas grown by organic, inorganic and integrated methods at Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar. The study found that no significant difference was observed in terms of pod length but significant difference was observed in number of seed per pod that was higher in pea grown by integrated method of cultivation. The organically grown peas scored higher total sugar, sweetness, colour, flavor and taste, besides in terms of minerals; organically grown peas had higher copper and zinc levels as compared to inorganically grown peas and peas grown by integrated method of cultivation.

Thakur et. al., (2003) examined the comparative economics of organic produce (OFS) vis-à-vis inorganic produce (IFS) in the backward and tribal hilly area of Himachal Pradesh, India. The study revealed that the poisonous and toxic inorganic chemical inputs used under IFS have turned out to be highly destructive, injurious and harmful causing large scale polluting and poisoning of soil, water, air ecosystem, agro-ecosystem, environment, plants and crop produce which in turn, induce many deadly diseases including cancer. The organic produce or organic food is best for health; more nutritious of better quality, free and safe from toxic inorganic chemical residues, looks fresh and good and tastes delicious. Hence, the health conscious buyers and

consumers are buying organic produce at very high premium prices which are generally 3-4 times higher depending upon products.

In Japan, similar study was conducted by Yukio Yokoi (2002) on the policy development of organic agriculture and future perspectives. The study revealed that the public greatly concern about food safety issues owing to the recent incidents of mad cow disease (Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy) and the detection of excess pesticide residues and the use of prohibited pesticides. Hence, policies on organic agriculture and organic food have been developed in terms of the "JAS Organic" (Japanese Agricultural Standards) accreditation system and technological support of organic farming.

Wiebel et. al., (1999) assessed fruit quality in golden delicious apple from five organic farms and five farms using integrated production methods. They found that in terms of taste, firmness, dietary fiber and phenolic compound contents, fruits from organic farms outperformed the others. Hogstad et al., (1997) examined sensory quality and chemical composition of carrots from designed trials and from organic and conventional farms. The data were analyzed using principal components and partial least squares regression to identify the main factors responsible for variation in quality. One of the most important factors was fertilizers application. Carrots grown with fertilizer, low levels of mineral fertilizer or with organic fertilizer, had more total sugars, stronger flavor but less crispness, protein and carotene than carrots grown with high levels of mineral fertilizer.

VI. CONCLUSION

Agriculture is a critical sector of the Indian economy. Increased use of chemicals, under intensive cultivation has disturbed the harmony existing among soil, plant and animal and human health. The extensive use of chemicals and antibiotics in inorganic food production technology has compelled the health conscious people to explore and support organic farming. World organic food consumption has grown at a rate of 25 percent per annum in the last decade and it is expected to grow more than 15 percent of total food consumption in future. Moreover, the findings of the literature-reviewed reveals the fact that food produced using organic methods are taste better and contain a better balance of vitamins and minerals than inorganically grown food. The eating of organic food considerably reduces the heart attacks, strokes, cancer, bowel cancer and many other diseases. Hence, importance of organic farming has increased due to its environmental friendly methods and growing consumer awareness of food safety. The role of the Government is critical in motivating the farmers switching over from inorganic farming system to organic farming system where organic farming is economically viable in the country. Besides, the government has to take appropriate measures like the separate market for organic products; announcement of support price, creation of demand by more awareness programmes, organic inputs/subsidies for encouraging organic farmers; certification of farms and increase in investment on research and development activities in organic farming practices.

IMPLEMENTATION OF GST IN INDIA AND ITS IMPACT ON SME SECTOR

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Abstract

GST- A broad based and single comprehensive tax system was most awaited bill, which passes on 6th May 2015. It was debated that, GST will remove the cascading effect of tax by giving input tax credit to SMEs and lead to economic integration¹. With broad debate on GST, country's most important sector, SME, also feel the heat of GST. SMEs are the model of socio-economic policies of Government of India. India has second largest number of SMEs in the world next to china, and they are the next best sector which provides largest employment after agriculture in the economy. It is been argued that GST will enhance the SMEs efficiency. Thus, it has been a focus of study about the impact of GST on SME sector. In this paper, concentrates on the GST model, to learn the basics of GST implementation in India and extend the topic to the SME sector's growth.

Keywords: *GST model, efficiency, input tax credit, SMEs.*

I. INTRODUCTION

GST Bill has been described as a reform measure of unparalleled importance in independent India². A much delayed bill, passed on 6th May 2015, took its birth in 2000 by Vajpayee Government. Since then GST has been in the news for numerous reasons. It is expected that GST will transform the India's indirect tax system by simplifying it at both centre and state level. A very important point to be noted here is, there would be 'no tax on tax'. On the destination principle, the tax is at the last stage. The Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are the major sector which is promoting Indian economic growth by

contributing 40% Indian workforce and nearly 17% to the GDP growth rate. Thus, it is inevitable to study the major change in the tax system which is going to occur in 2016.

Objectives of Study

1. To understand the present structure of tax
2. To study the loophole in the VAT
3. To know the implementing model of GST
4. To understand the GST's impact on the SME sector of India. Analysis of SMEs future prospects with GST

Methodology

Secondary sources of data are used. Data published by various institutions such as Government of India, World Bank, Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), etc are used for the purpose of the present paper. The paper is organized into 9 parts. Following this introduction, we understand the present tax structure by basing the knowledge before VAT and after VAT. It then takes up the theoretical and conceptual issues surrounding the GST on SME development. Part three present understanding of the Input credit mechanism and the benefits to SME sector as a whole.

II. UNDERSTANDING GST- GST MODEL

Goods and Service Tax creates an audit-trail of value chain across the income and production chain. Introduction of GST make the Indian products competitive in domestic and international market. GST regime intends to subsume most indirect taxed under a single taxation regime. GST is a value added tax levied across goods and series. This is expected to

help broaden the tax base, increase tax compliance and reduce economic distortions caused by inter-state variations in taxes.³ The main idea is no good and service is exempt, and there is no differentiation between a good or service, whether as an input or as a finished product. The simple model of GST can be summed in the following diagram:

Certain main features of GST

- GST would be applicable on supply of goods or series as against present concept of tax on the manufacture or on sale of goods or provision of services. It would be dual GST: Centre and State simultaneously levying it on common base
- Integrated GST on inter-state supply of goods/series collected by Centre. Import of goods and services are treated as inter-state supply of goods and series and subject to IGST.
- A non-votable additional tax not exceeding 1% on inter-state supply of goods would be levied by centre and retained by originating state at least for 2 years. ?CGST, SGST, IGST would be levied at rates to be recommended by Goods and Service Tax Council (GSTC) which will be chaired by Union Finance Minister and will have State Finance ministers as members. GST will exempt alcohol, tobacco and tobacco products, petroleum products.
- Zero rating exports GST and its impact on SME. SME is always represented the model of socio-economic policies of Government of India which emphasized judicious use of resources. The SME are being the major sector of the Indian economy face problems with respect to finance and procedural haphazard. The present threshold prescribed in different state VAT acts below which VAT is not applicable varied from state to

state. The existing threshold of goods under state VAT is Rs. 5 lakhs for a majority of bigger states and a lower threshold for north eastern states and special category states

III. INPUT CREDIT MECHANISM AND SME

The input credit mechanism under goods and services tax will help price products more competitively. The proposed goods and service tax (GST), which has seen the main political parties adopt opposing views, spells a mixture of good news and some restrictions for small and medium enterprises (SMEs). It is said that, the GST will enhance the competitiveness and efficiency of SMEs to the global level and mitigate the cascading effect of the current tax system. Further GST will help in “normal tiering”. Usually SMEs will have Tier-I, -II and -III suppliers. When they go from sub-contracting to bought-out, the four per cent Central sales tax makes it uneconomical to do a complete bought-out. Therefore they have hybrid models, which are not efficient, and quality suffers in the process. Once the GST comes in, there will be tier-I units to make complete assemblies, tier-II units to make sub-assemblies and tier-III units to make ‘child’ parts.

IV. CONCLUSION

The SMEs being the core sector of Indian economy today by contributing to 40% of employment and 17% to the GDP has to look into the depth. The proposed GST will have major positive effect on the growth of SMEs and it expected from the Finance Minister that, GST will increase the GDP growth by 2%. Thus, there is a need to look into the impact of GST on SMEs and have to make proper road map for them to sustain in the international competition flood.

GST & ITS PROBABLE IMPACT ON THE FMCG INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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Abstract

Goods and Services Tax (GST) will be a game changing reform for Indian economy by developing a common Indian market and reducing the cascading effect of tax on the cost of goods and services. GST is a consumption based tax levied on sale, manufacturing and consumption on goods & services at a national level. Many taxes such as central excise duty, service tax, central surcharge and cess etc. levied by Central Government and VAT / sales tax, entertainment tax, octroi & entry tax, purchase tax, luxury tax, taxes on lottery etc. levied by State Governments have been subsumed under GST. The fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector of India comprises more than 50 percent of the food and beverage industry and another 30 percent from personal and household care, thereby spanning the entire rural and urban parts of the country (Subramanian, 2015). Under the proposed GST regime, it is expected that it would result in a simpler tax regime, especially for industries like FMCG. Presently the peak tax costs for industry players amount to approximately 27% (i.e. Excise Duty of 12.5% and VAT ranging from 12% to 15%).

I. INTRODUCTION

The Goods and Services Tax (GST), the biggest reform in India's indirect tax structure since the economy began to be opened up 25 years ago, at last looks set to become reality. The Constitution (122nd) Amendment Bill finally got the nod of Rajya Sabha. Government successfully stitching together a political consensus on the GST Bill, to pave the way for much-awaited roll out of the landmark tax reform that

will create a common market of 1.25 billion people. GST will be a game changing reform for Indian economy by developing a common Indian market and reducing the cascading effect of tax on the cost of goods and services. It will impact the Tax Structure, Tax Incidence, Tax Computation, Tax Payment, Compliance, Credit Utilization and Reporting leading to a complete overhaul of the current indirect tax system

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

This paper deals how proposed Goods and Services Tax will affect the economy of India. The paper has the following objectives:

1. To understand how GST will operate in various cases.
2. To understand how it will become boon or bane for Indian Economy.
3. To study the proposed impact of GST on the FMCG Industry in India.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the study is to compare the current and proposed tax system in India by studying the applicability of GST in various cases. The secondary data has been used for this study.

Dual GST model:

The Dual GST model and the taxes levied on each kind of transaction and procedure of set off of

GST can be understood with the help of illustration given below:

The GST can be of three type viz. (i) SGST – 'State GST' collected by the State Government, (ii) CGST – 'Central GST' collected by the Central

Government and (iii) IGST – ‘Integrated GST’ collected by the Central Government.

How GST operates?

Let us understand how GST will operate under the new system. Three cases have been taken to clarify how GST will operate under the proposed system-

Case 1: Sale in one state, resale in the same state

In the Figure 1 (Asawa, 2016), goods are moving from Mumbai to Pune. Since, it is a sale within a

state, CGST and SGST will be levied. The collection goes to both the Central Government and the State Government as described in the diagram. Then the goods are resold from Pune to Nagpur. This is again a sale within a state, so CGST and SGST, both will be levied. Sale price is increased so tax liability will also increase. In the case of resale, the credit of input CGST and input SGST (Rs. 8) is claimed as shown; and the remaining taxes go to the respective governments.

Figure 1: Applicability of GST in case of sale in one state followed by resale in the same state.

Note. Adapted from “What is the difference between the current taxation and the new Goods and Service Tax (GST) in India: What is the impact”, by P. Asawa, 2016.

Case 2: Sale in one state, resale in another state

In Figure 2 (Asawa, 2016), goods are moving from Indore to Bhopal. Since, it is a sale within a state, CGST and SGST, both will be levied. The collection goes to both, the Central Government and the State Government as pointed out in the

diagram. Later, the goods are resold from Bhopal to Lucknow (outside the state). Therefore, IGST will be levied. Whole IGST goes to the central government. Against IGST, both the input taxes are taken as credit. But we see that SGST never went to the central government, still the credit is claimed. This is the crux of GST. Since this amounts to a loss to the Central Government, the respective State Government will compensate the central government by transferring the credit to the Central Government.

Figure 2: Applicability of GST in case of sale in one state followed by resale in another state

Note. Adapted from “What is the difference between the current taxation and the new Goods and Service Tax (GST) in India: What is the impact”, by P. Asawa, 2016.

Case 3: Sale outside the state, resale in that state

In Figure 3 (Asawa, 2016), goods are moving from Delhi to Jaipur. Since it is an interstate sale, IGST will be levied. The whole collection will go to the Central Government. Later the goods are resold from

Jaipur to Jodhpur (within the state). Therefore, CGST and SGST will be levied. Against CGST and SGST, 50% of the IGST that is Rs. 8 is taken as a credit. But one can see that IGST never went to the respective State Government, still the credit is claimed against SGST

Figure 3: Applicability of GST in case of sale outside the state followed by resale in that state

Note. Adapted from “What is the difference between the current taxation and the new Goods and Service Tax (GST) in India: What is the impact”, by P. Asawa, 2016.

How GST is boon for Indian Economy:

A. Introduction of a GST is very much essential in the emerging environment of the Indian economy.

B. There is no doubt that, in production and distribution of goods & services are increasingly used or consumed. Separate taxes for goods and services, which is the present taxation system, requires division of transaction values into value of goods and services for taxation, leading to greater complications, administration, including compliances costs. In the GST system, when all the taxes are integrated, it would make possible the taxation burden to be split equitably between manufacturing and services.

C. GST will be levied only at the final destination of consumption based on VAT principle and not at various points (from manufacturing to retail outlets). This will help in removing economic distortions and bring about development of a common national market.

D. It will also help to build a transparent and corruption-free tax administration. Presently, a tax is levied on when a finished product moves out from a factory, which is paid by the manufacturer, and it is again levied at the retail outlet when sold. Improvement in International investor’s confidence as there will be single tax in all over of the country in place of multiple taxes.

How GST is bane for Indian Economy:

- Doesn't include petroleum and alcohol products. Heavy loss to the exchequer.
- It requires strong IT (Information Technology) infrastructure at grass-root levels. India essentially lacks this. This

factor is going to be the bottleneck, if not addressed well in advance.

- Very high rates 5%, 12%, 18%, 28% compared to current 12.5 % VAT.
- Tax-sharing between States and the Centre is another bottleneck. Nice to see that there is a consensus now.
- Majority of dealers are not covered with the Central Excise but are only paying VAT in the states. Now all the VAT dealers will be required to pay “Central Goods and Service Tax”.

Impact of GST on FMCG:

The fast moving consumer good (FMCG) sector of India comprises more than 50 percent of the food and beverage industry and another 30 percent from personal and household care, thereby spanning the entire rural and urban parts of the country. Reports suggest the sector contributes a significant USD 6.5 billion in direct and indirect taxes (Subramanian, 2015). The current Indirect Tax regime in India provides for a complex tax environment due to multiplicity of taxes, tax cascading and elaborate compliance obligations. In the ensuing paragraphs, we have sought to identify the key issues arising from the Model GST Law as may be relevant for the FMCG Industry.

1. Input Tax Credit

Reconciliation of inward and outward supplies, if there is a mismatch between the details of outward supplies uploaded on the GST Network by the vendors and the inward supplies uploaded by the recipient. Such mismatch will be communicated to the recipient. If the mismatch is not rectified by the vendor in the month of communication, the recipient will be liable to pay the differential GST along with interest, in the subsequent month. This provision places the liability for non-compliance on the recipients, i.e. the FMCG companies, as against their

vendors. Placing the responsibility on FMCG companies for non-compliance by vendors and stockists will cause undue hardship to these companies.

2. Area based exemptions under the Excise legislation and State Industrial Policy

The First Discussion Paper on GST had stated that area-based exemptions under the Excise legislation and incentives under the State Industrial policies should be converted to a tax refund mechanism. However, the transition provisions prescribed under the Model GST Law do not provide for the treatment of the said exemptions/ Incentives. Further, the valuation provisions envisage that subsidies should be included in the transaction value. This would impact the benefits available to the industry.

3. Transition provisions for traded goods

The transition provisions provide that the credit balance which was admissible under the present regime would be carried forward under GST. In case of stocks of imported finished goods, Countervailing Duty is not admissible under the present regime, and in case of goods procured from contract manufacturers, Excise Duty credit is also not available. Accordingly, based on these provisions, under the GST regime, such stocks would suffer double taxation.

4. Power to challenge the transaction value

The Model GST Law provides that if there is a reason to doubt the accuracy of the transaction value declared by the supplier, then the authorities can determine the transaction value as per the GST Valuation Rules. Such an unfettered power to question the transaction value can lead to litigation.

5. Taxability of Free Supplies

Supply of goods between persons without consideration is deemed to be a ‘supply’. Accordingly, stock transfer of promotion materials/ free samples will be subject to GST. Subsequent supply of the said promotion materials to

stockists/end customers will also attract GST. The valuation of such samples/ materials will be as per the GST Valuation Rules, i.e. the transaction value of goods of like kind and quality or the cost of sales. Under the present regime, free supplies are not subject to VAT. Hence, promotion expenses of FMCG companies will increase under the GST regime.

6. In case of warehouse across the states

Many of the FMCG companies set up units which offered tax benefits. They set up warehouses across the states in a bid to have a more tax efficient system. The very fact that they do not have to pay CST led them to carry out stock transfers to the warehouses. With the GST roll out the CST will be subsumed into GST and will have far reaching implications.

7. In the current scenario the traders are not entitled for any credit other than state

VAT

In the countries where GST or similar tax structure is prevalent the retailers avail of tax credits when they create infrastructure. This is likely to change for the FMCG industry with the GST implementation. Since the GST encompasses the goods and services under one fold, there will not be any distinction between manufacturers, traders and service providers with regard to taxation.

8. Impact on working capital

The impact on the working capital is likely to be significant for the FMCG industry. This is because of the time gap expected between the payment of GST and recovery of the tax credit. A sizeable chunk of money is expected to be blocked between the two

transactions. Stock transfers do not attract tax and the VAT is paid when the sales take place. However, with the GST in place it will be payable on the stock transfer as it is a destination based tax. The realization of the tax credit will only happen when the goods are actually sold which may take a long time. A serious rethink is required on the warehousing strategy.

IV. CONCLUSION

In short, under the proposed GST regime, various Indirect Taxes would be subsumed (except for few taxes such as Stamp Duty) and hence it is expected that it would result in a simpler tax regime, especially for industries like FMCG. Apart from simplification of tax compliances, the rate of tax will also have a significant impact on the FMCG sector. Presently the peak tax costs for industry players amount to approximately 27% (i.e. Excise Duty of 12.5% and VAT ranging from 12% to 15%). Under the GST regime, it is proposed that the revenue neutral rate would be in the range of 5% to 28%, thereby resulting in significant benefit for the sector. So, GST would have an impact on the pricing, working capital, contracts with vendors and customers, ERP systems, processes, internal control and accounting. Another important impact of GST on FMCG companies would be the opportunity to review the supply chain and move to a supply chain based on business parameters. Hence, GST would impact every aspect of the business.

TAXATION OF E-COMMERCE UNDER GST

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E-commerce as anything that involves an online transaction. E-commerce provides multiple benefits to the consumers in form of availability of goods at lower cost, wider choice and saves time. The general category of e-commerce can be broken down into two parts: E-merchandise: E-finance. E commerce involves conducting business using modern communication instruments: telephone, fax, e-payment, money transfer systems, e-data interchange and the Internet. Online businesses like financial services, travel, entertainment, and groceries are all likely to grow. Forces influencing the distribution of global e-commerce and its forms include economic factors, political factors, cultural factors and supranational institutions. Goods and Service Tax or GST as it is known is all set to be a game changer for the Indian economy. Overall it is known to be beneficial to both the consumer, business and the Government. In India, there are different indirect taxes applied on goods and services by central and state government.

GST is intended to include all these taxes into one tax with seamless ITC and charged on both goods and services. Thus excise duty, special additional duty, service tax, VAT to name a few will get repealed and will be added into GST. For this, GST will have 3 parts CGST, SGST and IGST. The central taxes like excise duty will be subsumed into CGST and state taxes like VAT into SGST. This going

to be forward on all transactions of both goods and services, only one tax will apply which is GST comprising of CGST and SGST. IGST would be applied instead of SGST for interstate transactions. Input credit of all these taxes will be available against all the respective outputs. This paper is outcome of a review of various research studies carried out on Impact of GST on E-commerce.

I. INTRODUCTION

E Commerce in India is one of the most growing market in India in Recent Years . India is adding three new Internet users every Second. E commerce companies have the potential creating 12 million Jobs in Next 10 Years. The unprecedented growth of the e commerce sector has been largely driven by Rapid Technology adoption and access to Internet through broadband, 3G, 4G etc. The explosive growth in the e - commerce sector sector has given rise to Multiple Tax Issues. Disputes have been arisen in case of e commerce Companies that Undertake Storage of goods procured from various sellers in their warehouse Would fall under ambit of VAT/CST.

Vat authorities are of View that e commerce companies are involving in Supplying and distribution of goods therefore would qualify as Dealer. Therefore they are liable to VAT. Some states are also Charging Entry Tax for delivering products to Customer in their state. Further levy of Service Tax on E Commerce transaction Under Aggregator Model has been brought into with effect from 01.03.2015.

II. HISTORY AND GROWTH OF E-COMMERCE IN INDIA

In recent years, e-commerce in India has managed to capture the eye-balls and also the mind-space of the consumers at large such as never before and with this

Unprecedented growth, India has become the second largest market for e-commerce. India is adding three new internet users every second. E-commerce companies have the potential of creating 12 million new jobs in the next 10 years. The e-commerce market in India is expected to breach the \$100-billion mark by 2020. To tap the opportunity, e-Commerce companies are aggressively ramping up their technology. E-Commerce is still less than 2% of the overall consumption in India, as against 14% in China. India can also take a leaf out of the example of Taobao village program in China created by Chinese internet giant Alibaba. From 20 such villages in 2013, the number has grown to 780 by 2015. These digital villages are spread over 17 provinces in China, and cover more than 2,00,000 active online shops. In India, more than 800 million people live in 640 lacs villages.

III. ADVANTAGES OF E-COMMERCE

Sell Internationally

Using e-Commerce, organization can expand their market to national and international markets with minimum capital investment. An organization can easily locate more customers, best suppliers and suitable business partners across the globe.

24x7 support to customers

Customer can do transactions for the product or enquiry about any product/services provided, anytime and anywhere from any location.

Reduces cost

E-Commerce helps organization to reduce the cost to create process, distribute, retrieve and manage the paper based information by digitizing the information.

Helps Government to deliver services

E-Commerce helps government to deliver public services like health care, education, social services at reduced costs and in improved way.

IV. E - COMMERCE CHALLENGES

High cash-on-delivery (COD):

COD is the preferred payment option in India which is risky, expensive and burdensome.

Payment gateways have a failure rate and also has a cost associated

Most of the customers do not make a second attempt after a transaction fails which is a loss point for e-commerce companies using Indian payment gateways.

Internet Connectivity:

Internet is the backbone of e-Commerce. But internet penetration in India is very low. Thus e-Commerce remains far away from common man. Cost of internet connection in India is also quite high.

Reach Ability:

Thousands of towns in India are not accessible and have poor transportation facility. A large population face an absence of seamless access, thus, e-Commerce companies loose a big portion of potential customers.

Low level of Digital Literacy:

At present, digital illiteracy is one of the formidable problems faced by e-commerce in India. Most of the India lie in the rural segment and is not in line with the growing digital trend.

V. VARIOUS MODELS OF E-COMMERCE

The need for e-Commerce companies to adopt and innovate in the light of technological challenges and rising competition, has led to the evolution of multiple business models resulting into a very crowded and complex market. Various models adopted by e-Commerce players include – managed marketplace model (MMP), open market place model (OMP), inventory led model, social networks, aggregator model etc. and many more hybrid models

still developing. Taking a holistic view of industry trends, with progressive liberalizations in the FDI policy, evolution of tax laws governing digital channels and advent of secure technology, e-commerce is poised for an exciting period of growth in times to come with simpler and legally compliant business structures.

Provisions under CGST/IGST Act:

CGST Act

Section 2: Definitions

Section 2(44): electronic commerce means supply of goods or services or both including digital products over digital or electronic network.

Section 2(45): electronic commerce operator means any person who owns, Operates or manages digital or electronic facility or platform for electronic commerce.

Section 9: Levy and Collection of Central/ State Goods and Services Tax(relevant part)

VI. IMPACT OF GST ON E-COMMERCE:

The provisions of GST Act will influence business strategies of both e-Commerce operators and suppliers in the following manner:-

Both e-Commerce player and seller will have to upload invoice wise details of supplies in their respective returns and the GST system will match them. If they do not reconcile then it will be added to the liability of the seller. This will lead to additional compliances.

TCS provisions shall be attracted on the first form of e-Commerce model, where both operator and supplier act on principal-to-principal (P2P) basis. It will lead to a lot of compliances and penalty provisions shall be applicable in case of non-compliance.

Most of sellers registered with marketplace operators are small and medium businesses. Government has introduced composition scheme under GST Act. Section

10(2) of CGST Act prescribes that if a person is engaged in making any supply of goods through an electronic commerce operator who is required to collect tax at source, then he cannot opt composition scheme. The advantages of composition scheme is one need to file only 5 returns per annum as against 37 in a normal case.

As per section 24, e-Commerce operators and persons who supply goods or services or both are required to be registered compulsorily under this Act. Thus the small seller having turnover up to 20 lacs who is not otherwise required to be registered, will have to be compulsorily registered under this Act.

As per the registration provisions under Chapter-VI of CGST Act, every business involved in E-commerce is required to get registered in each State in which they making taxable supplies. Since the e-commerce business model is as such that the seller expects order from all the states, they are liable to obtain registration in all the states.

VII. CONCLUSION

Looking at the intricacies involved in the taxation of sale of goods under various models of e-commerce, it is necessary that a regulation proposed to be framed under GST to look into the various issues relating thereto. For the time being, E-commerce companies have to be very vigilant while drafting of agreement between vendors and tax burden must be casted on the vendors.

FEATURES AND BENEFITS OF GST IN INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a value added tax to be implemented in India, the decision on which is pending. GST is the only indirect tax that directly affects all sectors and sections of our economy. The goods and services tax (GST) is aimed at creating a single, unified market that will benefit both corporate and the economy. Under the GST scheme, no distinction is made between goods and services for levying of tax. In other words, goods and services attract the same rate of tax. GST is a multi-tier tax where ultimate burden of tax fall on the consumer of goods and services. It is called as value added tax because at every stage, tax is being paid on the value addition. Under the GST scheme, a person who was liable to pay tax on his output, whether for provision of service or sale of goods, is entitled to get input tax credit (ITC) on the tax paid on its inputs.

Introduction of the Value Added Tax (VAT) at the Central and the State level has been considered to be a major step – an important step forward –in the globe of indirect tax reforms in India. If the VAT is a major improvement over the pre-existing Central Excise Duty at the National level and the sales tax system at the State level, then the Goods and Services Tax (GST) will indeed be an additional important

perfection – the next logical step – towards a widespread indirect tax reforms in the country.

Keywords: *GST, Features, Constitution, Indirect Tax Central Excise Duty.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The government has taken many initiatives to realize its objectives. In this context, the discussion on GST has been underway for more than a decade. In 2005 budget, the Government had announced the introduction of GST. However it was deferred to a later date. In December 2009, the GST Bill was tabled for the First Reading in the Dewan Rakyat in 2010. Present Taxation System in India includes Multi-stage taxation on manufacture and distribution channels, Sectors specific taxes like Entertainment Tax, Luxury Tax and Textile Cess etc. Difference types of Cess like Education Cess, Secondary & Higher Education Cess etc. Tax on value additions i.e. Value Added Tax and Tax on Inter State transaction i.e. Central Sales Tax Goods and Services Tax or GST is a consumption tax based on value-added concept. According to the 122nd CAB, 1 the term ‘GST’ was defined by introducing a clause 12A in Article 366 of the Constitution of India, to mean “any tax on supply of goods or services or both except taxes on supply of the alcoholic liquor for

human consumption.” Unlike the present sales tax or service tax which is a single stage tax, GST is a multi-stage tax. Payment of tax is made in stages by intermediaries in the production and distribution process. The tax itself is not a cost to the intermediaries since they are able to claim back GST incurred on their business inputs. GST is imposed on goods and services at every production and distribution stage in the supply chain including importation of goods and services.

Goods and Services Tax

- CGST
- IGST
- SGST

Updated New GST Tax Rates of 27 Items & Other Services Slashed

The Finance Minister Arun Jaitley has announced a growing list of rate reductions. The unbranded ayurvedic medicines now come under the tax slab of 5%, down from 12%. Gas stove and consumer articles have been moved to a lower tax bracket from the high of 28%. Giving a relief to the artisans, the GST Council has cut the rate of some handicraft items to 5% from the existing 12%. The rates of yarn and clips are also slashed to 12% and 18% respectively, providing a fillip to the country's textile industry. Even the rates for several job work items are reduced to 5% from 12%. Meanwhile, the council has granted an in-principle approval to bringing down the rates of AC restaurants to 12% from 18% at present.

Various GST Tax Slabs in India

No Tax 0%

- Goods - No taxes will be levied on goods like milk, fruits, vegetables, bread, salt, bindi, curd, sindoor, natural honey, bangles, handloom, besan, flour, eggs, stamps, printed books, judicial papers, and newspapers.

- Services - All hotels and lodges who carry a tariff below Rs.1,000 are exempted from taxes under GST.

GST Tax Slab of 5%

- Goods - The goods which will attract a taxation of 5% under GST include skimmed milk powder, fish fillet, frozen vegetables, coffee, coal, fertilizers, tea, spices, pizza bread, kerosene, ayurvedic medicines, agarbatti, sliced dry mango, insulin, cashew nuts, unbranded napkin, lifeboats etc,

- Services - Small restaurants along with transport services like railways and airways will come under this category.

GST Tax Slab of 12%

- Goods - Items coming are the tax slab of 12% include frozen meat products, butter, cheese, ghee, pickles, sausage, fruit juices, napkin, tooth powder, medicine, umbrella, instant food mix, cell phones, sewing machine, man-made yarn, etc.

- Services - All Non-AC hotels, business class air tickets will attract a tax of 12% under GST.

GST Tax Slab of 18%

- Goods - As mentioned above, most of the items are part of this tax slab. Some of the items are flavored refined sugar, cornflakes, pasta, pastries and cakes, preserved vegetables, tractors, ice cream, sauces, soups, mineral water, stones used in flooring other than marble & granite, stationery items like clips, some diesel engine parts, some parts of pumps,

- Services - All those AC hotels which serve liquor, IT and Telecom services and financial services along with branded garments will be part of this tax slab.

GST Tax Slab of 28%

- Goods - Over 200 goods will be taxed at a rate of 28%. The goods which will be part of this category under GST are deodorants, chewing gum, hair shampoo, sunscreen, pan masala, dishwasher, weighing machine, vacuum cleaner. Other items

include shavers, automobiles, hair clippers, motorcycles.

- Services - As mentioned above, five-star hotels, racing, and movie tickets and betting on casinos and racing will come under this category.

What is GST

GST stands for Goods and Service Tax, which by virtue of its launch, has replaced the previous structure of multiple taxes levied by the State and Central government. It is a consumption based indirect tax which is charged on sale, manufacturing and consumption on goods and services at the National level. Exports and direct taxes like Income tax, corporate tax and capital gain tax will not be affected by GST. The much-awaited GST has a dual tax system comprising of –

- Central GST or CGST – To be charged by the central government.
- State GST or SGST – To be charged by the state government.
- Integrated GST or IGST – To be charged by central government on the inter-state supply of various goods and services.

Features of GST

1. GST would be applicable on “supply” of goods or services as against the present concept of tax on the manufacture of goods or on sale of goods or on provision of services.

2. GST defined as any tax on supply of goods and services other than on alcohol for human consumptions.

3. Entertainment tax, imposed by States on movie, theatre, etc will be subsumed in GST, but taxes on entertainment at panchayat, municipality or district level to continue.

4. Import of services would be treated as inter-state supplies and would be subject to IGST.

5. CGST, SGST/UTGST & IGST would be levied at rates to be mutually agreed upon by the centre and the states under the aegis of the GSTC.

6. Central taxes like, Central Excise duty, Additional Excise duty, Service tax, Additional Custom duty and Special Additional duty and State level taxes like, VAT or sales tax, Central Sales tax, Entertainment tax, Entry tax, Purchase tax, Luxury tax and Octroi will subsume in GST.

7. Petroleum and petroleum products i.e. crude, high speed diesel, motor spirit, aviation turbine fuel and natural gas shall be subject to the GST on a date to be notified by the GST Council.

8. 1% origin based additional tax to be levied on inter-State supply of goods will be non-creditable in GST chain. The revenue from this tax is to be assigned to the Origin State. This tax is proposed to be levied for initial two years or such period as recommended by the GST Council.

Benefits of GST

Make in India

(i) Will help to create a unified common national market for India, giving a boost to foreign investment and “Make in India” campaign.

(ii) Will prevent cascading of taxes as Input Tax Credit will be available across goods and services at every stage of supply.

(iii) Improve the overall investment climate in the country which will naturally benefit the development in the states.

Ease of Doing Business

(i) Reductions in the multiplicity of taxes that are at present governing our indirect tax system leading to simplification and uniformity.

(ii) Simplified and automated procedures for various processes such as registration, returns, refunds, tax payments, etc;

Benefits to Consumers

(i) Final price of goods is expected to be lower due to seamless flow of input tax credit between the manufacturer, retailer and service supplier;

(ii) Average tax burden on companies is likely to come down which is expected to reduce prices and lower prices mean more consumption.

a) To Centre Government and State Governments

- GST Bill will promote more Exports
- Increase in employment opportunities which will reciprocate with a boost in growth of the economy.

- The tax burden is divided between manufacturing and services.

b) To Individuals and Companies

- Centre and State Government will collect taxes at the point-of-sale and both will be charged on manufacturing cost.

Advantages of GST

- GST is a transparent Tax and also reduces number of indirect taxes. With GST implemented a business premises can show the tax applied in the sales invoice. Customer will know exactly how much tax they are paying on the product they bought or services they consumed.

- GST will not be a cost to registered retailers therefore there will be no hidden taxes and the cost of doing business will be lower. This in turn will help Export being more competitive.

- GST can also help to diversification of income sources for Government other than income tax and petroleum tax.

- Under Goods and Services Tax, the tax burden will be divided equally between Manufacturing and services. This can be done through lower tax rate by increase Tax base and reducing exemptions.

- In GST System both Central GST and State GST will be charged on manufacturing cost and will be collected on point of sale. This will benefit people as prices will come down which in turn will help companies as consumption will increase.

- Biggest benefit will be that multiple taxes like Octroi, central sales tax, state sales tax, entry tax,

license fees, turnover tax etc will no longer be present and all that will be brought under the GST. Doing business now will be easier and more comfortable as various hidden taxation will not be present.

Disadvantages of GST

- Critics say that GST would impact negatively on the real estate market. It would add up to 8 percent to the cost of new homes and reduce demand by about 12 percent. Some Economist says that CGST, SGST and IGST are nothing but new names for Central Excise/Service Tax, VAT and CST and hence GST brings nothing new for which we should cheer.

- Very high tax rates of 16% compared to current 12.5 % VAT. Since taxes are distributed across the chain, the consumer prices are likely to rise to maintain the current tax revenue levels.

- All goods and services brought under the GST with only few items are exempted and make the people's life miserable.
- Amendment to constitution is a formidable task- where state governments consent is needed.
- Training of Government officials /personnel.

II. CONCLUSION

The successful implementation of GST depends on the understanding and co-operation between Central and State Governments. Further, there are many hurdles to be crossed in its implementation. Whether, the GST makes life easy or more comfortable, future remains to be unseen. But it is certain that the monthly budget of people if goes beyond the essential consumer goods, will impact their overall expenses and creates more complications. In addition to this, the impact of inflation is always unpredictable, even there is no guarantee that the manufacturer will pass on the tax benefit to the end user. Keeping these issues aside, it can conclude that GST will be a welcome change for the development of the economy since it is expected to simplify the indirect tax structure in India.

AN IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST) ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

GST also known as the Goods and Services Tax is defined as the giant indirect tax structure designed to support and enhances the economic growth of a country. More than 150 countries have implemented GST so far. However, the idea of GST in India was mooted by Vajpayee government in 2000 and the constitutional amendment for the same was passed by the Lok Sabha on 6th May 2015 but is yet to be ratified by the Rajya Sabha. However, there is a huge hue and cry against its implementation. It would be interesting to understand why this proposed GST regime may hamper the growth and development of the country.

Key words: *Goods and service tax; Indian economy*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a vast concept that simplifies the giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of a country. GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacturing, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. The Goods and Services Tax Bill or GST Bill, also referred to as The Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Second

Amendment) Bill, 2014, initiates a Value added Tax to be implemented on a national level in India. GST will be an indirect tax at all the stages of production to bring about uniformity in the system.

On bringing GST into practice, there would be amalgamation of Central and State taxes into a single tax payment. It would also enhance the position of India in both, domestic as well as international market. At the consumer level, GST would reduce the overall tax burden, which is currently estimated at 25-30%.

Under this system, the consumer pays the final tax but an efficient input tax credit system ensures that there is no cascading of taxes- tax on tax paid on inputs that go into manufacture of goods.

In order to avoid the payment of multiple taxes such as excise duty and service tax at Central level and VAT at the State level, GST would unify these taxes and create a uniform market throughout the country. Integration of various taxes into a GST system will bring about an effective cross-utilization of credits. The current system taxes production, whereas the GST will aim to tax consumption.

Importance of GST

Presently, the Constitution empowers the Central Government to levy excise duty on manufacturing and service tax on the supply of services. Further, it empowers the State Governments to levy sales tax or value added tax (VAT) on the sale of goods. This exclusive division of fiscal powers has led to a multiplicity of indirect taxes in the country. In addition, central sales tax (CST) is levied on inter-State sale of goods by the Central Government, but collected and retained by the exporting States. Further, many States levy an entry tax on the entry of goods in local areas.

a) This multiplicity of taxes at the State and Central levels has resulted in a complex indirect tax structure in the country that is ridden with hidden costs for the trade and industry. Firstly, there is no uniformity of tax rates and structure across States. Secondly, there is cascading of taxes due to 'tax on tax'. No credit of excise duty and service tax paid at the stage of manufacture is available to the traders while paying the State level sales tax or VAT, and vice-versa. Further, no credit of State taxes paid in one State can be availed in other States. Hence, the prices of goods and services get artificially inflated to the extent of this 'tax on tax'.

b) The introduction of GST would mark a clear departure from the scheme of distribution of fiscal powers envisaged in the Constitution. The proposed dual GST envisages taxation of the same taxable event, i.e., supply of goods and services, simultaneously by both the Centre and the States. Therefore, both Centre and States will be empowered to levy GST across the value chain from the stage of manufacture to consumption. The credit of GST paid on inputs at every stage of value addition would be available for the discharge of GST liability on the output, thereby ensuring GST is charged on Indian Economy

Benefits of GST

- It would introduce two-tiered One-Country-One-Tax regime.
- It would subsume all indirect taxes at the center and the state level.
- It would not only widen the tax regime by covering goods and services but also make it transparent.
- It would free the manufacturing sector from cascading effect of taxes, thus by improve the cost-competitiveness of goods and services.
- It would bring down the prices of goods and services and thus by, increase consumption.
- It would create business-friendly environment, thus by increase tax-GDP ratio.
- It would enhance the ease of doing business in India.

Reason for the development of Indian Economy after GST

- Elimination of Number of Taxes-The most significant benefit of GST for Indian economy is that it has abolished the system of multiple taxes. With the introduction of GST, the various taxes like octroi, excise, sales tax, service tax applicable earlier are absorbed in one tax.
- Boost the Government Revenue- Under the GST regime appropriate steps have been taken to check tax evasion which will result in increased revenue of government. Also, the facility of input tax credit will motivate more people to pay taxes.
- Remove Cascading effect- GST will be applicable on every stage from manufacturer to consumer. Facility of input tax credit is also available at every stage in the chain. GST is basically the cost to the end consumer. Thus it will help in getting rid of the cascading effect of the current taxation system. This will also reduce the rate of inflation.
- Lesser Cost of transportation and Warehouses- The business entities in India had to maintain multiple warehouses across states to avoid

the earlier applicable CST and state entry taxes on inter-state movement. Most of the times, these warehouses were forced to operate below their capacity thus increasing their operating costs. After the implementation GST these restrictions on inter-state movement of goods will be lessened which will motivate the business entities to consolidate their warehouses. Reduction in unnecessary transportation and warehouses costs will increase profits for businesses involved in the supply of goods through transportation that will contribute in the growth of the economy.

- **Increased Investment-** With the introduction of GST input tax credit on capital goods will be available which was not available earlier which will motivate the business entities to invest more in capital goods.

- **Transparency-** GST is a complete online procedure. Also, the dealers are required to add every detail regarding the sale and purchases which will result in much more transparency in the system. This will boost the Indian economy.

- **Increased GDP rate-** GST is expected to have a positive impact on Indian economy. As the GDP rate is expected to rise by 0.80% with the introduction of GST.

However, the experts are still skeptic about the short implications of goods and service tax on the Indian economy. There are a lot of reasons due which the growth of the Indian economy may be harmed by the introduction of GST. In the short run, the growing Indian economy will be suffering due to the reasons like-

- **Increased Operating Cost-** In the earlier taxation system the small business units did not employ tax professionals and preferred to pay taxes and file returns on their own to save costs. However, post-GST regime they will require professional assistance to become GST compliant as it is a completely new system. While this will benefit the

professionals, the small businesses will have to bear the additional cost of hiring experts. Also, they are required to train their employees regarding the new system which will further add to the overhead cost. This will adversely impact the growth of the Indian economy.

- **Increased Compliances-** The compliances requirements under the GST regime are much higher than the earlier tax regime. Every taxpayer is required to submit 3 returns monthly along with the annual return. That means a total of 37 returns are required to be filed by a taxpayer annually.

These additional costs may result in the increment of the price of products which may harm the growth of Indian economy as a whole.

Positive Impact of GST

All most every industry body are "fully prepared" for implementation of the new indirect tax regime, while commending the government's efforts towards its rollout. The nationwide GST will overhaul India's convoluted indirect taxation system and unify the over \$2 trillion economy with 1.3 billion people into a single market. The medium-term impact of GST on macroeconomic indicators is expected to be extremely positive. Inflation will be reduced as cascading of taxes will be eliminated. ASSOCHAM president Sandeep Jajodia said India would move many notches up the global ease of doing ladder by this single, but the most important tax reform in the country.

Negative Impact of GST

India has adopted dual GST instead of national GST. It has made the entire structure of GST fairly International Journal of Management and Applied Science, ISSN: 2394-7926 Volume-3, Issue-5, May-2017 <http://iraj.in> Positive and Negative Impact of GST on Indian Economy 160 complicated in India. The centre will have to coordinate with 29 states and 7 union territories to implement such tax regime. Such regime is likely to create economic as well as

political issues. The states are likely to lose the say in determining rates once GST is implemented. The sharing of revenues between the states and the centre is still a matter of contention with no consensus arrived regarding revenue neutral rate. Pre GST service tax of 15%, which would increase to 18-20% in post GST. Hence, although prices of goods and products can come down, service industry will bear the brunt of higher taxes. Air travel, hotels would become more expensive. Currently, economy class tickets are taxed 6% and non-economy class tickets are charged 9%. Once GST is implemented, it would increase to 18%, thereby leading to direct increase of 9-12% tax on the tickets. Unless the airlines absorb this increase, the

Additional tax has to be paid by the consumer.

1. Proposed GST Rate Is Higher Than VAT

The rate of GST is proposed to be higher than the current VAT rate in India, which although reducing the price in the longer run, will be of no help in cutting down prices of commodities.

2. Dual Control

A business will be indirectly controlled by both the Centre and the State in all tax related matters. The

State will lose autonomy to change the tax rate which will be regulated by the GST Council.

3. Loss Incurred By the Manufacturing States

Since GST is mostly related to the manufacturing segment, most manufacturing states may incur losses. But the government has proposed to compensate for those losses for a period of 5 years.

II. CONCLUSION

The proposed GST regime is a half-hearted attempt to rationalize indirect tax structure. More than 150 countries have implemented GST. The government of India should study the GST regime set up by various countries and also their fallouts before implementing it. At the same time, the government should make an attempt to insulate the vast poor population of India against the likely inflation due to implementation of GST. No doubt, GST will simplify existing indirect tax system and will help to remove inefficiencies created by the existing current heterogeneous taxation system only if there is a clear consensus over issues of threshold limit, revenue rate, and inclusion of petroleum products, electricity, liquor and real estate. Until the consensus is reached, the government should resist from implementing such regime.

IMPACT OF GST IN INTERNATIONAL TRADE

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Abstract

The present paper is an attempt to evaluate the impact of GST on India's Foreign Trade. GST will be rolled out sometime during April to October 2017. The implementation of the Bill is expected to ease India's cumbersome tax system, help goods move seamlessly across state borders, curb tax evasion, improve compliance, increase revenues, spur growth, boost exports, and attract investments by improving ease of doing business in India. In short, GST when implemented is expected to perform miracles. But the question is – Can it really bring such radical changes?

Keywords: GST, India, Foreign Trade

I. INTRODUCTION

India is the fastest growing economy in the world and is just preceded to the economy of china. India has the seventh largest economy in the world. The basic tool to evaluate any country is its Balance of Payment (which includes reserves, current and capital accounts). One of the most significant factors that lead to a growth in the economy of a country is Trade (import-export). So it becomes a vital part to have a watch trade performance on both, domestic as well as international markets. Implementation of the regime would be a speculation to all the sectors of industry.

Meaning

What is Import-Export of goods?

“Export of Goods”, as defined in central GST Act, 2016, means taking out of India to a place outside India.

“Import of Goods” with its grammatical variations and cognate expressions, means bringing in India from a place outside India.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Nishitha Guptha (2014) in her study stated that implementation of GST in the Indian framework will lead to commercial benefits which were untouched by the VAT system and would essentially lead to economic development. Hence GST may usher in the possibility of a collective gain for industry, trade, agriculture and common consumers as well as for the Central Government and the State Government.

Jaiprakash (2014) in his research study mentioned that the GST at the Central and the State level are expected to give more relief to industry, trade, agriculture and consumers through a more comprehensive and wider coverage of input tax set-off and service tax setoff, subsuming of several taxes in the GST and phasing out of CST. Responses of industry and also of trade have been indeed encouraging. Thus GST offers us the best option to broaden our tax base and we should not miss this opportunities to introduce it when the circumstances are quite favorable and economy is enjoying steady growth with only mild inflation.

Saravanan Venkadasalam (2014) has analysed the post effect of the goods and service tax (GST) on the national growth on ASEAN States using Least Squares Dummy Variable Model (LSDVM) in his research paper. He stated that seven of the ten ASEAN nations are already implementing the GST.

He also suggested that the household final consumption expenditure and general government consumption expenditure are positively significantly related to the gross domestic product as required and support the economic theories. But the effect of the post GST differs in countries. Philippines and Thailand show significant negative relationship with their nation's development. Meanwhile, Singapore shows a significant positive relationship.

It is undeniable that those countries whom implementing GST always encounter grows. Nevertheless, the extent of the impact varies depending on the governance, compliance cost and economic distortion.

III. INTERNATIONAL TRADE

International Trade is usually referred to the exchange of goods, and services across international borders or territories. In most countries, it represents a significant share of gross domestic product (GDP).

International economics is a field of study which assesses the implications of international trade in goods and services and international investment.

Advantages & Disadvantages of International Trade

Advantages of International Trade:

(i) Optimal use of natural resources:

International trade helps each country to make optimum use of its natural resources. Each country can concentrate on production of those goods for which its resources are best suited. Wastage of resources is avoided.

(ii) Availability of all types of goods:

It enables a country to obtain goods which it cannot produce or which it is not producing due to higher costs, by importing from other countries at lower costs.

(iii) Specialization:

Foreign trade leads to specialization and encourages production of different goods in different

countries Goods can be produced at a comparatively low cost due to advantages of division of labour.

(iv) Large – scale production:

Due to international trade, Goods are produced not only for home consumption but for export to other countries also.

(v) Stability in prices:

International trade irons out wild fluctuations in prices. It equalizes the prices goods through the world (ignoring cost of transportation, etc.)

Disadvantages of International trade:

Through foreign trade has many advantages, its dangers or disadvantages should not be ignored.

(i) Impediment in the development of Home Industries:

International trade has an adverse effect on the development of home industries. It poses a threat to the survival of infant industries at home. Due to foreign competition and unrestricted imports, the upcoming industries in the country may collapse.

(ii) Economic Dependence:

The under developed countries have to depend upon the developed ones for their economic development. Such reliance often leads to economic exploitation.

(iii) Political Dependence:

International trade often encourages subjection and slavery. It impairs economic independence which endangers political dependence.

(iv) Import of Harmful Goods:

Import of spurious drugs, luxury articles, etc. adversely affects the economy and well – being of the people.

(v) Storage of Goods:

Sometimes the essential commodities required in a country and in short supply are also exported to earn foreign exchange. This results in shortage of these goods at home and causes inflation.

IV. IMPACT OF GST ON IMPORTS AND EXPORTS IN INDIA

The new goods and services tax (GST), launched on July 1, 2017, will change how business is done in India. It is likely to have a significant impact on the international trade of goods through changes in the structure of import and export taxation, and the withdrawal of various indirect taxes and exemptions.

GST impact on imported goods and services

In the previous tax system, the imports of goods were subject to import duties such as custom duty, countervailing duty (equivalent to excise duty), and special additional duty (equivalent to value added tax), and the import of services was subject to service tax.

Duty and GST on Imported Goods

Under the reformed tax structure, the integrated goods and services tax (IGST) replaces the previous indirect taxes imposed on the import of goods and services. Certain exceptions such as imports of pan masala and petroleum products, however, continue to attract levy of countervailing duties.

In addition to IGST, customs duty, education cess, and other protective taxes, such as the anti-dumping duty and safe-guard duty, also continue to be levied on imports of certain goods – carrying over from the previous tax regime. For the import of services, only IGST is levied.

The Integrated Goods and Services Tax (IGST)

Imports under GST are treated as inter-state supply. Since GST is a destination-based tax, IGST will be levied in the state where the imported goods are consumed and imported services are received. GST can be paid using input tax credit of central goods and services tax (CGST), state goods and services tax (SGST), and IGST. Input tax credit is the credit that dealers can avail for taxes paid on their purchases, at the time of paying final tax on their sales.

In case of CGST and SGST, no cross utilization of input tax credit is allowed. This means that input tax credit of CGST can only be utilized for CGST and IGST, and input tax credit of SGST can only be utilized to pay for SGST and IGST.

Import of Services Under GST

Under GST, the import of service is taxable if –

- The supplier of service is located outside India;
 - The recipient of service is located in India;
 - The place of supply of service is in India;
- and

Transitional Provision

Businesses must note that if the import of services is made on or after July 1, 2017, it shall be chargeable to tax under GST law even if the transaction was initiated before July 1, 2017. Furthermore, if the tax on import of services has been paid in part under the previous law, the balance tax shall be paid under the new GST law.

Tax Returns

An importer is required to file monthly tax returns under GST. Under the previous law, the importer was required to file returns under state tax law for purchase of goods (import of goods) and under central tax laws for claiming countervailing duties. While filing monthly returns, importers must declare the goods imported in table-5 of the GSTR-2 form, and services imported in table-6 of the GSTR-2 form.

Exemptions

Previously, the transportation of goods by aircraft and inbound shipment was not liable to service tax. Under GST, there is no such exemption.

V. NEED OF GST IN INDIA

The GST is being introduced not only to get rid of the current patchwork of indirect taxes that are partial and suffer from infirmities, mainly exemptions and multiple rates, but also to improve tax compliances. The spread of GST in different

countries has been one of the most important developments in taxation over the last six decades, owing to its capacity to raise revenue in the most transparent and neutral manner, more than 150 countries have adopted the GST.

Take the form of a “dual” GST, to be levied The words “levy, legislate and administer” are chief, since the Centre and the state will legislate the respective GST Acts and both will have power to administer the taxes.

Finance Minister Arun Jaitley presented the bill in the lower house of the Parliament in 2014. It is defined as any tax on the supply of goods or services that will subsume CENVAT, service tax, additional excise duties, central excise duty, excise duties levied under the Medicinal and Toilet Preparations (Excise Duties) Act, 1955, service tax, additional customs duty (countervailing duty or CVD), central surcharges special additional duty of customs (SAD) and cesses, State sales tax, entertainment tax, State VAT, not levied by local bodies, luxury tax, taxes on lottery advertisements.

VI. GST – HOW IT WORKS IN INDIA

The GST system is based on the same concept as VAT. The GST model has some aspects which are as follows:

Components: GST will be divided into two components, namely, Central Goods and Service Tax and State Goods and Service

Applicability: GST will be applicable to all Goods and Services sold or provided in India, except from the list of exempted goods which fall outside its purview.

Payment: GST will be charged and paid separately in case of Central and State level Input Tax

Credit: The facility of Input Tax Credit at Central level will only be available in respect of Central Goods and Service tax.

VII. CONCLUSION

The enumeration of benefits casts a welcome setting for GST, Proving GST as a superior and sufficient system depends upon the structure it is designed into and the manner of implementation. While it serves to be beneficial set up for the Industry and the Consumer, it would lead to increase in revenue to Government.

GST IN INDIA: A SWOT ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Goods and service tax being a broad based, single comprehensive system of tax is in its birth stage in India. Therefore the understanding of the concept of GST is important. The paper therefore studies the concept of GST and also examines the mechanism of it. The paper also focuses on analyzing the SWOT of GST implementation in India.

I. INTRODUCTION

GST is a broad based, single, comprehensive tax levied on goods and services at each point of sale of goods or provision of service, in which, the seller or service provider may claim the input credit of tax which he has paid while purchasing the goods or availing the service; the final consumer will thus bear only the GST charged by the last dealer in the supply chain. With the introduction of GST at the State level, the additional burden of CENVAT and services tax would be comprehensively removed and major Central and State taxes will get subsumed into GST which will reduce the multiplicity of taxes.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ahmad, E., & Poddar, S. (2009), GST reforms and inter-governmental Considerations in India, in their working paper have given a detailed explanation about the shortcomings of the current tax regime and the objective of the tax reform. Besides these it also gave options for Centre and State GST. It threw light on the tax base and tax rates for various sectors. It concluded by giving means of harmonizing taxes and ways of administering them.

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III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Every initiative taken by the Government will have both pros and cons. It is important to study which of these two is greater. Therefore an attempt has been made to analyze the SWOT of GST implementation in India.

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROBLEM

Since India hasn't implemented GST, a study of this kind besides creating awareness would also help

in analyzing the pros and cons of GST and the important points that has to be kept in mind before its implementation as it would affect different stakeholders differently.

V. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To study the concept of Goods and Services Tax
- 2) To examine the mechanism of Goods and Services Tax
- 3) To analyze the SWOT of GST implementation in India

Limitations of the Study

The study is restricted only to India although other countries have made great progress in this field.

VI. METHODOLOGY-DATA COLLECTION

Data has been obtained from Secondary sources like National & international Journals, Government reports, publications from various websites which focused on various aspects of Goods and Service tax.

VII. GOODS AND SERVICE TAX IN INDIA

Emergence of GST

The concept of VAT was introduced in the year 1986 to overcome the limitation of levy of duty i.e., cascading of taxes, where duty was collected on both inputs used and outputs produced. This problem was addressed with the help of VAT where the tax paid on the inputs can be deducted from the tax payable on the outputs produced. Even though the problem of cascading of taxation was addressed there were other problems like goods and services were taxed differently, sectors like real estate, oil and gas productions, etc were exempted from tax, several central and state taxes were exempted from tax. Thus, in order to overcome these problems GST was introduced. In the year 2011, 115th amendment was made in the constitution bill for the introduction of GST but the bill was lapsed with the dissolution of 15th Lok Sabha. And in December 2014 122nd amendment was made in the constitution bill for the introduction of GST and the bill was passed by the

Lok Sabha. It has not been approved by the Rajya Sabha yet.

Scope of GST

- GST would be applicable on the supply of goods or services.
- GST exempts alcoholic liquor for human consumption.
- Taxation of the following items will be kept on hold as GST initially would not be apply to: (a) petroleum crude, (b) high speed diesel, (c) motor spirit (petrol), (d) natural gas, and (e) aviation turbine fuel. The GST Council will decide when GST will be levied on them.
- Tobacco and tobacco products would be subject to GST. It might also be subject to excise duty by the Centre.

Expected workable pattern of GST in India

The GST system is based on the same concept as VAT. Instead of the set-off being available for the tax paid in the previous level in GST it would be charged only at the time of sale. Important aspects to be observed:

- Components: GST will have two components, namely, Central Goods and Service Tax and State Goods and Service Tax.
- Rate: Rates charged across all states and the central level will be uniform along with the regulations, definitions and classifications
- Applicability: GST will be applicable to all Goods and Services sold or provided in India, except from the list of exempted goods which fall outside its purview.
- Payment: GST will be charged and paid separately in case of Central and State level.
- Input Tax credit: The facility of Input Tax Credit at Central level will only be available in respect of Central Goods and Service tax. In other words, the ITC of Central Goods and Service tax shall not be allowed as a set-off against State Goods and Service tax and vice versa.

Mechanism of GST

The idea behind the implementation of GST was to subsume all existing taxes of the state and Centre under one value added tax, which would be levied on all goods and service. No good or service would be exempt and also there would not be any differentiation a between goods or services. This rule would apply to both input and finished product. The tax paid on input tax would be deducted from the tax paid on the output produced and it continues from manufacturing stage to the distribution stage. Tax would be collected only at the place of consumption. This system of tax addresses the issue of cascading of taxes.

Below given table explains the modus operandi of GST. It tries to compare the taxation under the current system and the GST.

Table No:1: Comparison of tax under the current indirect tax system and the GST regime

Particulars	Current system	GST
Cost of raw material	100	100
Tax on raw material	10	10
Value added by manufacturer	10	10
Tax payable by manufacturer	1 (CENVAT: 10% of 10)	1 (GST: 10% of 10)
Retailer's cost	121	121
Retailer's margin	10	10
Tax payable	13.1 (Sales Tax: 10% of 131)	1 (GST: 10% of 10)
Final price paid including taxes	144.1	132
Of which taxes	24.1	12

In this example, the cost of the raw material is 100. The manufacturer and retailer add Rs 10 value each. The tax rate is assumed to be 10% for all taxes.

- Current tax regime: Both Excise and Sales Tax are a VAT system, but the set off for taxes paid is not applicable across these taxes. Therefore, sales tax is applicable to the excise duty (CENVAT) paid.

Thus, tax paid is 11 (excise) plus 13.1 (sales tax). Here there is 'tax on tax' effect where the final selling price not only has two taxes, but also a tax-on-tax.

- GST regime: There is a single tax with input credit. This means that each person pays tax only on the value added by him. Consequently, the total tax is less, resulting in a lower price of the good.

This comparison makes it clear that with the implementation of GST, the ultimate consumer will get the goods and services at a lower price.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- GST provides a comprehensive and a wider coverage of input credit set off service tax credit could be used for the payment of tax on the sale of goods etc.
- A single GST could be used instead of other indirect taxes at the state and central level.
- It would end the cascading effects.
- There would be uniformity of tax rates across the states.
- It ensures better compliance as the aggregate tax reduces.
- It helps in the reduction of prices of the goods and services to the consumer with the reduction of tax.
- It would reduce transaction costs and unnecessary wastage to both government and individuals.
- It encourages transparency and unbiased tax structure.
- It brings efficiency in the indirect tax mechanism.

Weakness

- It doesn't include alcohol and petroleum products which would lead to incurring of huge losses.
- It requires strong IT infrastructure which is not highly developed in India.

- Single GST rate would be high compared to individual indirect tax rate.

- In reality, it might result in a dual tax system in which both state and the Centre would collect tax separately.

- Dealers paying VAT in the state will be required to pay GST at the Centre

Sudden implementation of GST might create confusion to the common man Opportunities

- Reduction in tax burden will increase the competitiveness of Indian products in the international market

- There would be a gradual increase in the revenues of state and the union

- Helps reducing corruption as the implementation of GST would result in a gradual decrease of procedures and formalities

Threats

- It is entirely dependent on the efficiency and effectiveness of the system
- Beneficiaries of the system are uncertain. It could be either state or the Centre. This would create a chaos while preparing budgets and financing polices
- Lack of co-ordination between the Centre and the state might affect the system and also the revenues generated

Interpretation of the SWOT Analysis

From the above SWOT analysis it is clear that GST would create uniformity of taxes and also reduce tax burden. This in turn would increase revenues of the state and the union at the country level and increase competition at the international level. But this in reality might appear to be a dual tax system and would also require a strong IT infrastructure. Besides this, it is entirely dependent on the efficiency of the system. Co-ordination between the Centre and the state only can help in its implementation and execution of the proposed plan. Therefore before implementation of such a tax regime, it should be

carefully examined at every levels to benefit all the stakeholders.

VIII. SUGGESTIONS

- Sufficient preparations need to be made by both Central and State governments for implementing GST at all levels
- Besides Government, there could be other professional bodies which could assist in the execution of the proposed system
- Tax-payers should be clear about the system and the mechanism
- Alternative schemes should be offered to those who would be adversely affected.

Policies should be framed to protect the interest of the SSI and small traders who could be adversely affected.

IX. CONCLUSION

Implementation of GST will be a significant step towards a comprehensive indirect tax reform in India. History has proved by giving success stories of various countries that have benefited from moving to a GST regime. From the SWOT analysis presented in the paper it is clear that GST would not only bring about an efficient and a transparent system but also help in removing economic distortions. With a well-planned GST regime, India would be both business friendly and consumer friendly economy. At present, consensus among political parties and the states only would help in the successful implementation of GST.

GST RATE FOR GOLD & JEWELLERY

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Abstract

GST was meant to simplify Indian tax regime by unifying the entire country into a single market with one tax rate. However, what is being implemented this week is a web of tax with seven different tax slabs and numerous rates on luxury items and sin goods. One key item of contention which drew much discussion on the rate of tax under the new GST regime, with opinions sharply divided across the spectrum, is gold.

I. INTRODUCTION

The GST Rate for all goods and services is decided by the GST Council in India. The GST rate for goods including gold fall under the seven slabs of 0%, 0.25%, 3%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. The GST rate for all goods is linked to HSN code or Harmonized System Nomenclature, a system of classification for goods adopted by over 200 countries internationally. In this article, we look at the GST rate for Gold along with the applicable HSN code.

Gold jewellery will attract 3% goods and services tax (GST). Though it is higher than the current applicable taxes, including 1% excise duty and 1.5% VAT, it is below the anticipated GST of 5%. Customs duty will continue to be 10% and processing charges will be taxed at 5%. Approximate industry average processing charges are around 12% of gold price. Prior to GST, total tax and duties are nearly 12.4%. After the implementation of GST, it will marginally increase to approximately 14%. Larger players such as Titan, owner of brand 'Tanishq', would be the biggest beneficiaries as the

cost gap between the organised and unorganised players will come down.

Advantages of GST:

1. GST is structured to simplify the current indirect system by removing multiple taxes. It creates India as a single market.

2. It taxes goods and services at the same rates so many disputes are eliminated on tax matter.

3. GST will be levied only at the final destination of consumption based on VAT principle and not at various points (from manufacturing to retail outlets). This will help in removing economic distortions and bring about development of a common national market. 4. The procedural cost is reduced due to uniform accounting namely, CGST, SGST, IGST have to be maintained for all types of taxes.

5. The reduced tax burden on companies will reduce production cost making exporters more competitive at national and international level.

6. More business entities including unorganized will come under the tax system thus widening the tax base. This may lead to better and more tax revenue collections.

7. Many businesses create depots and go downs in different states simply because there is a difference in tax rates. Now that GST will come, this difference between states will vanish. It would help to remove the tax difference as a bias, thereby helping businesses.

Disadvantages of GST:

1. There will be dual control on every business by Central and State Government. So compliance cost will go up.

2. All credit will be available on from online connectivity with GST Network. Hence, small businesses may find it difficult to use the system

3. VAT and service tax on some products may become higher than the current levels.

4. States may lose autonomy to change their tax rates.

5. Manufacturing states would lose big revenue

6. Service sector may oppose because they have to register in every state with central and state government. So every business at all India level will have around 60 registrations while they are having just one today. Moreover their rates will also go up.

7. Retail business may oppose because their taxes will go up and they will also have to deal with Central Government now in addition to States.

8. GSTN may not work optimally for quite some time.

GST Rate for Gold

The GST rate for gold, gold jewellery, precious stones and precious metals is 3%. While purchasing gold jewellery or other gold items, the end consumer will have to pay 3% of the taxable value mentioned on the invoice.

Since most gold sold in India is through offline mode, only SGST and CGST would be applicable on the purchase. If a gold purchase is made through an online platform and the supplier is based out of a different state, then IGST would be applicable.

In addition to the GST, gold will attract customs duty of 10% and a gold making charges of 5%. Customs duty of 10% was levied prior to the implementation of GST. However, the GST on gold making charges has been introduced at 5% recently. Hence, the cost of gold and gold jewellery will be marginally higher in the GST era.

Gold Rate after GST

The price of gold following the adoption of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) regime has seen some

fluctuations. Analysts were apprehensive that the tax would lead to a decline in demand for gold due to the high incidence of taxation. The GST for gold was fixed at 3%, with an additional 8% tax levied on making charges. The tax on the making charge was then reduced to 5% due to concerns raised by various groups.

At present, gold prices are seeing a rise due to unstable markets in spite of the additional tax burden. While the overall price of gold has risen, this has been due to the import duty associated with the metal, which has been retained. As a result, gold continues to attract an import duty of 10%, in addition to the 3% GST and 5% making charges GST.

The price of gold after GST has been steadily increasing due to higher demand for the yellow metal in overseas markets. The plunging U.S. dollar has led to higher volumes of trade in the metal, thereby increasing its value.

Long-term outlooks regarding the gold rate in India after GST appear to be mostly positive. Fears of increased smuggling due to the high costs associated with buying the metal abound, but it remains to be seen if these will come to pass. For the moment, the jewellery sector appears to be content with the price of gold after GST, though consumers have a few complaints over the rising cost.

GST on Gold Purchase

The tax slabs were announced on June 3rd, 2017 and gold will be taxed at a rate of 3%. In other words, all gold and gold-related jewellery would be taxed at a flat rate of 3%, which would be borne by the end consumer.

GST on Gold Making

In addition to this, the government has also levied a 5% tax on making charges. At present, there is no tax on making charges, which account for close to 12% of the actual cost of the gold.

The tax on making charges was initially fixed at 18%, but appeals from Indian jewellery councils and bodies to reduce the rate resulted in the government fixing it at the present 5%.

A higher tax on making charges would have increased the burden on consumers, since the added cost would have been passed on to them. The initial rate of 18% would have also resulted in consumers having to pay close to 4% as tax.

Jewellery bodies and councils have lauded the change in rate and are confident that it will result in greater transparency in the gold manufacturing market.

Tax net

A higher tax rate could have prompted people with propensity to evade taxes to keep the transactions completely out of the tax net, as had happened following demonetisation. When Narendra Modi demonetised high value currency notes, people turned to convert their black money to gold overnight. Gold demand in November surged, with the import of the yellow metal doubling to over 100 tonnes in the month. On the other hand, keeping the tax incidence under the new regime close to the current levels could encourage several small and unorganised players to move to an organised

reporting structure, widening the tax net and bringing additional revenue for the government.

II. CONCLUSION

The country's gold market is becoming more organized and transparent, and it is likely that GST will accelerate this process, which will be good for consumer's. Apart from the regular tax slab, the GST council has decided 3 percent GST on gold. It is a positive move towards the jewelry association and their growth as the sector was demanding lower tax rates earlier. This was a positive move towards cooperation as the industry was aching with higher tax burden and the lower tax rates will definitely give a boost towards a friendly approach with customers of this precious yellow metal.

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GST-A BOON OR A BANE FOR INDIA

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Abstract

GST, a biggest reform in the Indian tax structure will be implemented in April 2017. GST will simplify the indirect tax regime in India. It is expected that GST will broaden the tax base and increase the revenue of the Central Government. Indian current tax system has various imperfections like complexity, Cascading effect, Lack of tax compliance etc. GST is expected to remove all these deficiencies in the taxation system. This paper is an effort to shed the light on the positive as well as negative effects of Goods and Services tax bill.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tax is a compulsory payment which has to be made by the people. Income earned by the way of taxes is used by the Government to finance the various activities carried out by it. Tax is a major source of revenue for the Government. So, tax policies play an important role in the growth of economic activities and capital formation of a country. GST stands for Goods and Services Tax.

Present Indian taxation system:

Excise duty	Service tax	VAT
Custom duty	Local body tax(Octroi)	Central sales tax

- Excise duty:-On the Manufacture of Goods in India
- Service tax:-On the services provided in the taxable territory

- VAT-Sale of goods within the state
- Custom duty:-On imports and exports
- Local body tax:-Entry of goods to a State from a place outside the State
- Central sales tax:-On inter-state sale

Presently Indian tax structure has various loopholes like Complex procedures, cascading effects of tax, tax evasion. GST is a biggest reform ever in context to India to remove all these problems. It will impact the tax incidence, tax payment, compliance. The GST structure would follow the destination principle. Accordingly, imports would be subject to GST, while exports would be zero-rated. In the case of inter-state transactions within India, State tax would apply in the state of destination as opposed to that of origin. (1)

GST is simply very similar to VAT. It can be termed as National level VAT on goods and services. It is a domestic trade tax that will be levied in the form of a value added tax on all goods and services - in practice with some exemptions. (2)

In India, GST will be levied at both the levels- centre and state. It is a tax on supply of goods and services. With the implementation of GST, Indian trade scenario will be total changed.

Let us understand GST with an example:-

Present tax system

Product sold from Mumbai to Nagpur, Price=Rs. 1000

VAT @ 10%=Rs. 100

Product sold from Nagpur to Chennai

Cost=Rs. 1100

Profit=Rs. 1000

Selling price=Rs. 2100

CST @ 10%=Rs. 210

Total cost of product=Rs. 2310

GST system

Product sold from Mumbai to Nagpur, Price=Rs. 1000

CGST@ 5%=Rs. 50
SGST @ 5%=Rs. 50

Product sold from Nagpur to Chennai

Cost=Rs. 1100

Profit=Rs. 1000

Selling price=Rs. 2100

IGST @ 10% = 110

=210-CGST-SGST

Total cost of product=Rs. 2210

Exclusions in GST

Following products are excluded from GST –

- Petroleum Products
- Alcoholic Beverages
- Diesel
- Tobacco

Table1.1 GST-Rates Worldwide:

1.	China	17%
2.	Brazil	10%
3.	France	19.6%
4.	Germany	19%
5.	Indonesia	10%
6.	Ireland	23%
7.	Italy	21%
8.	Russia	18%
9.	UK	17.5%
10.	Australia	10%
11.	New Zealand	15%

Why a GST

According to Indian PM Modi, "GST is great step of transformation".

It will eliminate the cascading effect of taxes, where the tax paid at one stage gets added on to the

price of a good on which tax is levied at the next stage. So it will reduce the tax burden on goods and services for the final consumer. It will improve indirect tax collections by broadening the tax base, making evasion less attractive. Above all, it will create a common market in India, since the rate will

be uniform across the country and taxes paid in one state can be offset for transactions done in another.(3)

II. BENEFITS OF GST

Reduction in cost of production

The GST paid on goods and services, whether procured from within or outside the state, would be eligible as ITC against the output GST, hence would not be a cost.(4)

Ease of doing business

With the implementation of GST, Multiple taxes like octroi, central sales tax, state sales tax, entry tax, license fees, turnover tax etc. will no longer be present.

Common national market

GST follows the destination principle. It will be levied only at the final stage of consumption and not at various stages. This will help to develop a common national market.

Reduce the cascading effect of taxes

GST will be levied on the final price of the product. Eliminate tax-on-tax effect. No more Tarikh pe Tarikh pe Tarikh...ooops Tax pe Tax pe Tax pe Tax.(5)

Economic integration of India

According to Arun Jaitley Indian Finance Minister "GST will subsume all central and state level indirect taxes like Excise duty, Service tax, additional custom duty, surcharges and cesses, VAT, Sales tax, CST, Octroi, Purchase tax, Entry tax etc." (6)

More transparency

A single system of taxation rather than multiple taxes will help to increase the transparency. Under GST regime the burden of taxation will be allocated fairly between manufacturing and services via lower tax rates resulting in increased tax base and minimized exemptions. It is anticipated to help in establishing an effective and transparent tax administration.(7)

Increase in the consumption

It is expected that GST will help to decrease the cost of products to the final consumers.

Economic growth

According to experts, by implementing the GST, India will gain \$15 billion a year. This is because it will promote more exports, create more employment opportunities and boost growth. It will divide the burden of tax between manufacturing and services. (8)

One country-one tax

GST offers a new unique and single structure of the indirect tax. All the complexities of the present indirect tax structure will be removed by this.

Growth in GDP

It is assumed that by the application of GST, There will be growth in the production in the economy. The exclusion of cascading effects i.e. tax on tax will significantly improve the competitiveness of original goods and services which leads to beneficial impact to the GDP growth. (9)

Better for manufacturers and exporters

The subsuming of major Central and State taxes in GST, complete set off of input goods and services would reduce the cost of locally manufactured goods and services. This will increase the competitiveness of Indian goods and services in the International market and give boost to Indian exports. (10)

Better for the consumers

It is anticipated that, other things remaining the same, this would encourage manufacturers and distributors to reduce the prices of their produce and ultimately benefit the consumers. (11)

III. LIMITATIONS OF GST

Dual GST model-still complexity

India is going to implement a dual structure of GST, wherein the GST will be levied at both the levels-Centre as well as state, unlike some other countries wherein only center levies GST and then proceeds to divide it among states.

Old wine in a new bottle

- Some Economist says that CGST and SGST are nothing but new names of Central Excise, Service tax, VAT and CST.
- Higher compliance and administrative cost
- It is understood that new implementation of any structure includes high compliance and administrative cost.
- HR problem
- For the effective implementation of India's greatest reform in tax 'GST', Indian Government has to recruit trained staff in various aspects i.e. IT, Finance, Taxation.
- Major revenue items out of scope of the GST
- In India, Tax rates on the tobacco and alcohol products is very high. But these are not included in the GST bill.

Loopholes of GST bill:

Tobacco and alcohol products are kept away from the GST

Tax on the tobacco and alcohol products is a major source of revenue for the Government. But in the recently passed GST bill, these products are not included. It means now various states will charge tax on these goods according to their will. However if tobacco products are included in GST bill, it would be chargeable at 40% app.

Entertainment tax-not included in GST

- It means if you are planning to see a movie in multiplex or PVR, The ticket price would not be reduced.
- Not good for real estate business
- According to various experts, Due to GST the cost of new homes will increase by 8%. In India, Real estate business is already in depression. With this change, the situation will become more worse.
- Need of a strong IT system

- With the GST bill, India would have a unique indirect tax structure and it would be easy to administer it. But it is a big challenge for the Government of India to construct a strong IT system for GST bill. New Goods and Services tax identification number will be provided to all dealers. GST number is a 15 digit number, which would be based on the state code and pan card.

IV. CONCLUSION

There is still uncertainty about the final GST rate or rates. The GST is likely to be at 18 per cent. The GST is worldwide accepted system. GST is framed in India to remove the cascading effects of tax and increase the tax base. It will be beneficial for the country or not that can't be finalized now. According to Some Economists, There is nothing new in the GST and GST will not be able to achieve its objective like decrease in the cost of production, increase in productivity, Economic growth etc.

BENEFITS AND IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

GST also known as the Goods and Services Tax is defined as the giant indirect tax structure designed to support and enhances the economic growth of a country. GST has be detailed discuss in this paper as the background, silent features and the impact of GST in the present tax scenario in India. India is a centralized democratic and therefore the GST will be implemented parallel by the central and state governments as CGST and SGST respectively. The objective will be to maintain a commonality between the basic structure and design of the CGST, SGST and SGST between states .In this article, started with the introduction, in general of GST and have tried to highlight the benefits and objectives the proposed GST is trying to achieve and the impact of GST.

Keywords: *Global Economy, Goods and Services Tax*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a vast concept that simplifies the giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of a country. GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacturing, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. The Goods and Services Tax Bill or GST Bill, also referred to as The Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Second Amendment) Bill, 2014, initiates a Value added Tax

to be implemented on a national level in India. GST will be an indirect tax at all the stages of production to bring about uniformity in the system. Integration of various taxes into a GST system will bring about an effective cross-utilization of credits. The current system taxes production, whereas the GST will aim to tax consumption.

Objectives

GST would be to eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution cost of goods and services. The exclusion of cascading effects i.e. tax on tax will significantly improve the competitiveness of original goods and services which leads to beneficial impact to the GDP growth. It is felt that the GST would serve a superior reason to achieve the objective of streamlining indirect tax regime in India which can remove cascading effects in supply chain till the level of final consumers only when all such above mentioned indirect taxes are completely included in GST. It is understood that alcohol, tobacco and petroleum products will not be enclosed by GST as alcohol and tobacco are considered as Sin Goods, and governments do not like to allow free trade on these property.

Benefits

1. GST provide comprehensive and wider coverage of input credit setoff, you can use service tax credit for the payment of tax on sale of goods etc.

2. It would introduce two-tiered One-Country-One-Tax regime.

3. It would bring down the prices of goods and services and thus by, increase consumption.

4. Uniformity of tax rates across the states.

5. Ensure better compliance due to aggregate tax rate reduces.

6. By reducing the tax burden the competitiveness of Indian products in international market is expected to increase and there by development of the nation. Prices of goods are expected to reduce in the long run as the benefits of less tax burden would be passed on to the consumer.

II. IMPACT OF GOODS SERVICE TAX

I. Food Industry - The application of GST to food items will have a significant impact on those who are living under subsistence level. But at the same time, a complete exemption for food items would drastically shrink the tax base. Food includes grains and cereals, meat, fish and poultry, milk and dairy products, fruits and vegetables, candy and confectionary, snacks, prepared meals for home consumption, restaurant meals and beverages. Even if the food is within the scope of GST, such sales would largely remain exempt due to small business registration threshold. Given the exemption of food from CENVAT and 4% VAT on food item, the GST under a single rate would lead to a doubling of tax burden on food.

2. Housing and Construction Industry - In India, construction and Housing sector need to be included in the GST tax base because construction sector is a significant contributor to the national economy.

3. FMCG Sector - Despite of the economic slowdown, India's Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) has grown consistently during the past three – four years reaching to \$25 billion at retail sales in 2008. Implementation of proposed GST and opening of Foreign Direct Investment (F.D.I.) are expected to

fuel the growth and raise industry's size to \$95 Billion by 201835.

4. Rail Sector - There have been suggestions for including the rail sector under the GST umbrella to bring about significant tax gains and widen the tax net so as to keep overall GST rate low. This will have the added benefit of ensuring that all inter – state transportation of goods can be tracked through the proposed Information technology (IT) network.

5. Financial Services - In most of the countries GST is not charged on the financial services. Example, In New Zealand most of the services covered except financial services as GST. Under the service tax, India has followed the approach of bringing virtually all financial services within the ambit of tax where consideration for them is in the form of an explicit fee. GST also include financial services on the above grounds only.

6. Information Technology - enabled services to be in sync with the best International practices, domestic supply of software should also attract G.S.T. on the basis of mode of transaction. Hence if the software is transferred through electronic form, it should be considered as Intellectual Property and regarded as a service. And if the software is transmitted on media or any other tangible property, then it should be treated as goods and subject to G.S.T. 35 According to a FICCI – Technopak Report. Implementayion of GST will also help in uniform, simplified and single point Taxation and thereby reduced prices.

7. Impact on Small Enterprises - There will be three categories of Small Enterprises in the GST regime. Those below threshold need not register for the GST those between the threshold and composition turnovers will have the option to pay a turnover based tax or opt to join the GST regime.

III. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the above discussion that GST will bring One Nation and One Tax

market. GST is the most logical steps towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country since independence. GST is livable on all supply of goods and provision of services as well combination thereof. All sectors of economy whether the industry, business including Govt. departments and service sector shall have to bear impact of GST. All sections of economy viz., big, medium, small scale units, intermediaries, importers, exporters, traders, professionals and consumers shall be directly affected by GST. One of the biggest taxation reforms in India the Goods and Service Tax (GST) is all set to integrate State economies and boost overall growth. GST will create a single, unified Indian market to make the economy stronger. Experts say that GST is likely to improve tax collections and Boost India's economic development by breaking tax barriers between States and integrating India through a uniform tax rate. Under GST, the taxation burden will be divided equitably between manufacturing and services, through a lower tax rate by increasing the tax base and minimizing exemptions.

IMPACT AND CHALLENGES OF GST IN INDIA

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Abstract

GST goods and service tax create a huge impact on tax system. GST (GOODS AND SERVICE TAX) is most useful for revenue and development of technology. The researcher in his study focuses the areas of influence and the implementation of tax system .it covers all the aspects of tax payments with two major components such as SGST and CGST.The research area of the study is conducted in Coimbatore city. The sample design of the study is convenience sampling. The source of researcher study is based on primary data collection among 50 respondents. The statistical tools used in the study are percentage analysis and Reliability analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

A tax may be defined as a “compulsory extraction made by the central government from the general public. It is a financial charge imposed on individuals or legal entities by the government in pursuant to its legislative authority. A tax is not a voluntary payment or donation, but an enforced contribution, exacted pursuant to legislative authority. The proceeds from taxes constitute a major source of revenue to government that spends the collected amount for common benefits of the society. Over the years, a number of taxes have been imposed by various government covering different aspects such as income, wealth, sales expenditure, service provided, production, import, export, etc.

II. STRUCTURE OF INDIAN TAXATION SYSTEM

India is a socialist, democratic, and republic country. Constitution of India is supreme law of land. All other laws, including the income Tax Act, are subordinate to the constitution of India. The constitution provides that “no tax shall be levied or collected except by authority of law”.

India taxation system is one of the world’s largest taxation systems in terms of its wide application on large number of people and other business entities. It is a well structured system derived from Indian constitution. As we know that India has a federal system of government with clear demarcation of power between the central government and the state government. Like political set up of governance, the tax administration is also based on clear demarcation between the central government and the state government at first instance and then between state government and local bodies.

III. TYPES OF TAXES

Taxes are mainly classified into two types. They are

1. Direct tax
2. Indirect tax

Direct taxes are the taxes which are levied and collected directly from the person, company etc. when the government collects money directly from the ultimate person or from a consumer, who bears it, then it is called as direct tax. Example is income tax.

Indirect taxes are levied and collected from consumers through manufactures, traders or services

providers. Thus, in case, of the government collects tax through a third person (such as manufactures in excise, service providers in service tax, traders in VAT) than the person who bears it ultimately, then it is called as "Indirect tax".

In legal sense, the responsibility to pay an indirect tax rests with the manufacture or seller or service providers finally the tax is collected from the consumer. Indirect taxes are levied on activities such as manufacture, sale, trading of goods and provision of services exchange hands; typically, they are subjected to indirect tax levies and prescribed compliances.

Some of the indirect taxes are:

- Excise duty
- Customs duty
- Value Added tax
- Central sales tax
- Service tax
- Expenditure tax
- Stamps duty
- Securities transaction tax

IV. UNDERSTANDING MULTIPLE TAXATION SYSTEM IN INDIA

India is a federal country and both centers and states have their own rights to collect taxes. Each state is independent in levying and collecting taxes. Center collects all the direct taxes (income tax, corporate taxes etc) along with the Indirect taxes like Service tax, Excise duty and customs duty. The state collects indirect taxes like VAT on goods, CST and Local taxes. These revenues are kept by themselves. Earlier instead of VAT, states had sales taxes on various goods. Now states have replaced sales taxes with VAT. Each state has adopted its own structure of VAT with different duties and structure.

GST is an extended version of Value Added Tax (VAT) and aims to cover all goods and services. VAT covers mostly goods and GST covers all goods and

services. GST is an attempt to get rid of weakness in the VAT structure.

V. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

For a smooth transition, the difficulties related to implementation of GST have to be realistically considered. Some of the key factors that need to be considered are given below:

- Infrastructure for tax administration
- Road map for migration to the new system
- Training of staff of the tax departments of both central and states
- Promoting awareness and understanding of GST among the public and professionals

All stakeholders which would include central government, state governments, tax administration, trade and industry, professionals who act as facilitators and consumers who are tax payers have to be well prepared. Understanding the concerns of the stakeholders will help in better implementation of GST. A hasty implementation of GST without adequate and timely preparation will hamper the progress of the tax structure and could lead the confusion among tax department staff and taxpayers, which would have adverse impact on revenue collection.

VI. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study gives an understanding of some issues of GST from the perspective of various stake holders. An important factor is the process of implementation both in allowing effective prior consultation to identify possible problems and improvements as well as preparing the taxpaying public for change. Incorporating the views of the trade and industry will be helpful for laying a clear roadmap and better implementation of GST. This will help the stakeholders in identifying critical areas to be considered during the transition phase.

VII. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the benefits and challenges of GST
2. To examine the view of stakeholders towards GST
3. To analyze the problems that can hinder the smooth transition to GST
4. To provide suggestions to mitigate risks and overcome constraints

VIII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**Area of Study**

The study was conducted in Coimbatore City.

Sources Of Data

The source of researcher study is based on primary data collection among 50 respondents.

Sampling Design

The sampling design used in the study is convenience sampling

Statistical Tools Used

Percentage Analysis

Reliability Analysis

IX. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is restricted to the Coimbatore city only.

This study does not reveal the accurate output since the number of respondents is limited

So the result may not be very accurate and cannot be generalized.

X. ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION**Percentage Analysis and Personal Factors.**

PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Male	36	72
Female	14	28
TOTAL	50	100
PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Below 30 years	10	20
31-40 years	09	18
41-50 years	14	28
Above 50years	17	34
TOTAL	50	100
PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Auditor	20	40
Industrialist	10	20
Tax consultant	20	40
TOTAL	50	100
PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Less than 5 years	08	16
5-10 years	15	30
10-15 years	16	32
15-20 years	11	22
TOTAL	50	100
PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Media	13	26
Discussion paper or task force paper	17	34
Seminars/workshop/discussion	20	40
TOTAL	50	100
PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Very high	15	30
High	13	26
Neutral	05	10
Low	11	22
Very low	06	12
TOTAL	50	100

Reliability Analysis

It is the most common measure of internal consistency, it is used when the multiple liker questions in a survey that form a scale and it is required to determine if the scale is reliable.

In this survey the multiple liker questions that form a scale is used to determine the necessity, justification and reasons for the implementation of GST and all the questions reliably measure the variables that it is advisable to implement GST.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha Based on standardized items	No. Of items
.824	.826	8

Item Total Statistics

Factors	Scale mean if item deleted	Scale variance if item deleted	Corrected item – total correlation	Squared multiple correlation	Cronbach's alpha if item deleted
Increase in revenue of government	21.0800	21.340	.091	.647	.933
Broaden tax base	21.5400	21.560	.559	.555	.949
GST minimizes tax evasion	21.5400	16.335	.525	.357	.811
Ease of doing business	21.7200	21.789	.574	.631	.838
GST enhances the economic efficiency of the tax system	20.9800	20.918	.563	.711	.700
GST encourage voluntary compliance	20.9800	20.306	.229	.547	.872
Easier compliance for tax payers	20.6600	19.576	.260	.593	.856
Helps in reducing the black money and corruption	20.6600	21.424	.604	.431	.626

From the reliability analysis, it is inferred the reason that measure the reliability to implement the GST appeared to have a good internal consistency and thus GST enhances the below factors.

- Increase in revenue
- Broaden tax base
- GST minimizes the tax evasion
- Ease of doing business
- GST enhances the economic efficiency of the tax system
- GST encourages voluntary compliance
- GST helps in reducing the black money and corruption

Findings

- Majority 72% of the respondents are male
- Most 34% of the respondents are from the age group of above 50 years
- Majority 80% of the respondents are auditors and tax consultants
- Most 32% of the respondents have 10-15 years of experience in their profession
- Most 40% of the respondents' main source was from seminars/workshops/discussion
- Majority 30% of the respondents have very high awareness of GST

Suggestions

- Sufficient time should be provided to the tax department and the industry to prepare for GST

- Organizations should gear up for the transition of information technology (IT) system
- Government should assist to provide soft loans or incentives for small taxpayers who having inadequate infrastructure for the compliance of GST
- The government needs to build its capacity quickly to handle queries from trade and industry

XI. CONCLUSION

GST is also accepted to bring many benefits to the Indian economy. Though, all these benefits are based on the assumption that overall taxation structure is less bureaucratic and cumbersome than present. The implementation is going to be crucial so that the promised benefits are realized. The government also needs to be weary of inflation spurts in initial implementation phase of GST as pointed by experiences from international economies. Ideally, one should be first easing all these state-wide inefficiencies and then implement GST. However given the challenges in India, the policymakers are hoping GST will help ease these inefficiencies and eliminate them over a period of time.

It is an accepted fact that GST is not merely a tax change but a business change as it will impact all functions of an organization such as finance, product pricing, supply chain, information technology, contracts, commercials etc. thus, it's imperative that all these functional teams should be aware about the GST.

IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST) ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

GST also known as the Goods and Services Tax is defined as the giant indirect tax structure designed to support and enhance the economic growth of a country. More than 150 countries have implemented GST so far. However, the idea of GST in India was mooted by Vajpayee government in 2000 and the constitutional amendment for the same was passed by the Lok Sabha on 6th May 2015 but is yet to be ratified by the Rajyasabha. However, there is a huge hue and cry against its implementation. It would be interesting to understand why this proposed GST regime may hamper the growth and development of the country.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a vast concept that simplifies the giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of a country. GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacturing, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level [1]. The Goods and Services Tax Bill or GST Bill, also referred to as The Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Second Amendment) Bill, 2014, initiates a Value added Tax to be implemented on a national level in India. GST will be an indirect tax at all the stages of production to bring about uniformity in the system.

On bringing GST into practice, there would be amalgamation of Central and State taxes into a single tax payment. It would also enhance the position of India in both, domestic as well as international market. At the consumer level, GST would reduce the

overall tax burden, which is currently estimated at 25-30%.

Under this system, the consumer pays the final tax but an efficient input tax credit system ensures that there is no cascading of taxes- tax on tax paid on inputs that go into manufacture of goods [2].

In order to avoid the payment of multiple taxes such as excise duty and service tax at Central level and VAT at the State level, GST would unify these taxes and create a uniform market throughout the country. Integration of various taxes into a GST system will bring about an effective cross-utilization of credits. The current system taxes production, whereas the GST will aim to tax consumption.

Experts have enlisted the benefits of GST as under:

- It would introduce two-tiered One-Country-One-Tax regime.
- It would subsume all indirect taxes at the center and the state level.
- It would not only widen the tax regime by covering goods and services but also make it transparent.
- It would free the manufacturing sector from cascading effect of taxes, thus by improve the cost-competitiveness of goods and services.
- It would bring down the prices of goods and services and thus by, increase consumption.
- It would create business-friendly environment, thus by increase tax-GDP ratio.
- It would enhance the ease of doing business in India.

Why no to GST

However, the question is: is the picture as rosy as it is portrayed?

Wall Street firm Goldman Sachs, in a note 'India: Q and A on GST — Growth Impact Could Be Muted', has put out estimates that show that the Modi Government's model for the Goods and Services Tax (GST) will not raise growth, will push up consumer prices inflation and may not result in increased tax revenue collections [3].

There appears to be certain loopholes in the proposed GST tax regime which may be detrimental in delivering the desired results. They are:

India has adopted dual GST instead of national GST. It has made the entire structure of GST fairly complicated in India. The centre will have to coordinate with 29 states and 7 union territories to implement such tax regime. Such regime is likely to create economic as well as political issues. The states are likely to lose the say in determining rates once GST is implemented. The sharing of revenues between the states and the centre is still a matter of contention with no consensus arrived regarding revenue neutral rate.

Chief Economic Advisor Arvind Subramanian on 4 December 2015 suggested GST rates of 12% for concessional goods, 17-18% for standard goods and 40% for luxury goods which is much higher than the present maximum service tax rate of 14%. Such initiative is likely to push inflation.

The proposed GST structure is likely to succeed only if the country has a strong IT network. It is a well-known fact that India is still in the budding state as far as internet connectivity is concerned. Moreover, the proposed regime seems to ignore the emerging sector e-commerce. E-commerce does not leave signs of the transaction outside the internet and has anonymity associated with it. As a result, it becomes almost impossible to track the business transaction taking place through internet which can be business to business, business to customer or

customer to customer. Again, there appears to be no clarity as to whether a product should be considered a service or a product under the concept of E-commerce. New techniques can be developed to track such transactions but until such technologies become readily accessible, generation of tax revenue from this sector would continue to be uncertain and much below the expectation. Again E-commerce has been insulated against taxation under custom duty moratorium on electronic transmissions by the WTO Bali Ministerial Conference held in 2014 [4].

Communication is considered to be necessity and one cannot do without communication. In modern times, communication has assumed the dimension of telecommunication.

The proposed GST regime appears to be unfavorable for telecommunication sector as well

"One of the major drawbacks of the GST regime could be the direct spike in the service tax rate from 14% to 20-22%" (GST: Impact on the Telecommunications Sector in India). The proposed GST appears to be silent on whether telecommunication can be considered under the category of goods or services. The entire issue of telecommunication sector assumes a serious proportion when India's rural teledensity is not even 50% [5].

The proposed GST regime intends to keep petroleum products, electricity, real estate and liquor for human consumption out of the purview of GST

It is a well-known fact that petroleum products have been a major contributor to inflation in India. Inflation in India depends on how the government intends to include petroleum products under GST in future.

Electricity is essential for the growth and development of India. If electricity is included under standard or luxury goods in future then it would badly affect the development of India. It is said that GST would impact negatively on the real estate market. It

would add up to 8% to the cost of new homes and reduce demand by about 12%.

The proposed GST regime “would be capable of being levied on sale of newspapers and advertisements therein”

This would give the governments the access to substantial incremental revenues since this industry has historically been tax free in its entirety” [6]. It sounds ridiculous but the provision of GST is likely to make the supervision of operations by its Board/senior managers across the company’s offices in different parts of the country a taxable service by allowing each state to raise a GST demand on the company.

Again there appears to be lack of consensus over fixing the revenue rate as well as threshold limit. One thing is for sure, services in India are going to be steeply costly if GST is fixed above the present service tax rate of 14% which in turn will spiral up inflation in India. “Asian countries which implemented GST all had witnessed retail inflation in the year of implementation [6,7].

II. CONCLUSION

The proposed GST regime is a half-hearted attempt to rationalize indirect tax structure. More than 150 countries have implemented GST. The government of India should study the GST regime set up by various countries and also their fallouts before implementing it. At the same time, the government should make an attempt to insulate the vast poor population of India against the likely inflation due to implementation of GST. No doubt, GST will simplify existing indirect tax system and will help to remove inefficiencies created by the existing current heterogeneous taxation system only if there is a clear consensus over issues of threshold limit, revenue rate, and inclusion of petroleum products, electricity, liquor and real estate. Until the consensus is reached, the government should resist from implementing such regime.

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CONTRIBUTION OF SHG'S IN ENTERPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

“One of the most important things I have learned is that businesses don't fail, entrepreneurs give up. Now sometimes, giving up is the right decision. But usually you just need to dig in and figure out how to make things better. Remember: Every day is a new opportunity to get up and do it better than Yesterday”. – Adda Birnir, Founder and instructor, Skillcrush.

Entrepreneurship plays an eminent function in creating an avenue for employability for rural communities, providing self-employment for those who have started-up a Business of their own and enhancing the economic status of the rural sector. Women entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Self-help group is a small voluntary association of poor people preferably from the same socio-economic background. They have been recognized as useful tool to help the poor and as an alternative mechanism to meet the urgent credit needs of poor through thrift. SHGs enhance the equality of status of women as participants, decision-makers and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, social and cultural spheres of life. The paper tries to focus upon the role of self-help groups in promoting women entrepreneurs. The role played by self-help groups beyond access to finance and employability needs to be considered to promote holistic and sustainable entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurship development is an essential part of human resource development. Entrepreneurship

amongst women has been a recent concern. Women have become aware of their existence their rights and their work situation.

Key-words: *Entrepreneurship, Self-Help Groups, Women Entrepreneurs, Role of Women.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Women play a very important role in the economic development of India. They are involved in business activities at all levels, making important contributions to economic growth. Now days, Indian women are increasingly active in part of economy that were previously considered male domain. But the development of women entrepreneurship is very low in India, especially in the rural areas. Entrepreneurship amongst women has been a recent concern. Women have become aware of their existence their rights and their work situation .Now days self-help groups (SHGs) is doing very important role to women motivated in entrepreneurship through micro-finance. SHGs are not only increasing in rural women entrepreneurship but also in urban women entrepreneurship.

India has adopted the Bangladesh's model in a modified form. To alleviate the poverty and to empower the women, the micro-finance has emerged as a powerful instrument in the new economy. With availability of micro-finance, self-help groups (SHGs) and credit management groups have also started in India. And thus the movement of SHG has spread out in India. The members of SHGs now become entrepreneurs. Innovative thinking and farsightedness, quick and effective decision making

skill, ability to mobilize and marshal resource, strong determination and self confidence, preparedness to take risks, accepting changes in right time, access and alertness to latest scientific and technological information these are basic qualities in women therefore they are actively running their own business with help of SHGs. They are actively running business like, food processing and preservation, catering services and fast food centers, interior decoration, DTP and Book binding, dairy, poultry, house-hold appliances, stationeries, packing and packaging, diagnostic lab and pathology clinics, communication centers with telecom, fax, browsing and Xeroxing facilities, readymade garments, embroidering and fashion designing, retail selling, art and painting works, hiring of warehouses and godowns, floral decorations, jewellery, beauty parlors. Though women entrepreneurship is a recent phenomenon in India which came into prominence in late 1970's now we see that more and more women are venturing as entrepreneurs in all kinds of business and economic activities and service sector. Though at the initial stage women entrepreneurship developed only at urban areas, lately it has extended its wings to rural areas.

Entrepreneur:

It is a process where one person getting himself self employed provides job to others also. The person is called "entrepreneur".

Women Entrepreneurship:

Women entrepreneurship is the process where women take lead and organize business or industry and provide employment opportunities to others. Women entrepreneurship is the process where women organize a business or industry and provide employment opportunities to others. Women entrepreneurs can be engaged in both unorganized and organized sectors.

Entrepreneurship Development:

Entrepreneurship development means all those activities that aim at stimulating the individuals for becoming entrepreneurs.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has following objectives:

1. To study the Women Entrepreneurship Development.
2. To know the role played by SHGs in Women Entrepreneurship Development.
3. To analyze income, expenditure and profit of women entrepreneurs.
4. To find the drawbacks and to instruct remedy for Women Entrepreneurship Development.
5. To find the answer for women backwardness.
6. To suggest appropriate suggestion for women entrepreneurship.

Characteristics of an ideal SHG:

According to MARADA [2000] well functioning SHG should have following structural features:-

1. An ideal SHG comprises 15-20 members.
 2. All the members should belong to the same socio-economic status of society.
 3. Rotational leadership should be encouraged for the distribution of power and to provide leadership opportunities to all the members.
 4. Member should regularly attend meetings, save money and participate in all activities
- Voluntarily.**
5. The procedure of decision-making in SHG should be democratic in nature.
 6. The group frames rules and regulations, which are required in its effective functioning.
 7. Transparency in account keeping and accounts should be maintained and updated regularly.
 8. An SHG should be socially viable institution.

Problems and Constraints:

Women entrepreneurs are facing so many problems at every stage in all over the country. The major ones are:

a) Social barriers:

In our male dominating society women entrepreneurs are always seen with suspicious eyes, situation in rural areas is too worse.

b) Caste and Religions:

Though India is a secular country, so many castes and religions dominate with one another and it restricts women entrepreneurship.

c) Lack of self-confidence and risk bearing capacity:

Women have lack of self-confidence and always feel that they may not be successful and hence hesitate to take risk. Their risk bearing capacity is always less than man.

d) Psychological factors:

Mostly women feel that she is 'women' and less effective than man. Secondly, Family and homemaking enhance her moral duty if she is engaged in work than how can she manage both or play dual role? She has to strive hard to balance her family life with care and hence feels better to be housewife.

e) Lack of family support:

Due to some taboos and restriction, which are still prevalent in our society woman is not getting enough support by her husband and family members to undertake any entrepreneurship.

Remedial measures and suggestions:

To solve the problems facing by women entrepreneurs, some remedial measures undertaken and suggestions are given below:

Governmental efforts:

Government agencies, associations of women entrepreneurs and NGO's have carried on so many programs for development of women

entrepreneurship. India has been the pioneer in initiating Entrepreneurship Development Programs, to identify, select, motivate, train and guide first generation entrepreneurs from all spheres of life. Now a day, Programs for entrepreneurship development are being introduced in school and colleges to provide the impetus for youth seeking self-employment opportunities.

Stress on women education:

Government has increased number of opportunities for women education and special programs have been introduced. Yet it is necessary to increase the number of professional school for women.

Financial Assistance:

Banks, financial institutions are lending more freely to women entrepreneurs today. Yet, Government has to lend more subsidies to women entrepreneurs.

Enhance practical and Technical Knowledge:

As it is necessary to provide practical and technical knowledge of the business, during their study levels, some schools and colleges are providing such knowledge during the education period. It should be increased and informal education on small-scale entrepreneurship development should also be given.

Market Facilities:

As women entrepreneurs have to face severe marketing problems, they should be taken into consideration by the Govt. and steps should be taken to solve them. Markets should be developed in rural and semi urban areas so that women entrepreneur can sell them easily in the nearest markets more and more fairs and exhibitions should be arranged for women products.

Infrastructural Development:

The development of transport and communication throughout the country will help for women entrepreneurs to market their products easily.

Self Employment Training Programs:

As self employment breeds entrepreneurship, more and more self employment programs should be undertaken and proper training should be given to rural and urban youths including women.

Transfer Of Technology And Information:

As women entrepreneurs have lack of information as regards to their enterprise, it is necessary to start information bureaus, to help them in getting the required information.

Research And Survey Programs:

Emphasis should be given to conduct research and survey, to identify the problems and needs of women entrepreneurs. Then steps should be taken to solve the problems of women entrepreneurs.

Yet, the Government at center and states has organized specific programs for promoting women entrepreneurship and getting their talent useful to the society. But still, rural women are not getting benefits, due to ignorance and marketing problems. Hence there is an urgent need to popularize these programs and proper marketing strategy should be planned and implemented, which will provide scope for women entrepreneurs.

Industries Promoted By Women Entrepreneurs:

- Agar Bathi Making
- Pappad Making
- Embroidery
- Handicrafts
- Catering services
- Small Retail Shops
- Beauty Parlors
- Pickle Manufacturing

Organizations Promoting Women Entrepreneurship In India:

- National Resource Centre for Women
- Women's India Trust
- Women Development Corporation
- Association of Women Entrepreneurs in India

- Working Women's Forum
- Self-Employed Women's Association.

III. CONCLUSION

SHGs have been successful in empowering rural women through entrepreneurial activities. Increase in income, expenditure and saving habits of rural women were observed. The SHGs had major impact on social and economic life of rural women. The study revealed an increase in social recognition of self, status of family in the society, size of social circle and involvement in intra family and entrepreneurial decision making. There was an increase in self confidence, self reliance and independence of rural women due to the involvement in the entrepreneurial and other activities of SHGs. SHGs could be linked to literacy programmes run by government and it could be made an integral part of SHG activities.

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A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PRESENT INDIRECT TAX SYSTEM AND GST IN INDIA

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Abstract

Tax is major source of revenue to government in India. Since from past two decades India tax system had a major reform in indirect tax. Goods and service tax is one of the biggest reform in India. The present scheme of indirect taxation has various short coming like the way it taxes input and output, bringing service under tax net which is not possible under VAT system. So in order to overcome the shortcoming of present taxation system, Goods and service tax in India is introduced. It Focus to improve the existing VAT system and tax system of India. Goods and service tax is value added tax to be implemented in India. It aim is to overcome the shortcoming of present tax system is to eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution cost of goods and service. In this article, we have given introduction of tax and specifically focus on various type of indirect tax and also various shortcoming of present indirect tax system. Brief overview about goods and service tax (GST) and how it will overcome the present tax shortcoming, the tax that

subsumed under GST. We have compared GST with present taxation system.

Keywords: *Goods and Service tax (GST), Value added tax (VAT).*

I. INTRODUCTION

History of GST

The present indirect tax system (VAT) in our country was introduced in the year 2005 and 2006 in almost all the states. India has a well-developed tax structure with clear demonstration of authority between central and state governments and local bodies I.e. central government levy taxes on incomes except tax on agricultural income, which the state government can levy, customs duties, central exercise and services tax. State government levy's taxes such as value- added tax (vat), stamp duty, state exercise, land revenue and professional taxes. Where local bodies are empowered to levy tax on properties, octroi and for utilities like water supply, drainages etc. due to the burden caused from the present tax system (tax on tax), the concept of GST was introduced.

The reference to Goods and services tax in India was made in the year 2006 in the union budget by our former finance minister Mr. P Chidambaram. Which was to be actually implemented from 1st April 2010. But due to some reasons in the upper house, it was postponed from year to year. It is believed that GST will be implemented from the year 2016.

The term GST is known as goods and service tax bill or GST bill, officially known as the constitution (one hundred and twenty- second amendment) bill, 2014.

GST is a comprehensive indirect tax on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and service throughout India. This system is more feasible than the present tax system as it indicates setoff of tax rather than tax on tax system. It replaces the taxes lived by the central and state government and provides for uniform tax structure throughout the country.

The GST at the central and at the state level will give more relief to industry, trade, agriculture and consumers through a more comprehensive and wider coverage of input tax set-off and service tax set-off.

A fee or a charge levied by a government on a product, income or any activity that generates revenue. Tax can be further classified as direct tax and indirect tax.

Direct tax

It is the tax levied directly on personal or corporate income this tax cannot be passed or shared on to other parties.

Types of direct tax are:

1. Income tax
2. Transfer tax
3. Entitlement tax
4. Property tax
5. Capital gain tax

Indirect Tax

Tax levied on the price of a good or service is called indirect tax these taxes are played on almost daily basic products and services.

How does indirect tax works:

Most consumable products are featured by indirect tax that is collected by the merchants and then paid to the government, and hence it is a indirect route of collecting tax. When it comes to consumers, they don't think about the extra money they pay when purchasing goods and unaware that the money represents an indirect form of taxation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Girish garg, (2014) studied "The concept and features of goods and services tax in India", and found that GST is the compressive indirect tax reform in our country since independence. GST will create a single ,unified Indian market to make the economy stronger under the goods and services tax scheme, the taxation burden will be divided equally between manufacturing and services through a lower tax rate by increasing the tax base and minimizing exemptions.

Syed mohd ali taqvi, (2013) studied "challenges and oppurnities of goods and services in India "found that GST would eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution of cost of goods and services where it would eliminate the concept of tax on tax and brings a new concept of tax system of setting off of tax which would in turn enhance GDP of the economy and reduce the transaction cost and unnecessary wastage, in turn reduce the corruption.

III. OBJECTIVES

1. The study the present scheme of indirect taxation and its shortcoming
2. To highlight the provision of new Act GST
3. To do a comparative analysis of present tax system and GST

Methodology

Over research work is done on base of secondary data collection for the study include the present VAT system provision of GST.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of present tax system

In the present taxation scheme of India, taxes are levied by the central and state government. The local authority such as municipality takes care of minor ax. The computation, levy and collection of tax are done by the department of revenue of finance minister Short coming of present tax system in India

Presently India follows a dual tax system for taxation of goods and services. This tax system is described by central taxes and state taxes, which is further described as exercise duty, service tax, vat and customs duty. India follows a vat mechanism which was introduced in the year 2005 which is working on input tax credit principle but this is limited to intra state transaction. However this problem is not for service sector, as service sector, as the service tax is levied by central government.

- The first main drawback of the indirect tax system is the burden on economically backward people. Indirect tax is generally imposed on consumption of goods. They are unfair in the sense that poor people have to pay as much as rich people.

- The imposition of indirect tax on a commodity increase price though the cost of production is less. It has regressive in nature.

- The administrative cost involved in collecting the tax is heavy as they have to be collected from large number of persons.

It causes uncertainty – the revenue from indirect tax cannot be estimated accurately. An indirect tax leads to rise in the price of the commodity. Which in turn result in fall of demand and thus it is difficult to know the extent to which the demand of the commodity has fallen.

- It has cascading effect that is there are different tax levies on supply chain till it reach the customer.

Overview of GST

The GST is an indirect comprehensive tax levied on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. The main objective is the coverage of all indirect taxes in to a single tax replacing multiple taxes levied, overcoming limitations of current indirect taxstructure and creating efficiency in tax administration. France was the first country to introduce this system in the year 1954. However, out of 196 countries, 140 countries follow the system of GST.

GST is collected on value added goods and services at each stage of purchase or sale in the supply chain i.e. GST is paid on the procurement of goods and service can be set off against that payable on the supply of goods or services. But the consumer being the last person in the supply chain has to bear this tax and hence it is like a last point retail tax. It is a setoff benefit. Many countries have a unified GST system. However countries like Brazil and Canada follow a dual system where GST is levied by both federal and state or provincial government.

In India a dual GST is being proposed where in a central goods and services tax (CGST) and a state goods and services tax (SGST) will be levied on the taxable value of transaction.

Three prime model of GST

Central GST State GST Dual GST

- GST to be levied by center
- GST to be levied by state
- GST to be levied by center and state concurrently

How will GST overcome present tax shortcoming-

1. End of cascading effect- If GST is implemented in India, I will overcome the shortcoming of present taxation scheme which is

cascading effect. It will bring to an end of the cascading effects. This will contribute an immense benefit to the business and commerce.

2. Eliminate the multiplicity of taxation -

Industry, trade and agriculture-GST rate of 20 percent is suggested by a parliamentary committee, which in turn would benefit the industry and will also not impact on the consumers. The raja Sabha select committee has suggested that the goods and services tax rate should not exceed beyond 20 percent as higher rates could increase inflation and erode the confidence of consumers in a new indirect tax regime which is to be implemented from 16 April 2016.

So GST will give more relief to industries, trade and agriculture through a more comprehensive and wider coverage of input tax set off by subsuming of several central and state taxes in the GST.

3. Exporters-the subsuming of major central and state taxes in GST would provide a comprehensive set off of input goods and services and phasing out of central sales tax (cst) would reduce the cost of locally manufactured goods and services. This will increase the competitiveness of Indian goods and services in the international market and give boost to Indian exports

4. Common consumers- in GST taxes for both center and state will be collected at the point of sale. So the customer will be benefit as price will be come down the customer will be paying less to its consumption and it will reduce the average tax burdens on the consumers.

5. Single tax –Due to GST, the manufacturer and trader will be benefit such as one tax as all the tax will subsume and will not need to pay all the tax, common exemption between center and state. This will give a more opportunity and time for manufacturer to pay more focus on business rather than worrying about other taxation.

6. Uniformity of tax rate across the states

How does GST works?

GST is a continuous chain of setoff benefit from producer's point and services provider's point up to the retailer's level. It is basically a value addition at each stage and a supplier at each stage is permitted to set off through a tax credit mechanism, the GST paid on purchase of goods and services is available for setoff on the GST to be paid on the supply of goods and services. The final consumers will thus bear only the GST charged by the last dealer in the supply chain with set off benefit at all precious stages.

GST is proposed to merge service tax, vat and customs exercise into one tax i.e. GST. Since the current taxation frame work allows limited inter-levy credits between central exercise duty and service tax. However no cross credits are available in respect of other taxes specifically vat, central service tax, entry tax. Introduction of GST would allow the

Taxes that may or may not be subsumed

There are few other indirect taxes that may or may not be subsumed under the GST regime as there is no consensus among States and Centre & States –

- Purchase tax
- Stamp Duty
- Vehicle Tax
- Electricity Duty
- Other Entry taxes and Octroi
- What will be out of GST?
- Levies on petroleum products
- Levies on alcoholic products
- Taxes on lottery and betting
- Basic customs duty and safeguard duties on import of goods into India
- Entry taxes levied by municipalities or panchayats
- Entertainment and Luxury taxes
- Electricity duties/ taxes
- Stamp duties on immovable properties
- Taxes on vehicles

Comparative analysis of present tax system and GST.

1. The present structure of indirect tax structure is very complex in India. As it is demonstrated by both the authorities central and state. There are so any types of tax levied by central and state government on goods and services.

Example-

Entertainment tax is paid for watching a movie or any other entertainment

Value added tax (VAT) on purchase or production of goods.

Other taxes like excise duties, import duties, luxury tax, central sales tax, service tax and so.

There are certain taxes were both the central and state government take an active part in determining the tax rates.

2. Goods and services subject to tax: As we know the present tax system does not have much impact on the service firms i.e. the rate is less when compared to the goods tax or any other form of tax).

New act, "GST" as the word indicates goods and service act operates on a negative concept – all goods and services are subject to GST b unless specifically exempted.

3. The entire Indian market will be unified market with the implementation of GST. A specific standard rate will be implemented and followed throughout India.

4. It is more transparency and better compliance: The present indirect tax system does not provide transparency and compliance as consumers are not aware of the percentage of tax which the local, state and central government collects. By the implementation of GST a common tax rate is implemented and also provides a clear view of tax rate.

5. Corruption: Number of departments will reduce which in turn may lead to less corruption.

V. CONCLUSION

Introduction of GST in India needs to be well-planned and requires a sufficient long period to

familiarize the public with its working. GST needs advance preparation though it is to be implemented in 2016." GST is needed not only to raise more revenue for the government, but also to diversify its source of income". GST was introduced to replace and rectify the shortcoming of current taxation scheme. As GST facilitates set off of tax rather than tax on tax, which would benefit the economy at large.

THE IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST) ON END CONSUMERS OF MANUFACTURING

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Abstract

Around 140 countries in the world have adopted GST model of Taxation. The idea for introducing GST in the country is found in the budget speech of the union finance minister in the year 2005-06. Over the subsequent budget speeches, the path way for introducing GST was spelt out in more detail. The proposal involved restructuring of indirect taxes levied by both the Centre and the State. This responsibility was entrusted with the empowered committee of the State Finance Ministers. The principle idea behind the concept of GST is to eliminate various forms of indirect taxes that are levied and collected at different points of consumptions and to overcome the shortcomings of the existing indirect tax system. This will benefit all stake holders like central and state government and the ultimate consumer by mitigating the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution cost of goods and services. This paper presents the background, salient features and impact of GST on the end consumers of manufacturing goods.

I. INTRODUCTION

GST will be one of the biggest tax reforms that will replace all indirect taxes (like Central Excise Duty, Additional Exercise duty, Service Tax, Customs duty, State VAT etc.) levied on goods and services by the government both center and state once it is implemented. It is an indirect consolidated tax, based on a uniform tax rate fixed for both goods and services (namely automobile, food products, telecom, insurance etc.) payable at the final point of consumption through a tax credit mechanism. GST subsumes a series of all indirect taxes under a single domain. The recommended GST bill gives concurrent powers to both states and the center to make laws on the taxation of goods as well as services.

Consumer of manufacturing goods mean any form of an article or a component that is manufactured or distributed for sale to a consumer for his/her ultimate consumption. Implementation of GST bill will eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production or distribution which will reduce the prices of goods and services and this will benefit the end users.

Implementation of GST bill will mark an important milestone in the field of Indirect Tax Reforms in India. It's likely to benefit all stake holders like The Governments, The Trade and Industry and the consumers at large. It will harmonize the taxing of consumption of goods and services uniformly throughout the country and will pave way for creation of common market across India.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. R. Vasanthagopal, (2011) Studied and found a balance in conflicting interests of various stakeholders with the implication of the constitutional amendment.

Girish Garg, (2014) Studied and found that GST is the most analytical step towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country.

'The constitution (122nd Amendment) Bill, 2014 (GST) shared the idea behind GST is to subsume all existing indirect taxes under one value added tax which will be levied on goods and services. This shall intend to harmonize the tax system across the country. It seeks to address the challenges of the current indirect tax systems by broadening the tax base eliminating cascading effect and increase compliance by benefiting the manufacturers and the consumers.

A seminar on 'Implication on Constitutional Amendment of GST on Trade and Industry' states that "Introduction of GST marks an important milestone in the indirect tax reforms in India. It is likely to benefit all the stake holders namely the governments, the trade and industry and the common man at large. It will pave way for creation of a common market across India and harmonize the taxing of consumption of goods and services uniformly both at central and state level".

It further states that India should reformulate the GST bill with great insight. The ultimate objective is to achieve a low tax rate structure along with few rational exemptions. An effective and transparent

administrative system should be set up with world class computer system at central, state and inter-state levels that will create and awareness to modern tax payers (consumers).

III. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The fundamental idea behind the concept of GST is to eliminate various forms of indirect taxes that are levied and collected at different points of consumptions and to overcome the shortcomings of the existing indirect tax system. This study analyses how GST bill would impact the manufacturing sector of our country and benefit the end consumers.

IV. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the concept of GST and its policies.
2. To analyze the impact of GST on end consumers of manufacturing goods.

Scope of Study

The present study is made to understand GST and its impact on manufacturing sector and end users. Its main focus is to understand whether GST will burden the end users (i.e. Common man) or will it be beneficial. A critical analysis is made on the impact of GST on price of goods.

V. METHODOLOGY

This research is an exploratory research.

Methods and Materials

Primary data for the study includes views on the present tax system and the impact of implementation of GST by an expert from service tax department through means of personal interview.

Secondary data for the study includes provisions discussed about GST under various Article, Journals, Newspaper, and Service tax book

VI. ANALYSIS

Key Features of the proposed GST Bill

The proposed GST Bill which seeks to amend the constitution provides for subsuming of various indirect taxes levied at state and central level under a single tax regime. This is expected to broaden the tax

base, reduce economic distortion, increase tax compliance and reduce cascading effect. GST will be levied on supply of goods and services on the consumer tax base with full input tax credit mechanism. It is also expected to create a common market across the country by improving the efficiency in factors of production and distribution in respect of all intra and inter- state transactions.

The ideal GST structure will not differentiate between goods and service and are subjected to one tax at the point of final consumption. Goods include all materials, commodities and articles-Article 366(12).Services means anything other than goods proposed-Article 366(26A). But it excludes the following:

1. Exempted goods and services which include alcohol, electricity and real estate.

Petroleum products are to be brought under GST from a later date.

2. Goods and services outside the purview of GST.

3 .Transaction below threshold limit.

Another important feature of GST Bill is that it will have two concurrent components as mentioned below-

1. Central Goods and Service Tax levied and collected by Centre(CGST)

2. State Goods and Service Tax levied and collected by state(SGST)

And an integrated Goods and Service Tax called IGST would be levied by the Centre on all inter-state transactions involving supply of goods and services. Cross utilization of input tax credit between the Central GST and State GST would in general not be allowed except in case of inter-state transactions subject to certain conditions.

To the extent feasible, uniform procedure for collection of both Central GST and State GST would be prescribed in the respective legislations for Central GST and State GST. Additional tax not exceeding 1%

on inter-state supply of goods is to be levied by the Centre for 2 years or longer as recommended by GST Council. The Tax collected will be accrued directly to the state from where the supply of the goods originate. Compensation for the loss of revenue to the state for a period of 5 years will be given.

Perceived Benefits of GST Bill to the Government

An ideal GST regime intends to create a harmonize system of taxation by subsuming all indirect Taxes which simplifies the tax system. GST bill also seeks to address the challenges with the current indirect tax system by broadening the tax base and reducing the number of exemptions. It improves compliance of the tax payer and boost revenue collection in long run for both State and Centre. It will also pave way for creation of a common market across India which will lead to the efficient use of resources.

GST at State level will be a major improvement in the Tax base for future revenue generation. Currently the major revenue contributing goods like alcohol for human consumption, electricity and real estate are outside the purview of GST. Thus the GST bill will be more progressive. Moreover the center has promised to levy an additional tax of 1 % on all interstate transactions for a period of about 2 years for the states.

Perceived benefits of the GST Bill to the consumer of Manufacturing Goods

Introduction of GST is expected to simplify our present Tax system in which only a single uniform Tax will be levied on both goods and services at state and central level. This tax will amalgamate several other indirect taxes like Customs Duty, Service Tax levied by Centre, Sales Tax and VAT levied by respective states into a single tax. This will actually reduce the cascading effect of Tax on production and distribution of goods and services which in turn will lead to decline in the prices of goods and services.

The proposed Goods and Services Tax (GST) would reduce manufacturing cost and benefit end-consumers. The elimination of multiple tax structure at Central and State levels would make the manufacturing sector viable and globally competitive. A slight percentage reduction in the production cost will increase the profit by a comparative higher percentage which will create way for reduction in the price of goods and benefiting the end consumers.

Roughly more than half of trucks transit time is wasted due to material scrutiny and local based tax compliances which negatively impact the overall production and logistics time. These unproductive transit hours along with regulatory impediments cause in efficiency in the working of Indian manufacturers.

To overcome the above problem, an integrated GST (IGST) will be levied by the Centre for all inter-state transactions involving supply of goods and services. Thus abolition of CST and Entry Tax would reduce the cost of production of goods and services and also it is considered as a great boon to the consumers because the movement of goods between inter-states is faster and the consumers can obtain the goods at a reduced cost.

It is observed that inter-state sale of goods and services may avail input tax credit which will lead to removal of extra level warehousing in the supply chain, thereby leading to greater cost benefits which will be passed on to the consumers.

Table No -1: Comparison of Tax under the Current Indirect Tax System and the GST regimee.

Transaction	Current System	GST
Cost of Raw Materials	100	100
Tax on Raw Material @ 10%	10	10
Value added by Manufacturer	20	20
Tax payable by Manufacturer	2 (CENVAT : 10% of 20)	2 (GST : 10% of 20)
Retailers Cost	132	132
Value added by Retailer	20	20
Tax Payable	15.2 (Sales tax : 10 % of 152)	2 (GST : 10% of 20)
Final price paid including Taxe	167.2	154
Of which taxes	27.2	14

In the above example the cost of raw materials is 100. Manufacturer and retailer add Rs 20 value each. The tax rate is assumed to be 10 % for all Taxes.

Under the current tax system both Excise and Sales Tax are VAT system, but the set off facility is not available for all the taxes. Thereby sales tax is applicable to the excise duty (CENVAT) paid. Thus tax paid is 12(Excise) plus 15.2 (Sales Tax).note the 'tax on tax' effect where the final selling price not only has two taxes, but also 'tax on tax'.

Under the GST system, there will be only one single uniform Tax with input credit mechanism. This means each individual pays tax only on the extent of value added by him and thereby the total tax is less

resulting in lower price of goods benefiting the end consumer.

A clear comparison is made between the present system and the GST system of tax calculation. The cascading effect is eliminated in the GST system which reduces the final price of the product by Rupees 13.2 /unit. And the benefit of this is enjoyed by the consumer.

We could see a major dip in cost, if the taxes paid are refunded on inputs made by producers, distributors and other relevant service providers. Thus consumers will stand by it in order to gain the cost benefit translated by the producers into lower prices. This will also lead to efficiency of supply chain

structure because it ensures that even if one link in the supply chain will insist on an invoice, the entire chain will have to come under the Tax net. Therefore setting up provisions of GST has far reaching implications for manufacturers and distributors.

It is also estimated that a reduction in cost of goods will lead to an increase in companies' profits, thus attracting investors. The Centre and state will be in favor for this. The broadening of tax base along with greater compliance would boost the revenue collections because the tax rate itself is unlikely to increase the revenue.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The existing tax system in India provides for levy and collection of multi-layered taxes both at Centre and State level in accordance with the taxing powers. GST is the simple tax regime in which only a single tax shall be levied covering both goods and services at both State and the Central level. This tax will replace a number of existing taxes and mitigate the cascading effect which will reduce the cost of production and distribution.

Also in the present tax regime the manufacturers and distributors file returns for different taxes on different dates but under the GST regime they will have to file the returns only bi-annually or quarterly basis fixed by the government.

Under GST, the tax is effectively paid not on the value of the output, but on the value added to the output at that particular stage. Since set-offs are only available once tax is paid, incentives for compliance increase as each person in the chain ensures that the previous person has paid the tax. This will reduce tax evasion.

Central government has ensured that few items like alcohol, electricity etc. are exempted from the purview of GST because they are the major revenue generating items for the state. And an additional tax of 1% to be levied for all inter-state transactions which would compensate the loss likely to be

incurred by the state for a period of about 2 years. Though initially the States may lose out on its revenue, in the long run both the State and Centre will be boosted up with its revenue.

VIII. COMMENTS

Implementation of GST bill will have a positive impact on manufacturers and distributors because the cascading effect is reduced and supply chain cost comes down. This will not only reduce the final price on the goods but also increase the competitiveness of the industry along with profits and create a common market. And we observe that GST bill will not only reduce the paper work but also increase compliance of manufacturers and distributors.

There is a 'tax on tax' effect on the final selling price in the present indirect tax system but in the GST regime there will be a single tax levied with input tax mechanism. This means that each person pays tax only on the value added by him. Consequently the prices of the goods reduce because the total tax paid is less. Ultimately implementation of GST bill will benefit both the manufacturing sector as well as the end consumers.

IX. CONCLUSION

Introduction of a uniform tax rate for both goods and services will lead to a harmonize system in terms of process and procedures between CGST/IGST/SGST law. It will lead to reduction in multiplicity of taxes along with mitigation of cascading/double taxation and help in development of common national market. Under GST there is no differentiation between a good or service whether as an input or as a finished product. The tax paid on inputs is deducted from the tax payable on the output produced. Thus input credit set off operates through the manufacturing and distribution stage of production. The tax is collected only at the place of consumption that is the end users. This addresses the cascading effect of "tax on tax".

IMPACT OF GST ON VARIOUS SECTORS AND CHALLENGES FOR GST IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract

GST in India is expected to be a destination based consumption based levy. GST stands for “Goods and Services Tax”, and is proposed to be a comprehensive indirect tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods as well as services at the national level. It is a taxation system where there is a single tax in the economy for goods and services. Its main objective is to consolidate all indirect tax levies into a single tax, except customs (excluding SAD) replacing multiple tax levies, overcoming the limitations of existing indirect tax structure, and creating efficiencies in tax administration. It would also bring raise in employment, promotion of exports and consequently a significant boost in overall economic growth and factors of production-land labour and capital. GST would ensure equitable burden between the manufacturing and services. GST would also solve several issues like inflation and fiscal deficit. More important, from the businessman and consumer perspective, this change is going to have substantial impact on the business as well cost to consumers depending upon the structure of the business and location of business and consumer. Therefore it becomes essential to restructure the business and location depending upon the assessment of implication of GST on each type of transactions. The impact analysis and planning for restructuring can be done only after the draft law is released.

Introduction of GST should thus rationalize tax content in product price, enhance the ability of companies to compete globally, and possibly trickle down to benefit the ultimate consumer. Since the dual GST is considerably different from the present indirect tax regime, a massive training initiative would be required at both federal and State levels to familiarize the respective administrations with the concepts and procedures of the dual GST.

I. INTRODUCTION

GST in India is expected to be a destination based consumption based levy. GST stands for “Goods and Services Tax”, and is proposed to be a comprehensive indirect tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods as well as services at the national level. It is a taxation system where there is a single tax in the economy for goods and services. The GST is a consolidated tax based on a uniform rate of tax fixed for both goods and services and it is payable at the final point of consumption. Its main objective is to consolidate all indirect tax levies into a single tax, except customs (excluding SAD) replacing multiple tax levies, overcoming the limitations of existing indirect tax structure, and creating efficiencies in tax administration. The single tax would be shared between the Centre and State. (Dual Levy). It would also bring raise in employment, promotion of exports and consequently a significant boost in overall economic growth and factors of production-land

labour and capital. GST would ensure equitable burden between the manufacturing and services GST would also solve several issues like inflation and fiscal deficit.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kanojia.N(2014) made an attempt to study on Goods and Services Tax in India. This paper result shows that reasons for moving GST i.e., current system of indirect taxes is not able to increase the competitiveness of industry, exports and company. This paper also emphasized that how a goods and service tax is an improvement over VAT and Service Tax.

Syed Mohd. Ali Taqvi(2013), in his article on "Challenges and Opportunities of GST in India" stated that GST is the only indirect tax that directly affects all sectors and sections of our economy. The goods and services tax (GST) is aimed at creating a single, unified market that will benefit both corporate and the economy. Goods and service tax is a new story of VAT which gives a widespread setoff for input tax credit and subsuming many indirect taxes from state and national level. The GST Implementation is not yet declared by government and the drafting of GST law is still under process and a clear picture will be available only after announcement of implementation. The objective will be to maintain a commonality between the basic structure and design of the CGST, SGST and IGST between states. In this article he also discussed the possible challenges and threats; and then, opportunities that GST brings before strengthening our free market economy.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The real problems with the introduction of GST in India have not been addressed. The unorganized sector in India employs 93 percent of the workforce. The Small and tiny units producing and selling locally would lose from a unified market which will benefit large scale products. This will aggravate

under employment, distress in the farm sector and adversely impact the poorer states. No wonder, GST is being strongly backed by large businesses. Hence, in order to know the impact of GST on various sectors like Consumers, Traders, Manufacturers, Service providers, and government and also to identify the various challenges faced by way of implementation of GST, the present study has been undertaken.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To know the benefits of introduction of Goods and Service Tax
2. To study the impact of GST on various Sectors
3. To identify the challenges/hurdles to be overcome by way of implementation of Goods and Services Tax

V. METHODOLOGY

The present study aims to find out the impact of GST on various sectors and challenges to be faced by way of implementing GST. The necessary data were collected from opinions given by financial experts that were stated in the various finance related websites.

VI. DATA COLLECTION

Secondary data have been used for analyzing and interpreting the results.

Limitation of the Study

The results of the study provided based on the views of the financial experts. It will be varied in future.

Advantages of GST

It has the following advantages:

1. GST is a transparent tax and also reduces numbers of indirect taxes.
2. GST can also help to diversification of income sources for government other than income tax and petroleum tax.
3. Biggest benefit will be that multiple taxes like octroi, central sales tax, state sales tax, entry tax,

license fees, turnover tax etc will no longer be Present and all that will be brought under the GST. Doing business now will be easier and more comfortable as various hidden taxation will not be present.

5. The tax collection would become more balanced as most hitherto "tax evaders" would be forced to enter the mainstream. Tax Collection by both the Centre & the States on the whole would increase over period of 2 years

6. Benefit people as prices will come down which in turn will help companies as consumption will increase.

7. It would promote exports

8. Raise employment and boost growth.

9. Under Goods and Services Tax, the tax burden will be divided equally between Manufacturing and Services.

All goods or services likely to be covered under GST except

- i) Alcohol
- ii) Electricity
- iii) Real Estate
- iv) Petroleum Products
- v) Tobacco products.

VII. IMPACT OF GST ON VARIOUS SECTORS

Consumers: Generally the purchase price would reduce as tax content of most products would come down. However if a product has evaded tax completely then it may find increase. Further those items which are now taxable where tax rate earlier was zero may be more expensive as exemption and zero rated list may come down in the GST regime.

The tax paid would be transparent in the invoice given to the customer. No hidden taxes would have been paid. The difficult choice of paying more if bill demanded and less if without bill would over a period of time disappear as this is a self policing system.

The free flow of trade (over a period of time) between states and throughout the country would provide more choice to the consumer.

Traders: The impact of tax on the wholesaler or retailer would be limited to the value addition. The tax paid at earlier stages (except SGST of other states) would be available as set off for payment of GST on supplies. Therefore traders would prefer to buy/ receive supplies with invoice. The tax payable as a percentage of the supply value would be small whereby the compliance would be more cost effective than evasion. Cost of products and services would reduce due to the cascading effect of tax being reduced. Traders in GST regime can concentrate on growth into large entities instead of remaining small and fragmented.

Manufacturers: There would be a saving in taxes absorbed at various stages of manufactures thereby reducing the cost of goods sold. This would make them more competitive both in domestic and international markets. The exports would be cheaper as taxes paid at earlier stages could be refunded. The difference between large manufactures and small would reduce. The indignity of harassments and bribe for honest manufacturers would substantially reduce over a period of time.

Service Providers: The present rate of tax on services is 14% (w.e.f 01.06.2015) which would be doubled in GST. This may seriously impact all the service providers especially who have long periods of realization. Those working on low margins may become unviable. The net tax payment maybe substantial as most advisory services the manpower costs is the maximum. Hardly any set off would be available. The goods used in providing the services would be eligible for credit. Hopefully the service exporters would see refunds coming promptly without a direct transaction cost. Present destination based to consumption based levy: Presently, service tax is levied at origin and is a destination based levy, the burden of which is borne by the end customer. Under GST, they would be taxed at the place of consumption.

Service tax-SGST levied by States: Under GST law, the service tax would be levied not just by Centre but also by the States who would be empowered to levy SGST by amendment to the Constitution of India. Taxes received by consuming State- If services are rendered from one State to another, then tax would ultimately go to the consuming State.

Government-Centre: The collection of Income tax would increase with increase disclosure. The country would as a whole reduce corruption and move up ethical chain gradually. The compensation of loss to the states on account of implementation of GST would be an outgo.

Government-State: The trading sector, manufacturing and service sector in the parallel economy would also get into the mainstream and pay taxes. This would lead to buoyant revenues over a period of time. The tax administration would be easier and cost of collection would be reduced.

VIII. CHALLENGES FOR GST IMPLEMENTATION

Some expected hurdles to be adequately overcome could be as under:

i) One time coverage: Share of revenue from such commodities, which would be kept outside the GST structure, e.g., petroleum products, tobacco, liquor, etc. However, Central Govt. can charge excise duty on tobacco products over and above GST. Numbers of taxes to be subsumed in the GST, for example stamp duty, property tax, toll tax, etc. are kept outside the GST structure.

iii) Uniformity of 4 rates across most products: All efforts should be made to keep the GST rate as low as possible.

iv) Protecting present/future revenues of States- Compensation to the Under the GST structure, the tax would be collected by the States where the goods or services are consumed, and hence losses could be heavy for the producer States and the Centre would be required to compensate them for loss of revenue.

The Centre had earlier come out with a similar scheme to compensate States for loss of revenue following implementation of value added tax (VAT), which came into effect from April 1, 2005. The compensation structure was 100% in the first year, 75% in the second year and 50% in the third year. Compensation was also provided to the States for loss of revenue due reduction in CST rate from 4% to 2%

v) Safeguarding interest of less developed states with low revenue – Due to switch over from origin based to destination based levy model could lead to safeguard the interest of less developed states, which are not major producers but major consumers. The consuming states to get more revenues.

vi) Seamless credit system – restriction baggage. Presently, no cross credits are available across these taxes and the sales tax paid (on input) or payable (on output). Introduction of GST should thus rationalize tax content in product price, enhance the ability of companies to compete globally, and possibly trickle down to benefit the ultimate consumer. However, it is learnt that under the proposed GST regime, the Centre will give input tax credit (set off) only for Central GST and the States will give input tax credit only for State GST. Cross-utilization of credit between Central GST and State GST will not be allowed. Nevertheless, the dealers could claim set-off within the respective heads.

vii) Transition from origin based to destination based: The only exception could be B2C end consumer supplies which could continue to be taxed in the state of origin of the supply.

viii) Standardization of systems and procedures all over India- This includes items such as the taxpayer registration system, taxpayer identification numbers, tax forms, tax reporting periods and procedures, invoice requirements, cross-border trade information systems and IT systems.

ix) Unfair dispute resolution with equal powers. A common dispute resolution mechanism [state+

centre] as well as a mechanism for giving advance rulings would further facilitate trade and industry.

Training/ Equipping Tax administration: Since the dual GST is considerably different from the present indirect tax regime, a massive training initiative would be required at both federal and State levels to familiarize the respective administrations with the concepts and procedures of the dual GST. However, the task is not limited to technical training but also extends to a similar effort to reorient the attitude and approach of the tax administration in order to achieve a fundamental change in mindset.

xi) Adoption of huge capacity IT to improve efficiency and credit states for input credit utilized as taxes collected would be on account of destination state.

IX. CONCLUSION

More important, from the businessman and consumer perspective, this change is going to have substantial impact on the business as well cost to consumers depending upon the structure of the business and location of business and consumer. Therefore it becomes essential to restructure the business and location depending upon the assessment of implication of GST on each type of transactions. The impact analysis and planning for restructuring can be done only after the draft law is released. However as per the analysis of paper writer, the rate for goods would be lower than it is now in average by 3-4 %. Depending of components of cost, in case of most of the services, the cost to final consumer is going to go up by about 10%.

A STUDY ON PUBLIC AWARENESS TOWARDS GOODS AND SERVICES TAX

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Abstract

Goods and Service Tax GST is all set to be a game changer for the Indian economy. The tax is expected to reduce the concept of 'tax on tax', increase the gross domestic product of the economy and reduce prices. In India, there are different indirect taxes applied on goods and services by central and state government. GST is intended to include all these taxes into one tax with seamless ITC and charged on both goods and services. For the introduction of GST, the Government needs to get the Constitution Amendment Bill passed so that the proposed objective of subsuming all taxes and allowing states to tax subjects in Union list and vice versa is achieved. Without these powers, it is not legally possible to move towards GST. Conceptually GST is expected to have numerous benefits like reduction in compliances in the long run since multiple taxes will be replaced with one tax.

It is expected to bring down prices and hence the inflation since it will remove the impact of tax on tax and enable seamless credit. It is expected to generate revenue for the country as the tax base will increase as the GST rate will be somewhere around 27% with both goods and services covered. It is also expected to make exports from India competitive and India a preferred destination for foreign investment since GST is a globally accepted tax. Unless the issues relating to GST has been overcome, the GST would

become a bare wall without any scripts to describe in future.

I. INTRODUCTION

"Goods and Services Tax" would be a comprehensive indirect tax on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services throughout India, to replace taxes levied by central and state governments. Goods and Services Tax would be levied and collected at each stage of sale or purchase of goods or services based on the input tax credit method. This method allows GST-registered businesses to claim tax credit to the value of GST they paid on purchase of goods or services as part of their normal commercial activity. Taxable goods and services are not distinguished from one another and are taxed at a single rate in a supply chain till the goods or services reach the consumer. Administrative responsibility would generally rest with a single authority to levy tax on goods and services.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The new GST (Amendment) Bill is yet to be ratified by all the states of India and is yet to be passed by the Parliament of India. Since there is a dilemma in the GST (Amendment) Bill, there is a lack of awareness among the general public. Even the professionals in the Indian Financial System are facing problems of clarity in the concepts of GST. Therefore, it is the need of the hour to have a study

on the public awareness towards GST (Amendment) Bill.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To have an overview about the new GST Bill in India.
2. To have a study on public awareness towards GST (Amendment) Bill.
3. To provide suggestions based on the findings of the study.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The following review of literature has been studied:

Nor Iza Biniti Ishak et al., in their article "Students' perception towards the newly Implemented goods and Services Tax (GST) in Malaysia" explained that the majority of the students disagree with the methods taken to implement the GST and also taxation is the main source of revenue for the government.

Noormahayu Binti Mohd Nasir et al., in their article "public Awareness towards Goods and Services Tax (GST) in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia" explained that the key factor that has contributed to the public awareness towards Goods and Services Tax (GST) in Kuala Lumpur and also revealed that all of three independent variables were found to have significant impact towards the publics' awareness on goods and services Tax (GST).

Mohd Rizal Palil and Mohd Adha Ibrahim in their article "The impact of Goods and Services Tax (GST) on Middle

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Income Earners in Malaysia", explained that the overview on consumer readiness, perceptions and acceptance of GST in a developing country, particularly in Asian countries that were previously under researched.

V. NEED FOR THE STUDY

There are many research projects regarding the students' perception towards GST, Public Awareness, Impact of GST and so on. "A Study on public awareness towards Goods and Services Tax (amendment) bill in Sivakasi Region" is an untouched topic, hence the present study has been undertaken to fill up that gap.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The research was based on both primary data and secondary data. Primary data was collected by using questionnaire and

secondary data have been collected from journals, websites and so on. The researcher was not possible to study the entire population of Public Awareness about GST in Sivakasi. So the researcher has collected only limited respondents i.e. 40 respondents. The researcher has selected the method of Judgement sampling.

VII. LIMITATIONS

The limitations of the study include

1. The area of the study is restricted to Sivakasi Municipality area only.
2. The content of the study is subject to change since the GST Bill has not been passed in the Parliament.
3. The researcher has collected data only from 40 general public due to time constraint.

VII. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Table I Socio- Economic Details

S.No.	Particulars		No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	24	60
		Female	16	40
		Total	40	100
2	Occupation	Business	20	50
		Government Employee	10	25
		Private employee	10	25
		Total	40	100
3	Income Level	1,00,000 – 2,00,000	25	62.5
		2,00,001 – 3,00,000	10	25
		Above 3,00,000	5	12.5
		Total	40	100
4	Education level	Primary level	10	25
		Secondary level	10	25
		UG	15	37.5
		PG	5	12.5
		Total	40	100

60% of the respondents are Male; 50% of the respondents are occupied in Business people; 62.5%

VIII. FINDINGS

The following are the findings of the study:

1. It is found that 60% of the respondents are male.
2. It is found that majority of the respondents (50%) are Business people.
3. Most of the respondents (37.5%) are UG Degree Holders.
4. The analysis revealed that 62.5% of the respondents are earning an annual income ranging from Rs.1,00,000 to Rs. 2,00,000.
5. Majority of the respondents (52.5%) know about the new GST Bill.
6. It is found that 80% of the respondents have no idea about the proposed rate of tax in GST.
7. Most of the respondents (60%) disagree that; the new GST Bill will reduce the 'tax burden' on consumers.
8. The analysis revealed that 72.5% of the respondents disagree that; the new GST Bill will

of the respondents are Rs. 1,00,000 – 2,00,000; 37.5% of the respondents are UG Degree Holder

Table Iii Level Of Expectation

S.No.	Particulars		No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Price of goods would reduce after implementing GST	Agree	13	32.5
		Disagree	20	50
		No Idea	7	17.5
		Total	40	100
2	GST is India's move towards a developed nation	Agree	8	20
		Disagree	11	27.5
		No idea	21	52.5
		Total	40	100
3	Satisfy the principle of "One Nation One Tax"	Agree	11	27.5
		Disagree	8	20
		No Opinion	21	52.5
		Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

completely eradicate the differentiation of tax rates in various states.

9. It is found that 67.5% of the respondents quote GST as a bane rather than a boon to India.
10. Most of the respondents (32.5%) agree the statement, "The price of goods would reduce after implementing GST".
11. It is found that 52.5% of the respondents have no opinion about the statement, "GST is India's move towards a developed nation".
12. The analysis revealed that 52.5% of the respondents have no opinion about the statement, "GST Bill in India would satisfy the principle of 'One Nation One Tax'".

IX. SUGGESTIONS

The following are the suggestions of the study:

1. It is suggested that the awareness towards GST should be provided to the illiterate and the women community.
2. It is also suggested that the government should come forward to take short films with respect

to the new GST Bill and screen the same in familiarized televisions’.

3. The educated should provide awareness to the general public so as to promote economic development and overall growth of the nation.

4. Even the educated and the business people are not aware of the various important issues in the new GST Bill, so the Government should take necessary steps to make familiarize the concepts of the new GST Bill in India.

X. CONCLUSION

A great revolution is yet to take place in the near future in the indirect tax system i.e. GST, so the general public is almost unaware of the concepts. But, India being a democratic country should make clear to its citizens about the emerging amendments. Therefore, it is the need of each and every citizen to have awareness about the new GST (Amendment) Bill.

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GST: A STUDY ON THE TREATMENT OF INTER- STATE TRANSACTIONS IN INDIA

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Abstract

India's indirect tax structure has been undergoing a lot of changes since 1947. The method of learning for India has always been, the learning through experience way. When a law is amended, within a period of time, by observing the applicability of the law (i.e. by noticing the loopholes in the law being taken advantage off), corrections are made by re- amending the law to make it more transparent. This is the reason why, GST is thought about by the government for implementation as a replacement for all taxes such as Central Excise, Service tax and Central sales tax. This paper studies the framework of taxes for the inter-state transactions as proposed by the government. It uses the available secondary data for the study which includes- research articles, journals, news articles, books, etc. Hence, this paper brings out the various provisions under the proposed model which are discussed in order to eliminate the issues with regard to double taxation or tax cascading and tax burden on the manufacturers and consumers.

I. INTRODUCTION

India, after sixty eight years of independence, has transformed into a fast growing economy, which is characterized by fast adaptability. After the

implementation of the liberalization, privatization and globalization policy in 1991, there have been a lot of reforms in various sectors of our economy, including the banking sector, the industries, the agriculture, etc. Hence, India is experiencing a growing trend in the economy year on year.

In this race of all the sectors being updated to meet with the global standards, the tax structure of India also has no staying back. The tax reform is now gaining ground with experience and exposure and the pace of reform is faster. After achieving an almost impossible task, of moving from sales tax system for taxation of goods at state level to more modern system of value added tax at the state level, now is the time to shift to consolidation of taxes on goods and services and achieve true value added tax system (also referred to – as Goods and Service Tax) encompassing both goods and services at all levels.

The tax reforms aims to address the problems of the current system and establish a tax system which is economically efficient, neutral in its application, attractive in its distribution and simple to administer.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The Central Sales Tax, 1956, (Act LXXIV of 1956), drafted by the government, in the act has explained in detail all the provisions pertaining to the

prevailing sales tax in the country. Also, it has defined various terms in relation to the sales tax applicable.

Poddar, S., and Ahmad, E., (March 2009) in their research paper, "GST Reforms and Intergovernmental Considerations in India", have examined in detail on the shortcomings of the current model and the various provisions under the proposed model. Also, it gives a comparison of the rates applicable currently and the proposed rates and how would it impact on the burden of tax.

Rao, G., (2014), in his newsletter titled, "GST in India: Challenges and prospects" updates about the proceedings in the GST council and the proposals made. The paper also indicates the various challenges and the implications on the implementation of GST in India.

Gupta, U., (March 2015), in his article, "Goods And Services Tax (GST) IGST Model" has briefly explained the various provisions related to inter- state transactions and has given out the various advantages of the implementation of GST in India. The relevant data is collected from the meetings held by the GST council.

The ICAI, in its paper, "GST Model for India- Suggestions", has briefed in the paper about the background of Indian tax structure and also has pointed out some of the issues with regard to the implementation of GST in India. The paper proposes some of the suggestions to the government on the implementation of GST in India.

"States Sales Taxes"- by an anonymous author, points out the various pitfalls existing in the current tax structure and indicates how GST could be a solution to cover such pitfalls. It also denotes the vicious circle between which the state taxes are stuck up and the need for its improvement. Also, the paper cites examples of various products and the applicable rates of taxes under the present tax system.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem statement of the research is to examine the treatment of inter- state transactions under the current system of tax and how differently it is going to be treated on the implementation of GST in India. Also, this study will help to understand how GST will affect the inter- state transactions and lower the burden of taxes for the assessee; and focus on the efficient functioning of the taxation department in the country.

IV. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the framework of the proposed tax structure with regard to the inter- state transactions.
2. To examine the prevailing tax structure and the proposed GST model in India.

Scope of the study

The study mainly focuses on the impact of the provisions of the proposed GST model pertaining to India. It also considers the provisions applicable to the inter- state transactions on account of the purchase and sale of goods and services between the states.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

The relevant data is collected from various secondary sources such as research articles, journals, news articles, etc. also, the information regarding the provisions is collected from various acts and amendments made. Specifically, the information is collected from the existing Tax provisions and the various proposals made with regards to GST. Also, various reports of the meetings of the Indian GST Council is referred.

Discussions

Current System

India currently has a mixed system of taxation of goods and services; the taxes on goods are described as "VAT" at both Central and State level on goods and it has adopted value added tax principle with

input tax credit mechanism for taxation of goods and services. Till the time MODVAT (now called as CENVAT) was introduced in India in 1986, in Central Excise duty, the duty was only an origin based system of tax which was levied at the time of manufacture. Even with the introduction of the State VAT, the tax was a combination of both the origin based single-point tax as well as destination based multi-point tax. Central Excise exists only at the manufacturing level and does not proceed to the retail level. The structure of the Indirect Taxes in our country is in a sense a dual one where the tax on manufacture of goods and provision of services is collected by the Union and the sale of goods is collected by the State.

Inter-State Sales

Although sales tax was applicable for those transactions (purchases and sales) taking place within the jurisdiction of the state territory, the same was used for inter-state sales as well. In order to regulate the taxation of inter-state sales between dealers or between dealers and consumers, a law was enacted in the Parliament designated as the Central State Tax (CST). The proceeds of inter-state tax was to be collected by the Centre but, with the introduction of CST, a rate of CST was to be levied on inter-state sales and the proceeds were to be kept with the State.

Initially the rate of CST was at one percent, the current rate stands at four percent. As CST was applicable to sales, inter-State movement of goods as consignment was not liable to any CST in the exporting State.

According to the recent amendment, the single-point of taxation- CST was replaced by the multi-point tax structure- Value Added Tax (VAT). VAT was structured in all Union and State territories. The State VAT eliminated all the complexities concerned to double taxation on the goods. The Input tax credit was made available to the manufacturers so as to reduce the burden of taxes. The services on the other hand, had different rates of taxes for specified

services. Hence, the services were classified into one hundred categories. Also, the goods under CETA (Central Excise Tariff Act), 1985 are classified based on the HSN nomenclature, while the services are not classified on any such standardized basis.

GST (Goods and Services Tax)

The Goods and Services Bill (GST Bill), commonly known as the Constitution Bill, 2014 is a VAT which is yet to be implemented in India from April, 2016. GST is said to integrate all the taxes levied on goods and services; including the CST, VAT and Service tax. It is proposed to be a dual model; in the sense, GST is to be implemented at the Centre and at the State. There would be no categorization of goods and services; so both the categories will be integrated in the supply chain and a single rate of tax will be applicable till the product or the service reaches the consumer. It would be called as CGST (Central) and SGST (State). The levy and collection is on the value addition at every point of sale or purchase of goods or supply of services based on input tax credit method but without State boundaries.

GST is known to be the global standard in the context of designing the tax structure of a country. Approximately, 150 plus countries have adopted this model of taxation in their countries. By implementing this model, all the Central and State taxes are integrated and will pave way for competition on the same platform. Also, it will not only open the doors for standardized domestic and international competition but also, mitigate cascading of tax or double taxation and pave way for common national market.

In the context of inter-state transactions, exports will be zero rated and imports will be levied at the same taxes as domestic goods and services adhering to the destination principle. The State VAT will expand its ground of the prevailing VAT for the inclusion of the services. The simplification of the tax

structure is expected to be done by merging some of the taxes such as motor vehicle tax, goods and passengers' tax, entertainment tax, electricity duty and entry taxes including those in lieu- of- octroi- local taxes on the entry of goods into a municipal area for consumption, use or sale. For the time being, the bill has kept certain goods out of the purview of GST, which have been a point of contention between state governments and the Centre. These include: Petroleum crude, high speed diesel, petrol, natural gas, aviation turbine fuel and alcohol for human consumption. States shall have the power to levy taxes on these items, except in the case of imports and inter-state trade.

The bill which is yet to be passed proposes that, the inter- state tax will be called as the Integrated Goods and Service Tax (IGST). The Empowered Committee of State Finance Ministers met and approved that, the Union Government will be responsible to levy and collect IGST (which would be equal to the sum of CGST and SGST rates on inter-state supply of goods and services) and the proceeds will be shared between the Centre and the states. The consuming states would get the proceeds of the SGST component of it and the manufacturing states will not get any share but would have the right to levy an extra 1 per cent non-Vatable tax. Under the proposed IGST, states will not have any right to restrict input tax credits on interstate transactions as the idea is to facilitate free flow of tax credits and thus move towards a common national market. Sources also said cross utilization of CGST or SGST credit will be allowed for payment of IGST. Imports into the territory of India will also be deemed as inter-state

commerce and attract IGST. IGST on imports, however, will not include basic customs duty, safeguards duty and anti-dumping duty.

VI. REQUIREMENTS FOR IGST MODEL

- There should be a uniform e-registration system
- There has to be a common e-return for CGST, SGST & IGST in place
- Common periodicity of returns for every class of dealers
- There has to be a uniform cut-off date for filing of returns
- The reporting of sales and purchase invoice details prior to or along with filing of e-return should be a mandate
- A system- based verification of returns on monthly basis to be implemented
- A system- based validations/consistency checks on the ITC availed, utilized & Tax payments is required.
- It has been suggested that the tax would need to be levied at a combined Centre-State tax rate of 20 percent, of which 12% would go to the Centre and 8% to the states; while they fall below the present combined Centre and State statutory rate of 26.5% (CENVAT of 14%, and VAT of 12.5%).
- In order to show the reason for implementation of GST in our country, a simple calculation with regard to the difference in the tax burden borne by the consumer along with the share taken by the states involved in the inter- state transactions and the centre is illustrated bellow:

Table No: 1: Comparison of the impact of tax on the cost of a product with regard to the Present and the Proposed tax structure

Particulars	Inter - State	
	Present	Proposed
Initial Value	121.00	120.00
Centre's Tax	11.00	12.22

State (A's) Tax	11.00	1.10
State (B's) Tax	16.91	12.22
State's total Tax	27.91	13.32
Total tax paid to the Govt.	38.91	25.54
Non Vatable tax borne by the Business	25.00	1.10
Total tax paid by the consumer	13.91	24.44
Final value paid by the consumer.	152.97	146.65

Source: "Goods And Services Tax (GST) IGST Model" by Upender Gupta, (March,2015)

From the above table it is clear that the final value paid by the consumer for a given product will decrease if GST is implemented as there is a decrease in the value of the from Rs. 152.97 to Rs 146.65. Also, the total amount of tax paid to the government is reduced from Rs. 38.91 to Rs 25.54. The state's total tax paid has also reduced from Rs. 27.91 to Rs 13.32. So, implementing this model will help reduce the tax burden on the consumers as well as the manufacturers.

VII. CONCLUSION

India, being one of the biggest democratic countries is trying to improve in its every move towards development. Amending the tax structure would impact all or most of the sectors of the economy, thereby, initializing the change that is needed for the country. Some of the advantages of implementing the integrated goods and services tax model (IGST) could be:

For the Taxpayers

The IGST may help the dealers in maintaining an uninterrupted input tax credit (ITC) chain while trading between the states. There will be no refund claim for suppliers in the exporting State, as ITC is used up while paying the Tax. The blockage of funds for the inter- state supplier or buyer is eliminated on the implementation of IGST. This model considers both B2B as well as B2C categories as it includes transactions between dealers as well as between dealers and the consumers.

For Tax Administration

The dual-GST model to be implemented in our country is characterized by the self monitoring model,

which is easily adaptable and makes it convenient to operate. The tax gets transferred to the importing state on the basis of the destination principle, which makes it easier to administer. Also there is a transparency in the break- up of the proceeds of the inter- state transactions between the Centre and the State.

GOODS AND SERVICE TAX IN INDIA: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

India is a federal country where Indirect Tax is levied by Federal and State Government. Value Added Tax is levied by State Governments. Every State has authority to decide the Tax rate and to control the Tax system as per their convenient. The Taxation power has been well defined in Indian Constitution. The Constitution (122nd Amendment) Bill that seeks to usher in a Goods and Services Tax (GST) regime in the country will finally be taken up for discussion in Parliament. Finance Minister Arun Jaitley has been affirming that India will implement GST from 1st April 2016. It can be looked as simplification of Taxes in country and avoiding unnecessary complexities. India is a federal country which has various Tax regimes and structure, where Tax is levied by both Governments. After the implementation of GST all the Indirect Taxes will be subsumed under an umbrella, it will be a milestone in the history of Indirect Tax reform. In this paper, an attempt has been made to examine the major features of GST. This paper has also focused on the problems likely to be faced by Central and State Governments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Value Added Tax (VAT) was proposed for the first time by Wilhelm Von Siemens in Germany 1919, as an improved turnover Tax. In 1921, Sales Tax was recommended by Prof. Thomas S. Adams of United State of America. In 1949, the Shoup mission (A group of American Tax experts, under the leadership of Carl S. Shoup) has suggested VAT for the reconstruction of the Japanese economy. Then, France was the first country to implement VAT in 1954.

At present Value Added Tax (VAT) has been implemented by more than 160 countries in the world, even our neighbor country Pakistan is also implementing GST. However, GST is known as “General Sales Tax” in Pakistan. In one of the countries of Africa, it is known as “General Consumption Tax (GCT)”. In various countries (Table-1), all over the world, it is also known by the name of Goods and Service Tax (GST). Where in Australia, Canada, Singapore and New Zealand it is also famous as “GST”. After Brazil (1960) and Canada (1991), India will be the 3rd country which is going to introduce dual GST (levied by both Federal and State Government) structure. There is no

difference between GST and VAT except a minor difference that VAT is levied on goods and GST will impose on goods plus services. Again, GST is not an additional Tax; it is subsumed of all Indirect Taxes. This means all Indirect Taxes will come under one umbrella.

1.1 Direct Tax

Direct Tax is a kind of duty, which is charged directly on the Taxpayer and paid directly to the Government by the Taxpayer. It cannot be shifted from one person (Taxpayer) to another. There are several Direct Taxes levied in India are as follows

1. Income Tax
2. Corporation Tax
3. Property Tax
4. Estate Tax
5. Gift Tax

1.2 Indirect tax

An Indirect Tax is one which is imposed on commodity (goods) or services that is paid by the consumer. Indirect Tax is basically collected from intermediary sources such as company, dealer and retailer while the mediator collects Tax from the end user (consumer). It can be shifted from one person to another and is not levied directly. There are some Indirect Taxes are as follows

1. Custom Duty
2. Central Excise Duty
3. Service Tax
4. VAT
5. Entertainment Tax
6. Octroi

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A number of studies have been conducted to examine various facets to the introduction of the GST. The studies suggested some important issues of GST like Dual GST Tax structure, where Federal and State Government will work mutually. Uniformity in Tax rate and distribution of the Tax between CGST and SGST etc. remain in the system. M. Govinda

Rao, (2009) has found that GST is not a new Tax. It is only the further improvement over the existing consumption Tax system at the Central and States level. At present Federal and State Government levy Service Tax and VAT respectively and GST will be subsumed of all Indirect Tax. While some of the important shortcomings of the proposed GST are summarized in the following- Reforming the consumption Tax system, List of exempted goods and services. Management of the Tax system, what will be the rate of Tax and who will decide the Tax structure etc?

G. C. Ruggeri & K. Bluck (1990) have examined that the Canada Federal Government implemented the GST as a replacement of the Manufacturers' Sales Tax (MST) in 1989. The study has focused the comparison between MST and broad-based VAT. They found VAT is more regressive than that of MST and at the same time GST is also found to be more regressive than MST. This weakness of GST can be reduced if Tax rate will be in progressive form, which indicates lower income credit financed by a high-income class pay surtax or higher GST rate.

Amol Agarwal (2011) has studied the impact of GST on the Indian economy. In his study, he mentioned that Dr. Vijay Kelkar, Chairman of the 13th Finance Commission cited the work of renowned Tax economist Prof. Charles McLure, who identified six characteristics of a well-designed GST in a federal system as given below.

1. Uniformity rate of Taxation within a given jurisdiction, ideally at a single rate.
2. Sales would be Taxed under the destination principle.
3. Low cost of compliance and administration.
4. Each level of Government to set its own Tax rate subjects to agreed floors
5. A substantively common Tax base for Central and State Governments

6. Substantial Co- operation in Tax administration between all levels of Government

Kelkar added that first two are important for economic reasons; the third for the administrative while the fourth is for political reason along with the last two operates a system of multilevel finance that we have in our country. These principles should be adopted while designing GST in India as well.

Alasdair Roberts & Jonathan Rose (1995) has examined that the Canadian Federal Government campaign communication program in favor of GST to influence public opinion towards GST. It is possible that communications program will be able to get an important influence from public opinion. It will also help to discuss the controversial issues which include constitutional reform, free trade, environmental and energy policy. The goal of above mentioned GST campaign is to evaluate its efficiency regarding the basis of public opinion. The Department of Finance is also concerned about the political problems created by Bill C-62 which is clear enough to the counselors, appointed to give advice on its communications strategy. Amaresh Bagchi (2006) has observed a unified Tax on goods and services that discusses about the several difficulties in introducing single national VAT. This will levy and administered only by the federal Government. Otherwise, Tax at the Central level is neither practicable nor desirable for India. Another alternative option is that Government could implement dual GST where Tax rate would be uniform all over India. But for this Central has to allow the Tax and at the same time State should accept extension of the Tax powers approved by the Central at all stages or vice-versa. But there is neither the discussion about the amendment of Tax in the Constitution and nor mentioned who will decide the Tax rates. Major problems of the study are

1. Amendment in the Constitution.
2. Uniformity in the Tax rate.

3. Administration of GST, both at the Central and State levels will have to be prepared themselves to deal with transitional issues.

4. The first discussion paper on GST released by the empowered committee does not specify the list of exempted goods and services. The list of goods and services is yet to be concluded and it is quite likely that some discretion may be allowed to individual States.

5. The power of decision making about the Tax rate and collection of Tax. In what percentage and how Government will share Indirect Tax? These are the major problem for both Governments (CGST and SGST).

6. Regarding the source of awareness to understand and gain knowledge of about GST system, most of the dealers are dependent on Tax consultant.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the problems and prospects of GST in India.

3.1 Research methodology

The paper is based on secondary sources of data, which have been obtained from various GST implementation discussion papers, published article in journals, web articles (internet sources), past studies and news paper etc. With the help of these secondary sources, attempt has been made to find the obstacles coming on the way of GST and looking for future opportunities of it in India.

3.2 GST in India

In India, GST was first time introduced on 28th February 2006 in the Budget Speech of the year 2006-07 by Finance Minister Sh. P. Chidambaram. A message was left by the Finance Minister in the Union Budget 2007-08 that GST will be introduced with effect from 1st April 2010. Central and State Governments will be work together to prepare a roadmap for the introduction of GST in India. They planned to introduce GST or “replacing the previous VAT and Service Tax” on 1st April 2010, but some

of the States were not ready to implement the GST. After that on 1st April 2012, again Government was going to introduce GST, but due to some management and infrastructure problems it was not introduced. Finance Minister Arun Jaitley introduced the 122nd Constitution Amendment Bill in Parliament and intends to implement GST reform by 1st April 2016 (Table-2). The advantage of GST is that it will replace Indirect Taxes which are levied by Central and State Government. The GST structure will present a transparent system which will be helpful to reduce the burden of cascading effect and it will also improve the Tax compliances and Tax collection. GST will prove the uniformity of Taxes in all over the country.

IV. MODEL OF THE GST

There are three prime model of GST:

- a) GST at Central Government level only
- b) GST at State Governments level only
- c) GST at both, Central and State Government level

4.1 Important features of GST

“First time the discussion on GST in India” exhibits in detail the basic features of its structure and implementation aspect. Of course, some of the details are already known to us and a few others will help to clarify some details of the proposed design. Some of the important features of the proposed GST reform are:

a) This dual GST model would be implemented through a certain number of legal provisions. The GST shall have two mechanisms: one levied by the Centre (CGST), and the other levied by the States (SGST).

b) In the First Discussion Paper on GST released by Empowered Committee has given its recommendations that the Central Taxes and State Government Taxes should be subsumed under the GST.

4.2 Central Government tax

These Taxes will subsume under Central Goods and Service Tax (CGST).

1. Service Tax
2. Central Excise Duty
3. Additional Excise Duty
4. Excise Duty under Medicinal and Toiletries preparation Act
5. Additional customs duty (Countervailing Duty)
6. Surcharge
7. Cess

4.3 State Government Tax (SGST)

The Taxes will come under the State Goods and Service Tax (SGST).

1. VAT/ Sales Tax
 2. Entertainment Tax
 3. Luxury Tax
 4. Taxes on lotteries
 5. Betting and gambling
 6. Entry Tax
 7. Octroi
- c) The GST would be applicable to all transactions of goods and services except the exempted goods and services.

d) The Empowered Committee has proposed two Tax rate structure for GST- one a low rate for essential items and another standard rate for the remaining goods and services.

Proposed rate of GST will be 16% to 20% and a special rate will also be levied on precious metals

e) There will be separate Tax administrations at the centre and the States level. The Central GST and State GST are to be paid to the accounts of the Centre and the States individually.

f) The CGST will have a threshold of 1.5 crores and SGST proposed at 10 lakhs.

g) Every Taxpayer would be allotted a PAN-linked Taxpayer identification number (TIN) It will be 12-15 digits.

h) Alcoholic product, Tobacco and Petroleum products will not come under the GST. State Government could continue with the VAT and Central Government could also continue its levies.

i) 13th Finance Commission has also announced 50,000 crores compensation package for States in case of revenue deficit, there is a concern raised by the States regarding their freedom to levy Tax and increase the Tax rates at their discretion.

4.4 Problems with GST

4.4.1 Amendment in the Constitution

Implementation of GST is necessary to perform the Constitutional Amendments for State to levy Service Tax as well as Central Government has the power to enhance revenue from dealers and retailers transaction. Central and State Government is accepted that the substitute is desirable. It is not a big problem, but the system will take some time for amendment of the constitution. After the amendment in Constitution, a separate entry 92C was incorporated in the Union List to empower it to levy the Tax on services. Numbers of modified measures have been undertaken by both the Governments before implementing the GST and these should be initiated as soon as possible.

4.5 Administration issue

GST is subsumed of various types Indirect Taxes where revenue will be divided between the Central and State Government. But there may occur various problems in this case regarding the matter of authority- who will control the system? Who will decide the Tax rate and how will the administration work? On the basis of the discussion of the first paper we can suppose that there will be separate Tax management both for the Centre and each State level.

The administration of the State GST will be under the control of State while Central GST will be under the Central Government.

4.6 Tax Awareness among the stakeholders

When GST implemented in Canada in 1990, Canadian Government "Department of Finance" spent \$11.6 million on print, radio and television media for awareness of people on the matter of GST that how it will work. A video was exposed by satellite in cable television stations across the country. Around \$5 million was spent on operating costs for GST by the Communication Groups within the department. They provided the service of toll-free hotline which attended 6,000 calls per day. In 1990-1991, Excise and Customs Department have also spent \$ 10.6 million on GST, and another \$9.2 million for printing and mailing materials for the explanation of how the new Tax will work. Total expenditure on GST was \$ 85 million. In 1989, Proctor & Gamble was the largest private-sector advertiser, which spent \$ 56.7 million on the advertisement of GST. India is a developing country and more than 60% people lives in rural areas. The (Central and State Government) have to spend a large amount of money for the awareness of people on the matter of GST.

4.7 Political issue

Presently VAT is levied by 29 States and 7 Union Territories of India. Every State has authority to decide the Tax rate and to control the Tax system as per their convenient. If it is handed over to the Central Government, they will control the Tax rate along with the Tax system. It is a matter of great concern, but the question arises why all the States hand over their right to the Union Government.

4.8 Inflation

Australia has implemented GST on 1st July 2000. Critics have argued that it is a regressive Tax; means a person with higher income will pay lower Tax compared to those are earning the lower income.

Due to the reduction in federal Sales Tax and some fuel Taxes, State banking Tax that was implemented when the GST was introduced. Australia is a conservative nation as India. Before implementation of GST, the consumer has purchased goods in bulk and stored. When GST Tax came into effect, consumer consumption and economic growth declined in the first fiscal quarter of 2001. First time in last decade, Australian economy recorded negative economic growth. The Government was also criticized by small-scale industry due to the excess of administrative responsibilities.

4.9 Prospects of GST

4.9.1 India and GST

India has federal structure. Union Government has planned for a dual GST model where Central Goods and Services Tax (CGST) and a State Goods and Services Tax (SGST) will be levied on the Taxable value of goods plus services.

4.9.2 Benefit to industry

The GST is expected to be complimentary to the user of the supply chain of goods and services which include from beginning to ending the whole industry, Agriculture and trade via a comprehensive Tax regime. This is expected to generate the higher amount of revenue for the industry as well as business prospects as Tax burden goes down.

4.9.3 Benefit to exports

The cost of manufactured goods and services will decrease with the comprehensive reduction of input cost of major Central and State Taxes in GST. This will create a competitive environment of goods and services of India, in the international market.

4.9.4 Benefit to Consumer

The management of GST should be transparent and rationalized so that consumers will get benefits from lowering the Tax burden on goods and services consumed by them.

4.9.5 Reduction in Cost

As per the Government report of India "Task Force on Goods and Services Tax: Thirteenth Finance Commission" 2009, shows that the implementation of the GST will result in a sharp decline in the prices of cotton textiles (by 6.44 percent), wool, silk & synthetic fibre textiles (by 11.4 percent), and textile products including wearing apparel (by 17.45 percent). To the extent, the contribution of expenditure on clothing in the total overheads on consumption is relatively higher than in the case of the rich, the poor will be benefited more from deduction in prices. To some extent it will also help to solve the burning question poverty. Implementation of GST will increase the actual returns of land, labour and capital.

V. CONCLUSION

In the light of the above discussion, the authors have recommended that GST system is more beneficial for the Government as well as stakeholders from the management and analysis point of view. We believe that CGST must have the authority to collecting Tax and SGST should be given the power to take the decision regarding Tax rate. In case, if there is any change in the Tax rate it should be decided through democratic consent so that there are minimum chances of political interference. GST is also helpful in avoiding Tax evasion, improved Tax collection and compliances. It reduces the cost of goods and services to some extent and creates a supportive environment for the facilitation of international trade, thereby helping in revenue generation leading to the increase in the GDP of the country. Similarly, it will also be helpful in lowering the Tax burden on the various segments of the economy. Industries, dealers, retailers and the agriculture sector as a whole will benefit from GST.

It is found that in countries where GST has been implemented had positive impact on their economies. It can be looked as simplification of Taxes in country

and avoiding unnecessary complexities. Researcher's observation is in support of GST system, experience of other countries strengthen the belief that it will be a milestone in the development of Taxation in India. As for challenges are concern it is between State and Central Government proportion in Taxes majorly, but directly or indirectly it is adding wealth to nation only. It has great prospects in favor of the nation. Researcher advocates that it should be implemented as soon as possible, delayed in implementation has negative impact on economy only.

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AN OVERVIEW OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX - REDUCTION OF TAX BURDEN

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Abstract

Goods and Service Tax, a significant breakthrough and the next logical step towards a comprehensive Indirect tax reform in India. This paper gives an overview of GST and further discusses how the mechanism reduces the tax burden and other cascading effects. Brief description is given on the history of tax, GST background, introduction, salient features and illustration of reducing tax burden. GST is the new story of VAT to be implemented in India decision on which is pending. It aims at creating a single and unified market benefiting both corporate and economy because this is the only Indirect tax that directly effects all sectors of economy, it enables widespread setoff for Input Tax Credit(ITC) and subsuming of many indirect taxes having a dual concept model operating at centre(CGST) and state(SGST) to maintain commonality. Therefore this paper focuses on the overview and reducing tax burden through GST.

I. INTRODUCTION

Meaning of Tax

The word tax is derived from the Latin word “taxare” meaning to estimate. It is a compulsory contribution to the state revenue levied by the government on worker’s income and business profits or added to the cost of some goods, services and transactions. In general it is a financial charge or fee

imposed by the government and tax is the principle source of revenue for a country’s government.

History of Tax

The history of tax in the world is dated back to ancient Egypt around 3000 B.C in the first dynasty of the old kingdom where Pharaoh would conduct a biennial tour of the kingdom collecting tax revenues from people where early taxation is also mentioned in the Bible. We can find tradition of taxation in India from ancient times where references can be drawn from many ancient books like “Manusmriti” and “Arthasastra”, even Islamic rulers imposed “Jizya”

If we look into the Indian context, India witnessed remarkable changes in the whole taxation system during the period of British rule, even though it was highly favourable to the British they incorporated modern and scientific methods of taxation. In 1922, a paradigm shift occurred with the enactment of a new income tax which led to setting up of a comprehensive taxation system with own administration. In 1924, a Central Board of Revenue was created to administer central taxes. The attainment of independence marked another shift for taxation whereby taxes were paid for welfare of the people rather than compulsion from British.

Introduction of Goods and Service Tax

If the value added tax (VAT) is considered to be a major improvement over the pre-existing central

excise duty at the national level and sales tax system at the state level, then the Goods and Service Tax (GST) will be a further significant breakthrough, we can say it is the next logical step towards a comprehensive indirect tax reform in the country. The concept of GST has gone through various stages and phases not just from present scenario but from past few years.

In 2000, the Vajpayee Government started discussion on GST by setting an empowered committee headed by Asim Dasgupta (Finance minister, Government of West Bengal). Later it prolonged its discussions and the proposal of GST was announced by Shri P. Chidambaram (Finance Minister) in the budget speech of 2006-07, which led to formation of empowered committee of State finance ministers which gave the report and the model of GST including design, road map for implementation etc. the empowered committee released its first discussion paper on GST in India on 10th November, 2009.

A dual GST model has been accepted by the centre, it has two components, the Central GST to be levied and collected by the centre and the State GST to be levied and collected by States.

With introduction of GST Central Excise Duty, Additional Excise Duty, Service Tax, Additional Duty of Customs, State VAT, Entertainment Tax, Taxes on Lotteries, Betting, Gambling and Entry Tax (not levied by local bodies) would be subsumed within GST. For further development on GST a joint working group consisting of officers from central as well as state was constituted. The Goods and Service Tax (GST) Bill officially known as the Constitution (122nd Amendment) Bill, 2014 to be implemented in India from April, 2016. It was introduced in Lok Sabha by Finance Minister Arun Jaitley on 19th December, 2015 and further moved to Rajya Sabha on 11th May, 2015 and report will be given at the end

of monsoon session. The further process is pending until the decision given by Rajya Sabha.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Prasad (April 5th, 2015) GST will enable simplified Indirect tax regime as per the proposal given and therefore its implementation will remove complications and multi-layered taxation mechanism.

Mehta (April 5th, 2015) points out that the implementation of GST will at least increase 1.5% to 2% GDP due to cost reductions and other changes made in tax system, it will also make black money impossible as the transactions can only be routed through legitimate route only.

Zhong (March 19th, 2015) explains the idea of replacing patch work of taxes with a single nationwide sales levy, lowering of commercial barriers, the government study estimates that broad GST would deliver an immediate boost output of 1% to 2% and lasting gains in productivity.

Stromer (December 9th, 2014) suggests if GST system comes into effect the infrastructure develops and the logistics service will be increased and improved. The implementation of GST alone can boost growth of the economy by 2% and reduce logistics cost by 15%.

According to Garg (2014) the impact of GST on Indian Indirect tax will reduce the tax burden and boost overall growth with the new proposal which highlights subsuming of taxes

Gupta (2014) is of the opinion that GST assures single taxation system making tax compliance easier and more effective and which boosts our Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

According to Sharma and Neha (2014) GST is a better approach of charging tax on Goods as well as Services to solve the existing problem of tax evasion, distortion and cascading effect which can be minimised through this and broaden tax base

structure increasing tax revenues which may be used for the growth the nation.

Shah (2014) examines that GST is set to integrate state economies and boost overall growth by removing tax barriers between states and low tax rate by increasing tax base and minimising tax exemptions through proposed GST Model.

IANS (Indo Asian News Service) (2014) points out that the final consumer will bear only GST charged by the last dealer in the supply chain with the set off benefits at all previous stages.

Kelkar (2009) analyses that GST will bring a qualitative change in the tax system by redistributing tax burden equitably, boosts GDP in the long run through cost reduction and it will be successful if taken in similar fashion at both centre and state.

Statement of the problem

Goods and Service Tax system subsumes various taxes and avoids the problem of multiple or double taxation and other indirect taxes having cascading effect thereby reducing the burden of taxes. Therefore creating a single, unified market to make economy stronger breaking tax barriers between states and integrating India through uniform tax rate reducing the burden overall. This study analyses to what extent the burden is reduced and how the mechanism works.

Objectives of the Study

1. To give clear overview of new indirect tax reform, Goods and Service Tax (GST)
2. To examine how the GST mechanism reduces the tax burden eliminating the multiple taxation and other cascading effects.

Scope of the Study

The study aims at discussion on the GST overview and mechanism reducing burden of tax in India. The study focuses on the Indian indirect tax reforms, milestones, developments and economy. The scope of the study limits to the Indian context i.e. India's taxation, mechanisms and further growth and development of the country.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research paper is an attempt of exploratory research on a conceptual analysis where the data is based on the secondary sources like journals, magazine, articles and media reports.

Discussion

Overview of GST

Goods and Service

Tax proposed to be comprehensive indirect tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods as well as services at the national level. It will replace all the indirect taxes levied on goods and services. Any commodity in general is produced on the basis of physical inputs as well as services, there should be integration of VAT on goods with tax on services at the state level as well at the same time there should also be removal of cascading effect of service tax.

In the present scenario CENVAT and State VAT have remained incomplete in removing fully the cascading burden of taxes already paid at earlier stages, there are several other taxes which centre and state levy, where no set off is available in the form of ITC leading to 'tax on tax' but with introduction of GST, both cascading effects of CENVAT and Service Tax are removed with set-off and a continuous chain of set-off from the original producer's point and service

producer's point up to retailers level is established which reduces burden of all cascading effect. This is the essence of GST, this is the reason it is not simply Vat plus Service Tax but an improvement over the previous system of VAT and dis-jointed Service Tax. Now the power of levying Service Tax is given to state as well.

Salient features of GST Model

- GST has two components hence called Dual GST Model. It consists of :
- Central Goods and Service Tax (CGST)
- State Goods and Service Tax (SGST)

- CGST and SGST are applicable to all goods and services except for certain exempted goods and services outside the purview of GST.

- CGST and SGST are treated separately, taxes paid against CGST shall be allowed to be taken as Input Tax Credit (ITC) for and utilize only for CGST and the same is applicable for SGST.

- Uniform procedure for collection of both CGST and SGST would be prescribed.

- Uniform SGST threshold across states is desirable.

- Tax payer would need to submit periodical returns in common format as far as possible to both CGST and SGST concerned authorities.

- Each tax payer would be allocated a PAN-linked tax payer's identification number with total of 13 or 15 digits. This would bring GST PAN-Linked system in line with prevailing PAN system for Income Tax.

- Inter-State supplies of goods or services in India called Integrated Goods and Service Tax (IGST), which are levied and collected by the centre.

Justification of GST

With reference to the above illustrations and comparison table, it shows that the tax burden is less in the GST system on all stages for manufacturer, dealer as well as the final consumer. Where all the cascading effects of CENVAT, Service Tax would be removed and it clearly shows that set off mechanism in the form of Input Tax Credit (ITC) there by reducing the 'tax on tax' or tax burden which the final consumer has to bear this not only benefits the consumers but also industry, trade, agriculture, exports, imports etc. Tax burden also reduces in way of subsuming all indirect taxes in GST and there will be transparent and complete chain of set offs, this will help in widening the coverage of tax base and improve tax compliance leading to higher revenues resulting in possibility of lowering average tax burden.

IV. CONCLUSION

The overview of Goods and Service Tax (GST) gave an insight about the entire concept and reducing tax burden, therefore it can be considered as a most logical step towards indirect tax reforms in our country. All sectors of the economy have benefits and impact with GST whether individual, industry, trade, government departments, service sector, professionals, importers etc. It is a simple mechanism yet can boost economy compared to the previous system also having uniform and transparent system to all players than existing complexities. It is ready to integrate state economies and boost the overall GDP as it reduces the tax burden making single unified Indian market with growth dynamics and strong economy.

GST AND ITS PROVISIONS – AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

India has witnessed substantial reforms in indirect taxes over the past two decades. The Goods and Service Tax (GST) is one of the biggest taxation reforms in India, the decision on which is pending in Parliament since March 2011. The central idea behind this form of taxation is to replace existing levies like value-added tax, excise duty, service tax, and sales tax by levying a comprehensive tax on the manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services in the country. GST is expected to unite the country economically as it will remove various forms of taxes that are currently levied at different points. This paper presents the background, silent features and the impact of GST in the present tax scenario in India.

Key Words-Goods and Service Tax, Value added tax, Excise duty, Service tax and Sale tax.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tax policies of a country play an important role on the economy through their impact on both efficiency and equity. A good tax system should keep in view issues of income distribution and at the same time, also generate tax revenues to support government expenditure on public services and infrastructure development. The framework of value added tax (VAT), recognized as GST as well in several countries, has been one of the major development in taxation structures worldwide. More than 135 countries adopted the GST/ VAT framework effectively. Indian economy is getting more and more

globalised. Introduction of an integrated Goods and Services Tax (GST) to replace the existing multiple tax structures of Centre and State taxes is not only desirable but imperative in the emerging economic environment. The implementation of GST would ensure that India provides a tax regime that is almost similar to the rest of the world. It will also improve the international cost competitiveness of native goods and services.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. According to Suresh (March 2, 2015) the key point discussed includes centre to educate motivate and convince the state on being GST. This discuss was all about GST would cut down on their own revenue. The discussed pointed out that some sectors like construction, cigarettes, liquor were not in GST. EX: WHILE MAHARASHTRA wanted to keep Octroi with itself where as Telangana wanted the revenue from the stamps and registrations.

2. Bipin Sapara (Feb 28, 2015) in this article, analasized the expectations and curiosity whether implement of GST in India. However the finance minister set a positive aspect on enforce of GST and also he mentioned that o=it will play a transformative in India economy and also develop a common Indian market. There is a time limit of availing credit on input and input service and also being increased from 6 months to 1year. There is lot benefits are expected in GST in Indian economy and the most important one it would provide seamless flow of credit across the supply chain for business.

3. Seth and Dhasmana (August 18, 2015) according to this article, we have taken all the steps to implement GST. If this bill passes quickly, we would be able to roll out from the scheduled deadline. Only if there is a co-operation between central and state. If GST is implemented the consuming state will benefit from the first year itself. Whereas manufacturing states might initially face losses first 2 years. The advantage of GST is that we get India as one single unified market.

4. According to S Krishnamurthy, adjunct faculty in the finance and control area at IIM Bangalore. GST is a proposed tax reform that centres around efficient and harmonized consumption tax system in the country. The introduction of goods and services tax will lead to the abolition of taxes such as octroi, central sales tax, state level sales tax, entry tax, turnover tax, tax on consumption or sales of electricity, taxes on transportation of goods and services and eliminate the cascading effects of multiple layers of taxation.

5. NDTV (December 18, 2014) articles state that GST will enable the creation of a unified market for facilitating seamless movement of goods across states. There is expectation that if we implement GST it might reduce the transaction cost of business.

Ex: GST will impact some of Indian leading firms.

Dish TV: Impact tax evasions which come down forcing operators to raise tariffs.

- Godrej consumer products: FMCG firms will benefit from labour warehouse cost. Some of the companies like paper industry GST will increase the tax burden. Secondly PVR cinema: implementation of GST might lead to lower entertainment taxes.

Statement of Problem

Under GST system the consumer pays fair prices for most of the goods and services at a single shot. The cost of doing business increases as they are not allowed to claim services tax and accounting

telecommunication and legal services and sales tax on indirect services.

GST will not only make the tax system simpler but will also help in increased compliance, boost tax revenues, reduce the tax outflow. This can be a single tax which will be levied on the product or services which is sold.

The whole country which is one sixth of the world's population would become a single market and hence it would give a fillip as far as trade is concerned.

Objectives of the Study

The study has been geared towards achieving the following objectives:

- 1) To understand the concept of Goods and Services Tax.

- 2) To know the benefit of Goods and Services Tax to economy, business and industry and consumer.

- 3) To examine the features of Goods and Services Tax.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is wide since once it is implemented, it might help the nation at large.

Research Methodology

The research paper is an attempt of exploratory research, based on the secondary data sourced from journals, magazines, articles and media reports. Looking into requirements of the objectives of the study the research design employed for the study is of descriptive type. Keeping in view of the set objectives, this research design was adopted to have greater accuracy and in-depth analysis of the research study.

Data Analysis Tools

What is the GST?

Goods and Service Tax (GST) is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. In simple terms, GST may be defined as a tax on

goods and services, which is liveable at each point of sale or provision of service, in which at the time of sale of goods or providing the services the seller or service provider may claim the input credit of tax which he has paid while purchasing the goods or procuring the service. It is basically a tax on final consumption.

Under the GST regime, both the Centre and the State would have the powers to tax the supply of goods and services right from their primary stage to final consumption. At the centre's level, introduction of the GST will mean that it takes the place of central excise duty, service tax and additional customs duties. At the state level, the GST will take the place of State VAT.

Goods and Services Tax in India

The introduction of GST in India is not an entirely new initiative, but it is to rectify certain basic implementation shortcomings of VAT. So, this is an attempt to improve the existing VAT system further and also the tax system of India. VAT was introduced in the Indian taxation system from April 1, 2005 in an effort to address the with the earlier Sales Tax. The States have switched over from a multiple point Sales tax to a Value Added Tax (VAT) covering all transactions of sale of goods within the State. The essence of GST is to correct certain shortcomings of VAT like, the way it taxes inputs and outputs, bringing services under tax net, which is not possible under the VAT system. Hence, GST has been modelled as an extension of the current VAT that would make the tax system more comprehensive and smoother in its functioning.

Key Features of the Goods and Services Tax

1. The GST would be applicable to all transactions of goods and services made for a consideration except the exempted goods and services, goods which are outside the purview of GST.

2. GST will be paid to the accounts of the Centre (Central GST) and the States (State GST) separately, rates for which would be prescribed appropriately, reflecting revenue considerations and acceptability.

3. The GST will be levied on import of goods and services into the country

4. The rules for taking and utilization of credit for the Central GST and the State GST would be aligned.

The taxpayer would need to submit common format for periodical returns, to both the concerned Central and State GST authorities.

Dual GST Model

India is a federal country where both the Centre and the States have been assigned the powers to levy and collect taxes through appropriate legislation. It has been proposed that there would be a "Dual GST" model in India, taxes will be levied by both centre (Central GST) and state (State GST) on Goods and Services. Hence, a dual GST would be according to the Constitutional requirement of fiscal federalism.

Taxes to be Subsumed

Central tax and levies to be subsumed:

- 1) Central Excise Duty;
- 2) Additional Excise Duties;
- 3) The excise Duty levied under the Medicinal and Toiletries Preparation Act;
- 4) Service Tax;
- 5) Additional Customs Duty, commonly known as Countervailing Duty (CVD);
- 6) Special Additional Duty of Customs – 4% (SAD);
- 7) Surcharges; and
- 8) Cesses.

State taxes and levies to be subsumed:

- 1) VAT/Sales tax.
- 2) Entertainment tax (unless it is levied by the local bodies).
- 3) Luxury tax.

4) Taxes on lottery, betting and gambling.

Why is it Important?

- GST will widen the tax base, improve tax compliance, remove existing unhealthy competition among state

- GST would integrate the tax base and allow seamless flow of input tax credit across the value chain of goods and services which will lead to reduced cost of goods and services

III. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Some Economist say that GST in India would impact negatively on the real estate market. It would add up to 8 percent to the cost of new homes and reduce demand by about 12 percent.

2. Some Economist says that CGST, SGST and IGST are nothing but new names for Central Excise/Service Tax, VAT and CST.

Results and Discussion

- For business and industry
- Easy compliance
- Removal of cascading
- Improved competitiveness
- For Central and State Governments Simple

and easy to administer

- Better controls on leakage
- Consolidation of tax base
- Higher revenue efficiency
- For the consumer Single and Transparent tax
- Proportionate to the value of goods and services

Reduction of price

IV. CONCLUSION

GST is a single national uniform tax levied across India on all goods and services. In GST, all Indirect taxes such as excise duty, octroi, central sales tax (CST) and value-added tax (VAT) etc. will be subsumed under a single regime. Introduction of The Goods and Services Tax (GST) will be a significant step towards a comprehensive indirect tax reform in the country. Further it will also encourage an unbiased tax structure that is neutral to business processes and

geographical locations. Given the enormity of the implication of GST, it requires a consensus among all political parties and states. However the implementation of GST has been delayed several times on account of lack of consensus among the States and Centre on aspects relating to limiting fiscal autonomy of the States.

A BENEFIT STUDY OF PETROLEUM INCLUSION IN GST BILL

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Abstract

The paper aims at studying the inclusion of Petroleum under GST Bill in India. The paper begins with introduction and tries to highlight the objectives of the study. After a brief introduction on GST there will be a study on analysis of GST rates on petroleum product of the two countries, Australia and Canada. The third section broaches as to why GST should be levied on petroleum in India. Section four concludes the paper with a short summary. The secondary data collected is from year 2000 and the outcome of the paper is to include Petroleum in GST bill. The paper focuses on scholarly articles and current research so as to keep theory as close as possible to reality.

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods and Service Tax (GST) is a comprehensive tax levied on manufacturing, sales and consumption of goods and services at a national level. GST is a tax on goods and services with value addition at each stage having comprehensive and continuous chain of set-of benefits from the producer's/service provider's point up to the retailer's level where only the final consumer should bear the tax. In 2000, the discussion on GST Bill was started. During the Central Budget of 2007-08 it was announced to be introduced on April 1, 2010, but the Empowered Committee missed its deadline. In 2014, Constitution Amendment Bill introduced in the Lok Sabha and taken up for discussion. On 6 May, 2015, Lok Sabha passed the bill and it is introduced in Rajya Sabha with minor amendments and it is still

pending in Rajya Sabha for the winter session of the Parliament to be passed

GST is a simple, transparent and efficient system of indirect tax, introduced to over 140 countries across the globe. It was first introduced in France in 1954. Many countries have a unified GST system, whereas in our country a dual GST is proposed wherein a central goods and services tax (CGST) and a state goods and services tax (SGST) will be levied in the taxable value of the transaction. The CGST will subsume central excise duty (Cenvat), services tax, additional duties of customs at the Central Level and value-added tax, central sales tax, entertainment tax, luxury tax, octroi, lottery taxes, electricity duty, state surcharges related to supply of goods and services and purchase tax at the State Level.

GST has a vast impact on all the sectors such as Food and Industry, Housing and Construction Industry, FMCG, Rail Sector, Financial Services, Information Technology, MSME. We are only taking in consideration the impact of including petroleum under GST Bill.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pigeon (2005) studied "Federal taxes on Gases and Heating Fuel" and explored that Gases and Heating fuel are 'inelastic goods'. In Canada, at the Federal Level, the three taxes are levied on oil namely Royalty tax, Excise tax and Sales tax.. Unlike the Excise tax, GST/HST is calculated as a percentage and therefore increases or decreases with every increase and decrease in price and/or other

taxes. The paper suggests that at some point the tax increases may actually lead to reduced tax revenue due to the reduced consumption or production of goods that are highly taxed because higher tax leads to higher tax evasion.

Kumar (May 2014) studied "Goods and Service Tax in India-A way forward" and found that GST will be levied on all the goods and services except those exempted, dual model of GST will be there, which will include Central GST (CGST) collected by Center and State GST (SGST) collected by State. Central tax such as Central excise tax, additional excise duty, service tax, surcharges, countervailing duty, special additional duty of customs and state tax such as VAT/Sales tax, entertainment tax, luxury tax, taxes on lottery, betting and gambling, state cesses and entry tax not in lieu of Octroi to be subsumed. GST will not be charged on exports, it will only be charged on imports and Input Tax Credit will be available on the GST paid on import on goods and services. Some advantages of GST are higher revenue efficiency, easy compliance, and reduction of prices, improved competitiveness and better control on leakage.

Garg (2014) studied "Basic Concepts and Features of Good and Service Tax in India" and found that a tax is not a voluntary payment or donation, but an enforced contribution, exacted pursuant to legislative authority" and is any contribution imposed by government whether under the name of toll, tribute, impost, duty, custom, excise, subsidy, aid, supply, or other name. The challenges faced for the implementation of GST bill are with respect to tax threshold, nature of taxes, number of enactments of statutes, rates of taxation and tax

management and infrastructure whereas the opportunities are – end to cascading effect, growth of revenue in States and Union, reduces transaction costs and unnecessary wastages, one point single tax, avoids the multiplicity of taxes, reduces average tax

burden and reduces corruption. All sectors of economy whether the industry, business including Govt. departments and service sector shall have to bear impact of GST. All sections of economy viz., big, medium, small scale units, intermediaries, importers, exporters, traders, professionals and consumers shall be directly affected by GST.

An article "Petrol, Excise and GST" published by Parliament of Australia states that in Australia taxes account for approximately 34-39 percent of the retail price of petrol and consist of two components, excise and the Goods and Services Tax (GST). When propositioned about the possibility of removing GST from fuel, Mr. Michael Potter from the Australian Chamber of Commerce and Industry asserted that whilst this would possibly benefit consumers, it would provide no advantage to business. But the important problem with making fuel GST-free is that that would have absolutely no effect on the price of fuel purchased by business. Businesses can claim an input tax credit for all the GST, so effectively they get a 10 per cent reduction in the cost of fuel. If you made fuel GST-free, of course it would reduce the price for the final consumer but it would keep it exactly the same for business. Two distinct perspectives arise: one in which the Government should seek to lower petrol taxes to reduce the impact of escalating petrol prices; and another which argues that the Government should increase the level of excise applied to petrol to reduce Australia's dependence on petroleum.

In one of the articles published by The Hindu named "States want petroleum , alcohol out of GST" it stated that petroleum and alcohol will not be included under the proposed GST according to the statements given by Abdul Rahim, chairman of the empowered committee of state finance ministers. He said that "These are the main sources of income for the states and if they are not included in the GST the states will stand to lose a lot". If petroleum is

included then the center is ready to provide Rupees Nine thousand crore to the states as a compensation.

III. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Petroleum products form the major crunch of the revenue for the country. Also the Government of India is mainly focused on the GDP growth of our economy. Therefore, inclusion of petroleum in GST Bill has a high significance. Canada and Australia are the two economies who have had petroleum under their indirect taxes for more than a decade. With reference to the same, the benefits of including petroleum in GST in the two countries namely Canada and Australia are studied. Hence this paper has made an attempt to study the benefits of the same in Indian context.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the effect of including petroleum in the GST fold by drawing analysis of two countries, Australia and Canada charging GST on petroleum.
2. To highlight the importance of including petroleum in GST of India.
3. To bring out the benefits obtained by various industry sectors due to the inclusion of petroleum in GST.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Type of Study

The research paper is an exploratory study keeping in view the needs of the objective, because GST is still in the genesis form in India. It is yet to be passed by the Government of India. Various Government bodies are still exploring the feasibility, viability and the administrative impact of GST on the Government Administrative structure. To support the study, various secondary data from other countries and bodies is taken for supporting the exploratory data.

As GST is not implemented in India, there is no accurate data available on the same. Hence, the study relies on the secondary data mainly from the sources

like Parliament of Australia, articles published on newspapers, expert's opinion and views of Government Ministers.

VI. LIMITATIONS

Currently, GST in India does not include Petroleum products whereas countries such as Australia and Canada include such products under GST. Therefore, due to unavailability of statistical information of GST in India, the views expressed are subject to change.

Due to the time constraints, the research is limited to descriptive study.

Discussions

Analyzing GST Rates levied on Petroleum Products in Australia and Canada

Australia

The New Tax System came into effect on 1 July 2000 in Australia. The GST replaced the inefficient wholesales taxes and state transaction taxes and personal income taxes were substantially reduced. Taxes account for approximately 34-39 percent of the retail price of petrol and consist of two components, excise and the Goods and Services tax (GST). Excise is capped at 38.143 cents per litre (cpl) and is levied the corresponding customs duty which is levied on imported petrol. GST is charged at the standard rate of 10 percent of the total purchase price.

Some of the benefits due to the inclusion of petroleum in GST Australia received are:-

- More efficient sources of revenue were generated through GST that lead to increased growth and higher living standards.
- Government revenue coming from personal taxation decreased and inflation was pushed down.
- Since, petroleum is a scarce resource; the increase rate of GST on petroleum has helped reduce the consumption of petroleum.

Canada

There are three taxes in Canada on Petroleum oil. First is Royalty tax levied on the companies that dig

or pump oil out of the ground, it is structured such that it increases from 1-5% of gross revenue over the first six years of production or until the initial investment have been recovered, after that the royalty is 30 percent of the net cash flows and 5 percent of gross revenue. Second is Excise tax which is calculated on volumes and quantities of energy, third is Sales tax that is calculated on values. Sales tax includes Goods and Service tax and Harmonized Sales tax. Harmonized Sales tax is a combination of the Goods and Service tax and Provincial Sales tax, they are levied after the manufacturers and retailers have priced the cost and profit margins and after the federal and provincial government have added excise taxes. The rate of GST and HST levied is 7 and 15 percent respectively.

In Canada some of the benefits due to the inclusion of petroleum in GST received are:-

The increased rate on GST reduced the consumption rate of petroleum and made it last long.

Comments

The implementation of petroleum in GST has highly benefited the two countries in terms of increased revenue, high standards of living, saving scarce resource and using the revenue obtained to provide funds for other development activities. India being a highly populated nation the consumption of petroleum product is very high. Thus, the implementation of GST rates on petroleum can help reduce its consumption level and make it last long. As the GDP of the two countries increased by including petroleum under the GST similarly, this inclusion can also help our country in increasing the GDP growth rate which is one of the stated objectives of GST.

Importance of including Petroleum in GST Bill in India

The Indian oil and gas sector is the largest revenue earner for the Central and State Governments. In 2010-2011, the revenue generated was 27.8 percent of the total indirect tax collected by

both the Governments. Of this, the five petroleum products- Crude Oil, Diesel, Petrol, Aviation Turbine Fuel and Natural Gas (to be excluded from GST) alone makes upto 96 percent of revenue. If these products are not included in GST, 27 percent (a little less than one-third) of all indirect taxes will remain excluded from GST. In this case GST will cover only two-third of all taxable revenues. Surely this would not be enough to meet some of the stated objectives of GST, which is to boost the GDP growth of the country and to make Indian Goods

Services internationally competitive. Economists and industrialists suggest that only the implementation of GST will increase the GDP rate of India by 1-1.5 percent. Thus with the focus on GDP growth, inclusion of Petroleum Products under the Bill would be beneficial for the nation's economy.

Secondly, in case of "Oil Linked Products" if the central government includes all the petroleum products under the ambit of GST which in turn would eliminate double taxation it would likely create a cost advantage of about 15-20 percent for industries purchasing bulk fuel, petroleum products like lubricants.

Another undesirable impact of exclusion of petroleum products is the loss of credit on goods and services covered by GST received and used to produce non- GST products. For instance, in case of oil exploration and production industries who already have the burden of excise, VAT and service tax on capital goods will suffer more if the credit is not available on crude oil/natural gas. It is, therefore, imperative that the Parliamentary Standing Committee recommends amendments to the Bill for a holistic GST covering all goods and services in the interest of all stakeholders, without excluding petroleum products.

Comments

By the above study of the objective it is evident that the inclusion of petroleum in GST is highly

advantageous for increasing revenue, improving growth of the economy, eliminating double taxation and creating a cost advantage for industries linked to the oil production and consumption.

Benefits on various industry sectors on inclusion of petroleum in GST

- Industries purchasing bulk fuel petroleum products like Lubricants would be eliminated from double taxation. It would create a tax advantage of 15-20 percent.

- Oil exploration and production industries will be provided with credit on crude oil or natural gas.

- Transport service industries will see a major impact on its Cash flow. The liability to pay tax will shift from recipient of service from provider of service.

- The inclusion of petroleum tax would provide input tax credit to transportation sector.

Comments

It is prudent from the above that sectors which are directly or indirectly linked with oil products will see a major change in its cash flows. The process of double taxation will be eliminated, input tax credit will be provided and it will create a cost advantage for the above mentioned sectors leading to better development of nation.

VII. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- Since the petroleum and other related products are excluded from GST, it ceases from functioning as a 'national tax'

- Petroleum products including Crude Oil, Diesel, Aviation Turbine Fuel, Natural Gas will continue to be taxed under excise duty and VAT during the initial few years of GST implementation. This will prevail until the states reach comfortable revenue levels.

- In India, 50 percent of the revenue is earned by States from indirect taxes charged on Petroleum and other related products. Hence, including

Petroleum products under GST Bill has increased the fear of loss of revenue for the states. This is one of the reason due to which GST is not levied on Petroleum Products.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

GST will integrate the Indian market and stimulate economic activities, potentially leading to an increase in GDP growth. As petroleum is one of the product that involves various goods and services from stages such as exploration, production, refining etc, the input tax credit from which could be utilized under the GST. This would lead to substantial price advantage for petroleum products which is critical since it impacts everyday life. Thus inclusion of petroleum products under the GST Bill will be a welcoming change for the developing economy of our Country.

Like a coin has two sides similarly petrol inclusion under the GST Bill has its own prospects. The system of including petroleum under GST though has proven positive in the economies of Australia and Canada, the same impact in India is yet to be explored. This is due to the large size of population, administrative complexities in the working of the Indian Government, policies and legal procedures and most importantly the attitude of politicians..

A STUDY ON GST AND ITS IMPACT ON GOVERNMENT AND RETAIL SECTOR – AN ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The government has been at the receiving end of the revenue and the retail sector will witness a sea of change with the invent of GST. This forms the core area in this research as it gives a bird's eye view of the entire supply chain related to GST. This paper aims at understanding the impact of GST on the different sectors of the economy wherein the central objective is to throw light on three main aspects to give an overview of the provisions of GST, to analyze the impact of GST on retail sector and to study the impact of GST on government revenues. The ideology behind incorporating this transformation is to replace the existing taxes – VAT, service tax, CENVAT, excise duty to adopt a uniform rate structure on goods and services through GST.gov – revenue, retailers – lesser prices of the final commodity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tax is a very important source of revenue to the government as it spends its revenue in administrating the country, developing the country's infrastructure and looking after the nation's well-being. India being a developing nation, has been striving to fulfill the obligations of a Welfare state with its limited resources. The government's primary sources of revenue are direct and indirect taxes. Central excise on goods manufactured or produced in India and customs duties on goods imported constitute the two

major sources of indirect tax. However, revenue from customs and excise has been declining due to World Trade Commitments and rationalization of commodity duties. The tax structure has undergone tremendous changes over the years with the key objective of increasing the tax base and reducing the tax rate. However, achieving this objective to its fullest has not been possible. The service sector has been witnessing a phenomenal growth all over the world although it may vary in the degree and magnitude among the countries. The growth of this can be gauged by the significant contributions from the service sector to GDP, thereby pushing back the traditional contributors like agriculturalists and manufacturing sector.

In the present day, the services are so widespread that they encompass a plethora of activities right from professional services to retail, wholesale, hospitality, research etc. Service sector is occupying the center stage in the economy so much so that in the contemporary world it is synonymous with the advancement of the economy. It is needless to say that exclusion of the service sector from indirect taxes will result in loss of considerable potential revenue.

Many new concepts and trends have taken place in the sphere of Indirect taxes, one such concept that is undergoing a lot of contemplation by the government and the empowered committee and

representatives working on behalf of the government for its successful implementation is to introduce GST in India as well as gaining an insight on its impact.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

FICCI's paper aims at discussing how the various aspects of GST should be considered by the empowered committee, government bodies and authorities at various levels before its implementation so as to make it business friendly and a win-win situation for everyone. For GST to be successful it is imperative for all of them to reach a consensus on the underlying proposals.¹

Girish Garg states that moving towards GST is the next most logical step that India should adopt. He believes that GST will integrate the state economies and create a robust nation. His studies reveal that the tax burden will be equally divided amongst manufacturing and service sectors by lowering the tax rates and increasing the tax base.²

The studies conducted by Nitin Kumar talks about how the various indirect taxes have to be subsumed into a single tax regime. With the advent of GST in India it is certain that it will bring about transparency, efficiency and uniformity in tax structure thereby reducing economic distortions.³

Neha & Manpreet Sharma's paper lays an emphasis on how GST reduces the cascading effect of tax structures and distortion. Introduction of GST will only be a boon to the economy as it will act as a catalyst in developing industries and various other sectors.⁴

According to Ehtisham Ahmad and Satya Poddar, GST has a likely potential to be the single most significant initiative in the fiscal history of India as it paves way for modernization in the tax regime by simplifying the tax structures and promoting transparency along with enhancing voluntary compliance.

III. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Government of India is striving to bring in a uniform tax structure in India by introducing GST which will reduce the incidents of double taxation.

Since introduction of GST will increase revenue for government and reduce the incidents of taxation for retailers, this study concentrates on an overview of GST and impact of GST on the government and retailers.

Objectives

1. To give an overview of the provisions of GST.
2. To analyze the impact of GST on retail sector
3. To study the impact of GST on government revenues.

Scope of Study

This concept paper suggests the reasons for introducing GST in India and identifies the impact it has on the government's revenue and the retailers, if a comprehensive GST is implemented in India.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sources of Data: The source(s) of data used for this research paper is Secondary Data.

Secondary Data includes the highlights and discussions on the provisions of GST.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The data analysis and interpretation is done in three parts. They are as follows:

Part I: This section analyzes the factors that have contributed to the advent of GST.

Part II: This section studies how new factors affect the Government's revenues.

Part III: In this section, an attempt has been made to find out those factors that will contribute to the growth of the Retail Sector.

VI. FEATURES OF THE GST MODEL

The primary feature of GST is to adopt a comprehensive tax base i.e. to have a single rate on all goods and services.

GST will have dual components: one levied by the Centre (CGST) and the other levied by the States (SGST).

CGST and SGST would be applicable to all transaction of goods and services except the exempted goods and services.

The CGST and SGST are to be paid separately to the Centre and State's respective accounts.

The essence of GST is not just the combination of VAT plus service tax but an advancement of the previous tax system.

Inference: From the overview it can be inferred that with the genesis of GST, it will have a positive stimulus on the economy as it will bring about uniformity in the tax structure and how it can contribute to attaining a double digit GDP figure and curb distortions.

Part II: Impact of GST on Government Revenue

The archaic tax structure has witnessed opportunity cost loss on the revenues it could have earned one such example is VAT. Although VAT has been successful there have been shortcomings in the VAT structure at both Centre and State Level.

When GST is introduced the simple transparent and stable tax system is sure to be a boon to the Union Government.

Some States fear how the GST Model will unfold because if the uniform tax rates are lower than the existing rates it will dent collections. However the Central Government has said that it will compensate States for the potential revenue loss. P.Chidambaram has set aside Rs.9000 crores towards the first installment of the balance of CST compensation. Also, instead of an earlier proposal of a uniform GST rate across the country, the Union Government has agreed to have a floor rate of taxation with a narrow band.

CRISIL said "The government has to implement structural tax reforms such as the goods and services tax (GST), which will lift the government's tax

revenues, lower the cost of conducting business and boosts growth". The declining trend of the Centre's debt ratio after fiscal 2009 has been driven more by high inflation rather than lower fiscal deficit or faster GDP growth. "With inflation expected to moderate, a strong commitment to fiscal consolidation is an imperative to lower the country's debt-to-GDP ratio".

According to a report by National Council of Applied Economic Research, GST is expected to increase economic growth between 0.9% - 1.7%. Exports are expected to increase between 3.2% - 6.3%. From the above it can be deduced that the State Government must take a leap of faith and consent with the Union's decision towards the implementation of GST as they are backed by a great degree of assurance with regards to recouping losses.

Hence it is evident that GST would simplify India's tax structure, broaden tax base and create a common market across States. This will lead to increased tax compliance and increase India's tax-to-GDP ratio.

Inference: As the government is at the receiving end of revenue, it is necessary for the government to adopt a tax structure without loopholes and GST being a game changer if implemented aims to eliminate the loopholes in the area of indirect tax .

Part III: Impact of GST on Retail Sector

The retail sector in India has grown leaps and bounds over the years. India has witnessed a transformation from a multitude of unorganized family owned businesses to organized modern retailing.

India's retail sector accounts for 22% of the country's GDP and contributes to 8% of total employment.

The key agent of change that GST would bring about in the retail spectrum is, that the services would be eligible for set-off against taxes on goods. This is definitely a positive sign to the retailers as the VAT structure resulted in compliance issues and uniformity

of VAT laws resulted in additional cost burden to the retailers.

The previous tax structure was very ambiguous with regards to quantum of input service tax credit as it recognized the manufacturers and not service

providers. GST is expected to remove this anomaly, as it would result in a shift to sale of goods from manufacture of goods resulting in redesign of input tax credit. The below illustration explains how GST will benefit the retailers and the ultimate consumers.

Table No:1

Stage of supply chain	Purchase value of Input	Value addition	Value at next stage	Rate of GST	GST on output	Input	Net GST= GST
						Tax	on output -
						credit	Input tax credit
Manufacturer	100	30	130	10%	13	10	13-10 = 3
Whole seller	130	20	150	10%	15	13	15-13 = 2
Retailer	150	10	160	10%	16	15	16-15 = 1

Source: goods and service tax.com

From the above table it is understood that at every stage tax has to be paid thereby increasing the price of the goods. With GST, this tax burden will come down the retailers will pass on the benefit of the reduced tax incidence to their consumers thereby reducing the prices of goods sold.

One area that requires prime focus with regards to retail sector is MRP based valuations which were litigated under customs and central excise laws. The GST regime must have a sound mechanism in place to combat such issues.

Inference: In the recent past, Indian consumers have always witnessed hikes in the prices. Reduction in the prices will be a welcome new phenomenon for them. With GST coming into effect, their purchases will cost them less and hence they will be willing to shop more. More shopping would mean more revenue for retailers.

VII. CONCLUSION

After having referred to the various resources mentioned in the literature review and other sources, we can say that GST is a grand bargain and is going to be a game changer for India. One can be certain that GST is going to have a ratified impact on the Government's revenues. The retail sector should proactively be prepared to migrate from the old model to the new model to ensure smooth operations

under this new regime. This model will be flawless, provided GST is followed thoroughly without falling back on the old forms of taxation.

GST AND ITS IMPACT ON TAX BURDEN

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Abstract

This paper studies the concept of Goods and Service tax, and its implications on tax burden at different levels and various sectors in the economy. An idea which was initiated in the year 2000 now making steady progress to almost being implemented, the Goods and service tax or GST bill is a transparent bill ,a Value Added Tax that will substitute all indirect taxes and bring uniformity amongst the tax levied on goods and services. In India indirect taxes go up to 28.2 to 30.8 per cent, where as the average GST rate globally is close to 16.4 per cent, this will beg the question on how far the tax burden will rise or drop and on whom. A study on the various sectors in the economy show that GST seems to be more favourable for the nation, it is stated that the country will gain up to 15 billion dollars in a year. This is because GST will promote more exports, create more employment opportunities and boost growth it will divide the burden of tax between goods and services. A dual GST plan is to be implemented in India i.e. State goods and service tax and Central goods and service tax, GST rate is expected to be about 10 per cent on services and 20 per cent on indirect tax of most goods. The new deadline for the bill is now set at April 1st 2016.However, there will always be a few repercussions on all changes, GST might not be beneficial to everyone in the nation, some states that are majorly dependent on a particular good or service might face difficulties in sharing its revenue with the government, also a uniform tax rate means no distinction between the economically weak and well off in the society. The government can still take

various measures to keep these challenges in control. Some experts argue that the exclusion of few products such as alcohol, tobacco and petroleum products may result in loss of revenue as the state can still enforce the local tax rates it determines. An objective view point of the topic is presented by an expert's opinion on the matter in which it explains the benefits GST can bring and thoughts on why implementation is being delayed, also a study on different sectors gives us the framework on how these sectors must adapt to the new reform and can benefit greatly from it. Finally, a deliberation on the benefits the Goods and Service Tax bill will carry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods and service tax is an indirect tax imposed on most goods and services, its objective is to eliminate taxes levied separately on goods and services and to consolidate under a single domain for both goods and services. It's a Value Added Tax payable at the final point of consumption.

A dual GST is planned to be implemented in India:

- State goods and services tax (SGST)
- Central goods and services tax (CGST)

GST will combine Central excise, Additional excise, Service tax, State VAT and entrainment tax all under one banner.

Table No: 1: Rates of GST

Country	Rate of GST
Australia	10 %
France	19.6%
Canada	5%
Germany	19%
Japan	5%
Singapore	7%
Sweden	25%
New Zealand	15%

In India the government proposed the GST rate at 27% which is well above the global average of 16.4% for similar taxes. At present, 10% is levied on services and the indirect tax on most goods is around 20%.

Items such as alcohol, tobacco, petroleum products are not included under GST.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mukhopabhyay, (2015), How GST will benefit manufactures and traders, GST will benefit the manufactures the most as they will have no entry tax, there will have a common market and central excise tariff will disappear. The abolition of entry tax will be a great boon for the movement of goods transport, giving relief to input duty will be more comprehensive GST is implemented this is termed as zero rating. The GST regime will make it one uniform tax which will make rate of duties same all over India

Rumani Saikia Phukan, (2015), what is GST: How will in change India? GST would no doubt do well for the economy in various ways one of the major ones being a reduction of the tax burdens for manufactures and various other sectors in the

economy. GST will help build a corruption free tax administration and will avoid many hidden tax issues. Tax will be levied and collected once and for all rather than at different points of manufacturing to consumption, consumers will see a fall in prices and lower prices will mean more consumption and more production

Times, (2015) GST to reduce tax burden: “The global average of GST rate is 16.4 per cent but in India, indirect taxes are as high as 28.2 to 30.8 per cent. The GST will help in decreasing the tax burden on the consumers”, said an RBI board member indirect tax amounts to almost 28 per cent in our country; hence the implementation of the GST bill would absolutely reduce this by almost 12 per cent. It will replace an array of indirect taxes. States such as Punjab, Haryana and Maharashtra would lose their purchase tax levied on food, grains, oils etc

Statement of the problem

The study looks into the impact of the GST bill on different sectors of the economy as the tax burden would vary depending on who it's levied. This study would benefit the various sectors and sections of the business community to understand the intricacies of GST and its nuances that would affect their business plan. Hence these people can benefit from this study by taking appropriate measures.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the impact GST will have on the tax burden on individuals.
2. To highlight the benefits GST on different sectors of the market Scope of the study

The study of the paper will give an insight about the benefits of the GST bill amongst different sectors in the country, it studies the comparison of now and when GST will be implemented. GST would bring about uniformity with the tax rates and will reduce a lot of complications with regards to indirect tax.

Goods and Services tax would definitely be beneficial for the major part of the economy.

Research Methodology

- The research method used is both primary and secondary data from various websites and published articles.

- Interview conducted with an income tax officer for an expert's opinion on the matter.

Limitation of the study

- Time constraint on the research, hence city limited was limited to Bangalore.

- Most data found was speculatively exploratory in nature since the bill is yet to be passed in the GOI.

- Final conclusions may differ on different perceptions.

Discussions:

Why GST?

- Uniformity, the main aim of GST is to eliminate all other indirect taxes and to bring it under a single, unified market that will benefit both corporate and the economy.

- GST will be paid at the final point of consumption and not at every stage; this will promote a stronger economy and will bring about a common national market.

- If GST were to be implemented it can alter the tax administration

- GST is expected to increase economic growth between 0.9 to 1.7 per cent

- The current rate of indirect taxes levied in India is about 20 per cent GST is expected to be around 15 per cent in the first year and eventually come down to 12 per cent in the second year

- GST will reduce production costs hence making exporters more competitive.(Economic Time, 2015)

Demerits of GST

The main aim of GST is to create a uniform market however due to exclusion of some goods like

tobacco, alcohol and petroleum products it might be a hurdle for the government.

- For states like Jharkhand who are more dependent on products rather than services they will be sharing their revenues with the government, also they might not have adequate services to compensate for their loss in revenue

- Some States also feel that a uniform tax rate will create a dent in their collections

- The blunt tax would penalise everyone making no differentiation between the rich and the poor

- The most affected will be the consumers as they will have to pay tax at the final point of consumption, which means there may not be a difference between the necessities such as food, clothing and medicines and luxuries

- There will be no distinction between the rich and the poor which may affect the equity of society(Goel, 2015)

Merits of GST

- There might be no distinction between necessities and luxuries; fortunately GST can be progressive if the government taxes more on luxuries and less on necessities, the government can also lend a helping hand to those financially needy citizens.

- Separate taxes is a hassle for the government and the producers it involves division of transactions values into value of goods and services for taxation leading to greater complications, GST will be able to solve this issue and integrate the tax giving an equal split between manufacturing and services

- GST will see to it that there is no hidden cost hence making the cost of doing business lower, this will ensure that export being more competitive.

- Both the State GST and the Central GST will be charged on manufacturing cost and will be collected on the point of sales, this would mean that prices will come down for the citizens and companies will benefit as consumption will increase.

- Doing business will be much easier as multiple taxes such as octroi, central sales, entry tax will be consolidated into one, which is perhaps the greatest benefit for manufactures as there will be hidden taxation involved.

Tax Burden- Less with GST?

Looking at the various aspects of GST we can only help but imagine what benefits or repercussion it might have on the burden of tax be it at any stage i.e. the producer, retailer or consumer, the bill seems to be leaning more in favour of the fact that this is beneficial for the country and apart from various other benefits it looks like the reduction on tax burden would be a major one.

GST on Consumers

We pay entertainment tax for watching a movie, a VAT when purchasing a good and so on and so forth as of today there are some taxes levied by the central and some by the state a uniform tax rate would certainly make things easier according to Indira Rajaraman GST will result in a lesser tax burden on consumers, besides boosting the country's economic growth.

"The global average of GST rate is 16.4 per cent but in India, indirect taxes are as high as 28.2 to 30.8 per cent. The GST will help in decreasing the tax burden on the consumers", Indira Rajaraman (RBI board member) however a different point of view can be studied. As the tax is collected only at the final point of consumption the supplier will be able to offset the levy through a tax credit mechanism, since it's an indirect tax the ultimate burden will be borne by the consumer himself.

GST on Manufactures

Manufactures will be able to claim more tax credit on the GST regime, let's assume that a manufacturer makes a sale of 65 lakhs and the tax credit available to him is 25 lakhs (VAT) which means he will have to pay a sum total of 40 lakhs to the government under the current tax regime. The

same scenario under the GST regime would look like differently apart from the 25 lakh VAT credit available to him he can also credit on CST of 10 lakhs and on entry tax of 5 lakhs which means his net tax payable will amount up to just 15 lakhs, here we can see that the producers has saved up to almost 25 lakhs. The GST hence reduces tax burden on producers.

GST on service sector

The usual service tax rate on supply was close to 12% to 14% Thus cumulatively any tax above the 14% mark will act as a deterrent for the industry due to a rate hike in providing services. With the average rate suggestions by Kelkar committee being RNR 27% to a more optimistic assumption of RNR 18% as per media reports, all the assumptions certainly seem to indicate an uphill rate hike. The services providers will have to take a conscious call on whether to assume the additional cost through their margins or raise the cumulative price of their services.

GST on trading sector

According to DNA,2015 the Confederation of All India Traders (CAIT) has called upon the Prime Minister to convene a special session of Parliament soon to pass the deadlocked GST Bill and has asked parties not to play a "political innings" on the issue'.

GST will help the trading communities get rid of multiple taxes and tremendous amount of paper work. As of now goods are being sold within the state so as to avoid paying CST which is not credited in the course of trading. Good quality products being manufactured in one part of the country will find more market in the farthest part of the country because there will be no CST and no entry tax, hence in the absence of CST and entry tax a common market will be created.

III. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of GST is to make the current taxation system more comprehensive, efficient, effective, and transparent and business friendly. As a

developing country, it is important for India to review its fiscal policy continuously. The Indian government should always make sure sufficient revenues are raised for the country with minimum impacts on people and resources, while at the same time improve the standards of living of poor people. Moreover, the government should always seek for ways to lower poverty level in India, thus a more equitable society can be achieved. The Indian government and the people in the country have to get ready for the tax reform.

Various sectors in the economy also have a lot to benefit from GST, sectors like IT and service will be able to claim tax exemptions and a lot the other taxes such as CST for traders can be avoided, this will be a big relief on such sectors since the an enormous amount of the tax burden will reduce and in the long run they can lower the prices of their commodities which will be beneficial for the consumers.

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A STUDY ON IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST) ON REVENUE OF THE STATE

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Abstract

The study is to show the clear picture about GST and its mechanism and its impression on state's revenue in the country.. GST is not yet been introduced. And hence there is a dilemma in the minds of the consumer, retailer, other parties involved in supply chain about the tax burden. The state government's dilemma is about its impact on the revenue due to the change in the tax structure. The dual system of GST mechanism will help states generate more revenue than it was generating earlier with VAT. The darker side of GST as a threat to state's revenue that is subsumption of various indirect taxes turned out to be major reason for the fear of states about their revenue generation. The government assures the states about the compensation for the loss of revenue but when we see a similar situation accured in the history of finance of India that the government did not release enough funds to compensate for the loss suffered by the states due to Central sales tax (CST). This research will provide valuable information regarding GST and its role in revenue generation; it also highlights the importance of implementation of dual system of GST. Our finding throws light on how it can reduce the consumption of undesirable goods by proposing to introduce higher GST on goods like alcohol cigarette. This also emphasis on the opportunities that GST allows in administering tax compliance efficiently

and how is a boon for every party involved and its blunt sides as well.

I. INTRODUCTION

The idea of GST was initiated under the leadership of Atal Bihari Vajpayee in the year 2000. The government of India has introduced constitutional amendment bill for GST in lok sabha. Report of GST was prepared in the meeting of empowered committee on 20th of November 2007, after certain modifications the final version was prepared and sent to the government of India on 30th Of April 2008. It was decided to be introduced from 1st of April 2010 but due to the fear of loss of revenue to states, and they wrote to finance committee that they were not ready to introduce GST and this is the reason behind the delay. Bill was introduced in the lok sabha by Arun Jaitley the present finance minister and was published on 19th of December 2014.

Goods and service tax is a value added tax and is supposed to absorb most of the indirect taxes like octroi, central sales tax, state level sales tax, excise duty, service tax etc at state level and federal government. It is a tax that is paid by the final consumer while the retailer will be getting credit of the tax that he has paid while buying goods for the retailing. Every party involved in the chain of supplying goods or services to the end consumers will be taxed.

India has a sales tax regime at state level and excise duty regime at federal level to a value added tax separately for both state sales tax and federal excise duty few years back. GST will unify and integrate these tax reforms to a common base. This tax regime aims to convert the country into an integrated market by eliminating various taxes and replacing them with one tax.

GST has dual structure that is central component levied and collected as the central goods and service tax (CGST) and service taxes on goods and services that move from one state to another is state goods and service tax (SGST). Once the GST is introduced in states the states complain about the loss of revenue, so there are provisions made to compensate for it. The compensation may extend upto 5 years. The third main component of GST is dual GST and that is the expected model of GST in India.

GST is levied at the rate of 10% it is ultimately paid by the end users of goods and services. Certain types of supplies are GST free like fresh foods and medical supplies. Certain real estate sales are subjected to GST that is sale of commercial property. Producers of product or service pay tax on the materials required for production and they paid tax is set off when the consumer pays tax on the purchased goods.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jaitley in 2015 stated that that “the tax rates during GST regime will be closely aligned to the revenue neutral rates (RNR) of the centre and the state, revenues of the centre and the state governments will not be impacted in the long run.”

According to MBA RENDEZVOUS empowering MBA aspirants in 2014, the article mainly focuses on the clarity of GST concept as in when it was stated, when it was propose, by whom was it introduced and the current status of the bill. It also talks about the dual structure of the GST and

making the country into unified market by replacing various indirect taxes with one tax.

It emphasizes on the compensation of revenue loss for states. The article infers with its study that reduction in profits of service sector will lead to unemployment and increase the prices that will add up to the general inflation and impacting consumers of their buying capacity.

As reported by state finance ministers' in 2009 the structure of VAT is being explained and is giving a clear understanding about GST. The article highlights on the amendments of GST, the various indirect taxes subsumed, and products that are exempted under GST.

S.Krishnamurthy, adjunct faculty throws light on how GST is beneficial to common man and its cascading effects and the fear of states on loss of their revenue. It also highlights the fear of states in losing their revenue and concludes introduction GST is a wise decision taken.

Singh in the year 2013 depicts that states' have opportunities to generate revenue when GST is introduced that is by taxing even the service sectors which majorly contribute towards our nations GDP that is 57% and how dual taxation will generate revenue to states.

Statement of the problem

GST is a new tax regime in Indian indirect tax which will bring about change in the tax structure, which will affect the revenue of the states in the country. Therefore, this discussion throws light on why GST should be implemented? Will implementation of GST favor state's revenue or adversely effect, as various indirect taxes will be subsumed with the implementation of GST.

Objectives

1. To enlighten about the features of GST.
2. To analyze the impact of GST state's revenue.

Research Methodology

This paper is a descriptive study and an explorative study with the help of secondary data that is inclusive of articles and use of various professionals on GST and its impact on state's revenue.

Discussion

Salient features of GST

- GST subsumes various indirect taxes they are: At federal level, CENVAT, service tax,

Central excise duty etc. State taxes are state VAT, state sales tax, Luxury tax, taxes on lottery and tax on advertisement.

GST is proposed to be implemented on all goods and services. There are a few exemptions they are: Alcoholic liquor for human consumption. GST council is planning to revisit, whether GST should be extended for petroleum crude, high speed diesel, natural gas and aviation turbine.

- Center and state should maintain separate accounts.

- As center and state maintains two different accounts, input tax credit of center should be used against centre for payments. Similarly it is applicable incase of states.

- Cross utilization of funds is not allowed except in case of inter state supply.

- Each tax payer would be given a PAN linked tax payer identification number of 13 or 15 digits; this is linked with prevailing PAN based system of income tax.

If GST is levied at 10% which means the GST is to be added to the exclusive price of goods and services. Suppose the price of the product is inclusive of GST then the GST is equal to the 1/11th of the total which means the GST exclusive price is 10/11th of the total. For example: If the GST inclusive price of a product is Rs.110 then the GST would be Rs.10. The GST exclusive price of the product in this situation is Rs.100.

As per the passed bill of GST, it states that GST will subsume various other indirect taxes and it reduces the tax burden, as the parties' end up paying one tax. It is beneficial to the consumers and the parties in the supply chain. But when we see its impact on state revenue many states fear that they will lose revenue as entry tax or octroi is absorbed but the bill assures that if any losses incurred by states will be compensated for the first five years but some states want to be compensated for ten years. States have been assured 100% compensation for their losses, first three years, and 75% in the fourth year and 50% in the fifth year. The finance ministry expects that not all states will need compensation for five years, particularly consuming states may see their revenue increase with the implementation of GST. The council initially proposed to have 27% as GST rate in India but Arun Jaitley mentioned that it would be very high and proposed 18%.

GST is an important source of revenue for the government with the amount of GST collected government can manage the country more effectively. For example: the government can use the GST collected to build infrastructures like schools and hospitals.

The above justification clearly depicts GST, its salient features, important amendments and mechanism of GST model.

Analysis Of Gst's Impact On State's Revenue Gst as Boon for State's Revenue

GST can be used as a tool to curb the over consumption of undesirable goods. Government can set high GST for cigarette and alcoholic products. In economic terms tax varies for different products and services to reduce societies welfare, dead weight loss due to the over consumption of undesirable goods that imposes negative externality. As dual system of GST is proposed to introduce, the states will be levying their own GST apart from central GST and that revenue will be directly deposited to their own

treasury. Independence required by the states in the federal level will be maintained. Under GST regime states will have broader tax base. Central government has power to tax goods and services upto their production stage while state government are empowered for collecting sales tax for the goods that are being sold in their region. This system reduces litigation and evasion of tax.

Imported goods are charged with customs duty at the federal level and sales tax at state level. GST will enable states to tax not only on goods but also on services and imports and the federal government has planned to introduce a constitutional amendment to enable states with a power to levy VAT on services and central government to levy tax on sales. This wider tax base is benefit to states. As we know VAT under GST is a tax on value added to the product upto production stage and it will also cover all ancillary services and it will help the product reach its ultimate users and hence tax base is much higher under VAT even if we take pure service sector separately.

As per the above mentioned justification tax will progress and improves adequacy. Both centre and states would have simultaneous jurisdiction on the entire value chain and the tax base is common. Under this dual system of GST tax payers file returns twice that are one with centre and other with state. This will improve the submission of tax and ultimately effecting the improvement in the revenue of the state.

This will make the tax structure simple and maintenance of tax will be much easier than before, it will reduce paper work and human intervention. The cost of collecting tax will be comparatively less. GST is linked with income tax this makes the submission of tax better, this will also take into consideration the sector that is not filing tax, leading to enhancing the revenue of state which will consider unregistered production units cruel and unpredictable conditions. In case of loss suffered by state government, it has set aside Rs. 50,000 crore for compensation as a loss

proof jackets on states so that they are not exposed to loss of revenue.

If GST is implemented state revenue increases as justified above and leads to the increase in economic growth from 0.9 within 1.7%. Exports might increase from 3.2% to 6.3%, when exports increase the revenue generated out of exports to states due to GST increases.

GST as a threat to state's revenue

With the implementation of GST various other indirect taxes like octroi or entry tax will be eliminated and the revenue that the state earns from this source will also be eliminated. As the federal government assured about the compensation for losses to states upto five years, but it cannot compensate forever. Rs 50,000 crore is been set aside to compensate for loss. But without the implementation of GST there would be comparatively less loss of revenue and this set aside amount could be used for the any other development of the states.

According to the 2013-14 budget our former finance minister Mr. P. Chidambaram has set aside 9300 crore for CST compensation but could only release 1940 crore and states hardly had compensation funds, keeping this in mind there is no assurance that the federal government will have enough funds to compensate for five years and further more for extended years if requested by states.

The state government will have to approach the federal government for funds. CST was earlier reduced from 4% to 2% and it will be finally revoked due to the implementation of GST which will lead to the loss of revenue to the states. This is one of the fears of states to accept GST. Since the states revenue is majorly comprised of revenue from indirect taxes and any change in the tax structure will adversely affect the revenue of the state.

GST will have two or three levels of tax rates and that will be shared between the centre and the state with certain percentage and the states cannot

change the rates at their will as the rates are collectively decided. As stated earlier every under federal level GST the state should approach the centre to have funds for development, this becomes a threat to richer states that their revenue is being released to poor states to meet their expense on equitable distribution basis. This will put off the fire in states to generate more revenue. GST is favorable to a common man as it reduces the tax burden this has an inverse effect on the loss suffered by states due to change in the tax structure. GST will be progressive only if the government introduces more tax on luxurious products and less on necessities but the whole concept of GST is having single tax or unified tax on a common base. This becomes a hindrance for GST to progress.

The above analysis highlights the positive impact on State's Revenue increasing the GDP in the long run. It also shows the negligible drawbacks of GST which can be rectified with efficient implementation in both state and centre.

III. CONCLUSION

As per the study it is clear that change in the tax structure due to the implementation of GST has both complications and also benefits to the state for its revenue. The GST bill assures about the compensation of revenue loss so the implementation has possibilities of incurring loss. But once the economy and state adapts itself to the GST mechanism the state will earn good revenue in the long run and at the same time not over loading the common man with tax burden. It facilitates use of operations, reduction in black market industries and cascading effects of tax at different levels, it also reduces evasion and litigation of tax which will in turn facilitate accumulation of state's revenue. Every service involved in a good in its cycle of reaching the consumer is also taxed, this generates revenue to states. It acts as a foundation for future revenue generation. The present scenario is where service

sectors are growing rapidly resulting in source of revenue from this sector as well. According to 2011 data service sector contributes 57% of GDP and 28% from industrial sector this indicates that major revenue of state is from service sector where the efficient tax compliance will happen with the implementation of GST. Without GST Majority of the tax base will not be present in the stream of revenue of state government.

This GST tax regime will be improved as compliance of tax is computerized at all levels. As GST is an exemption of food articles and proposing to introduce high tax on luxury goods, this will ensure state adequate and stable funds or resources. Therefore GST is a wise step in directing Indian economy towards a better stage.

THE EFFECT OF GST ON SMALL ENTREPRENEURS AND SMALL TRADERS

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Abstract

The advent of GST structure into the tax model of India has a far vision of harmonizing and polishing the indirect taxes on goods and services. GST being a new concept to the country, its impact on various sectors or industries of the economy is not well known to the players of the same. The impact of the introduction of GST on the small entrepreneurs and small traders is a widespread effect. Indian market has a large number of small and medium scale industries and traders who will be exposed to reform in the tax structure without ample amount of knowledge. A vague picture about the system is not sufficient and detailed education restricted to their scope is required. Small entrepreneurs will require mending their systems in order to adapt to the changing structures. The various aspects like sourcing, distribution channels, pricing and profitability margins, cash flows and other system and transaction changes will be required. The government's initiatives towards the restructuring and its importance to the welfare of the small traders

are enormous. The shift in the threshold values and split of tax into central and state GST, the principle of destination taxing, the compensating measures and also the preparation of the IT requirements to favor the stakeholders will pay off only with a successful implementation. Whatever said or done, the implementation of the GST will benefit the taxpayers of the nation to a certain extent.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is defined as any tax on the supply of goods or services that will subsume CENVAT, service tax, central excise duty, additional excise duties, excise duties levied under the Medicinal and Toilet Preparations (Excise Duties) Act, 1955, service tax, additional customs duty (countervailing duty or CVD), special additional duty of customs (SAD), central surcharges and cesses, State VAT, State sales tax, entertainment tax not levied by local bodies, luxury tax, taxes on lottery, betting, and gambling, tax on advertisements, State cesses and surcharges related to supply of goods and services and entry tax not levied by local bodies.

GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. GST is a part of proposed tax reforms in India. It has an extensive base that adds fuel to the applicability of an efficient and harmonized consumption tax system. GST has been commonly accepted by world and more than 140 countries have acknowledged the same. Generally the GST ranges between 15%- 20% in most of the countries.

A unified GST is an economically efficient solution even for the multinationals, which have to compete with the companies in unorganized sector, as it simplifies the indirect tax structure to one general rate that can be paid by all companies.

To introduce the GST structure, many of the indirect taxes are to be subsumed in one tax known as GST. The various taxes to be subsumed under GST are:

Table No: 1 GST would replace most indirect taxes currently in place such as:

Central Taxes	State Taxes
Central Excise Duty [including additional excise duties, excise duty under the Medicinal and Toilet Preparations (Excise Duties) Act, 1955]	Value Added Tax
Service tax	Octroi and Entry Tax
Additional Customs Duty (CVD)	Purchase Tax
Special Additional Duty of Customs (SAD)	Luxury Tax
Central surcharges and cesses	Taxes on lottery, betting & gambling
	State cesses and surcharges
	Entertainment tax (other than the tax levied by the local bodies)

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dahal,2010 made an attempt to analyze the loopholes or the blockages that are present in the constitution that are hurdles in the way of progressing closer to the projected deadline of implementation of GST in India. He added that the biggest tasks for the lawmakers is to decide and agree upon what are those various taxes, duties, and levies that should be covered by GST due to the characteristic federal set up India has and the administrative, legislative and taxing powers that have been divided among states under the Constitution of India. He quotes the powers of various areas which lie equally in the hands of the union and the states. Some of which are the laws on price control (Entry No. 34), Weights and Measures (Entry No. 33-A), the laws on electricity (Entry No. 38), and Stamp Duties (Entry No. 44), etc. the other part of the paper highlights on the constitutional amendments required for GST implementation which includes a list of indirect taxes that are to be

subsumed for the new regime. He concluded that if each state is allowed to tinker with GST tax base and rate, then, there will be every possibility that this noble work will not bring any better situation than that is prevalent today.

Dahal, 2010, in another article said about the acceptability of the change by the states of our country. According to him, though the governments of States and Center acknowledges the needs of modern tax regime which is effective, transparent and assessee friendly, there is still no consensus among the states on its modalities and implementation. He says that more state taxes are to be subsumed in GST to bring the intended objectives into a reality. The other aspect of the paper speaks about the states to be ready to draw conclusions about the rate of tax to be charged on different types of goods and services. If the states succeed in bringing up different tax slabs, then the positive factors of the GST reform will be diluted. Also the issue of states demand for

compensation of taxes has kept the bill delayed. Various states that collect taxes such as road tax, octroi in Maharashtra, tax on agricultural produce in Maharashtra and states having low threshold on VAT are expecting a good compensation from the centre. He concluded by saying that the problem of GST can be resolved only through union and state consensus.

In 2012, Jain speaks about the rise of the VAT regime in the world. The IMF has played a major role in providing assistance to a number of developing countries in designing and setting-up their indirect tax structures on a VAT model. India's shift towards VAT from the sales tax structure was a smooth one. This positive transformation has not only provoked the factors fuelling the reform toward GST, but also emphasized on the indirect tax landscape of the country, leading to simplification and harmonization of the structure. The introduction of the service tax in 1994 gave way to an unavoidable situation of double taxation on the goods and services in India. However, this was eased with the inception of the CEN-VAT through partial alignment of the regulations. The existing rules are limited in scope as they cover only the duties of excise. The taxes on sale of goods being beyond their coverage and in the absence of a mechanism for availability of credit across different State taxes, the citizens not only end up paying tax on tax but also have to bear its inflationary branches. The intent of merging the major indirect taxes (State level VAT, excise duty and service tax) into a generic 'Goods and Service Tax' (GST) was expressed by the Government in 2006 and international commitments were also made. The Empowered Committee of State Finance Ministers has undertaken to design the GST Model with similar work also undertaken by the Finance Commission independently. To set the foundation for legislative functioning, a Constitutional Amendment Bill has also been introduced in the Parliament. He concluded with necessitating background on the present indirect taxes

and also the framework of the 'to be introduced' GST.

Statement of Problem

The introduction of a new regime into the tax structure of the Indian subcontinent has a huge impact on the small entrepreneurs and small traders who are a major part of the society of this developing country. This research paper studies the impact of such a change on the small entrepreneurs and small traders of India. The inception of this reform, its benefits and a brief comparison of its advantage over the indirect tax structure helps in understanding the impact it has on small entrepreneurs.

Objectives

1. To study the benefits of GST to small traders and entrepreneurs
2. To compare the indirect tax structure with the GST structure
3. To identify the governments initiative towards bringing harmony
4. To highlight the areas which require redressal from the business's side

Scope of the Study

This study is restricted to the impact of GST on small entrepreneurs and does not take into consideration the other industries of the economy and its impact on their economic enforcement.

Data Collection

This study was mainly restricted to secondary data. As the concept of GST is new to India and it is in the process of implementation, the access to primary data is not feasible.

Limitations of the study

This study is limited to the availability of data from various dotcoms and previous research studies.

It does not take into consideration the first hand information from small entrepreneurs and traders in the market.

Discussions

Impact of GST on small entrepreneurs and traders.

Many entrepreneurs across India were eagerly waiting for the announcements about GST during the annual budget. The VAT tax structure is largely considered to be unfair leaving companies and small business owners at the mercy of strict adherence to official formalities and under a constant threat. The present VAT system has made competition unfair as it forces the manufacturers to charge different prices for the same goods across states due to different tax rates. GST will put in place state-of-art tax system replacing the current VAT system allowing companies to grow evenly while helping the government to fill in leakages and loopholes.

Under the proposed GST structure, every company gets a deduction on the taxes already paid by its suppliers. In other words, it is the tax paid on the value addition or the transaction costs incurred in the supply chain. That results in every buyer ensuring that his supplier has paid his part to claim his deductions.

GST would be one of the most significant fiscal reforms of independent India. GST will result in major rationalization and simplification of the consumption tax structure at both Centre and State levels.

The final GST base and rate will result in a significant redistribution of tax across different goods and services. Goods currently subject to both Centre and State taxes should experience a net reduction in tax, with a positive impact on consumer demand.

Destination principle

The GST structure would follow the destination principle. Accordingly, imports would be subject to GST, while exports would be zero-rated. In the case of inter-State transactions within India, the State tax would apply in the State of destination as opposed to that of origin.

Benefits of GST to the traders

GST is expected to help build a transparent and corruption-free tax administration. GST will be levied only at the destination point, and not at various points (from manufacturing to retail outlets). With the implementation of GST, exports will be promoted, raising employment and boosting growth.

In the GST system, both central and state taxes will be collected at the point of sale. Both components (the central and state GST) will be charged on the manufacturing cost. This will benefit individuals as prices are likely to come down. Lower prices will lead to more consumption, thereby helping small companies through increase in demand for their goods and services.

Though there are common benefits in certain aspects to every trader from the GST, there are also a few different benefits in other aspects.

The advantages for manufacturers and traders are the following:

- Common market
- One tax
- Distinction between goods and services will be abolished
- Invoicing will become simple
- Common exemptions between Centre and states
- Abolishment of central excise
- Classification difficulties will be met
- Problem of identification is solved
- Government's steps to protect the interest of small vendors:

Under the VAT scheme, the threshold of state VAT varies from state to state. Presently it is Rs5 lakhs for a majority of states and a lower sum for north eastern states and special category states on goods. GST that will be introduced will be helpful in achieving uniformity. The state GST threshold to be adopted will be an annual income of Rs10 lakhs on both goods and services for all the states and union

territories, providing adequate compensation for certain states especially the states of the north-eastern region and the special category states which had a provision for a lower threshold under the VAT regime.

At the same time, the threshold for central GST for goods will be Rs1.5 crores and a similar slab on sales. This is mainly to protect the interest of small traders who will otherwise be exposed to dual taxes or dual control.

There will be three categories of Small Enterprises in the GST regime:

1. Those below threshold need not register for the GST
2. Those between the threshold and composition turnovers will have the option to pay a turnover based tax or opt to join the GST regime.
3. Those above threshold limit will need to be within framework of GST

Possible downward changes in the threshold in some States consequent to the introduction of GST may result in obligation being created for some dealers. In this case considerable assistance is desired. In respect of Central GST, the position is slightly more complex. Small scale units manufacturing specified goods are allowed exemptions of excise up to Rs. 1.5 Crores. These units may be required to register for payment of GST, may see this as an additional cost.

III. CONCLUSION

The country has been awaiting the introduction of GST since long and the wait has been a rigorous one. The fact that GST proposes to derive tremendous benefits and opportunities to business has assured continuing enthusiasm for GST. However, the anticipated benefits and opportunities can only be derived from a flawless GST model. If an efficient GST is to be implemented in an effective manner by April 2016, both Centre and State Government need

to show their state of readiness in meeting the challenges.

IMPACT OF GST ON IMPORTS

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Abstract

Vajpayee Government in 2000 first started the discussion on GST by forming an empowered committee. They thought of implementing GST which has various advantages like end of cascading effect, increase in GDP rate by 2 to 2.5%, increase in exports by 8 to 10%, by eliminating the multiplicity of taxation and also it create unified market. GST will help in setting off for input tax by the importer; it will also subsume major indirect taxes like sales tax, service tax, excise duty and also CVD & SAD. There are three main categories under GST there are SGST, CGST & IGST. IGST includes both SGST & CGST government has estimated IGST rate to 16%. GST implementation is only approved in Lok Sabha but in Rajya Sabha due to lack of majority it still in process of implementation. Only when it is implemented clear picture will be available. The main objective of GST is to maintain common tax rate structure between the states. This article will start with Introduction, History of GST and mainly concentrates on the impact of GST on imports and also how IGST works.

Key words – Central Goods & Service Tax (CGST), State Goods & Service Tax (SGST), Integrated Goods & Service Tax (IGST), Central Excise Duty (CED), Central Sales Tax (CST), Value Added Tax (VAT).

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods and Service Tax is a value added tax, levied at all points in the supply chain with credit allowed for any tax paid on inputs acquired for use in

making the supply. It would apply to both goods and services in a comprehensive manner with exemptions restricted to a minimum. This in contrast to current system where taxes are levied separately on goods and services. GST is payable only at the point of final consumption.

According to Federal structure of India, it is proposed that GST be levied concurrently by the Centre (CGST) and the states (SGST). Both CGST and SGST would be levied on the basis of the destination principle. Imports would be subject to GST, while exports would be zero rated. In the case of interstate transaction within India, the state tax would apply in the state of destination as opposed to that of origin.

Introduction of GST will not affect customs provision because GST model includes both basic custom duty and IGST. But for importing services, service tax will be subsumed by GST and IGST which will be levied. Both CGST and SGST will be levied on import of goods and services into the country. The incidence of tax will follow the destination principle and tax revenue in case of SGST will accrue to state where the imported goods and services are consumed. Full and complete setoff will be available on GST paid on import of goods and service. But the products like petroleum, liquor and tobacco does not come under preview of GST.

First discussion paper on GST in India was revealed by empowered committee of state finance ministers on 10th November 2009. This discussion

paper provides information about dual GST that is to be implemented in India. CGST and SGST are based on destination principle which means tax will be collected only by consuming country. Punjab finance minister Permindar Singh Dhindra suggested that state should allow levying purchase tax on wheat, paddy, sugarcane, cotton and milk under GST too, as the grain producing state would lose revenue from this new scheme.

GST subsumes the following indirect taxes:

Under Central Taxes central excise duty, service tax, additional customs duty, special additional duty and central surcharges and cesses are subsumed.

Under State Taxes value added tax, central sales tax, octroi and entry tax, purchase tax, luxury tax, taxes on lottery, betting and gambling, state cesses and surcharges and entertainment taxes are subsumed.

Benefits

GST eliminates dual tax system, simplify India's tax structure and create common market across states this will lead to increase India's tax-to-gross domestic product ratio. The production cost will reduce which leads to fall in tax burden on companies.

Difficulties

It may affect the service sectors like BPOs and KPOs the most because, they were claiming for service tax on input services, but after implementing GST, for claiming SGST they should get registered in every state which leads to high cost and more complexity.

History

In 2000 Vajpayee government started discussion on Goods and Service Tax by setting up an empowered committee, headed by Asin Das Gupta, finance minister of West Bengal. The committee was given the task of designing the GST model and overseeing the IT back-end preparedness for its role out. During this period a major improvement over

existing Centre excise duty at national level and sales tax at sales level was done.

Later in 2006, union finance minister P. Chidambaram moved towards GST in his budget and proposed to introduce it by 1st April 2010. However Empowered Committee of State Finance ministers (EC) released its "first discussion paper" on GST in November 2009.

In 2007-08 budget, empowered committee of state finance ministers on P. Chidambaram's request work with central government to prepare a road map for introduction of GST in India. State finance ministers, decided to set up Joint Working Groups on 10th may 2007 with the advice to the union finance ministers and minister's secretary of empowered committee.

In 2008 EC report to the titled "a model and road map for GST in India" containing broad recommended above the structure and design of GST.

In 2009 first discussion paper was released based on inputs from GOI and state with objective of generating a debate and obtaining inputs from all stake holders.

Statement of Problem

GST has positive and negative impact on imports.

Positive impacts are credit of import duties will make imports cheaper for retailer's thus final consumers will be benefited. Entry tax is a cost in most cases, along with additional tax burden. With GST entry tax and other indirect taxes will be eliminated.

Negative impacts are, at present stock transfers are not taxed but it will be taxed by the implementation of GST.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Halkhandi (2015), GST's implementation will have positive impact because the total tax will be paid on final consumptions and only country which is importing will pay the tax which

called destination based VAT. Main objective of implementing GST is to remove barriers for movement of goods from one country to another.

According to Shekar (2015), implementation of GST will emerge as tax of the future. In the competitive world income from direct taxes has been reduced and hence implementation of GST can increase the country's revenue through combining all indirect taxes in one single head.

According to Lath (2015), implementation of GST will make a major change. Supporting his statement, major changes can be single and unified market place, reduction in operational costs, major flow of credit and reduction in litigation. And there will be different impact on manufacturers, traders; service providers all together, like manufacturer need not pay tax on manufacturing and only consuming country would pay tax.

According to Jain, GST as it is claimed to be a destination based tax, so tax will be charged only on supply on goods and services. And also set off will be given by Centre and state separately. Centre will provide tax credit only on Centre GST (CGST) and state will provide tax credit set off only state GST (SGST). This will eliminate over utilization of tax credit between Centre and state.

Objectives

1. To study the impact of GST on imports
2. To find how IGST works on imports.
3. To find whether the implementation of GST

has positive or negative impact on imports in the country.

Methodology- Data Collection

Secondary data

The information for the study is collected through newspapers and various sources.

Limitations

Time wasn't sufficient for the research

As GST is not yet implemented our study is based on previous research.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

IMPACT OF GST ON IMPORTS

Import in India attracts VAT or CGST at the time of entry into the country. The tax is generally applied on the value of goods declared for custom purpose, including the amount of customs duty. Previously imports includes basic customs duty and along with that SAD and CVD of 4%. But now SAD and CVD are subsumed under GST.

As there are no well-established precedents for the application of subnational taxes to imports, it is difficult to analysis the effect of GST on imports.

The constitution one hundred and twenty second amendments 2014 proposes to treat supply of goods and services into territory of India as supplies in course of interstate trade or commerce.

Under present tax rate structure in INDIA imported goods are taxed with custom duty which includes BCD, CVD and SAD. Service is imported with service tax.

- Excise duty-12%
- Service tax-12.36%
- Sales tax/VAT-5%, 12.5% and 20%
- Customs duty-24.72%

After implementation of GST, tax rates in INDIA are expected to be 12% to 20% for the 1st year, 12% to 18% for 2nd year and 16% for 3rd year and onward.

Table No: 1 Rate structure of GST.

Goods/Services	Levy	Rate in 1st year	Rate in 2nd year	Rate in 3rd year
Goods Lower	CGST	6%	6%	8%
Rate	SGST	6%	6%	8%

Goods Standard	CGST	10%	9%	8%
Rate	SGST	10%	9%	8%
Services	CGST	8%	8%	8%
	SGST	8%	8%	8%

IV. CONCLUSION

It has the potential to be the single most important initiative in the fiscal history of India. It can pave the way for modernization of tax administration -make it simpler and more transparent and significant enhancement in voluntary compliance. We assume that implementation of GST will increase the GDP rate from 2%-2.5% due to elimination of dual cascading effect.

This assumption is made because the Canadian experience is suggestive of the potential benefits to the Indian economy. The GST in Canada replaced the federal manufacturers' sales tax which was then levied at the rate of 13% and was similar in design and structure as the

CENVAT in India. It is estimated that this replacement resulted in an increase in potential GDP by 1.4%, consisting of 0.9% increase in national income from higher factor productivity and 0.5% increase from a larger capital stock.

On levying IGST the country can eliminate double taxation and also it is based on destination principle where only final consumer will pay the tax. Therefore, when the country import the goods it can earn more revenue by collection the tax and also consumer will get input tax credit (set off).

At present, government of India is not able to meet the expected tax collection due to lack of transparency in the present tax structure. Therefore according to our results implementation of GST is very much required and GST rate should be fixed in such a way that they meet their target.

GST- A GAME CHANGER IN INDIAN TAX STRUCTURE

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Abstract

The research paper focuses on the importance of Goods and Services Tax(GST) embodied recently in the Indian Tax structure. The paper discusses the genesis of Indian Taxation System with reference to the Arthasastra and Revenue Act of 1924. The contents of the research paper include the evolution of GST in India. The research objectives focuses around the evolution of GST, the comparison of present and GST tax structure, How GST will function in India, the economic implication of GST which unifies India and the basic challenges faced in GST. The milestones of GST have been discussed to analyze how it impacts India's economic environment. The transition of GST to an amalgamated structure has also. The economic implications of GST in India, the challenges and roadblocks faced in India have been depicted in this research paper. The paper also illustrates how GST works in India.

Keywords: GST, Goods and services tax, Indian Tax, Indian tax structure, Indian tax scenario.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Constitution Amendment Bill for Goods and Services Tax has been approved by the President of

India in the Rajya Sabha on August 03, 2016 and August 08, 2016 in Lok Sabha. The intention is to replace all the indirect taxes levied on goods and services and implement GST by April 2017. This brings out the significance of the history on Indian taxation system.

In India the system of taxation (direct taxation) dates back from ancient times, the references of which we read in Arthasastra. Manu the ancient sage and Law-giver stressed on the importance of taxes which public should comprehensively and compulsorily pay to the Kings according to their income levels. Similarly, the Kautilyas of Arthasastra dealt with the system of taxation wherein the state was to provide necessary services including taxes imposed on goods imported from outside the country.

In the year 1924, central Board of Revenue Act constituted the Board as statutory body with the responsibility for the administration of income tax. Since then there have been plethora of amendments .with the widening of tax net various recommendations of expert committee's like Indian taxation Enquiry committee(1924-25) ,The taxation Enquiry commission (1953-54) were undertaken. The objectives of tax reforms were as follows:

1. Simplification of tax laws.
2. Widening tax base.
3. Restructuring income tax department to increase effectiveness and productivity

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Aurobindo Panda, Atul Patel, The Impact of GST on the Indian Tax Scene, SSRN Electronic Journal, July 201, DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.1868621.

The paper discusses on the impact of GST on Indian Tax Scenario, the need for change in tax structure from traditional to GST Model. The paper has vividly described the salient features and impact of GST in 2011. The other facets of GST include the limitation of the tax structure, the need for GST, the Kelkar Shah Model etc have been included in the research paper which gives a complete understanding of GST.

NehaKanojia, A Study on Goods and services Tax in India, the International Journal of Social science and Management, ISSN: 22511571

The paper discusses on the benefits of GST and its current implication in India. The current system of indirect taxes is not able to implicate tax evasion and distortion. It also indicates how GST is an improvement over VAT and Service Tax.

Monika Sehrawat, UpasanaDhanda, GST in India: A Key Tax Reform, International Journal of Research

Granthalaya, Vol 3, No: 12(2015) 133-141

The paper focuses on the overview of GST concept, the features along with its time line of implementation in India with the challenges faced in its implementation. It includes an exploratory research. It includes implementation to threshold limit.

Nishita Gupta, Goods and Services Tax: its impact on Indian Economy, International Research Journal of Commerce Arts and Science, Vol 5, Issue 3, Year-2014, ISSN 2319-9202.

The research paper focuses on the relevance of VAT and GST, how GST contributes to the improvement of the tax structure in India toward a world class system. The paper included intricate details of VAT. It indicated a significant improvement in the comprehensive indirect tax reforms in the country. It discusses about the differences in treatment for the service and manufacturing sector. It has also included the integration of taxation with an intent to harmonize the consumption tax system.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The particular study is an attempt undertaken to analyze the following objectives:

1. Evolution of GST.
2. Comparing Present Tax structure and GST
3. How GST would function in India
4. The Challenges in implementing GST
5. The Economic Implications of GST-System of unifies India

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research paper has gathered data based on secondary research and information gathered from the other research papers, the current affairs, news dailies and the current GST discussion etc have been imperative in framing this conceptual paper.

V. AN INSIGHT INTO EVOLUTION OF GST IN INDIA

India is one of the latest growing economies to adopt GST. It also featured latest to adopt the VAT as well. The Southeast Asian economies adopted consumption taxes like the VAT, or the GST based on value-addition way back in the 1980s and 1990s. Laos, one of the least developed countries (LDCs) from the region implemented VAT from 2009, four years after India did. Malaysia was an interesting exception which introduced a GST of 6 per cent only from April 1, 2015. In South Asia, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Pakistan and Nepal had VAT implemented from the 1990s, latest by early-2000s.

VI. GST- MAJOR MILESTONE

- The idea of GST was first introduced and in budget 2006-2007 .The empowered committee of state finance ministers (EC) formulated the design of GST .If VAT was a major improvement then GST is seen as another milestone towards tax reforms.
- GST have been described by political analyst as the concept of “cooperative financial federalism” and one nation one tax one market.
- GST is claimed to be game changing tax reform as it will pave way for common national market. This would facilitate free movement of goods and services across the country.

VII.COMPARISON OF PRESENT TAX AND GST TAX

Present Tax Structure:

The existing tax structure of India has been indicated in the Fig 1.1 below. This shows the relation between direct tax, income tax, indirect tax, central excise, VAT, entry, luxury tax etc.

Fig 5.1 Existing Tax Structure Of India

GST Tax Structure:

The fig 6.1 shows the GST Tax structure which shows the relation between Intra state GST, Inter state GST, central GST, state GST, Integrated GST etc.

Fig 6.1 GST Tax Structure

VIII. HOW GST OPERATES IN INDIA?

Sale In One State, Resale In The Same State:

The illustration below indicates that goods are moving from Mumbai to Pune. The situation indicates a sale within a state, CGST and SGST will be levied. The levied fares go to the Central Government and the State Government as indicated in the diagram. The goods are resold from Pune to Nagpur. This is a sale again within a state, so CGST and SGST will be levied. Sale price will be increased so tax liability will also duly increase. In the case of resale, the credit of input CGST and input SGST (Rs. 8) is levied as shown; and the remaining taxes go to the respective governments.

Sale In One State, Resale In Another State:

The figure 7.2 depicts that the goods are moving from Indore to Bhopal. This indicates a sale within a state, CGST and SGST will be levied. The collection goes to the Central Government and the State Government as indicated in the figure. The goods are the resold from Bhopal to Lucknow (outside the state). Hence, IGST will be levied. The IGST goes to the central government.

The input taxes are taken as credit against IGST.SGST never goes to the central government, still the credit is claimed. This is the crux of GST. Since this amounts to a loss to the Central Government, the state government compensates the central government by transferring the credit to the central government.

Fig 7.2: Sale In One State, Resale In Another State.

Sale Outside The State, Resale In That State:

The figure 7.3 indicates that the goods are moving from Delhi to Jaipur. This is an interstate sale

hence IGST will be levied. The collection goes to the Central Government. The goods when they are resold from Jaipur to Jodhpur (within the state). The, CGST and SGST will be levied.

Against CGST and SGST, 50% of the IGST, that is Rs. 8 is taken as a credit. But we see that IGST never went to the state government, still the credit is claimed against SGST. Since this amounts to a loss to the State Government, the Central government compensates the State government by transferring the credit to the State government.

IX. SALIENT FEATURES OF GST IN INDIA

1. The GST would be applicable on the supply of goods and services as against the present concept of tax on the manufacture and sale of goods or services. It would be destination based consumption tax.

2. Dual GST with the center and states simultaneously levying it on a common tax base. Thus would be CGST (central GST) and state GST (SGST).

3. GST would apply to all goods other than alcoholic liquor, liquor for human consumption, and five petroleum products which is crude, motor spirit (petrol), high speed diesel, natural gas and aviation turbine fuel.

4. Tobacco and tobacco products would be subject to GST. In addition center would have the power to levy central Excise duty on these products.

5. There would be GST council which shall make recommendations to the union and states on taxes, cesses and surcharges levied by the center, the states and the local bodies

6. Taxpayer with the aggregate turnover in a financial year up to Rs 20 lakhs would be exempt from tax. For north east states and Sikkim the exemption threshold shall be Rs 10 lakhs.

7. An integrated GST (IGST) would be levied and collected by the center on inter-state supply of goods and services.

8. Tax payer shall be allowed to take credit of taxes paid on inputs (input tax credit) and utilize the same for the payment of output tax.

9. Import of goods and services would be treated as inter-state supplies and would be subject to IGST in addition to the applicable customs duties.

10. The laws, Regulations and procedures for levy and collection of CGST and SGST would be harmonized to every possible extent.

X. Impact Of Transitional Phase:

GST has been introduced in India to ward off the ill effects of wide variety of direct taxes which have proved to be detrimental to the growth and development. This is more evident in the dismal performance of the manufacturing sector which is the life line of our nation.

The various taxes which have been subsumed under GST are given below:

Fig 9.1 State Tax Vs Central Tax

The direct implication of the amalgamation of the above taxes would be diminished cascading effect of multitude taxes. Multitude of taxes reflected in the form of higher prices eventually pinching the final consumers. The reduction of taxes from the

consumer's side would stimulate demand both in the domestic market and international market.

Goods and services tax is seen as an historic step towards standardization of the tax rates. Standard taxes would accelerate the production since cost of production would also come down.

Input tax credit which is the soul of GST is seen as a major milestone towards tax liabilities. ITC in simple terms refers to the avail of taxes paid on input stage as credit that can be utilized as set-off for the payment of output tax liability by the tax payer .tax is paid only on the value addition rather than on the whole value of his outward supply.

Another unique feature of input tax credit is that it can be claimed only by business registered under GST. The mechanism is simple –the amount of GST incurred on input would be deducted from GST charged on output by registered person.

XI. ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF GST IN INDIA:

- It would help in lesser corruption and Increased Tax Revenue.
- It contributes towards a Better and improved economy with single taxation. The system will make it easier to identify the tax defaulters.
- The registration of GST will create a unified market. This will help in the facilitation of seamless movement of goods to different states of India and reduce the transaction cost of businesses.
- Tax evasion will be reduced considerably with lower tax cost which will result in better investments in manufacturing industry.
- One tax instead of so many different taxes will make tax compliance and tax monitoring easier.
- Increased investments in manufacturing sectors and reduced cost will result in increased volume of exports.

- Distribution of burden of tax between goods and service industries.

XII.EXPECTED ROADBLOCKS FOR GST:

- Goods and services tax is a transitional tax structure which would encompass wide variety of taxes into one. It is perceived to be a reformative tax structure unifying the market and expected to bring substantial increase in countries overall productivity through free movement of goods and services.
- However transitional phase also faces roadblocks as well as lack of clarity till it reaches final implementation. There are few blind spots which needs to be uncovered so that the benefits trickle down to every sector of the economy. One such is the dual structure. A strong mechanism is needed to monitor the tax levied on the origin state till the destination stage. It is essential that the tax payer should feel burden with zealous taxes and his cash flow is uninterrupted.
- In the present tax structure central excise is a tax on manufacturing and therefore is not reflected on invoices issues to final consumers. IN the GST regime, the entire tax liability would be reflected on the invoices which might create an impression of extra taxes or more taxes to be paid by the final consumers.
- The most evident issue is the exemptions of key sectors such as electricity, diesel, petrol,crude oil and real estate. These exemptions may not be able to reduce the cascading effect of indirect taxes as expected.
- The lower house of Indian parliament recently passed four GST legislations. The Bill proposes central GST at 20% and the Integrated GST rate at 40%.It is believed that the states would cap the State GST rate 20%.These rates could turn out to be counterproductive.
- There are panels expected to overcome these few hitches, however only time and effective

implementation would help the nation to reap the benefits of unifying tax structure.

XIII. DEMONETIZATION: WHAT DOES THIS MEAN FOR GST?

- The absence of a widespread black market economy encourages more dealers to register under indirect tax acts. The buyers of goods can avail themselves Input Tax Credits (ITC) only on purchases made from registered dealers.

- The incentive structure will motivate buyers to restrain from buying from an unregistered dealer if the option to buy from a registered dealer exists.

- Dealers below the registration threshold will find it an economic necessity to register, in order to survive in the market. Black money eradication will also force dealers to come into the light since no buyers will exist for them.

- Registration of dealers will help to automate the process, which is a prerequisite for GST and will help achieve the aim of unifying the Indian market by identifying each commercial transaction.

XIV. CONCLUSION:

India's historic and bold move towards integrated tax structure is viewed by most economist as an answer to regressive indirect tax structure. It is believed that GST would put India's indirect tax structure at par with more than 140 countries and would be productive for all the sectors. Implementation of such reforms does faces surmountable challenges, however this is expected to bring in benefits in the form of higher GDP and also transparency in the tax system. The GST would be imposed on the value –addition and thus would leave lesser scope for tax evasion.

GST: AN ECONOMIC OVERVIEW: CHALLENGES AND IMPACT AHEAD

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Abstract

Goods and service is very comprehensive tax structure when implemented at the national level . It is one of the significant step towards the development of the country. It is one of the biggest tax revolution which is all set to integrate the state and national economy to boost the overall growth of the country. Presently companies and businesses pay multiple taxes which increases the cost of product and also hampers the profit level of the company. Multiple tax and complex taxation system is one of the biggest hurdle for economic growth of the country. Once the GST system is applied their would be single tax system which would record a significant development in comprehensive indirect taxation reform. Under the GST system their would be only on rate applicable for both goods and services. GST will create a business friendly environment, as prices will fall and it would also control the inflation rates.

I. INTRODUCTION

Taxation plays an very important in economic development of country. With much awaited GST system and in-depth analysis , here we are with final GST bill passed by the parliament. Because taxes are only means for financing the public goods because

they cannot be properly priced in the market. And government is only the source of funding using the taxation methods. As taxes are the drivers of the economy. Tax regimes should be designed in such a manner that is does not become the source of distortion in the market or result in failure of market. Raising a sufficient amount of revenue is main aim of tax law in efficient , effective and equitable manner. Tax policies are important contributor to the economy in both the cases efficiency and equity. Good tax system should keep in view the issues of income distribution and also focused on strategies to generate tax revenues to support government expenditures on public services and infrastructural development. GST stands for Goods and Service Tax. Domestic trade tax will be levied in the form of a value added tax on all goods and services , in practice with some exemptions. VAT exempts all inputs including capital goods.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Poonam, 2017 in her study , she had cleared that GST would be a very important step in the field of indirect taxation. The cascading and double taxation effects can be reduced by combing central and state taxes. Consumer's tax burden will approximately

reduce to 25% to 30% when GST is introduced. After introduction of GST concept, Indian manufactured products would become more and more competitive in the domestic and international markets. This taxation system would instantly encourage economic growth. GST with its transparent features will prove easier to administer. In this paper the author has tried to attempt to spot the concept of GST & its current status in India. Paper has tried to give information about GST system. The study also aims to be familiar with the advantages and challenges of GST in Indian scenario.

Shefali Dani has proposed that GST regime is a half-hearted attempt to rationalize indirect tax structure. Approximately more than 150 countries have implemented GST concept. As per researcher government of India must study the GST regime set up by various countries and also their fallouts before implementing GST. It is the need of the hour that, the government must make an attempt to insulate the vast poor population of India, against the inflation due to implementation of GST. There is no doubt, GST will simplify its existing indirect tax system and will have to help to remove inefficiencies created by the existing current heterogeneous tax system, only if there is a clear consensus over issues of threshold limit, revenue rate, and inclusion of petroleum products, electricity, liquor and real estate.

1. Research Problem

The concept of Goods and Service Tax (GST) is one of the biggest revolutions in decades around the world. But it seems that India is taking very slow steps to meet target. This research intends to focus on understanding concept of goods and service tax and its impact on Indian economy.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the concept of Goods and Services Tax (GST)
2. To study the impact of GST on Indian Economy

3. To understand how GST will work in India.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study focuses on study of Secondary data collected from various books, national & international journals, government reports, publications from various websites which has been published and focused on various aspects of Goods and Service tax.

V. CONCEPT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX

GST or Goods and Services Tax is applicable on supply of goods and services. It will replace the current taxes of excise, VAT and service tax. Currently there are different VAT laws in different states. This creates problems, especially when businesses sell to different states. Also, most businesses have to pay and comply with 3 different taxes – excise, VAT, and service tax. GST will bring uniform taxation across the country and allow full tax credit from the procurement of inputs and capital goods which can later be set off against GST output liability. This reform gives equal footing to the big enterprises as well as SMEs. The aim of GST is thus to simplify tax hurdles for the entire economy. Who will have to pay GST? GST will be paid by all manufacturers and sellers. It will also be paid by service providers such as telecom providers, consultants, chartered accountants etc. However, being an indirect tax, GST will be ultimately borne by the end consumers, just like in the current process. What kind of GST will be implemented in India? India will implement the Canadian model of Dual GST, i.e., both the Centre and State will collect GST. GST is a destination based tax system. Supply of goods and services are base for charging tax. GST is very comprehensive indirect taxation system on manufactured products and services, sale and consumptions of goods and services at national level. GST is going to be one of the biggest tax reforms after independence till the date. GST is very comprehensive indirect taxation system

on goods manufactured and services provided. It is one of the biggest tax reform in country. Clause 366(12A) of the Constitution Bill defines GST as “goods and services tax” means any tax on supply of goods, or services or both except taxes on the supply of the alcoholic liquor for human consumption. Further the clause 366(26A) of the Bill defines “Services” means anything other than Goods. Thus it can be said that GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. The proposed tax will be levied on all transactions involving supply of goods and services, except those which are kept out of its purview.

GST – How It Works In India

GST is based on the grounds of VAT. Same set-off system is also available in the respect of the taxes paid in the previous level against GST charged at time of sale. Following are some of the module of GST.

Components: GST will be basically divided into two components i.e namely, Central Goods and Service Tax and also State Goods and Service

Applicability: GST will be also applicable to all the Goods and Services sold and provided in India, only except from the list of exempted goods which fall outside its purview. Payment: At central and State level GST will be paid separately.

Credit: The facility of Input Tax Credit at Central level will only be available in respect of Central Goods and Service tax .

VI. IMPACT OF GST ON INDIAN ECONOMY

Expect reduction in prices of :

- FMCG goods such as shampoos, chocolates
- Eating out
- Small cars
- DTH

Increase in prices of:

- Luxury cars
- Tobacco

- Aerated beverages
- Textiles

Advantages Of GST For Citizen

Simpler tax system

• Reduction in prices of goods and services due to elimination of cascading.

- Uniform prices throughout the country.
- Transparency in taxation system.
- Increase in employment opportunities.

For Trade/Industry

- Reduction in multiplicity of Taxes
- Mitigation of cascading /double taxation

VII. CONCLUSION

GST is convenient and economically efficient way of taxing the consumption. Basically there are very few exemptions because it has single rate and it becomes a proportional tax on consumption. One level of tax is efficient way of collection , because it either goes to the state or central level. Multiple level of tax is distortion in case of destination of tax collection. Tax should go to the state in which the concerned consumer lives. This will automatically take place if tax is levied at the central level or state is in unitary level with the one and only level of tax collection. If GST has to be implemented at central level i.e. in one level, it has to face many challenges at central level

THE IMPACT OF THE GOODS AND SERVICE TAX ON THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

As the world is becoming expensive, the public is getting more careful on what they spend and where their money goes, the prevailing tax scheme does not allow the consumer to know how much he will be spending towards tax. In the hospitality sector, the consumer is presently bearing the heavy burden of tax on both the food they consume and the services they receive, but they are usually prey to a lot of hidden taxes and charges that are levied by the proprietor on the invoice. The implementation of GST will allow the consumer to be free from the unnecessary taxes that they pay as the bill will eliminate the differential taxes and will implement a unified tax regime for all goods and services provided. This paper is a conceptual study on how the introduction of the GST bill will affect the consumers of the Hospitality industry. The consumers of this sector of the market pay exorbitant tax charges under various heads of tax, i.e. service tax, VAT, Octroi duty etc. but with the implementation of GST all, the above-mentioned taxes will be subsumed under one unified tax rate system. This study

concentrates on how the implementation of a uniformed tax rate will affect the turnover of the Hospitality sector if it is not contained within a cap of 10%. Why the government should consider this plea while setting the tax rate.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a world, changing at momentous speeds and no aspect of our life is being spared from this change. The world of tax and tax administration is now seeing some drastic changes that are affecting everybody, be it the producer, retailer, or the ultimate consumer. The introduction of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) bill in the 122nd amendment of the constitution bill of 2014 has brought in a lot of speculation of its benefits and limitations to the payers of tax and the collectors of tax, i.e. The Government. Tax on consumption of goods and services on a value added basis, more commonly known as the Value-Added Tax (VAT) or presently being changed and popularized as the Goods and Services Tax (GST) is emerging as the tax of the future. In a global, competitive environment for keeping up with the global trend, we see the

reduction of direct taxes and the increase of indirect taxes in order to derive higher revenue.

An overview of Goods and Service Tax (GST)

A comprehensive value-added tax on goods and services, GST is levied and collected on the value addition of each stage of sale or purchase of goods and supply of services based on input tax credit without state boundaries. Input tax credit means the credit of tax paid on inputs. In simple words, every dealer is liable for output tax on the taxable sale that affects him, but the basic principle of VAT says that the dealer is liable only for the value addition in his hands.

A major indirect tax reform, GST will take VAT to its logical conclusion. Once introduced even, central sales tax will reduce. The Goods and Services tax is a system of taxation that imposes a single tax of both, goods and services. This system to taxation ensures a single tax for the entire country and when introduced will eliminate all indirect taxes. A worldwide-accepted system, France was the first country to introduce GST. It provides a uniform tax rate for goods as well as services. The assumed rate of GST will be 16%-20%, which is much lesser compared to the prevailing tax rates of 35%-40%. Once GST is introduced, the price of products will reduce. Generally, when the price of products reduces the demand for the product will rise; this in turn will raise working capital.

The implementation of GST into the Indian system of tax will bring about the elimination of the cascading effects of the prevailing tax systems. GST, being an indirect tax has both its positives and negatives.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

(India, 2009)

Speaking about the limitations of the prevailing system of taxation in the country said the central tax (CENVAT) of the government bears its shortcomings in the non-inclusion of many of the central taxes. In addition, while talking about the state level VAT, it pointed out the inclusion of the CENVAT to the value of goods that were to be taxed under the state level tax scheme, this brought about a cascading effect on the consumer who was to pay the taxes. The report further stated that any commodity produced is based on physical inputs as well as services, and that there should be an integration of VAT on goods with an addition of tax on services and at the same time, measures be taken to eliminate the cascading effect of taxes.

Furthermore, the committee said that the introduction of GST at the central level would comprehensively include the indirect taxes and service tax for the purpose set-off relief, and increase the revenue gain of the centre. GST is not simply VAT with the inclusion of service tax, but an improvement of the previous system of VAT with disjoint service tax. With the introduction of GST, the state will have to be given the power to levy taxes on all services, which was prior held only by the centre which will give multiple positive outcomes to the consumer by eliminating the effect of cascading taxes and subsuming several taxes under GST.

(Ms. Divya Sathyanarayanan and Mr. Sachin Dave, 2015) The introduction of GST will bring about uniformity in tax rates and will definitely reduce the paper work for the people working in the industry. This will only be beneficial if the tax rate is capped at 10% or lower. Anything higher will have an adverse effect on the revenue of the industry. This

will not only affect the industry but will also curb the spending ability and consumption capacity of the consumer.

(Lokesh, 2015)

The introduction of GST will be a huge milestone in the reforms that are required for the country. The quantum of the tax rates remains unclear as the bill hasn't yet been passed for implementation in India, but the assumed tax rates that are likely to be in the range of 16%-20%. For an industry that is already struggling of high costs of capital and extreme tax structures, these rates will be a huge burden when GST is introduced. Even though the passing of the GST will be a step in the right direction for our economy, the high rates would have to be brought down for the hospitality industry and the foreign travelers could be exempt from GST or allowed for a refund.

(Poddar, 2015)

Through the optimism of having substantially less paper work and filing, the HRAEI is unhappy with the fact that if the GST rates are going to be the speculated rates of 16%-20% and it will be too expensive for the Hospitality sector, and will be a bad blow to hotels and restaurants which will suffer badly. The members of the association feel that the rates should be capped at 10% for the hospitality sector, if not the turnover will start showing negative results. It is also important to note that the Hospitality industry will not gain much advantage from GST as their input credit will be much lower than the tax paid, as majority of the input expense of any hotel is their labour.

III. METHODOLOGY

Type of research: Exploratory
The secondary data for the study includes the provisions of GST and its after tax effects on the consumer. The sources of

secondary data are Government reports, news articles, official reports by recognised organizations of the Hospitality industry and other sources available on the internet.

IV. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A country that is filled to the brim with various cultures, traditions and spectacular natural and man-made heritage, India is a major attraction to tourists for various purposes, be it, pilgrimages, vacations or even for the purpose of business. This increase in travel and tourism is a sign of the growth the Hospitality Industry has been witnessing in the recent past. The hospitality industry is a major source to the revenue of the country. The development and maintenance of this sector is necessary for the increase in the national GDP. Already standing as one of the major contributors to the revenue of the country the Hospitality Industry is ever growing. Currently the tax rates that the government charges on this industry, pose as a burden on the consumers.

The introduction of GST will be instrumental in controlling the excess charges levied on the consumers, but if the rate of tax under GST is set at the assumed 16%-20% it will turn out to be a burden on the consumers and this in turn will result in the reduction of sales. The prevailing tax rates add up to be a burden on the consumer as the differential taxes on the food and services cascade onto the consumer. With the introduction of GST this cascading effect will reduce, but the high tax rates will only be a heavier burden for the consumer to bear.

Scope of the Study

The study restricts to analyse the impact of GST on the consumers of the hospitality industry only in India.

V. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To highlight the impacts of the Goods and Service Tax (GST) on the Hospitality industry.
2. To analyse the effect of taxes prior and post GST implementation
3. To suggest policy recommendation based on the results of the study

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The impact of GST on the Hospitality industry

A composite system of taxation, GST is a reform in the indirect tax system of India. It aims at subsuming all indirect taxes under a single universal tax regime. The tax rates under GST have not been finalised and this has caused unrest in the hospitality industry. The tax rates are assumed to be set in the range of 16% to 20% under the GST system.

The implementation of GST has more positives than negative, with the elimination of multiple direct and indirect taxes, the consumer will only benefit. As the tax rates are stabilised and made uniform, the

Hospitality industry will see a rise in revenue. The GST bill will prove to be beneficial to the government, the producer and the ultimate consumer. To the government, it will benefit, as the increased uniform rates will ensure better returns. To the producer, in this case the Hospitality industry, work will be easier as there will be lesser paper work and reduction in filing which will allow him to concentrate his time and effort on the business. Finally, to the consumer, the GST bill will have the effect of a double-edged sword. As the consumer benefits because of the elimination of various direct and indirect taxes, he can enjoy his time dining out without the worry of having to pay taxes for the food consumed, and also the additional tax that they would have to pay for the services rendered. On the other hand, the rate of 16%-20% that is the assumed rate is too high for the consumer to pay as tax. As the tax rates increase, the consumers will only reduce dining out, which in turn will bring down the revenues to this sector

Table 1: Prior GST

Sub-total	2000
Service charge @ 10%	200
(2000*10%=200)	
VAT@ 12.5%	275
(2200*12.5%=275)	
Service tax @ 12.36% (on 40% of bill, excluding VAT)	108
(2200*40%=880)	
(880*12.36%=108.76)	
Net amount	2584

Source: Tarini, 2014, March -switchme.com

With the implementation of the GST, the consumer of the Hospitality sector will be free from these additional heads of tax. The hospitality industry is positive that the tax regime will help reduce multiple taxation, giving a significant boost to the hospitality and tourism industry. It will give him the opportunity to pay only what he is entitled to and

reduce the burden of the cascading effect of tax. Conversely, if the GST rate is set at the assumed rate of 16%-20%, the consumer will face a heavy tax burden, as he will be paying a major portion of the invoice as tax. This will in turn reduce the revenue of the producer, which will ultimately affect the government.

Table 2: Post GST

Sub-total	2000
Service charge @ 10%	200
(2000*10%=200)	
VAT (assumed 16% under GST)	352
(2200*16%=320)	
Net amount	2552

Assumption: tax rate is assumed to be 16%

Comments

From the above two tables we can see the effect that the tax rates will have prior and post GST. Even after subsuming the various tax heads under one there is no much difference. This example assumes the GST rate to be at the lower limit of 16% but if it is set higher than the consumer will have to bear a heavy tax burden.

Recommendation

It will be beneficial for all the parties involved in tax regime i.e. the government, the producer and the consumer, if the GST rate is standardised for the Hospitality industry at a convenient rate. Standardising the tax rate between 8% to 10% for the hospitality industry will ensure that the consumer will not be hurt by the heavy tax implemented and make sure that the government does not face a detrimental effect on revenue. This study emphasises the effect of GST mainly on the hospitality sector, especially the Hotels and Restaurants. Therefore, we should remember that the above suggestions made are for the same and are not general.

The government decision to set the GST rates will obviously be a choice one that will either have positive or negative repercussions. Keeping all the factors that are involved in the tax regime, the rate set

should be beneficial, in terms of either revenue or value of the produce.

VII. CONCLUSION

As one of the prominent sources of revenue to the country, the government must take steps in order to help the Hospitality industry in keeping their revenues. The industry provides for 6.23% to the national GDP and 8.78% of the total employment in the country. Being main reason for increase in tourist population, the industry is now worried that the implementation of high rates of GST will hinder the growth of the country's revenue, as the tourist will now have to pay higher amounts as tax. Setting a limit to the increase in tax rates, the government should cap the GST rate for the hospitality industry at 10% for the benefit of the tax-paying consumer. It is a matter of importance that the government take into consideration the views of the leaders of the hospitality industry while setting the tax rates. Being one of the major revenue sources for the nation, a nominal fee must be decided upon, which will help the consumer by reducing the tax burden and at the same time provide a source of revenue for the country.

Due to the differential tax rates present in the prevailing tax regime, there is a cascading effect of these taxes that creates a burden on the consumer. This also creates more paper work for the industry.

With the implementation of the GST, both these issues will be dealt with as a single uniform tax rate will replace the differential taxes. The problem will only arise when the tax rates will be higher than the prevailing tax rates. This issue can be resolved if the

government caps the tax rate at 10%, which is a nominal rate. This rate can prove to be beneficial to both the consumer and the industry and the country at large.

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IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICES TAX ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The Good and services tax (GST) is the biggest and substantial indirect tax reform since 1947. The main idea of GST is to replace existing taxes like value-added tax, excise duty, service tax and sales tax. It will be levied on manufacture sale and consumption of goods and services. More than 150 countries have implemented GST so far. However, the idea of GST in India was mooted by Vajpayee government in 2000 and the constitutional amendment for the same was passed by the Lokshabha on 6th May 2015. The bill seeks to amend the constitution to introduce GST vide proposed new article 246A. This article gives power to legislature to every state and parliament to make laws with respect to GST where the supplies of goods or services take place. Despite the various amendments to the proposed transition, until the time GST is implemented, it would b worthwhile to assess its positive impact on the various development areas viz. Agriculture, Manufacturing industry, MSME, housing, poverty reduction, employment, price level, EXIM trade, GDP, government revenue etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word tax is derived from Latin word “taxare” which means to estimate. A tax is an

enforced contribution, exacted pursuant to legislative authority. Indian Taxation System comprise of Direct and Indirect Tax. Goods and Services Tax (GST) is one of the most discussed Indirect Taxation reforms. It is a comprehensive tax regime levied on manufacture, sales and consumption of goods and services. It is expected to bring about 2% incremental GDP growth of the country. So, GST is the need of the hour.

Initially the idea was that there would be a national level Goods and Services tax. But as the release of first discussion by the empowered committee of the state Finance Ministers on 10.11.2009, it has been made certain that there would be a “Dual GST” in the country. Centre and state both governments are entitled to charge taxes on the goods and services. Almost 150 countries have introduced GST in some form. France was the first country to introduce GST in 1954. While countries such as Singapore and New Zealand tax virtually everything at a single rate, Indonesia has five positive rates, a zero rate and over 30categories of exemptions. In China, GST applies only to goods and the provision of repairs, replacement and processing services. GST rates of some countries are given below in

Table 1: Rate of GST (Some Countries)

Country	Rate of GST
Australia	10%
France	19.6%
Canada	5%
Germany	19%
Japan	5%
Singapore	7%
Sweden	25%
New Zealand	15%

World over in almost 150 countries there is GST or VAT, which means tax on goods and services. Under the GST scheme, no distinction is made between goods and services for levying of tax. This means that goods and services attract the same rate of tax.

GST is multi-tier tax where ultimate burden of tax fall on the consumer of goods/services. It is called as value added tax because at every stage, tax is being paid on the value addition.

Under the GST scheme, a person who was liable to pay tax on output, whether for provision of service or sale of goods, is entitled to get input tax credit (ITC) on the tax paid on its inputs. Since VAT was beneficial for the taxation system but with certain shortcomings which are expected to be overcome by the Goods and Service Tax. Thus, it would definitely a positive reform for the Indirect tax system in India.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. R. Vasanthgopal (2011)² studied, “GST in India: A Big Leap in the Indirect Taxation System” and concluded that switching to flawless GST from current complicated indirect tax system in India will be a positive step in booming Indian economy. Success of GST will lead to its acceptance by more than 140 countries in world and a new preferred form of indirect tax system in Asia pacific region.

Nitin Kumar (2014)⁶ studied, “Goods and Service Tax- A Way Forward” and concluded that

implementation of GST in India help in removing economic distortion by current indirect tax system and expected to encourage unbiased tax structure which is indifferent to geographical locations.

Pinki, Supriya Kamma and Richa Verma (July 2014)⁷ studied, “Goods and Service Tax- Panacea For Indirect Tax System in India” and concluded that the new NDA government in India is positive towards implementation of GST and it is beneficial for central government, state government and as well as for consumers in long run if its implementation is backed by strong IT infrastructure

Akansha Khurana and Aastha Sharma(2016) studied, “Goods and services tax in India- A Positive reform for indirect test system” conclude from GST will provide relief to producer and consumer by providing wide and comprehensive coverage of input tax credit set –off, service tax set-off and subsuming the several taxes.

III. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

1. To collect information of current tax system and analysis of tax by GST
2. To study the concept of Goods and Services Tax (GST) and its impact on Indian economy.
3. To understand how GST will work in India.
4. To know the benefits of GST in India context.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is prepared through illustrative research which is based on secondary data of journals, research articles, newspapers and magazines. After taking into account different aspects of the study a descriptive research design is adopted to make the research more accurate which will further provide rigorous analysis of research study.

Concept

GST is an indirect tax which will include almost all the indirect taxes of central government and states governments into a uniform or whole tax. As the name suggests it will be levied on both goods and services at all the stages of value addition. It has dual model including central goods and service tax (CGST) and states goods and service tax (SGST). CGST will subsume indirect taxes like central excise duty, central sales tax, service tax, special additional duty on customs; counter veiling duties whereas indirect taxes of state governments like state vat, purchase tax, luxury tax, octroi, tax on lottery and gambling will be replaced by SGST. Integrated goods and service tax(IGST) also called interstate goods and service tax is also a component of GST. It is not an additional tax but it is a system to examine the interstate transactions of goods and services and to further assure that the tax should be received by the importer state as GST is a destination based tax.

Benefits of GST

1. A single registration for both CGST & SGST will reduce transaction costs and also unnecessary wastages. To make this more effective Government has to provide necessary IT infrastructure & integration of States level with the Union.

2. With the introduction of GST, Tax on Tax i.e. multiplicity of taxation will be eliminated. A

number of taxes currently levied on each level of transaction will be reduced. This will help clearing the confusion created by existing indirect taxes and also reduce the paper work associated with them.

3. There won't be any fear of taxation that may crop up at any stage of supply chain. This will not only help the business community to decide price modalities and supply chain but also the consumers in the long run. The goods will be competitive as the price will not be the main focus but the innovation and business intelligence will be.

4. Consumers will be benefitted the most as the average tax burdens will be reduced with the introduction of GST.

5. Implementation of GST will help reduce the corruption in the country, because GST reduces the multiple tax system.

6. Due to full end seamless credit manufactures or traders do not have to include taxes as a part of their cost of production which is very big reason to say that we can see a reduction in prices. However, if the government seeks to introduce GST with a higher rate this might be lost.

Impact of GST on Indian Economy

Amidst economic crisis across the globe India has posed on a beacon of hope with desirable growth targets, various schemes or missions like Make in India, Digital India etc. The Goods and Service Tax (GST) bill is expected to provide the much needed pace for growth of economy in India by transforming the existing complicated taxation system into single point taxation system in the country. Uniformity of tax will lead to single point taxation for supply of

goods or services across country. GST would improve the country's tax to GDP ratio and also prevent inflation. However, with GST manufacturing sector may be benefitted but things may get difficult

for the services sector. It is expected that the GDP growth is likely to be raised up to 1 to 2%, but the results can only be analysed after the implementation of GST. By merging large no. of centre and state taxes into one single point taxation system will reduce burden on producers and foster growth through more production. Various toll plazas and tax barriers leads to a lot of wastage for perishable items being transported which leads into the increase the costs of goods. GST could eliminate this road block which leads to lowering of prices for essential goods. GST would prove to be beneficial for the manufacturing sector where the tax rate is very high like FMCG, Auto and Cement sectors as they are currently reeling under 24 to 38%. The service sector is going to be adversely affected as the current rate of tax is much lower than expected rate of GST. GST would also add to government revenue by widening of the tax base. GST would be beneficiary for the sectors like FMCG, Pharmaceuticals, Consumer durables, Automobiles and logistic industries and will have negative impact on telecom, banking and financial services.

V. IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX

Fast moving consumer goods sector: The Indian FMCG sector is the fastest growing sector in the economy. FMCG sector is the major contributor in both direct and indirect taxes in the economy. Implementation of Goods and services tax will majorly influence Indian economy. The current rate of taxation in FMCG sector is around 22 to 25% and after GST rate is expected to be much lower which will result in reduction of prices of consumer goods.

Food Industry: A large portion of consumer expenses of lower income families spend on food so if there is any tax on food will influence majority of the population or may be regressive in nature. In

some of the countries like Canada, UK and Australia tax on food items is while in some countries like Singapore and Japan tax on food is negligible. So it would be ideal if the GST rates may be Zero or would be very low as it would affect people quite significantly.

Information Technology enabled services: - The IT industry will not hamper by the implementation Of GST. The expected rate of GST in IT sector is 27% According to proposed plan if software transferred through electronic form will be considered under services and if by any other media it would be under goods. So the IT industry will make mix taxation.

Infrastructure sector: - Development of Roads, Power, Railways, and Ports etc. are the major infrastructure sectors in India. As the taxation system in Infrastructure sector is very complex. There are exemptions and subsidies for this sector as it is very important for the development of the country. By the implementation of GST the complex tax will be removed and would increase tax base.

Real Estate Industry: The implementation of GST on real estate sector will effect partially. As the sale or transfer of immovable properties are not included in GST. However the procurement of materials of construction is falling under GST. The classification of goods and services is very important under this sector because it is very necessary to classify the things which will cover under GST and which are not. The implementation of GST will affect same as in service sector.

Transportation Industry: GST on transport sector will result in more efficient cross state transportation. It will bring down the logistics cost, reduced times for transportation. Currently all the 29 states of India collect taxes at different rates on goods that move

across the state borders that's why the tax on transportation is collected multiple times. This will make long delays at different interstate checkpoints for reviewing by state authorities who checks for the application of relevant taxes and other levies. This causes the delays for an average of 6 to 7 hours. GST would replace around 15 state and federal taxes and tariffs for a single tax at the point of sale of goods.

Pharma Industry: India is the largest producer of Generic Medicines and the country's pharmaceutical Industry is 3rd largest in the world currently. The implementation of GST would have a constructive effect on Healthcare industries particularly Pharma. It will help the industries by sorting out the taxation structure since 8 different types of taxes are enforced on pharmaceutical industries today. The merger of all the taxes into one uniform tax will ease the way of doing business. GST would also improve the transportation and supply chain of pharmaceutical products.

Textiles Industry: It is expected that the tax rate in GST would be higher in textile industry as per the current tax rate. Cotton and wool fibre which are currently exempted from tax would come under tax in GST but the textile industry may be beneficial from GST as manufacturing costs ,may be reduced due to subsume of various taxes like octroi, entry tax, luxury tax etc. There will be few drawbacks also but GST will support the industry in long run.

Services Sector: Services sector of India consists of 60% of the GDP. The GST rate for services is expected to be 18to 20% which is higher than the current rate of tax that is 15%. So there will be increase cost for services like Banking, Telecom and Insurance.

Agriculture Sector: The GST on agriculture sector will have a positive impact as all the taxes

subsumed under a single rate of tax. So the movement of agriculture commodities between states will be easier & hassle free which will save time and remove wastages for the transportation of perishables items.

VI. CONCLUSION

Taxation system is very important for the economy because they maintain equity of income group. Consumption and productions of goods and services undeniably rising and because of multiplicity of taxes in current tax system organization complexities and conformity cost is also increasing. Accordingly, a simplify user -friendly and transparent tax system is required. At present Indian economy have a major change in the taxation system. On 1st July the new tax system will be implemented that is Goods and Services Tax (GST). It will solve the problem of complexity of tax system because it will replace the current tax system of India. A single tax system will remove all other complex taxes of centre and state government like Vat, Cenvat, Luxury tax, Octroi, Entry tax etc. By the implementation of GST cost of manufacturing of goods will reduce. The cost of consumer goods will reduce. The Pharmaceutical industry is also benefitted as there is 8 types of taxes are bear by them in current scenario after GST these taxes will remove to one single tax. Similarly the impact of GST on all other sectors like Infrastructure, textile, IT, Agriculture, Food Industry, Transport, Real estate industry will positive and all the sectors will be benefitted with the implementation of GST. No doubt that GST will give India a world class tax system by grabbing different treatment to manufacturing and service sector. GST will provide relief to producers and consumers by providing wide and comprehensive coverage of input tax credit set off. Service tax set off and subsuming the several

taxes. GST is likely to improve tax collection and Boost India's economic development.

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GST: TRANSITION IN THE INDIAN PHARMA SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The cascading effect of tax on tax which prevailed prior to the introduction of VAT was reconstructed and revised on 1st April 2005. It is over a decade past the introduction of VAT which is a multi-stage tax system levied at each stage of production and distribution process. It is now realized that there is a strong necessity to amend the existing tax rates and make it uncomplicated and dynamic for the entire economy. As the implementation of GST in India is just around the corner, every industry and the nation as a whole, is looking at how this will influence their present tax obligations. This research paper presents the effect of GST, the big bang fiscal reform of India, on the Pharmaceutical industry. The focus has also been set to identify and analyze the “now and later” tax structure and its impact on the business of Indian Pharmaceutical industry.

Key words – Goods and Service Tax (GST), Indian Pharmaceutical Industry, Research Paper, Transition in the Pharma Sector, Value Added Tax (VAT), Central and State Government.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Indian pharmaceutical industry, with an estimated turnover of 450 billion (INR) is the third largest in terms of volume and thirteenth largest in terms of value, according to the department of PHARMA, ministry of chemicals and fertilizers. Indian Pharma is also a major source of revenue for India. The Bio-Pharma under the pharmaceutical

industry generates nearly 60% of total revenue (Wikipedia). Gujarat, Maharashtra, Hyderabad and Ahmedabad are the major Pharmaceutical hubs of India. The various categories of Indian Pharmaceutical industry are- Bulk Drugs, Biotechnology, Bio-Pharma, Biological products, Herbal products, Homeopathy, Surgical and Clinical research. The Pharma industry of India is expected to grow at 20% Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) over the next five years. This is presumed because of the certain strengths that exist in the industry such as- cost effectiveness, strong manufacturing base, low cost of innovation and manufacturing and availability of high quality skilled workforce. Currently, the pharmaceutical sector in India faces a multistage taxation system. Different taxes such as- customs duty, central excise duty on manufacture, CST/VAT on sale, and service tax on provision of services adds burden to the operating margins of Pharma industry. Further, the loss of tax credit on services such as logistics and patents impart inadequacies to the Pharma business. Also, multistage taxation increases compliance cost for the pharmaceuticals as the company is liable to file multiple returns on monthly basis to different authorities. To eliminate this problem, the finance minister has proposed another system of tax called as Goods and Services Tax (GST). GST may be defined as a dual taxation on goods and services, levied at each point of sale or provision of service, in which, at

the time of sale, the seller may claim the input credit of tax which he has already paid while purchasing the goods (Manindra).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Value added tax was first introduced by Maurice Laure, a French economist, in 1954. The tax was designed such that the burden is borne by the final consumer. In the Indian tax Regime, VAT was brought in to the picture in 2005. Since VAT can be applied on goods as well as services it has also been termed as goods and services tax (GST). A number of studies has been performed to examine the impact of implementing the GST. Most of these studies were on understanding the impact on the various factors affecting the economy.

Cullis & Jones (1992) stated that the increase awareness and knowledge on a new tax initiative is essential to gain public acceptance and confidence, particularly in tax situation. Tax involves public expenditure. New tax reform creates uncertainty of future expenditure.

Value Added Tax and Its Impact on Pharmaceutical Products (A Perception Study Among

Staff At Higher Secondary Schools in Madurai District) - Journal of Contemporary Research in Management, January (2008) states that, A long felt necessary to cope with global markets has compelled India to adopt this inevitable system Garish Garg (2014) Studied "Basic Concepts and Features of Good and Service Tax in India", and found that GST is the most logical steps towards the comprehensive indirect tax reform in our country since independence. GST will create a single, unified

Indian market to make the economy stronger.

Dr.R.Vasanthgopal (2011) Studied "GST in India: A Big Leap in the Indirect Taxation System", and found that the positive impacts are dependent on

a neutral and rational design of the GST balancing the conflicting interests of various stakeholders, full political commitment for a fundamental tax reform with a constitutional amendment, the switchover to a flawless GST would be a big leap in the indirect taxation system and also give a new impetus to India's economic change.

The Council of Applied Economic Research states that, GST is expected to increase economic growth by between 0.9% and 1.7%. Exports are expected to increase by between 3.2% and 6.3% while imports will likely rise from 2.4 - 4.7%.

Statement of the Problem

The proposed Goods and Services Tax (GST) has called for many arguments from numerous interested groups on how it would influence the various sectors of the economy. Pharmaceutical industry, being one of the fast growing and revenue generating industries of the country includes all aspects of business from manufacture, processing, distribution and service. Consequently the change in taxation rates will have an effect on the growth of the industry.

This paper concentrates on the differences that will be experienced by the Indian Pharmaceutical industries before and after the implementation of GST.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To portray the scenario under the VAT system.
2. To obtain a comprehensive overview on the impact of GST on the Indian Pharmaceutical Industry.
3. To ascertain the merits and demerits of the proposed system in the Pharmaceutical industry.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is an attempt of exploratory research, based on facts and findings which attempts to analyze and explain the scenario, while providing additional information about the topic.

Since GST has not yet been implemented in India and due to the non availability of primary data, secondary data has been considered for this study which is taken from various sources such as journals, magazines, articles, government and media reports.

V. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- A detailed study could not be undertaken because of time constraint.
- The information regarding the topic lacked in clarity.
- The study is based only up to the level of awareness.
- GST reports do not give us a clear picture of its impact on the FDI in the Indian Pharma industry.

Results and Discussion

Indirect tax is where one can shift his tax liability on someone else. Value Added Tax (VAT) is one form of indirect taxation in India. It comprises of State Level VAT (SLVAT) and Central VAT (CENVAT). In case of VAT, the tax is levied on the value addition and not on the input or output of a product. Even if the input of products is taxed, there is an input credit system available which will return the tax paid on inputs by the manufacturers. There is no uniform system of VAT rates, it varies among states and the products will be charged according to the SLVAT. But if a service is to be charged, both SLVAT and well as CENVAT will be considered. Service tax is generally levied by the Central government and Interstate trade is charged as Central Sales Tax (CST) at 2%.

Indian Pharma industry is currently following this system of taxation.

Some of the advantages it has attained over these years are-

- VAT is not charged on the imports of goods.
- The Pharma sector enjoys tax holidays in a few regions provisioned by the government for regional development. The accessibility and logistic cost to these regions is high, but is overridden by the tax benefits.

There are certain drawbacks in VAT system for the Pharma industry-

• It is a cost to Pharma manufacturers while procuring raw materials from outside their states on inter-state basis. This is because of the fact that the CST paid on purchases cannot be set-off against the VAT liability of manufacturers or dealers.

• Another impact would be a review of the present warehousing strategies followed by the Pharma industry. The common practice of most Pharma manufacturers is that they maintain warehouses in different states to support movement of goods from one warehouse to another so as to save on the CST. This is directed to the prosperity of Pharma sector only in those states and is not evenly dispersed across the country. Only Central taxes paid by the exporters are reimbursed and taxes levied by states are not reimbursed. This adds to their cost of production and discourages exports. On the other hand, if GST is implemented, it is more likely to sustain the pharmacy sector.

• The operations or processing of the pharmacy sector would be more consistent, uniform and rational with the other industries. Pharma industry also enjoys low cost of production due to economies of scale, but the levy of multiple taxes, loss of credit of tax paid, compliance and litigation

• The operations or processing of the pharmacy sector would be more consistent, uniform and rational with the other industries. Pharma industry also enjoys low cost of production due to economies of scale, but the levy of multiple taxes, loss of credit of tax paid, compliance and litigation

cost allied with the present tax structure tend to raise prices which eventually result in causing hardship to the Pharma industry.

GST is as well levied on the import of goods and services. While this is indeed serving the purpose of promoting the economy of the country, one element that is being ignored is that most of the capital goods required to manufacture the Pharmacy items are being imported by Indian manufacturers. Although there are dialogues that there will be an input credit for the goods imported for the purpose of export, it will again be a burden for manufacturers who are financially incapable.

In the case of exports, the industry is exporting more than half of its total production, which is estimated to be more than 20 billion dollars. The major destination for export is the USA, UK, Germany, South Africa and Russia.

Under the VAT system, the central government had introduced Export Promotion Capital Goods (EPCG) Scheme and any exporter licensed with EPCG scheme is eligible for exemption of custom duties. The question is, will the EPCG scheme continue to exist under GST system? As this is an important principle for the export of chemicals and pharmaceuticals.

VI. MERITS OF GST ON THE PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

- The GST will influence warehousing strategy of pharmaceuticals. Under GST, the transactions between two dealers at an inter-state level will extent to stock transfer or branch transfer. The country would be considered one common market and therefore, making inter-state transactions tax neutral. Currently, due to CST liability, Pharma manufacturers are forced to maintain warehouses in all states to avail exemption of CST.

- Currently, the tax credit can be obtained only on the raw materials or inputs procured. But GST is proposed to include services also under the concept of tax credit. This will motivate the Pharma manufacturers and suppliers to discover better logistics and transportation alternatives.

- The availability of excise duty holiday for a period of 10 years in selected states under VAT has resulted in many Pharma companies shifting their manufacturing base to these states. This has created a biased advancement in these states neglecting the other potential states. But with the implementation of GST, there will be unified tax rate and development of all states.

VII. LIMITATIONS OF GST ON THE PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

- The foremost limitation of GST is that it lacks in clarity of the rates and incentives to the manufacturers.

- Further, Increasing government pressures with harsh price controls and taxes will restraint the growth of Pharmaceutical industry.

- On an average, out of every 10,000 molecules been developed, only one or two are likely to reach the market. This indicates that there is lot of costs and risks involved in the manufacture of medicinal products. So, if GST tax rates are too high, there are possible chances that the market will not flourish.

- The government has recently permitted 100% Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the Pharma industry. But there is no clarity about GST's impact on the FDI. This may perhaps reduce the FDI in Indian Pharma industry.

- Most of the Pharma companies are outsourcing their business to different states where it is excise free, but after GST is introduced, they will

have to return to Gujarat which probably would be the only state which is excise free.

- Lastly, on generic terms, because of the flat rate which will be imposed as a result of GST, the rich get richer and poor get poorer.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Implementation of The Goods and Services Tax will play a major role in the tax regime of the country. It is expected to bring about competence and simplicity in the indirect tax reforms in India. Further, it will also support an unbiased tax structure that is impartial irrespective of any business processes or physical location. Though the exact details are still vague, the structure has been approximately laid down for all to see.

When it comes to the Pharmaceutical industry, it should start gearing up for the subsequent GST and identify the areas, which would require consideration during the implementation of GST and its after effects. The industry will have to re-assess the existing Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)/accounting system and make appropriate changes to put into effect the change in tax rate, format of invoice and so on for accurate and timely tracking, computation and payment of tax obligations, which seems time consuming and would probably result in turmoil in the initial stages. Further, the industry should identify the products, which presently enjoy exemption from payment of Central Excise/VAT so as to enjoy the same exemption.

IMPACT OF GST ON AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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I. INTRODUCTION

India is the seventh largest in area and second most populous country in the world. Agriculture plays a vital role in India's economy. It has a total area of 328.7 million hectares; of which about 141.4 million hectares constitute the net cropped area and 200.9 million hectares is the Gross Cropped Area with a cropping intensity of 142 per cent. The agriculture sector employs nearly half of the workforce in the country. It contributes to 17.5% of the GDP. India ranks third in farm and agriculture output globally. India's production of food grains has been increasing every year, and India is among the top producers of several crops such as wheat, rice, pulses, sugarcane and cotton. It is the highest producer of milk and second highest producer of fruits and vegetable, besides being the second highest exporter of cotton for the past several years. It is also the largest producer, consumer and exporter of spices and related products.

As a result of good monsoon during 2016-17, area sown under most crops increased in 2016-17. The largest increase was recorded under pulses which is around 43.66 lakh hectares (around 17.5 per cent) more over 2015 – 16. The area coverage under tur, gram, urad and Agricultural exports constitute 10% of the country's exports, and are the fourth-largest exported principal commodity. India is also among the top producers of wheat, rice, sugarcane and fresh

fruits. Given the importance of agriculture sector, Government of India took several steps for its sustainable development. However, the quantity of food which is wasted during the harvest and post-harvest processes in the country has increased over the years. Food wastage occurs at all levels of farming- the farmer, transporter, wholesaler and retailer. Some of the reasons for this wastage are crop damage, improper harvesting techniques, poor packaging and transportation, and poor storage.

II. GST IMPACT ON AGRICULTURE

The main aim of implementing Goods and Services Tax (GST) is 'One Nation, One Tax, One Market'. Globally, it is simple, efficient and will help to improve the economic growth of the country by eliminating a dozen of central and state levies like excise, service, and VAT.

In current tax regime, agriculture has enjoyed a various exemptions from indirect tax. The new definitions of agriculture and agriculturist are provided by GST in section 2(7) and 2(8) respectively. As per the Model GST law "agriculture" includes floriculture, horticulture, sericulture, the raising crops, grass or garden produce and also grazing. However

Dairy farming, poultry farming and stock breeding are specifically kept out of the definition of Agriculture; hence it seems that these will be taxable under GST regime.

The mere cutting of wood or grass, gathering of fruit and raising of man-made forest or rearing of seedlings or plants have also been specifically kept out of the definition of Agriculture, hence it seems that these will be taxable under GST regime.

Agriculture by persons other than Individual and HUF seems also kept out of the definition of agriculturist; hence it seems that these will be taxable under GST regime.

As the GST Act exempts only an agriculturist as defined above from GST, many involved in formal agriculture or agricultural business can be liable for registration, collection and compliance under GST. Since GST is a consumption based tax, any person involved in agricultural businesses and having GST registration would also be able to take input tax credit paid and pass on the ultimate GST liability to the end consumer. On the other hand, an agriculturist as per GST Act not having GST registration would not be required to comply with GST requirements. However, an agriculturist would still have to pay GST on purchases which attract GST tax. For example 12 per cent GST rate is applicable on items like water pump, milking machines and self – unloading trailers used for agricultural purposes. Hence, an agriculturist would be making GST payment while purchasing such goods or services which attract GST.

The simple uniform tax regime is expected to improve the transportation time, and curtail wastage of precious food. Food includes a variety of items, including grains and cereals, meat, fish, and poultry, milk and dairy products, fruits and vegetables, candy and confectionary, snacks, prepared meals for home consumption, restaurant meals, and Beverages. In India, while food is generally exempt from the CENVAT, many of the food items, including food

grains and cereals, attract the state VAT at the rate of 4%. Exemption under the state VAT is restricted to unprocessed food, e.g., fresh fruits and vegetables, meat and eggs, and coarse grains. Beverages are generally taxable, with the exception of milk.

Vegetables and produce from agriculture, including dairy, served fresh without any processing has been exempt from GST. Under GST, any person who is engaged exclusively in the business of supplying goods and services or both that are not liable to tax or wholly exempt from GST is not required to obtain GST registration. Hence, even a formal farmer selling fresh produce would be exempt from GST registration or compliance, as he/she would fall under the category of a person engaged exclusively in the business of supplying goods that are not liable to tax or wholly exempt from GST.

Seeds and fertilizers are a major input for agriculturist and farmers. Both seeds and fertilizers are exempt from GST. Hence, agriculturists would not have to pay GST tax on their major input.

Table 1: GST Rates on Agriculture Sector

S.No.	Goods	Old Rate	GST	Difference
Cheaper				
1	Seed, Organic compost without brand	0	0	0
2	Head pump and its parts	12.5	5	-7.5
3	Tractor	12.5	12	-.5
4	chemical fertilizer	12	5	-7
Expensive				
1	Tractor Tire & Rim	12.5	18	+5.5
2	Other tractor parts	12.5	18	+5.5
3	Harvester, Earth, Grader, Parts	0	12	+12
4	Insecticide	5.5	18	+11.5

III. NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL MARKET (NAM)

GST is vital to enhance the performance of supply chain mechanism in terms of transparency, reliability and timeliness, which in turn will ensure reduction in waste and cost of agricultural produce. As the GST is being introduced with the objective of having a unified tax structure for goods and services, a Central Sector Scheme for promotion of National Agricultural Market has been introduced by the Ministry. The scheme envisages networking of selected markets to a common electronic platform to be developed by the Central Government. The identified regulated markets across the country will be integrated with the common e-platform to provide farmers and traders with access to opportunities for purchase/ sale of agricultural commodities at optimal prices in a transparent manner, allowing free flow of agricultural commodities across states. The market will lead to enhanced regional cooperation. The common market is expected to have an advantage over existing markets in terms of transparency, competition, efficiency, market information, risk, price signal, etc due to operation on e-portal, participation of large number of traders and

integration of various services. Once transportation facilitated, it will improve the marketing efficiency and create access to virtual world.

GST is essential to improve the transparency, reliability, timeline of supply chain mechanism.

1. However an agriculturist, for the purpose of agriculture is not required to register under GST but A better supply chain mechanism would ensure reduction in wastage and cost for the farmers/retailers.
2. GST would also help in reducing the cost of heavy machinery required for producing agricultural commodities.
3. Under the model GST law, dairy farming, poultry farming and stock breeding are kept out of the definition of agriculture. Therefore these will be taxable under the GST.
4. Fertilizers which were having 0 to 8 percent of VAT (Value added Tax) will now be having 12% tax under GST .This is going to

hit very hard to farmers, if there is not enough government subsidy.

5. The condition is not very clear as which components are included in the tax slab. May the tax slab could be rationalised and brought down from 28% to 12%.
6. GST Rates of Pesticides have gone from existing 12–15% to 18%, this is really huge.
7. Changed the Definition of Agriculturist in the new GST Law i.e. many activities are taken out of agriculture purview like dairy farming which were previously considered as agriculture.
8. For tractors it is not seeming very clear as tractor is put on 12% slab and it's component are put on 28% slab.

IV. CONCLUSION

The implementation of GST in agriculture is expected to bring uniformity across states and centre which would make tax support policy of a particular commodity effective. GST may provide India with its first National Market for the agricultural goods. The transportation, logistics and preservation are the significant value additions for agricultural produces. It is highly probable that GST shall resolve the issue of transportation. The ease of availing tax credit under GST regime is expected to boost inter-state trade and terms of trade in favour of agriculture and agro based goods leading to achieving the objectives of National Agricultural Market. There are reasons to focus attention on agriculture and allied sector, which will continue to play a significant role in providing employment and sustainable livelihood's for the growing population in India. However, the agriculture sector is characterized by instability in

incomes owing to various types of risks related to production, market and prices. Hence, the government needs to be very cautious in implementing the new tax system and should have extra concern towards the farmers. Even a slightest burden on farmers will result in manifold distress and misery, they being the most vulnerable community of the country.

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ROLE OF GST IN E-COMMERCE

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Abstract

GST also known as the Goods and Services Tax is defined as the giant indirect tax structure designed to support and enhances the economic growth of a country. More than 150 countries have implemented GST so far. However, the idea of GST in India. However, there is a huge hue and cry against its implementation. It would be interesting to understand why this proposed GST regime may hamper the growth and development of the country.

The e-commerce industry in India is still in its infancy, but it has shown a remarkable growth over a period of time and has contributed significantly to the country's GDP. GST is basically an indirect tax levied on the sale of goods and services and is considered a solution to several complex tax maladies being encountered by the E-commerce companies in the retail sector. The introduction of GST which is a consumption based tax is expected to end the tussle between the states to tax e-commerce transactions. The implementation of GST for an e-commerce company can give them a much needed relief from the recurrent sales tax demands, investigations, and stoppage of goods at the check post. In this paper, the researchers have tried to find out the implications of GST on e-commerce in the retail sector and whether it proves to be more of a boon than a bane to the e-commerce companies.

Key words: *GST, E-commerce, Impact, Byers, Sellers etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic commerce or EC is buying and selling of goods and services, or the transmitting of funds or data, over an electronic network, primarily the internet. GST has a noticeable impact on each and every sector including E commerce sector. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a value-added tax levied on most goods and services sold for domestic consumption. The GST is paid by consumers, but it is remitted to the government by the businesses selling the goods and services. In effect, GST provides revenue for the government.

The goods and services tax (GST) is an indirect federal sales tax that is applied to the cost of certain goods and services. The business adds the GST to the price of the product; a customer who buys the product pays the sales price plus GST; and the GST portion is collected by the business or seller and forwarded to the government.

France was the first country to implement the GST in 1954, and since then an estimated 160 countries have adopted this tax system in some form or another. Some of the countries with GST include Canada, Vietnam, Australia, Singapore, UK, Monaco, Spain, Italy, Nigeria, Brazil, and South Korea. India is set to join the GST group on July 1, 2017.

Most countries with a GST have a single unified GST system, which means that a single tax rate is applied throughout the country. A country with a unified GST platform merges central taxes (e.g. sales tax, excise duty tax, and service tax) with state-level

taxes (e.g. entertainment tax, entry tax, transfer tax, sin tax, and luxury tax) and collects them as one single tax. These countries tax virtually everything at a single rate.

Only a handful such as Canada and Brazil has a dual GST structure. Compared to a unified GST economy where tax is collected by the federal or central government and then distributed to the states, in a dual system, the federal GST is applied in addition to the state sales tax. In Canada for example, the federal government levies a 5% tax and some provinces/states also levy a provincial state tax (PST) which varies from 7 to 10%. In this case, a consumer's receipt will clearly have the GST and PST rate that was applied to his or purchase value.

With the inclusion of retail entrepreneurs in the ambit of GST and the introduction of specific provisions for e-commerce companies, certain areas of GST will impact the e-commerce sector. Every company in India, be it a multinational company or a small/medium enterprise, is gearing up for the implementation of GST. The e-commerce sector would follow suit in its preparation by focusing on provisions specific to this sector in the GST law.

The success of the e-commerce sector is largely dependent on the increasing number of retail entrepreneurs, who fall in the unorganized retail sector category. The government has included such players in the ambit of GST with an intention of broadening the tax base and has introduced specific provisions for the e-commerce companies. Here are some of the key areas of GST that impact the e-commerce sector:

1. No trade barriers—one nation one tax

In the present regime, there is no uniformity in the tax rates among the different states and therefore every state determines its own tax rates

specific to the products. For example, a mobile phone in state 1 is taxed under VAT at five percent and in state 2 at 14.50 percent. As a result, the sellers in state 2 would not want to sell locally but would prefer to sell from state 1, resulting in loss of revenue for state.

E-commerce operators have set up distribution centers only in certain locations and collect the VAT applicable on sales made from such centers. In order to compensate for the loss of VAT revenue, many states have recently imposed entry tax on goods coming from other states, which discourages sales made from other states. The entry tax acts as a trade barrier, restricts free movement of goods from one state to another and increases the cost for traders.

However, such trade barriers will cease to exist as GST is inclusive of entry tax. The destination state earns the revenue from GST on sales regardless of where the sale was made. Further, there is no rate arbitrage under GST because the classification of goods and rate of GST is common across states.

2. Tax collection at source (TCS)

It is mandatory for all e-commerce operators to collect tax at the rate of two percent as TCS on the net value of sales made by suppliers through e-commerce operators. Such TCS has to be deducted in each state and deposited accordingly. This brings in significant compliance challenges to sellers and may discourage sales through marketplace model. However, this may not be applicable for inventory based models, where the e-commerce operator makes the sale from its own inventory. The key purpose of this provision is to encourage compliances under GST and provide a mechanism for the government to track suppliers who sell through e-commerce operators.

3. Increase in compliances for e-commerce operators

The e-commerce operators should report all supplies made by the seller and the TCS collected thereof on a monthly basis. The sales reported by the e-commerce operator will have to match with the sales declared by the supplier himself at the end of every month, and any difference will be added to the turnover of the supplier and consequently be liable to discharge GST on such additional turnover.

The e-commerce operator has to report the product/service code and the applicable rates for each item level individually. This requires them to map every sale done by the dealer and ensure TCS is deducted at the right value. The implementation of compliance is cumbersome for both e-commerce operator and the supplier.

Additionally, the e-commerce operators will have to register in each state and file the reports separately on a monthly basis. This process increases the challenges in compliance and costs of running the business.

4. Mandatory registration of sellers and unavailability of composition scheme

GST mandates that all sellers supplying through an e-commerce operator need to be registered under GST irrespective of the threshold limit of Rs 20 lakh. These sellers cannot opt for composition scheme, where they pay a flat tax at the rate of two percent and do not maintain details of each product sold. In this scenario, it is not feasible for small businesses to maintain a detailed record of purchases and sales and pay higher rate of tax. Because of this, many small retailers may not prefer to work with an e-commerce company, which impacts the business for e-commerce operators.

5. Increase in credits

The GST law has extended the meaning of 'input tax' to cover any goods/services used by the company in the course of business, which has widened the ambit of input GST credits. This has removed the requirement to establish the direct nexus of inputs/input services with the final product/service provided by companies. For e-commerce operators and sellers, the unavailability of credit towards excise duty and VAT on goods and service tax on certain services adds to the cost of running the business, which would be avoided under GST on account of increase in credits.

II. IMPACT OF GST ON E-COMMERCE

MARKETPLACE SELLERS

A high level impact analysis of Goods and Services Tax on the businesses of Sellers registered on Online Marketplace.

India's e-commerce market is estimated to have crossed Rs. 211,005 core in December 2016 as per the study conducted by Internet and Mobile Association of India. The report further claims that India is expected to generate \$100 billion online retail revenue by the year 2020.

The uprising of Electronic Commerce in India has also resulted in conception of online marketplaces. A Marketplace is an e-commerce platform owned by the E-commerce Operator such as Flipkart, Snapdeal and Amazon. Some of the features of a marketplace model are:

- Marketplace charges a subscription fees/ commission on sale value from listed sellers.
- Third-party sellers under this model gain access to a larger customer base, registered with marketplace.
- Customer on the other hand gains access to multiple sellers and competitive prices for desired products.

- Items purchased on such marketplaces are either shipped by Merchant/Third-party seller directly or through the fulfillment center managed by Marketplace Operator.
- Government has also allowed Foreign Direct Investments under such model to promote e-commerce marketplace business model in India.

Marketplaces have provided retailers with additional channel of sales and reach which was unimaginable for an offline seller. Major marketplaces claim to have lacks of sellers affiliated with their platform with millions of SKUs. While the number of sellers and their business have increased significantly, GST has specifically taken up marketplaces and has come out with rules & regulations specific to this segment. Introduction of these regulations requirements has compelled the online seller community to embrace GST regime. Some of these compliance are:

No threshold for GST registration: Government has specified a threshold limit for all the businesses. A business is liable to register under Goods and Services Tax once such threshold limit is breached. To read more about threshold limits under GST. However such limit is not applicable in case of E Commerce sellers. All the businesses carrying out e-commerce activity are required to get registered under GST irrespective of their turnover.

No Benefit under Composition Scheme: Most of these sellers registered with marketplace operators are small and medium businesses. Government has introduced composition scheme under GST law. This scheme is primarily aimed to reduce the burden of compliance for small and medium businesses. Under this scheme, businesses are required to file returns quarterly instead of monthly and pay taxes at nominal

rates up to 2%. To know more about Composition Scheme, However GST law has explicitly excluded e-commerce businesses from this scheme.

Tax Collection at Source by Marketplace Operator: Under the new tax regime, marketplace operators are mandatorily required to deduct a percentage amount as the GST liability of seller and deposit it with government. This mechanism is being termed as “Tax Collection at Source (TCS)” under the GST law. Eventually the marketplace seller will have to file monthly return under GST to claim the credit of TCS collected by the marketplace operator. This will also impact the liquidity and cash flow of these sellers.

While all the marketplace operator have already completed the first level analysis of impact of GST on their operations, marketplace sellers are still unaware of these rules.

Need of the hour is to keep themselves aware of the changes that are going to come. Also such sellers should now start planning their transition strategy for GST regime.

1. Get your GST enrollment done on time. To read more about the enrollment process and its relevance.
2. Plan your logistics and warehousing requirement carefully. To read our detailed guide on impact analysis on logistics and warehousing.
3. Adopt such platforms, technologies which will enable your business to be GST compliant.

III. CONCLUSION

As we can see, the GST law may have a negative impact on the e-commerce sector. Given that e-commerce sector in India is one of the most rapidly advancing sectors and the government is vigorously promoting digitized economy, the introduction of such cumbersome compliances cringes the growth of

this sector. Statutory framework introduced by the government should be towards the advancement of business rather than creating obstacles. The GST law should provide an enabling environment that encourages e-commerce operators and suppliers. The contribution of the e-commerce sector in the Indian economy has been immense and in order to reap the benefits of the ever-increasing, rewarding e-commerce sector, a stable indirect tax system is ntry.

required as a remedy to different tax maladies faced by the e-commerce entities in retail space. The implementation of GST will not only resolve tax issues but also resolve the supply chain issues faced by the e-commerce companies thus enabling faster shipment/returns and reduced paperwork formalities. The simplification of tax system will make it easier for those selling goods across states, which in turn, lowers the burden on the customers.

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A STUDY ON CHANGING PARADIGM TOWARDS GOODS AND SERVICE TAX IN INDIA

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I. INTRODUCTION

Against the backdrop of robust macroeconomic stability, the year 2016- 17 was marked by two major policy developments, the passage of the constitutional amendment, paving the way for implementing the transformational Goods and Service Tax (GST) and the action to demonetize the two highest denomination notes. Of these, the GST will create a common Indian market, improve tax compliance and governance and boost investment and growth. It is also a bold new experiment in the governance and boost investment and growth. The launch of the GST represents an historic, economic and political achievement, unprecedented in Indian tax and economic reforms.

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax which was introduced in India on 1 July 2017 and was applicable throughout India which replaced multiple cascading taxes levied by the central and state governments. The single GST (Goods and Service Taxes) replaced several former taxes and levies which included: central excise duty, services tax, additional customs duty, surcharges, state-level value added tax and Octroi. Other levies which were applicable on inter-state transportation of goods have also been done away with in GST regime. It was introduced as The Constitution (One Hundred and

First Amendment) Act 2017, following the passage of Constitution 122nd Amendment Act Bill.

The Goods and Services Tax was launched at midnight on 1 July 2017 by the President of India, Pranab Mukherjee, and Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi. The launch was marked by a historic midnight (30 June – 1 July) session of both the houses of parliament convened at the Central Hall of the Parliament. The GST is governed by a GST Council and its Chairman is the Finance Minister of India.

Much of the commentary has suggested that the GST has a complicated tax structure, implicitly comparing the new system with an ideal GST tax structure while implying that the comparing is with the past. It is inaccurate to suggest that the GST is more complicated than the system it replaced. Hence, the present study is undertaken with the following specific objectives.

1. To identify the Taxation Scheme and components of Goods and Service Taxes
2. To classify the GST Rates and Exclusion from GST Base and
3. To Examine the revised GST rates

Taxation Scheme and Components of GST

Goods and Services Tax Law in India is a comprehensive, multi-stage, destination-based tax

that is levied on every value addition. Previously, different states could impose different taxes and levies which included central excise duty, services tax, additional customs duty, surcharges, state-level value added tax and Octroi. Under the GST regime, the tax will be levied at every point of sale. GST consolidates multiple taxes into one. Previously, every good faced an excise tax levied by the centre and a state VAT. There were at least 8 – 10 rates of excises and 3-4 rates of State VATs, the latter potentially different across states. So, a structure of multiple rates (as much as 10 times 4 times 29 States/ has been reduced to a structure of 6 rates. More importantly, uniformity or the principle of “one good, one tax” all over India is now a reality. GST is levied on all transactions such as sale, transfer, purchase, barter, lease, or import of goods and/or services. There are multiple change-of-hands an item goes through along its supply chain: from manufacture to final sale to the consumer. Goods and Services Tax will be levied on each of the following stages, which makes it a multi-stage tax. (Fig 1.)

- Purchase of raw materials
- Production or manufacture
- Warehousing of finished goods
- Sale to wholesaler/Sale of the product to the retailer
- Sale to the end consumer

Components of GST

There are 3 taxes applicable under GST. (Fig 2)

- CGST: Collected by the Central Government on an intra-state sale (Eg: Within Tamil Nadu)
- SGST: Collected by the State Government on an intra-state sale (Eg: Within Tamil Nadu)
- IGST: Collected by the Central Government for inter-state sale (Eg: Tamil Nadu to Karnataka)

The Centre and states have collected Rs 92,283 crore as Goods and Services Tax (GST) in July, the first month of the implementation of the indirect tax regime. The amount is marginally higher than the projected target of Rs 91,000 crore. Of the total GST of Rs 92,283 crore for July, the amount collected as Central GST (CGST) has been Rs 14,894 crore and State GST (SGST) has been Rs 22,722 crore, while Rs 7,198 crore has flowed in by way of compensation cess on demerit goods. An amount of Rs 47,469 crore has been collected as Integrated GST (IGST), including Rs 20,964 crore as IGST from imports.

II. GST Rates and Exclusion from GST Base

Under GST, goods and services are taxed at the following rates, 0%, 5%, 12% ,18% and 28%. The GST tax rates an exclusion from GST Base shown in Table 4 have scope for further improvement.

Table 1 : GST Rates and Exclusion from GST Base

S.No	IGST (%)			Number of Goods Categories	Major goods / Sectors Excluded
	CGST (%)	SGST (%)	Total (%)		
1	0	0	0	88	• Alcohol
2	1.5	1.5	3	Gold and Jewelers	
3	2.5	2.5	5	173	

4	6	6	12	200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Petroleum and energy • Electricity • Land and Real Estate • Education • Health Care
5	9	9	18	521	
6	14	14	28	229	

Source : Economic Survey (2016 -17)

The above table indicates that the Indian Taxation System has categorized over 1211 goods for levy of GST under 6 broad categories or tax-slabs. These are 0% or No Tax, 3%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. There is a special rate of 0.25% on rough precious and semi-precious stones and 3% on gold. In addition a cess of 22% or other rates on top of 28% GST applies on few items like aerated drinks, luxury cars and tobacco products. Alcohol, petroleum and energy products, electricity and some of land and real

estate transactions are outside the GST base but are faced by the centre and / or states outside the GST. It will improve transparency and reduce corruption. Health and education are outside the tax net altogether exempted under the GST and not otherwise taxed by the centre and states because these are services consumed disproportionately by the rich. The product – wise GST rates are presented in Table 2 .

Table 2 : Product – wise GST Rates

S.No	Tax Rates	Products
1	0 %	Milk, Eggs, curd , Lassi , Unpacked Foodgrains, unpacked paneer, Gur, Tender Coconut water, Unbranded Natural Honey, Fresh Vegetables, Salt Education Services curd, Kajal, Education Services, Health services, Children’s Drawing and Colouring Books, Unbranded Atta, Unbranded Maita, Besan, Prasad, palmyra Jaggery, Phool Bhari Jhadoo.
2	3%	Gold and Jewelers
2	5 %	Sugar, Tea, Edible Oils, Spectacles, Domestic LPG, PDS Kerosene, Cashew Nuts, Mil food for Babies, Spices, Coal, Life Saving Drugs, Packed Paneer, Raisin, Roasted Coffee beans, Skimmed Milk Powder, Footwear (< Rs. 500), Apparels (< Rs.1000), Coir Mats, Matting and Floor Cover, Agarbatti, Mishti/ Mithai (Indian Sweets), Coffee (Except instant)
3	12 %	Butter, Ghee, Almonds, Fruit Juice, Packed Coconut water, Computers, Processed Food, Mobiles, Preparations of vegetables, Fruits, Nuts or other parts of plants including pickle murabba, Chutney, Jam, Jelly and umbrella
4	18 %	Hair Oil, Tooth Paste, Soap, Pasta, Corn Flakes, Soups, Capital Goods, Industrial intermediaries, CCTV, Stapler, Aluminum Foils, Ice – Cream, Toiletries, Computer Monitor (< 17 inches), Printers
5	28 %	Small cars (+1% or 3% cess), Consumer durables such as AC and fridge, High – End Motor cycles (+ 15 % cess), Beedis are NOT included here, Luxury and Sin items like BMWs, cigarettes and aerated drinks (+ 15 % cess)

Table 3 shows the tax calculations in pre and post GST of biscuit manufacturer along with some numbers.

Table 3 : Tax calculations in Pre - GST and Post - GST Regime :

S.No	Action	Pre - GST			Post - GST		
		Cost	10% tax	Total	Cost	Actual Liability	Total
1	Manufacturer	1000	100	1100	1,000	100	1,100
2	Warehouse ads label and repacks @ 300	1400	140	1540	1,300	30	1,430
3	Retail Advertises	2040	204	2244	1,800	50	1,980
	Total	1800	1800	2244	1,800	180	1,980

The table clearly indicates that in the pre-GST regime, tax on tax was calculated and paid by every purchaser including the final consumer. This is called the **Cascading Effect of Taxes** where a tax is paid on tax and the value of the item keeps increasing every time this happens. **GST** avoids this cascading effect as the tax is calculated only on the value-add at each stage of transfer of ownership. In the case of Goods and Services Tax, there is a way to claim credit for tax paid in acquiring input. What happens in this case is, the individual who has paid a tax already can claim credit for this tax when he submits his taxes. In the end, every time an individual is able to claim input tax credit, the sale price is reduced and the cost price for the buyer is reduced because of a lower tax liability. The final value of the biscuits is therefore reduced from Rs. 2,244 to Rs. 1,980, thus reducing the tax burden on the final customer

Revised GST rates

As per 23rd Council meeting on 10th November 2017, the revised GST rates are

- GST rates for 178 items have been reduced from 28% to 18%.
- GST Rate for manufacturers and traders under composition scheme is 1 %
- Reduced from 28% to 18% W.e.f. 15th Nov 2017 – Shampoo, Perfume, tiles, watches
- Reduced from 28% to 12% – Wet grinders, tanks
- Reduced from 18% to 12% – Condensed milk, refined sugar, diabetic food
- Reduced from 12% to 5% – Desiccated coconut, idli dosa batter, coir products
- Reduced from 5% to Nil – Duar meal, khandsari sugar, dried vegetables
- For Restaurants within hotels, and room tariff less than Rs. 7,500 the GST rate is 5%. Also,

the credit of ITC paid on inward supplies cannot be taken.

- For Restaurants within hotels, and room tariff greater than Rs. 7,500 the GST rate is 18% and credit of ITC paid on inward supplies can be availed.
- Outdoor catering continues to be charged at 18% with the availability of ITC on inward supplies.

Conclusion

GST replaced a slew of indirect taxes with a unified tax and is therefore set to dramatically reshape the country's 2 trillion dollar economy. As soon as the GST rates were announced a huge wave of curiosity hit across industry and trade bodies. Everyone is evaluating their position as a result of this change. One important hidden benefit of the GST is that the textile and clothing sector is now fully part of the tax net. Similarly one segment of land and real estate transactions has been brought into the tax net. The multiplicity of rates was a response to meeting a variety of objectives, including the need to keep rates down for a number of essential items to protect poorer sections from price rises. The GST council a remarkable institutional innovation in the governance of cooperative federalism and one that has proven to be already in the first few months of existence will need to take up these challenges in the months ahead to take India from a good GST to an even better one.

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GST IN INDIAN ECONOMY: A BIRD'S-EYE-VIEW

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Abstract

Goods and Service Tax is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at National Level. GST is a part of proposed tax reforms in India having an extensive base that instigate the applicability of an efficient and harmonized consumption tax system. GST has been commonly accepted by world and more than 140 Countries have acknowledged the same. GST is expected to pave way for better E- Commerce and will make industries more competitive. GST will be a game changing reform for Indian economy by developing a common Indian market and reducing the cascading effect of tax on the cost of goods and services. This research paper explains that Benefits of GST and Impacts of GST on Indian Economy.

Key Words: *Goods and Services Tax (GST), Indian Economy*

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods and Service Tax is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at National Level. GST is a part of proposed tax reforms in India having an extensive base that instigate the applicability of an efficient and harmonized consumption tax system. GST has been commonly accepted by world and more than 140 Countries have acknowledged the same. GST is similar to the VAT system which is a value added tax

on goods with an Input Tax Credit (ITC) mechanism but GST also includes services. Thus GST would be applicable on supply of goods and services as against the present concept of tax. GST is a value added tax on goods and services that is paid by the final consumer while the retailer will be taking credit of the tax he has paid while buying goods for retailing. So in this all the services of retailer or the chain behind him is taxed apart from the actual value of production of that good.

II. OBJECTIVES

The study has following objectives:

1. To understand the concept of GST
2. To analyses the benefits of GST in Indian economy
3. To know the impact of GST in Indian Economy

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Vasanthagopal (2011) in his study "GST in India: A Big Leap in the Indirect Taxation System" the author concluded that switching to seamless GST from current complicated indirect tax system in India will be a positive step in booming Indian economy. Success of GST will lead to its acceptance by more than 150 countries in world and a new preferred form of indirect tax system in Asia also.

Nishitha Guptha (2014) in her study stated that implementation of GST in the Indian framework will

lead to commercial benefits which were untouched by the VAT system and would essentially lead to economic development. Hence, GST may precursor in the possibility of a collective gain for industry, trade, agriculture and common consumers as well as for the Central Government and the State Government.

Nitin Kumar (2014) in their research article “Goods and Service Tax- A Way Forward” concluded that implementation of GST helps in removing economic distortion by current indirect tax system and GST encourages an unbiased tax structure which is indifferent to geographical locations.

Dhanda (2015) studied, “GST in India: A Key Tax Reform” and concluded that due to dissilent

environment of India economy, it is demand of time to implement GST

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive in nature and it used the exploratory technique. The data collected from secondary sources such as journals, newspapers, magazines and from research articles.

V. TAX SYSTEM UNDER THE NEW GST

The new GST will merge the aforementioned indirect central and state taxes into a four-tier schedule of 5, 12, 18 and 28 percent, as seen in below table. While necessity goods will be taxed at 5 percent and luxury and consumer durable goods at 28 percent, most goods and all services will be taxed at the standard rates of either 12 or 18 percent.

Proposed Tax Brackets

Goods				Services
Exempt 0% Agricultural Goods	Low Rate 5% Necessity goods	Standard Rate 12% and 18% Distribution is undecided	High Rate 28% Luxury goods and consumer durables	Standard Rate 12% and 18% Distribution is undecided

Example of GST Calculation

The GST is set at 5% Suppose that the manufacturing cost of a Product A is 100 and assuming a GST of 5% the total amount is Rs. 105 The next step of taxation would be when the Product is sold to consumers, let's say at a price of 150. So the GST will charge another 5% on just the difference of Rs. 150 and Rs. 105 i.e. only 5% on Rs. 45 which is equal to Rs. 2.25. So the final price is Rs. 150 + Rs. 2.25. Unlike the case of petrol pricing there is no tax on a tax now. This eliminates the cascading effect of taxes which is very prevalent in our economy and has been simplified to an elemental level in the example. Since the GST will be applied at every step of value creation it will be very difficult for black money owners to participate anywhere in the value chain with the GST without accounting for all other transactions.

GST'S 5 TAX SLABS	
0% Milk, eggs, curd, unpackaged food grains, salt, fresh vegetables, bindi, bangles, newspapers, judicial papers and services, including education and health	5% Domestic LPG, PDS kerosene, sugar, tea, coffee, edible oil, spices, fabric, agarbatti, medicines
12% Butter, ghee, processed foods, mobiles, fruit juice, almonds, packed coconut water, umbrellas; food served at non-AC restaurants	18% (general rate) Hair oil, toothpaste, soap, ice-cream, toiletries, pasta, computers, printers, food served at AC restaurants, film tickets costing less than Rs 100
28% AC, fridge, washing machine, small cars (+ 3 % cess), high-end motorbikes (+15% cess), luxury and sin items like BMWs, cigarettes, aerated drinks (+15 % cess); film tickets costing over Rs 100	

Source: Times of India

Benefits of GST

For business and industry

- Easy compliance
- Removal/mitigation of cascading/double taxation

- Improved competitiveness

For Central and State Governments

- Simple and easy to administer
- Better controls on leakage
- Consolidation of tax base
- Higher revenue efficiency and collections

For the consumer

- Single and Transparent tax proportionate to the value of goods and services

- Reduction of prices
- Increase in real income and purchasing power

Apart from these,

- The tax structure will be made lean and simple
- The average tax burden on companies will fall

which will reduce the costs of Indian goods and services in the international market and give boost to Indian exports

- It can facilitate seamless movement of goods across states and reduce the transaction costs of businesses.

- It is good for EOUs, as it is not applied for goods and services exported out of India.

- Uniform tax rates across the states

Impact of GST on Indian Economy

- Reduces tax burden on producers and fosters growth through more production
- Different tax barriers, such as check posts and toll plazas, lead to wastage of unpreserved items being transported. This penalty transforms into major costs due to higher needs of buffer stock and

warehousing costs. A single taxation system will eliminate this roadblock.

- More transparency in the system.
- GST add to the government revenues by extending the tax base.
- GST provide credit for the taxes paid by producers in the goods or services chain.
- GST will remove the custom duties applicable on exports. The nation's competitiveness -in foreign markets will increase on account of lower costs of transaction.

Impact of Goods and Service Tax in Sector wise

1. Food Industry

The application of GST to food items will have a significant impact on those who are living under subsistence level. But at the same time, a complete exemption for food items would drastically shrink the tax base. Food includes grains and cereals, meat, fish and poultry, milk and dairy products, fruits and vegetables, candy and confectionary, snacks, prepared meals for home consumption, restaurant meals and beverages. Even if the food is within the scope of GST, such sales would largely remain exempt due to small business registration threshold. Given the exemption of food from CENVAT and 4% VAT on food item, the GST under a single rate would lead to a doubling of tax burden on food.

2. Housing and Construction Industry

In India, construction and Housing sector need to be included in the GST tax base because construction sector is a significant contributor to the national economy.

3. FMCG Sector

Despite of the economic slowdown, India's Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) has grown consistently during the past three – four years

reaching to \$25 billion at retail sales in 2008. Implementation of proposed GST and opening of Foreign Direct Investment (F.D.I.) are expected to

fuel the growth and raise industry's size to \$95 Billion by 2018.

	Detergents	Baby foods	Sanitary napkins	Shampoo
GST RATE	28%	18%	18%	28%
CURRENT RATE	23%	5-12%	10-11%	24-25%
COMPANIES IMPACTED	HUL, P&G, Jyothy Lab	Nestle	P&G Hygiene and Health Care	HUL, P&G, Dabur, Himalaya

4. Rail Sector

There have been suggestions for including the rail sector under the GST umbrella to bring about significant tax gains and widen the tax net so as to keep overall GST rate low. This will have the added benefit of ensuring that all inter – state transportation of goods can be tracked through the proposed Information technology (IT) network.

5. Financial Services

In most of the countries GST is not charged on the financial services. Example, In New Zealand most of the services covered except financial services as GST. Under the service tax, India has followed the approach of bringing virtually all financial services within the ambit of tax where consideration for them is in the form of an explicit fee. GST also include financial services on the above grounds only.

6. IT sector:

Most IT service providers have a multi-locational presence with the preferred mode of service tax compliance being on a centralized basis from a single location and IT service provider also enjoys the input service credits as well as enjoys the refunds. But under GST, service provider may be required to pay State GST or Central GST or Integrated and GST across multiple states, which is not clear yet.

7. Tourism, Hospitality and Restaurant:

Presently, the rates in these industries are higher due to existing multiple taxes. With the implementation of RNR (Revenue Neutrality Rate) which is more than introducing the present tax rate, this would definitely discourage tourists and users of services and adversely affects the growth of sector.

8. Transport sector:

GST is a positive for transportation sector in two ways, as it reduces the logistics cost and increases the efficiency both within India and exports.

9. Impact on Small Enterprises

There will be three categories of Small Enterprises in the GST regime. Those below threshold need not register for the GST Those between the threshold and composition turnovers will have the option to pay a turnover based tax or opt to join the GST regime.

Conclusion

GST is expected to pave way for better E-Commerce and will make industries more competitive. GST will be a game changing reform for Indian economy by developing a common Indian market and reducing the cascading effect of tax on the cost of goods and services. One of the main

objectives of GST would be to eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution cost of goods and services. GST impacts a nation both ways, positively and

negatively. Ignoring negative aspects, positive aspects can be taken into consideration, in order to development of the country.

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IMPACT OF GST ON COMMON MAN AFTER ITS IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract

In today's scenario we pay various taxes i.e. Direct and Indirect taxes, which are felt as burden on us and due to these taxes the corruption is increasing. So, to overcome from all these taxation system the Central Government has decided to make one tax system i.e. Goods and Services Tax (GST). GST is one of the most critical tax reforms in India which has been long awaiting decision. It is a comprehensive tax system that will subsume all indirect taxes of State and central Governments and whole economy into seamless nation in national market. It is expected to remove the burden of existing indirect tax system and play an important role in growth of India. GST includes all Indirect Taxes which will help in growth of economy and proves to be more beneficial than the existing tax system. GST will also help to accelerate the overall Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country. GST is now accepted all over the world and countries are using it for sales tax system. This paper will help to show that, what will be the impact of GST after its implementation, difference between present Indirect Taxes and GST and what will be the benefits and challenges of GST after implementation.

Keywords: Central, State, Dual, GST, Indirect Tax, Direct Tax, GDP, Implementation

I. INTRODUCTION

India is the hub of taxes where people pay many taxes which create confusion for them. Presently we

pay two types of taxes i.e. Direct and Indirect in various sectors. Direct Tax paid directly to the government by the taxpayer i.e. Income Tax, Wealth Tax, and Corporation Tax. Indirect Tax is a tax levied on goods and services rather than on income or profits. It is not directly paid to government but collected from intermediaries (such as retail stores) from the person who bears the ultimate economic burden of the tax (such as consumers). The intermediary later files a tax return and forwards the tax proceeds to government with the return for example Sales Tax, VAT, Excise Duty, and Custom Duty and so on. Goods and Service Tax or GST as it is known is all set to be a game changer for the Indian economy. The Finance Minister in his budget speech of Budget 2015 has announced time and again that the tax will be introduced on 1 April, 2016 GST is a blanket of Indirect Tax that will subsume several indirect state and federal taxes such as Value Added Tax (VAT) and Excise Duty and different State Taxes, Central Surcharges, Entertainment Tax, Luxury Tax and many more. GST was firstly introduced in France in 1954, with introduction of GST France became the first country ever to introduce GST. Its introduction was requiring because very high sales taxes and tariffs encourage cheating and smuggling. After France it was adopted by 165 nations. GST bill is brought for the reason that the different taxes paid by us on different rates would be brought under one roof so that all the taxes

may get cancelled and only one tax is paid which is GST. Goods and Services Tax (GST) will include one tax one nation; this statement was given by the honorable Prime Minister Mr. Narandra Modi of India. In today's scenario we pay 30% to 35% tax on different things but with GST it will be only 18%, which shows it will be beneficial and one main thing that GST will remain similar in all nation. Both the State and the Central Government will levy GST on almost all goods and services produced in India or imported into the country. Direct Taxes such as income tax, Corporate tax and capital gain tax will not be affected by GST. It will make Indians tax structure , elaborate and create a similar market across states. GST will replace different Indirect Tax levies i.e. Sales Tax, Service Tax, VAT, Excise Duty, CustomDuty, Countervailing Additional Duty, Special Additional Duty, Securities Transaction Tax, StampDuty, Entertainment Tax, Anti-Dumping

Duty, Local Body Taxes, Property Tax, Entry Tax, Tax and Duties on electricity, Tax on Goods and Passengers and compliance cost will fall which will lead in getting life simpler. This process will help to increase India's tax-to-gross domestic product ratio. According to experts GST is regarded to increase economic growth by between 0.9% and 1.7%. Exports are expected to increase economic growth by between 3.2% and 6.3%, were as imports will likely raise 2.4% – 4.7%. GST is a Value Added Tax (VAT) to be implemented in India, from April 01; 2017. Government has promised that GST will reduce the compliance burdens at present. The rules of taking and utilization of credit for the central GST and the State GST would be aligned. Cross Utilization of input tax credit between the Central GST (CGST) and the State (SGST) would not be allowed except in case of interstate supply of goods.

Table:1 Taxes proposed to be submitted in GST: State and Central Taxes.

STATE TAXES	CENTRAL TAXES
Value Added Tax(VAT)	Excise Duty
Entertainment Tax levied by states	Additional Excise Duty
Luxury Tax	Excise Duty under Medicinal and Toilet Preparation Act
Tax on lottery, betting and Gambling	Service Tax
Entry Tax other than for local bodies	Additional Custom Duty Commonly as CVD, SAD

- CAD- Countervailing Duty
- SAD- Special Additional Duty

1.1 Need of the Study

This study will help us to examine the impact of GST after its implementation it will show the gap between the present indirect taxes and GST and also the study will show the benefits and challenges which GST may face after implementation.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Pinki et al. (2014) studied, "Goods and Service Tax-Panacea For Indirect Tax System in

India" and concluded that the new NDA government in India is positive towards implementation of GST and it is beneficial for central government, state government and as well as for consumers in long run if its implementation is backed by strong IT infrastructure. Kumar (2014) studied, "Goods and Service Tax - A way forward" and concluded that after implementation of GST in India many indirect tax system will be finished and there will be only one tax i.e. GST which is expected to encourage unbiased

tax structure. Sehrawat and Dhanda (2015) studied, “GST in India: A Key Tax Reform” and concluded that due to dissilent environment of India economy, it is demand of time to implement GST. Anushuya and Narwal (2014) studied, “Application of CGE Modals In GST” and concluded that both GST & CGE are very popular all over the world but GST is a powerful concept in the field of indirect taxes. Chaurasia et al. (2016) Studied, “Role of Goods and Services Tax in the growth of Indian economy” and concluded that in overall GST will be helpful for the development of Indian economy and this will also help in improving the Gross Domestic Products of the country more than two percent.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To enquire the impact of GST after its implementation.
- 2) To find out the difference between the present indirect taxes and GST.
- 3) To identify the benefits and challenges of GST after the implementation.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

On 7th October 2016 Government of India (GOI) PASSED Process and Flowchart of GST . Now the GST is going to implement very soon and all the sectors have to register for it. The First step for each sector is to register under Central Goods and Service Tax act (CGST) and State Goods and Service Tax act (SGST). If a person is bound to be registered for GST he/she shall register himself under SGST Act of his respective state where he perform his business work he/she also register under CGST Act. The Registration of GST is received within 30 days.

The Process Of Registration For GST Is Different From Other Registrations In Different Ways Such As:-

1. Permission from CGST and SGST Act for registration is required.
2. If one authority rejects the process for registration there will be automatic rejection by the other authority.
3. There shall be no rejection of application without giving a solid reason to the applicant.
4. Application shall be considered to be granted under CGST/SGST Act if the application for registration has been granted under SGST Act/CGST Act.
5. The non-residential and casual taxable person would also require registration from GST.

V. ANALYSIS/ DISCUSSIONS

Models of GST:

There are three prime models of GST, which are available in existing literature which are as follows:-

1. GST at Central (Union) Government Level only
2. GST at State Government Level only
3. GST at both, Union and State Government Levels

Importance of GST to the Economy

GST is designed to remove the burden by ending many indirect taxes. GST will be important for economy in following way like GST will reduce tax evasions it will help to provide more money to backward states like Bihar, Jharkhand etc which will improve the economy of the country it will also help in removal of local tax. In conclusion we can say that

GST is one tax that can be a major breakthrough in India taxation system.

VI. GST WILL POSITIVELY IMPACT THE COMMON MAN IN MANY WAYS

GST is a unified tax system removing bundle of Indirect tax like VAT, CST, Service tax, CAD, SAD, and Excise Duty which will have a positive impact on Common Man. There will be less tax Compliance and Simplified tax Policy as compared to earlier tax structure, GST will reduce the cascading effect of taxes in tax system. The increased production will lead to more job opportunities. GST will curb the circulation of black money. Thus GST will have a positive impact on Common man in many ways.

VII. PROBLEMS WHICH GST MIGHT FACE AFTER IMPLEMENTATION.

Disputes are likely to arise between Centre and State over tax. Highly sophisticated IT infrastructure is required issue of taxing e-commerce is to be appropriately addressed and integrated and some political imbalance. GST being consumption based tax states with higher consumptions of goods and services will have better revenues so co-operations from state government would be one of the key factors for successful implementation of GST.

VIII. PLACE OF SUPPLY RULES

In case of a sale of real property the place of supply is the jurisdiction in which the property is located. Similarly services directly connected with real property are also taxed in the place in which the property is located.

IX. TREATMENT OF DIFFERENT AREAS AFTER IMPLEMENTATION OF GST.

Full and instant input credit would be allowed for tax paid by both CGST and SGST on all purchases of goods in which GST would be included in different areas like

- Treatment of Capital Goods
- Treatment of Petroleum products
- Treatment of power sector
- Treatment of Transport services
- Treatment of Financial services
- Treatment of Small Scale Industries (SSI)

X. CONCLUSION

The GST system is basically structured to simplify current Indirect Tax system in India. A well designed GST is an attractive method to get rid of deformation of the existing process of multiple taxation also government has promised that GST will reduce the compliance burden at present there will be no distinction between imported and Indian goods and they would be taxed at the same rate. Many indirect Taxes like Sales Tax, VAT etc., will be finished because there will be one tax system i.e. GST that will reduce compliance present burden. GST will face many challenges after its implementation and will result to give many benefits. In overall through this study we conclude that GST plays a dynamic role in the growth and development of our country .

IMPACT OF GST ON E-COMMERCE

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to examine the impact of GST on E-Commerce. The Ecommerce industry is growing rapidly in the country. There are not just companies big and small but also individual sellers who are selling their goods using different ecommerce portals. Companies such as Amazon, Flipkart, Myntra, and Paytm are some of the largest ecommerce players in the market there are thousands of companies and individuals who have registered with them as third party sellers, and sell their products and goods. Every company in India, be it a multinational company or a small/medium enterprise, is gearing up for the implementation of GST. The e-commerce sector would follow suit in its preparation by focusing on provisions specific to this sector in the GST law. In the present regime, there is no uniformity in the tax rates among the different states and therefore every state determines its own tax rates specific to the products. For example, a mobile phone in state 1 is taxed under VAT at five percent and in state 2 at 14.50 percent. As a result, the sellers in state 2 would not want to sell locally but would prefer to sell from state 1, resulting in loss of revenue for state.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is the fastest growing E-commerce market in the world with increased internet users, online shoppers and investors. GST has been rolled with specific provisions for E-commerce market and an increased compliance have been placed on E-

commerce operators, as well as Suppliers in terms of the Registration, Invoicing, Returns and Tax Collected at Source. Thus, the Government can track the majority of suppliers who are currently unorganized and can broaden the tax base. Every company in India, be it a multinational company or a small/medium enterprise, is gearing up for the implementation of GST. The e-commerce sector would follow suit in its preparation by focusing on provisions specific to this sector in the GST law.

The Goods and Services Tax (GST)

It is the single biggest reform in India's indirect tax structure since the liberalisation of the economy in 1991. Through this reform, the government has integrated the previously disparate segments of the Indian economy and has truly begun the process of creating one market for the entire nation. The idea of a single tax on the supply of goods and services, from manufacturing to delivery to the final consumer, has eliminated the need for sellers to register with multiple tax platforms and file multiple tax returns.

A Projection of the Industry

India's e-commerce potential

Online spending by value

Internet users

Source: ASSOCHAM-Resurgent India study, EY

GST Registration

It is mandatory for every ecommerce operator and the sellers to register for GST and obtain a GSTIN. The threshold limit of Rs. 20 lakhs is not applicable to these ecommerce operators, as well as the sellers. Moreover, the sellers will not get the composition scheme benefit and cannot pay a flat tax of 1% for every product sold. This was expected to make sellers withdraw from the online space, however, such has not been the case and companies report that most sellers have continued with them.

The Key Areas of GST that Impact the E-Commerce Sector:

The success of the e-commerce sector is largely dependent on the increasing number of retail entrepreneurs, who fall in the unorganised retail sector category. The government has included such players in the ambit of GST with an intention of broadening the tax base and has introduced specific provisions for the e-commerce companies. Here are some of the key areas of GST that impact the e-commerce sector:

1. No trade barriers—one nation one tax

E-commerce operators have set up distribution centres only in certain locations and collect the VAT applicable on sales made from such centres. In order to compensate for the loss of VAT revenue, many states have recently imposed entry tax on goods coming from other states, which discourages sales made from other states. The entry tax acts as a trade barrier, restricts free movement of goods from one state to another and increases the cost for traders.

However, such trade barriers will cease to exist as GST is inclusive of entry tax. The destination state earns the revenue from GST on sales regardless of where the sale was made. Further, there is no rate

arbitrage under GST because the classification of goods and rate of GST is common across states.

2. Tax collection at source (TCS)

It is mandatory for all e-commerce operators to collect tax at the rate of two percent as TCS on the net value of sales made by suppliers through e-commerce operators. Such TCS has to be deducted in each state and deposited accordingly. This brings in significant compliance challenges to sellers and may discourage sales through marketplace model. However, this may not be applicable for inventory based models, where the e-commerce operator makes the sale from its own inventory. The key purpose of this provision is to encourage compliances under GST and provide a mechanism for the government to track suppliers who sell through e-commerce operators.

3. Increase in compliances for e-commerce operators

The e-commerce operators should report all supplies made by the seller and the TCS collected thereof on a monthly basis. The sales reported by the e-commerce operator will have to match with the sales declared by the supplier himself at the end of every month, and any difference will be added to the turnover of the supplier and consequently be liable to discharge GST on such additional turnover. The e-commerce operator has to report the product/service code and the applicable rates for each item level individually. This requires them to map every sale done by the dealer and ensure TCS is deducted at the right value. The implementation of compliance is cumbersome for both e-commerce operator and the supplier.

Additionally, the e-commerce operators will have to register in each state and file the reports separately on a monthly basis. This process increases

the challenges in compliance and costs of running the business.

4. Mandatory registration of sellers and unavailability of composition scheme

GST mandates that all sellers supplying through an e-commerce operator need to be registered under GST irrespective of the threshold limit of Rs 20 lakh. These sellers cannot opt for composition scheme, where they pay a flat tax at the rate of two percent and do not maintain details of each product sold. In this scenario, it is not feasible for small businesses to maintain a detailed record of purchases and sales and pay higher rate of tax. Because of this, many small retailers may not prefer to work with an e-commerce company, which impacts the business for e-commerce operators.

5. Increase in credits

The GST law has extended the meaning of 'input tax' to cover any goods/services used by the company in the course of business, which has widened the ambit of input GST credits. This has removed the requirement to establish the direct nexus of inputs/input services with the final product/service provided by companies. For e-commerce operators and sellers, the unavailability of credit towards excise duty and VAT on goods and service tax on certain services adds to the cost of running the business, which would be avoided under GST on account of increase in credits.

II. CONCLUSION

As we can see, the GST law may have a negative impact on the e-commerce sector. E-commerce sector in India is one of the most rapidly advancing sectors and the government is vigorously promoting digitised economy, the introduction of such cumbersome compliances cringes the growth of this sector. The GST law should provide an enabling environment

that encourages e-commerce operators and suppliers. Hence, under GST era, the ecommerce operators will have to bear a higher tax rate on the output side, but they can claim credit of all taxes on the input side. Moreover, all the output taxes will be credited to the ecommerce operator after services are provided by the sellers. Likewise, sellers will also have a higher tax rate on the output side, but can claim an input credit of all taxes other than the additional tax paid.

Overall, it is a good move for this industry and Indian online seller as inventory and logistics cost will come down and tax computation will be easy as there are fixed taxes on products falling under a particular category. So, businesses and consumers, both will benefit eventually.

ROLE OF GST IN E-COMMERCE

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Abstract

E-Commerce in India is often referred as the “sun-rising industry”. The growth it has seen in the recent years is not only unprecedented but it is also expected to grow twice of its size within a few years from now. While India stands on the brink of its biggest transformation in the tax reforms- that is the implementation of the Goods and Service Taxes “GST”, its impact on the E-commerce sector are vast. Currently, the indirect tax structure with different tax regimes in every state has led to confused and complex tax treatment of E-commerce Sector. The Model GST Law has incorporated major changes by including a separate chapter on e-commerce transactions. However, the proposed Model GST Law may result in compliance challenges for the e-commerce sector and open up many other issues which would require further clarity. This article tries to understand the effect of transition from the current model of indirect tax to the uniform model given by the GST.

Key Words: Goods and Services Tax, GST for E-Commerce Aggregators, Benefits or Barriers for E-Commerce.

I. INTRODUCTION

The current e-commerce sector of India is burdened with the plethora of taxes, there are multiple taxes applicable on a single transaction such as VAT, CST, EXCISE, SERVICE and TDS. It becomes even more difficult to differentiate between the goods and services when it comes to the products

like software download, music, e-books etc. moreover, to make the matter even more unfortunate, the statutory forms and e-way bills add complexity to interstate transactions. GST is the biggest transformation in the indirect tax regime in India, which will make India a unified common market with reduced compliance costs and bring in simpler tax structure. it intends to rationalize the current indirect tax regime, by following its motto of “one nation, one tax”, thereby providing a stable economic environment favourable for growth and development.

However, with the unifying tax structure, GST can result in the higher compliance challenges and open up certain other issue which would require further clarity. the model law of the GST defines e-commerce as to mean the supply or receipt of goods and/or services, or transmitting of funds or data, over an electronic network, primarily the internet, by using any of the applications that rely on the internet, like but not limited to e-mail, instant messaging, shopping carts, web services, Universal Description Discovery And Integration (UDDI), File Transfer Protocol (FTP) and Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) whether or not the payment is conducted online and whether or not the ultimate delivery of the goods and/or services is done by the operator.

Goods and Services Tax

GST is a unified consumption tax, which will be subject to a numbers of general principles. One of the principles is that it operates on a territorial basis. Another principle is that it must be neutral or in other

words, the business has not to bear GST as a cost. In B2B transactions, where the consumer is entitled to input tax credit, GST cannot be regarded as an item of expenditure. The GST payable by the supply receiver of goods or services will invariably be paid by the ultimate consumers, while GST paid previously will be allowed to set-off with GST recovered from the ultimate consumers and GST to the extent not recovered from the ultimate consumers be refunded.

Current Scenario

The E-commerce sector in India which took baby steps until about a couple of years ago is in a galloping mode today. The growth of the e-commerce sector in terms of revenue and shipments has been nothing but phenomenal. The e-commerce sector has successfully managed to capture the brain and focus of the consumers like never before and with an unprecedented growth trajectory expected to continue, is predicted to be the next BIG Industry.

Growth of any business is good news for the economy and especially the tax authorities. E-commerce sector, with its ever increasing number of transactions in goods & services, is a waste land for sowing the seed of indirect taxes. While it is good for the government to expect increase in income by collecting tax through growing businesses, the tax laws should also support the businesses with clear vision on taxation matters and ease of doing business at the maximum possible level. Unfortunately, for the e-commerce sector, the indirect tax laws in India have been more of obstacle than a driver for growth till date.

Aggregator

Section 43B(a) of the MGL defines aggregator to mean a person, who owns and manages an electronic platform, and by means of the application and

communication device, enables a potential customer to connect with the persons providing service of a particular kind under the brand name or trade name of the said aggregator. For instance, Ola cabs would be an aggregator.

GST for E-Commerce Aggregators

- Registration
- Tax rates
- Input tax
- Return
- Payment of tax

Concepts of TCS for E-commerce aggregators

II. GST IN INDIA: A BENEFIT OR BARRIER FOR THE E-COMMERCE SECTOR

With the inclusion of retail entrepreneurs in the ambit of GST and the introduction of specific provisions for e-commerce companies, certain areas of GST will impact the e-commerce sector.

Every company in India, be it a multinational company or a small/medium enterprise, is gearing up for the implementation of GST. The e-commerce sector would follow suit in its preparation by focusing on provisions specific to this sector in the GST law. The success of the e-commerce sector is largely dependent on the increasing number of retail entrepreneurs, who fall in the unorganized retail sector category. The government has included such players in the ambit of GST with an intention of broadening the tax base and has introduced specific provisions for the e-commerce companies.

No Trade Barriers—One Nation One Tax

In the present regime, there is no uniformity in the tax rates among the different states and therefore every state determines its own tax rates specific to the products. For example, a mobile phone in state 1 is taxed under VAT at five percent and in state 2 at 14.50 percent. As a result, the sellers in state 2 would

not want to sell locally but would prefer to sell from state 1, resulting in loss of revenue for state. E-commerce operators have set up distribution centers only in certain locations and collect the VAT applicable on sales made from such centers. In order to compensate for the loss of VAT revenue, many states have recently imposed entry tax on goods coming from other states, which discourages sales made from other states. The entry tax acts as a trade barrier, restricts free movement of goods from one state to another and increases the cost for traders. However, such trade barriers will cease to exist as GST is inclusive of entry tax. The destination state earns the revenue from GST on sales regardless of where the sale was made. Further, there is no rate arbitrage under GST because the classification of goods and rate of GST is common across states.

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Increase in Credits

The GST law has extended the meaning of 'input tax' to cover any goods/services used by the company in the course of business, which has widened the ambit of input GST credits. This has removed the requirement to establish the direct nexus of inputs/input services with the final product/service provided by companies. For e-commerce operators and sellers, the unavailability of credit towards excise duty and VAT on goods and service tax on certain services adds to the cost of running the business, which would be avoided under GST on account of increase in credits.

III. CONCLUSION

GST is the biggest transformation in the indirect tax regime in India, which will make India a unified common market with reduced compliance costs and bring in simpler tax structure. It intends to rationalize the current indirect tax regime, by following its motto of "one nation, one tax", thereby providing a stable economic environment favorable for growth and development of our country.